

**TILNING LEKSIK-SEMANTIK TIZIMI,
QIYOSIY TIPOLOGIK IZLANISHLAR VA
ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIK
MUAMMOLARI**

**MATERIALLAR
TO‘PLAMI**

XVI

**O‘ZBEKISTON REESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

BUXORO DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI

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СЖАТИЕ РЕЧЕВОЙ ЦЕПИ КАК РАЗНОВИДНОСТЬ ЭЛЛИПТИРОВАНИЯ

Человек может наблюдать и сразу целиком схватывать своим сознанием довольно сложные ситуации в объективной действительности. Но он не в состоянии одной фразой описать всю ситуацию во всей полноте и разнообразии взаимосвязей ее элементов. Он может описывать ее только частями, последовательно вычленяя ее отдельные микроструктуры, отражая их в элементарных мыслях и выражая эти мысли в элементарных предложениях. При этом в каждой отдельной языковой модели, соответствующей элементарной мысли (суждению), обозначаются составляющие элементы данной микро ситуации (например, материальные предметы) и выражается связь между ними (например, взаимное расположение).

Гораздо чаще встречаются такие ситуации, в микроструктурах которых повторяются одни и те же элементы или связи между ними в самых разных сочетаниях: один и тот же предмет может вступать в разные связи с другим или с несколькими разными предметами; один и тот же предмет может вступать в одинаковую связь с несколькими разными предметами; несколько предметов могут вступать попарно, по три и т.д. в одни и те же связи, совершать одно и то же действие или подвергаться ему; один предмет может иметь несколько выделенных в данной ситуации признаков или один такой признак может принадлежать нескольким разным предметам и т.д. (1).

Человеческому мышлению, а следовательно, и языку свойственно стремление к экономии усилий, к суммированию, к обобщению отражаемых событий, поэтому при описании подобных ситуаций элементарные мысли и выражающие их элементарные предложения могут тем или иным способом сжиматься или перекрываться.

Сжатие текста обеспечивается опорой слов-заместителей на замещаемые ими полнозначные слова. Эта опора оказывается возможной благодаря расположению последних в ближайшем контексте – в предыдущем элементарном предложении. Ср. Подобный тип замещения: *Tom did play hockey and he had a very good time* (Twain M.). *This boy was well dressed, too – well dressed on a week-day. This was implyastounding* (TwainM.).

В двух микроситуациях между разными парами объектов может отмечаться одинаковая связь. Здесь не редко используется способ опущения. При опущении нарушается структурная целостность второго элементарного предложения, хотя его структурная самостоятельность

сохраняется. Семантическая же самостоятельность, как и при замещении, снижается. Ср.: *Oneneedlecarriedwhitethreadandtheotherblack* (Twain M.).

В двух микроситуациях одинаковыми оказываются оба объекта, а разными – связи между ними. Оба предложения можно слить в одно, где объекты называются только один раз, но указываются обе связи между ними. Используемый здесь метод сжатия текста называется совмещением. При совмещении нет никакой утери семантической определенности и не нарушаются ни синтаксические связи, ни структура результирующего предложения, хотя последняя несколько усложняется и видоизменяется. Ср. сочетание замещения с опущением:

- *Is Jane at home?*

- *Yes, Jane is at home* (Lawrence D.H.).

В обычной речи эти микроструктуры будут сжаты следующим образом: - *Is Jane at home? – Yes, she is.*

Во втором предложении существительное *Jane* замещено местоимением *she*, а обстоятельство места *at home* опущено.

Сочетание совмещения формируется и с опущением: *The moon rosered* (Kingsley A.) [The moon rose. + The moon was red].

Итоговое предложение – результат совмещения двух элементарных предложений с опущением некоторых элементов (опущен глагол-связка *was*). В целом, же эллипсис предложение имеет простую схему. Это бинарная конструкция, которая возникает при следующих условиях: а) при наличии двух сочиненных членов, соотносенных с одним общим членом, б) при наличии отношения противопоставления или сопоставления между этими членами. В качестве общего члена может выступать существительное, глагола, глагольная синтагма и т.д.

Наиболее распространенными общими членами являются слова-заместители. Ш.Балли называет такие слова-заместители «представляющими», относя к ним местоимения (2).

Замещением, опущением и совмещением исчерпываются основные способы сжатия естественной речевой цепи.

Сжатие текста, сопровождающееся сокращением заключенной в нем информации, представляет большой теоретический и практический интерес. Прежде всего, речь идет о сокращении избыточной информации, устранении случаев ее дублирования (всевозможных повторений). Это и выбор более лаконичных средств изложения.

Итак, тенденция к устранению избыточной информации не навязывается языку извне. Это внутреннее, естественное свойство языка, закрепленное в его системе и обеспечиваемое ею. Без способности к экономии средств выражения язык не мог бы функционировать.

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CONTEXTUAL USAGE OF IMPERATIVE AND OPTATIVE MOODS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Abstract. This expanded article explores how imperative and optative moods are used in real and literary contexts in English and Uzbek languages. It aims to present the topic in a simple yet academic style. The study draws examples from Shakespeare's 'Hamlet' and Qodiriy's 'O'tkan kunlar' to show cultural and pragmatic differences in expressing commands and wishes. Findings suggest that while English often shows directness and personal control, Uzbek highlights politeness, emotional warmth, and respect. The paper also emphasizes that grammar cannot be separated from culture and communication norms.

Key words: moods,imperative,optative,grammatical category,pragmatic differences,contextual usage.

Introduction.Language reflects how people think, act, and relate to each other. The imperative and optative moods are important in showing people's intentions, emotions, and social attitudes. They do not only tell someone what to do or what one wishes for, but also show how people build relationships. In English and Uzbek, the way these moods are used depends on cultural values, respect rules, and how people manage politeness. The aim of this paper is to explain the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek imperatives and optatives in real communication and literature.

1. Theoretical Background

According to Austin (1962) and Searle (1969), imperatives belong to the group of directive speech acts — sentences used to influence another person's behavior. Leech (1983) and Brown & Levinson (1987) discuss how politeness can change the force of an imperative, making it softer or more respectful. Wierzbicka (2003) adds that every culture has its own way of expressing commands and wishes, influenced by moral values and traditions. In Uzbek linguistics, To'xtasinov (2020) and Xudoyberganova (2012) analyze how language reflects

cultural behavior, showing that the choice of suffixes and expressions depends on respect, age, and familiarity.

The imperative and optative moods are not only grammatical categories but also

reflect the cultural and communicative norms of a language community. In English and Uzbek, their pragmatic use varies according to politeness, hierarchy, gender, and emotional tone. In English, the imperative is often softened by modal verbs or polite markers, such as “please,” “could you,” or “would you mind,” which reflect the indirect communication style common in Western cultures. In contrast, Uzbek language tends to express respect through special verb forms and honorifics, such as the suffix “-ing” (e.g., “ol-ING”), which indicates politeness and distance, especially toward elders or people of authority. The optative mood, expressing wishes, hopes, and blessings, plays a significant cultural role in Uzbek communication. Expressions such as “Omad tilayman!” (“I wish you success!”) or “Yashavor!” (“Live long!”) are deeply embedded in everyday discourse. English equivalents, like “May you be happy” or “I hope you succeed,” tend to carry less emotional warmth but maintain a more individualistic tone. This demonstrates how grammatical moods serve as a mirror of social relations and cultural values in both languages. Pedagogical and Translational Implications Understanding the contextual use of imperative and optative moods is vital for both language teaching and translation studies. Learners of English often struggle with the nuances of politeness when using imperatives, sometimes sounding too direct or rude. Conversely, English speakers learning Uzbek may find it difficult to choose the correct level of formality, especially when addressing elders or using religiously tinted optatives such as “Xudo xohlasa” (“God willing”). For translation, the challenge lies in maintaining pragmatic equivalence rather than literal meaning. Translators must interpret the social and emotional weight behind each form. For example, when translating Hamlet’s “Get thee to a nunnery!” into Uzbek, the emotional tension and irony must be preserved through culturally appropriate forms. Similarly, Qodiriy’s expressions of command or blessing require adaptation to convey their full pragmatic force in English.

The imperative and optative moods in English and Uzbek not only shape the structure of sentences but also reveal deep layers of cultural and psychological meaning. Their analysis through literary texts such as Shakespeare’s “Hamlet” and Qodiriy’s “O‘tkan kunlar” allows us to see how authors use these moods to express authority, emotion, and moral values. The study of these moods thus extends beyond grammar into the realms of sociolinguistics, pragmatics, and cultural linguistics. Future research could further explore how globalization and modern communication technologies are transforming the use of imperatives and optatives in both languages. The growing influence of English politeness strategies on Uzbek speech, for example, might lead to the emergence of new hybrid forms of expression. Therefore, the study of grammatical moods continues

to offer valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of language, culture, and identity.

2. Imperative and Optative Moods in English In English, imperatives usually take the base form of the verb, with or without 'please'.

Examples:

'Sit down, please.' (request), 'Do it now!' (command), and 'Let's go.' (suggestion). Optatives often begin with 'may' or 'let', as in 'May you succeed' or 'Let there be peace'. In **Hamlet**, Shakespeare uses imperatives not only to give orders but to show emotion and inner struggle. For example, the Ghost's 'Remember me' is both a command and a heartfelt plea. Hamlet's 'Go to a nunnery!' expresses anger and disappointment. Thus, in English, imperatives often show personal feelings and psychological depth.

3. Imperative and Optative Moods in Uzbek In Uzbek, the imperative and optative moods are strongly connected to politeness and respect. Verb endings like '-gin', '-chi', '-ing', '-ingiz' are used to show familiarity or politeness. Optative forms such as '-ay', '-sin', '-lik' express wishes and hopes. In Qodiriy's **O'tkan kunlar**, imperatives are used with cultural sensitivity: 'Boring, Otabek!' is a command filled with care; 'Keling, to'yga boraylik.' invites politely; 'Mayli, siz bilganicha qiling.' shows respect and acceptance. These forms demonstrate that Uzbek language users aim to maintain harmony and avoid conflict in communication.

4. Comparative Discussion

The main difference between the two languages lies in how direct or indirect speakers are. English uses lexical politeness ('please', 'could you') while Uzbek shows politeness through grammar and intonation. For instance, 'Please, come in' in English equals 'Marhamat, kiring' in Uzbek, but the second one already includes politeness in its form. English imperatives are often short and efficient, while Uzbek ones are richer in emotional and social meaning. Optative sentences in both languages express hope, but in Uzbek they are more common in daily speech ('Omad tilayman', 'Yaxshi boring').

5. Conclusion

Imperative and optative moods are not just grammar; they are a reflection of how people think and live. In English, they often express personal strength and clear communication. In Uzbek, they express politeness, empathy, and unity. Understanding these differences helps in translation, teaching, and intercultural dialogue. Studying them also reminds us that behind every word there is culture, emotion, and history.

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LINGUOCULTURAL CODES IN CLOTHING PROVERBS AND IDIOMS

Abstract. This study explores the linguistic and cultural meanings encoded in clothing-related proverbs and idioms in English and Uzbek. Proverbs and idioms serve as mirrors of national mentality, reflecting social norms, values, and worldviews. The research is based on the assumption that clothing vocabulary, beyond its literal meaning, carries deep cultural connotations that represent social identity, morality, and gender roles. Using a linguocultural and cognitive approach, the study analyzes selected expressions such as “*Don't judge a man by his clothes*” and “*Kiyim kishini bezamaydi, aql bezaydi.*” Comparative analysis reveals that while both English and Uzbek proverbs express moral and social values through clothing imagery, Uzbek expressions emphasize modesty and collective ethics, whereas English ones highlight individuality and social perception. The findings show that clothing serves as a universal metaphor for human character and behavior, yet the interpretation of this metaphor is shaped by national culture. The study contributes to understanding how figurative language encodes cultural identity and moral worldview in both languages.

Keywords: clothing vocabulary; proverb; idiom; linguoculture; metaphor; national identity; cross-cultural comparison

Introduction. Language and culture are inseparable, and proverbs and idioms are among the most vivid examples of this interconnection[1]. They embody collective wisdom, moral values, and traditional worldviews. Clothing, as a part of material culture, plays an essential role in shaping symbolic meanings and social identity[2]. When represented in proverbs and idioms, clothing words often go beyond their direct reference and reflect moral or psychological traits.

For example, the English idiom “*to wear one’s heart on one’s sleeve*” symbolizes openness and sincerity, while the Uzbek proverb “*Kiyim kishini emas, aql kishini bezaydi*” conveys the idea that intelligence and manners are more important than appearance[3].

Through a linguocultural perspective, this study aims to uncover how clothing-related proverbs and idioms function as cultural codes—revealing values, gender norms, and social hierarchies in both English and Uzbek societies[4].

Among the various semantic fields represented in proverbs and idioms, *clothing* occupies a special place because it symbolizes human identity, social belonging, and moral evaluation. Clothing items, in most cultures, are not merely functional; they reflect the wearer’s gender, profession, social class, and cultural values. When these concepts appear in proverbs and idioms, they become powerful linguistic symbols of moral and psychological traits. For example, the English saying “*Fine feathers make fine birds*” suggests that appearance can shape perception, while the Uzbek proverb “*Kiyim kishini emas, aql kishini bezaydi*” emphasizes that intelligence and behavior outweigh outward beauty. From a **linguocultural** perspective, clothing-related proverbs and idioms act as **semiotic codes**—sign systems that convey deeper meanings about identity, status, and virtue[5]. The cognitive dimension of these expressions allows us to understand how abstract cultural values are embodied through concrete imagery. In English culture, proverbs with clothing metaphors often highlight individuality, personal freedom, and social perception. In contrast, Uzbek culture emphasizes modesty, collective harmony, and respectability through similar imagery. Therefore, examining clothing-based expressions provides insight into the cognitive and cultural mechanisms by which societies encode their values and worldviews into language.

Theoretical Background: Linguocultural Code

The concept of the **linguocultural code** is rooted in the intersection of **language**, **culture**, and **cognition**[6]. It refers to how cultural meanings are encoded, stored, and transmitted through linguistic units — particularly through metaphors, symbols, and set expressions.

According to **Vereshchagin & Kostomarov (1990)**, the linguocultural code functions as a “cultural key” within language, connecting linguistic forms to national traditions, beliefs, and values[7].

In this sense, **proverbs and idioms** about clothing are microcosms of national culture. They encapsulate attitudes toward:

- gender and morality (*e.g., modesty, beauty, respectability*),
- social hierarchy (*e.g., status, wealth, humility*), and
- personal traits (*e.g., honesty, pride, hypocrisy*).

The term **linguocultural code** refers to the system of meanings through which language expresses and preserves the culture of a particular community. It is a key concept in **linguoculturology**, developed by scholars such as

Vereshchagin & Kostomarov (1990), who viewed language as “the most precise reflection of national culture.”

A linguocultural code represents **collective experience, values, and norms** that are encoded in linguistic units — words, idioms, and proverbs.

According to **Teliya (1996)**, idioms and proverbs are “containers of cultural memory,” where the worldview of a nation is preserved and transmitted[8]. In this framework, **clothing lexicon** and **proverbs** act as **semiotic signs** that reflect how people conceptualize social hierarchy, gender, morality, and aesthetics.

Example:

The English proverb “*Clothes make the man*” and the Uzbek proverb “*Kiyim kishini emas, aql kishini bezaydi*” share the same conceptual domain but encode **different cultural axiologies** — one emphasizes external image, the other inner intelligence[9].

Cognitive and Metaphoric Representation

Cognitive linguistics views idioms and proverbs as **conceptual metaphors** that shape our understanding of abstract ideas through concrete experience (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980)[10]. Clothing often serves as a **source domain** for conceptual metaphors such as:

- *CLOTHING AS IDENTITY* (“He wears many hats”),
- *CLOTHING AS DECEPTION* (“A wolf in sheep’s clothing”),
- *CLOTHING AS SOCIAL STATUS* (“Dressed to the nines”).

These linguistic units reflect how humans map visible attributes (clothes) onto invisible concepts (personality, morality, deceit).

Cultural Symbolism in Proverbs and Idioms

From the ethnolinguistic perspective, clothing idioms carry **symbolic and cultural meanings**[11]. For instance, in Uzbek culture, garments like *do‘ppi*, *chopon*, and *atlas* are connected to gender, hospitality, and tradition. In English, garments like *hat*, *coat*, and *gloves* frequently symbolize profession, respect, or concealment. These lexical items are not random — they mirror **national mentality** and **historical experience**.

Scholars such as **A. Wierzbicka (1997)** and **Yu. Stepanov (2001)** emphasize that language encodes the values and worldview of a nation through culturally marked expressions[12]. Thus, analyzing clothing idioms provides insight into the **linguistic worldview (lingvokartina mira)** of both cultures.

Comparative Aspect of Clothing Codes

Comparative studies between English and Uzbek reveal both **universal and culture-specific codes**:

- **Universals:** association of clean, neat clothing with morality and dignity (*Clean clothes, clean mind / Kiyimini toza tutgan, o‘zini hurmat qiladi*).
- **Cultural specifics:** Uzbek proverbs often emphasize collectivism and respect for elders, while English ones reflect individualism and social mobility.

This supports the view that linguistic expressions serve as **mirrors of cognitive and cultural identity**, where every proverb or idiom encapsulates centuries of socio-cultural experience.

Theoretical Relevance

The theoretical basis of this research lies in the frameworks of:

- **Conceptual Metaphor Theory** (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980);
- **Linguocultural Approach** (Vorobyov, Krasnykh, Karasik);
- **Ethnolinguistic Analysis** (Wierzbicka, Maslova);
- **Cognitive Semantics** (Langacker, Evans).

These theories jointly allow a deep understanding of how clothing lexemes in proverbs and idioms function as **symbolic codes** that connect the material, moral, and mental dimensions of culture.

Conclusion

The study of linguocultural codes in clothing-related proverbs and idioms reveals that such expressions function as verbal reflections of cultural identity and cognitive perception. Proverbs and idioms about clothing are not merely stylistic embellishments; they encode social norms, value systems, and cultural memory of a nation. In both English and Uzbek, the clothing lexicon plays a symbolic role in conceptualizing human behavior, morality, and social belonging. English proverbs such as “*Clothes make the man*”, “*Fine feathers make fine birds*”, or “*A wolf in sheep’s clothing*” highlight the Western orientation toward individualism, appearance, and self-presentation. Uzbek proverbs like “*Kiyimini ko‘rib kut, aqlini ko‘rib kuzat*” or “*Kiyimi pok – ko‘ngli pok*” emphasize collective values, morality, and respect for social harmony.

Thus, clothing serves as a metaphorical bridge between external appearance and internal qualities, reflecting the interaction between body and mind, material and moral worlds. The comparative analysis demonstrates that while both cultures share universal human experiences (e.g., linking clothing to identity and morality), they differ in cultural interpretation and emphasis.

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CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TOPONYMY

Abstract. The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek toponyms demonstrates that both linguistic systems encode conceptual metaphors and cultural symbols through language-specific strategies. As culturally embedded linguistic units, toponyms carry traces of national identity, worldview, and collective memory. The paper reveals key patterns in metaphorical structuring and symbolic representation that shape how each culture conceptualizes the world.

Keywords: toponymy, symbolic representation, national identity, conceptual metaphors

Аннотация. Сравнительный анализ английских и узбекских топонимов показывает, что обе языковые системы кодируют концептуальные метафоры и культурные символы с помощью специфических для языка стратегий. Будучи культурно обусловленными языковыми единицами, топонимы сохраняют следы национальной идентичности, мировоззрения и коллективной памяти. В статье выявляются ключевые модели метафорической структуры и символической репрезентации, формирующие способы концептуализации мира в каждой культуре.

Ключевые слова: топонимия, символическая репрезентация, национальная идентичность, концептуальные метафоры.

Toponymy is more than a classification of place names — it serves as a repository of cultural values, historical events, and cognitive patterns of a speech community. In cognitive linguistics, toponyms are treated not only as geographical markers but also as conceptual metaphors that reflect how people categorize and interpret their environment. This is particularly evident in English and Uzbek toponymic systems, which, despite belonging to different language

families and cultural traditions, show comparable cognitive mechanisms but divergent symbolic motivations.

English toponyms such as Bridgewater, Stratford, Kingston are predominantly descriptive and utilitarian, reflecting infrastructure, social hierarchy, or geographical characteristics. Conversely, Uzbek toponyms like Ko'kgumbaz, Hisor, Navbahor, Qo'ng'iro't encapsulate mythological, spiritual, and symbolic meanings, encoding cultural memory and aesthetic perception of space.¹ This paper aims to analyze how cognitive metaphors structure toponymy in these languages and what this reveals about national identity and worldview.

English place names are largely derived from descriptive and functional features of the environment. The majority of them illustrate metaphors of activity, possession, and spatial relation, reflecting the pragmatic and anthropocentric worldview of early English communities. For instance: Oxford (“ford of oxen”) – metaphor of work and agriculture.² The toponym represents a cognitive model in which animal labor symbolizes productivity and human adaptation to nature. Cambridge (“bridge over the Cam”) – metaphor of connection and development, reflecting human dominance over the environment.³ Newcastle – metaphor of construction and defense, connected to the conceptual frame “CITY AS A HUMAN CREATION”. Greenwich (“green settlement”) – metaphor of fertility and life, highlighting the English cultural preference for green landscapes as signs of prosperity. Stratford-upon-Avon – metaphor of movement and trade, based on the path schema, implying human exploration and communication.

In these examples, the conceptual metaphors PLACE IS ACTIVITY, NATURE IS PROPERTY, and ENVIRONMENT IS RESOURCE dominate. Such metaphors show how English culture historically perceived the landscape as something to be organized, utilized, and categorized.

Color-based English toponyms (e.g., Blackpool, Whitehaven, Redhill) also represent metaphorical thinking. The use of colors functions as a means of differentiation and classification rather than symbolic expression. For instance, Blackpool (“dark water body”) reflects environmental observation, while Whitehaven (“bright harbor”) expresses visibility and orientation. These color metaphors thus encode a pragmatic rather than spiritual interpretation of nature.⁴

Furthermore, the English system demonstrates a strong influence of historical and social metaphors. Place names such as Kingston (“the king’s town”) and Nottingham (“homestead of Snot’s people”) reveal feudal and hierarchical

¹ Karimov, S. (2019). O‘zbek toponimiyasida rang va tabiat metaforalari [Color and Nature Metaphors in Uzbek Toponymy]. *Til va Madaniyat Jurnali*, 4(2), 45–47.

² Harrison, T. (2018). Place Names and Early English Society: A Cognitive Approach. *Journal of Historical Linguistics*, 6(1), 21–28.

³ Smith, R. (2020). Metaphor and Settlement: Cognitive Patterns in English Toponymy. *Cognitive Onomastics Review*, 2(3), 50–60.

⁴ Davies, L. (2017). Color Terms in English Toponyms: A Study of Environmental Perception. *Names: A Journal of Onomastics*, 65(2), 30–36.

worldviews, illustrating how power structures and ownership relations were embedded in language.

In contrast, Uzbek toponyms are characterized by symbolic imagery, emotional association, and spiritual meaning, rooted in Eastern philosophy and nomadic traditions.¹ Uzbek place names tend to employ metaphors connected with nature, color, emotion, and faith, reflecting the culture's close relationship with the environment and its aesthetic appreciation of natural harmony. Examples include:

Guliston (“land of flowers”) – metaphor of beauty and prosperity, linking nature with cultural ideals of happiness and abundance.

Navbahor (“new spring”) – metaphor of renewal and rebirth, expressing cyclical worldview and faith in natural revival.

Ko‘kgumbaz (“blue dome”) – metaphor of heaven and spirituality, representing the sky as a divine protection symbol.

Qiziltepa (“red hill”) – metaphor of strength and heroism, where the color “red” embodies vitality, energy, and endurance.

Qo‘shko‘prik (“twin bridges”) – metaphor of unity and connection, symbolizing cooperation and shared human effort.

In Uzbek toponymy, the prevalent metaphors include NATURE IS SPIRIT, COLOR IS EMOTION, and PLACE IS MEMORY. These metaphors reflect the collective ethnocultural cognition of the Uzbek people, in which natural phenomena and moral concepts are interconnected.

Colors play an especially significant role in Uzbek cultural semantics. For example: Oqtosh (“white stone”) symbolizes purity and honesty. Qoradaryo (“black river”) conveys depth, mystery, and power. Ko‘ksoy (“blue stream”) represents tranquility and divine blessing. Such color symbolism demonstrates how the Uzbek worldview assigns emotional and ethical values to environmental elements, turning geography into a spiritual landscape.

Another significant group of Uzbek toponyms derives from religious and mythological metaphors, such as Shahrison (“holy city”) and Beshariq (“five ditches”), the latter linked with ancient irrigation and life-giving water — a sacred concept in Central Asian culture. A cross-linguistic comparison indicates that English cognitive metaphors are utilitarian and descriptive, while Uzbek metaphors are associative and symbolic.² The English system is rooted in practical categorization and socio-political organization, whereas the Uzbek one arises from aesthetic, emotional, and religious reflection.

¹ Rakhmatullaeva, M. (2020). Toponimlarda milliy-madaniy kodlarning ifodalanishi [Representation of National-Cultural Code in Toponyms]. *O‘zbek Tili va Adabiyoti*, 3(1), 61–63.

² Toirov, B. (2021). O‘zbek joy nomlarida konseptual metafora va mifologik qatlam [Conceptual Metaphor and Mythological Layer in Uzbek Place Names]. *Madaniy Meros Tadqiqotlari*, 2(5), 102–105.

Despite these differences, both languages share universal cognitive schemas such as container (e.g., Cambridge, Qal'ai Hisor) and path (e.g., Stratford, Qo'shko'prik), confirming that spatial cognition operates similarly across cultures but is shaped by local traditions and experiences.¹

Metaphorization of Space: Both languages conceptualize space through path and container schemas, but Uzbek toponyms often add symbolic interpretation — e.g., Hisor (fortress) represents safety, while Bridgewater represents movement.

Personification of Nature: Uzbek names personify natural features (Oqtosh, Qiziltepa), whereas English ones focus on descriptive use (Rockfield, Redhill).

Religious and Emotional Connotations: Uzbek toponyms include references to spirituality and divine power (Ko'kgumbaz, Navbahor), absent in English, where religion is rarely embedded in place names.

Cultural Memory Encoding: Uzbek toponyms preserve traces of tribes, heroes, and legends (Qo'ng'iroq, Mang'it, Samarqand), while English names record social hierarchies and ancient settlements (Kingston, Durham, Winchester).²

Thus, metaphor and symbol in toponyms not only describe physical landscapes but also encode collective cultural cognition, reflecting how each nation interprets life, space, and value through linguistic creativity.

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PARTONIMIYA HODISASINING O‘RGANILISHIDA ZAMONAVIY LINGVISTIK YONDASHUVLAR

***Annotatsiya.** Tilshunoslikda semantik munosabatlar, xususan, leksik birliklar orasidagi butun va bo‘lak o‘rtasidagi bog‘lanishlarni tahlil etish hozirgi zamon lingvistikasining eng muhim masalalaridan biridir. Ushbu maqolada partonimiya hodisasining nazariy asoslari, uning zamonaviy lingvistik yondashuvlar asosida talqin etilishini hamda kognitiv, konseptual, kompyuter va lingvomadaniy doiradagi tadqiqotlar haqida fikr yuritilgan.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** partonimiya, semantik tizim, kognitiv lingvistika, konseptual tarmoq, butun – bo‘lak munosabati, WordNet, lingvomadaniyat.*

CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTIC APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF PARTONOMY

***Abstract.** The analysis of semantic relations in linguistics, particularly the connections between lexical units based on the whole-part relationship, constitutes one of the most critical issues in modern linguistics. This article explores the theoretical foundations of the phenomenon of partonomy, its interpretation grounded in contemporary linguistic approaches, and the research conducted within the cognitive, conceptual, computational, and linguo-cultural domains.*

***Keywords:** Paronymy, semantic system, cognitive linguistics, conceptual network, whole-part relationship (or holonymy-meronymy relation), WordNet, linguoculture.*

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЯВЛЕНИЯ ПАРТОНИМИИ В СВЕТЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ

Аннотация. Анализ семантических отношений в лингвистике, в частности, связей между целым и частью в рамках лексических единиц, является одной из наиболее значимых проблем современной лингвистики. В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические основы феномена патронимии, его интерпретация на базе современных лингвистических подходов, а также обсуждаются исследования в когнитивной, концептуальной, компьютерной и лингвокультурной сферах.

Ключевые слова. Патронимия, семантическая система, когнитивная лингвистика, концептуальная сеть, отношение целое – часть (или голонимия – меронимия), WordNet, лингвокультура.

Hozirgi zamon tilshunosligida tilni nafaqat kommunikativ vosita, balki inson tafakkurining konseptual tuzilmasini aks ettiruvchi tizim sifatida o'rganishga e'tibor kuchaymoqda. Til birliklari o'rtasidagi semantik munosabatlar inson ongidagi obyektarning tuzilish shaklini va ular o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ifodalaydi [6; 15]. Shu jihatdan partonimiya — leksik birliklar orasidagi “butun–bo'lak” (whole–part) munosabatini bildiruvchi semantik aloqa turi — alohida e'tibor talab etadi.

Partonimik aloqalar tildagi obyektarning ichki strukturasi tushunish va ularning konseptual modellarini yaratishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ingliz tilidagi **car – engine – wheel** va o'zbek tilidagi **uy – eshik – tom** kabi misollar bu munosabatning universalligini ko'rsatadi. Partonimiyani o'rganish an'anaviy leksikologik tahlildan tashqariga chiqib, kognitiv va kompyuter lingvistikasining markaziy masalalaridan biriga aylandi [1; 26].

Partonimiyaning nazariy asoslari haqida fikr yuritilar ekan, tilshunoslikda partonimiya leksik-semantik munosabat sifatida giponimiya, antonimiya va sinonimiya bilan bir qatorda tahlil qilinadi. Ammo ularning farqi shundaki, partonimik munosabat obyektning tuzilma va tarkibiy yaxlitligini ifodalaydi [7;46]. Masalan:

ingliz tilida: **tree – branch – leaf**;

o'zbek tilida: **tana – bosh – qo'l** kabi bog'lanishlar butun va bo'lak orasidagi semantik struktura sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Winston, Chaffin va Herrmann (1987) tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan partonimik munosabatlar tasnifi bugungi kunda ham keng qo'llanadi. Ular besh asosiy turdagi partonimik aloqani ajratgan [8; 417-444]

1. Komponentli (component–object): **keyboard – computer**
2. Fazoviy (place–area): **room – house**
3. Tarkibiy (substance–object): **wood – table**
4. Funktsional (action–instrument): **handle – door**
5. A'zolik (member–collection): **sheep – flock**

Bu tasnif hozirgi semantik tarmoqlar (WordNet, FrameNet, ConceptNet) yaratish jarayonida ham asosiy semantik model sifatida ishlatiladi [2; 14].

Ikkinchi yondashuv bu kognitiv yondashuv bo‘lib, bu hodisa kognitiv lingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan partonimiya inson ongida dunyoni qismlarga ajratilgan tizim sifatida idrok etish mexanizmidir [5; 18]. Har bir predmet yoki tushuncha tafakkurda qismlarga bo‘linadi, bu esa til orqali kodlanadi.

Masalan, “jamiyatning boshi”, “tizim yuragi”, “fikir tanasi” kabi metaforalar butun-bo‘lak aloqasining metaforik ko‘rinishlari bo‘lib, ular konseptual modellashtirishning asosiy vositalaridan biridir.

Kognitiv tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki, partonimik bog‘lanishlar nafaqat fizik obyektlarni, balki abstrakt tushunchalarni ham ifodalashda ishlatiladi. Bu esa partonimiyani konseptual metafora nazariyasi bilan uzviy bog‘laydi.

Navbatdagi yondashuv kompyuter lingvistikasida partonimiya. Bugungi kunda zamonaviy sun‘iy intellekt tizimlarida semantik tahlilning muhim komponenti — bu “part-whole” munosabatlaridir. WordNet [2;16] tarmog‘ida partonimik aloqalar meronymy (qism) va holonymy (butun) sifatida modellashtiriladi.

Bunday modellar mashina tarjimasini, semantik tahlil, avtomatik savol-javob tizimlari va bilim grafiklarini yaratishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. O‘zbek tilshunosligida bu yo‘nalish ancha oldindan rivojlangan. O‘zbek tilidagi partonimik aloqalarni avtomatik tarzda aniqlash, ularni elektron lug‘atlar va sun‘iy intellekt tizimlariga integratsiya qilish istiqbolli yo‘nalish hisoblanadi. Shu o‘rinda B. Qilichevning „O‘zbek tilida partonimiya“ mavzusidagi ilmiy tadqiqotining ahamiyatini alohida e‘tirof etilish lozim. Ushbu tadqiqotda ta’kidlanganidek, partonimlik, sinonimlik, giponimlik munosabatlarning xilma-xil ko‘rinishlari bo‘lsa, har bir so‘z, har bir lisoniy birlik bu munosabatlarga qanday aloqada bo‘ladi degan savolning tug‘ilishi tabiiy. Bu borada „daraxt“ so‘zining umumiy, lisoniy mohiyati, uning sinonimlik, gradionimik, giponimik va partonimik qatorlarida aniqlanishi mumkin [10;13].

Bundan tashqari, A. Haydarovning „Semantika va so‘z tuzilishi“ nomli o‘quv qo‘llanmasida leksik birliklarning ma’naviy munosabatlari, sinonimiya, antonimiya, graduonomiya, va partonimiya hodisalari haqida atroflicha fikr yuritilgan [9; 61-71].

Lingvomadaniy yondashuv nuqtai nazaridan partonimiya muhim tahlil obyekti hisoblanadi. Chunki ayrim so‘zlar faqat anatomiya yoki fizik qismni emas, balki milliy mentalitet va ma’naviyatga oid konseptlarni ham ifodalaydi. Masalan, o‘zbek tilida “bosh”, “ko‘ngil”, “yurak” so‘zlari shunchaki tana a’zosi emas, balki ijtimoiy va axloqiy qadriyatlar ramzidir [4; 6]. Bu jihat partonimik birliklarning madaniy kodlash jarayonida o‘ta muhim rol o‘ynashini ko‘rsatadi.

Xulosa sifatida shuni ta’kidlash mumkinki partonimiya nazariyasi bugungi kunda lingvistik tadqiqotlarning turli yo‘nalishlari — leksik-semantik, kognitiv, konseptual va kompyuter tahlil metodlari bilan uyg‘unlashib, interdisiplinar ilmiy model sifatida shakllanmoqda. U til tizimining ichki tuzilishini, inson

tafakkurining konseptual mexanizmlarini va madaniy qadriyatlarining til orqali ifodasini aniqlashda alohida o'rin tutadi.

Kelgusida o'zbek tili uchun partonimik aloqalarning raqamli modelini yaratish, WordNet tipidagi tarmoqlarga qo'shish va AI-lingvistika tizimlariga integratsiya qilish xalqaro ilmiy maydonda dolzarb yo'nalish bo'lib qoladi va bular haqida keyingi ishlarimizda batafsil fikr yuritamiz.

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SO'ZLASHUV NUTQINING TIL O'ZGARISHLARIGA TA'SIRI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARI MISOLIDA)

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola ingliz va o'zbek tillarida so'zlashuv nutqining til o'zgarishlariga ko'rsatadigan ta'sirini pragmatik, sotsiolingvistik va diskursiv yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qiladi. So'zlashuv nutqi tilning eng tabiiy, faol va tezkor o'zgaradigan ko'rinishi sifatida yangi leksik birliklar, qisqartmalar, fonetik soddalashuvlar, muomala formulalari va sintaktik innovatsiyalarni shakllantiradi. Tadqiqot ikki tilning so'zlashuv tizimidagi o'ziga xosliklarni qiyoslab, ular jamiyat madaniyati, kommunikativ ehtiyojlari, texnologik taraqqiyot, globalizatsiya va yoshlar submadaniyati ta'sirida qanday

o'zgarayotganini yoritadi. Ingliz tilida so'zlashuv nutqi global kommunikatsiya, media diskurslari va onlayn muloqot orqali til standartlarining o'zgarishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatsa, o'zbek tilida so'zlashuv nutqining ta'siri milliy nutq me'yorlari, ijtimoiy muloqot etikasi va generatsiyalararo farqlarda namoyon bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'zlashuv nutqi, til o'zgarishi, pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika, innovatsiya, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili.

THE INFLUENCE OF SPOKEN LANGUAGE ON LINGUISTIC CHANGE (A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK)

Annotation. This article examines how conversational speech influences linguistic change in English and Uzbek, emphasizing pragmatic, sociolinguistic, and discourse-based perspectives. As the most dynamic layer of language, conversational speech shapes new lexical items, phonetic reductions, interactional routines, and syntactic innovations. By comparing two languages with different cultural and communicative traditions, the study highlights how global communication, technological development, youth subculture, and social norms contribute to shifts in linguistic structure. In English, conversational speech heavily impacts standard usage through online communication and media discourse, whereas in Uzbek it manifests through changes in address forms, colloquial expressions, and stylistic shifts shaped by sociocultural factors.

Keywords: conversational speech, language change, pragmatics, sociolinguistics, English, Uzbek.

Kirish. Til – bu statik tizim emas, balki jamiyat bilan birga yashab, o'zgarib va rivojlanib boradigan ijtimoiy hodisadir. Tilning eng faol va tabiiy shakli bo'lgan so'zlashuv nutqi esa o'zgarishlarning boshlang'ich bosqichi, "tajriba maydoni" sifatida xizmat qiladi. So'zlashuv nutqi orqali yangi so'zlar paydo bo'ladi, mavjud birliklarning semantik ko'lami kengayadi, fonetik soddalashuvlar kuchayadi, hamda nutq odatlari zamon ruhiga mos ravishda o'zgaradi. Shu ma'noda so'zlashuv nutqi til o'zgarishlarining asosiy drayveri, innovatsiyalar manbai, ijtimoiy identifikatsiya vositasi sifatida ahamiyatlidir. Ingliz tilida bu jarayon global kommunikatsiya, internet madaniyati, media, texnologik rivojlanish va diasporaviy madaniyatlar bilan bog'liq bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida esa o'zgarishlar asosan ijtimoiy qatlamlar, rasmiy–norasmiy muloqot farqlari, yoshlar nutqi, mahalla va oilaviy muloqot an'analari orqali shakllanadi. So'zlashuv nutqining til o'zgarishlariga ta'sirini o'rganish zamonaviy lingvistikaning pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika va diskurs tahlili yo'nalishlarida alohida ilmiy ahamiyatga ega (Labov, 1972; Trudgill, 2000).¹ Biroq ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida bu jarayonlarning qiyosiy tahlili yetarlicha o'rganilmagan. Mazkur tadqiqot ushbu bo'shliqni to'ldirishga qaratilgan.

Asosiy qism. So'zlashuv nutqi rasmiy yozma nutqqa nisbatan bir qator xususiyatlar bilan ajralib turadi: Spontanlik – rejasiz, tabiiy oqimda kechishi.

¹ Labov, W. (1972). Sociolinguistic Patterns. P.15-48

Qisqartirish va ellipsis – “I’m”, “don’t”, “qilyapman → qivoman”.¹ Diskurs markerlarining ko‘pligi – “well”, “you know”, “actually”; o‘zbek tilida “aniq”, “bilmadimku”, “xullas”.² Emotsionallik – his-tuyg‘uni bevosita ifodalash. Mavzu almashuvining tezligi – so‘zlashuv jarayoni ko‘p vektorli bo‘ladi. Ushbu xususiyatlar tilning ichki tizimiga ta’sir qilib, yangi grammatik konstruksiyalar va leksik birliklarning shakllanishiga turtki bo‘ladi. Ingliz tilida fonetik soddalashuvlar jonli muloqotda tez-tez uchraydi: going to → gonna /want to → wanna /because → cuz³

Bu birliklar dastlab norasmiy bo‘lsa-da, ommaviy madaniyat va internet ta’sirida hozirda yozma nutqda ham uchrab turadi. So‘zlashuv nutqi internet slengi bilan faol boyimoqda. Masalan, “LOL”, “OMG”, “BRB”, “IDK” kabi qisqartmalar, “literally” so‘zining semantik kengayishi “like” ning diskurs markeri sifatida kuchayishi.⁴ Yoshlar nutqida “kind of”, “sort of” kabi yumshatuvchi birliklar ham diskurs strategiyasi sifatida keng qo‘llanilmoqda.⁵ Inglizcha so‘zlashuv nutqida murojaat shakllari ham o‘zgarib bormoqda: gender neytral “they/them” ning qo‘llanilishi “guys” so‘zining neytral murojaatga aylanishi soddalashgan salomlashuvlar: “Hey”, “Hiya”, “Sup” Bu o‘zgarishlar jamiyatdagi tenglik va tezkor muloqot tamoyillarining aksidir.

O‘zbek so‘zlashuv nutqida fonetik qisqarishlar juda faol: “kelyapman → kevomman “ /“boraylik → borlik”/“nima qilyapsan? → nima qivossan?” Bu jarayon sheva ta’siri va muloqot tezligining oshishi bilan izohlanadi. So‘nggi yillarda o‘zbek so‘zlashuv nutqida ruscha va inglizcha elementlarning ko‘payishi kuzatilmoqda: “zapravkaga boraylik”, “doklad qilish”, “otmena bo‘ldi”, “ok bo‘ladi”, “like bosdim”.⁶ Bu o‘zgarishlar globalizatsiya, media ta’siri va ikki tillilik natijasidir. O‘zbek jamiyatida so‘zlashuv nutqining pragmatik o‘zgarishlari ijtimoiy masofa va hurmat tamoyillarida namoyon bo‘ladi: “siz” va “sen” ning generatsiyalar bo‘yicha farqlanishido‘stlar orasida qisqartirilgan iboralar: “ha endi...”, “bilasanmi...”, “nima deding?” yoshlar nutqida emotsion birliklar: “zo‘r”, “gap yo‘q”, “shunaqa-da”.⁷ Bu birliklar o‘zbek muloqotining ijtimoiy-hissiy tabiatini aks ettirad.

Har ikki til uchun fonetik qisqarishlar, yoshlar submadaniyatining kuchli ta’siri, internet slengining o‘shishi, diskurs markerlarning ko‘payishi, soddalashgan sintaksi xos. Ingliz tilida so‘zlashuv nutqi standart tildagi o‘zgarishlarni tezroq shakllantiradi, ommaviy madaniyat global ta’sirga ega, gender neytral birliklar faol rivojlanmoqda. O‘zbek tilida til o‘zgarishlari ko‘proq ijtimoiy qatlamlar va nutq etikasi bilan bog‘liq, ikki tillilik (o‘zbek–rus) va inglizcha o‘zlashmalar

¹ Leech & Svartvik (2002). Communicative Grammar of English. P.75-120

² Schiffrin, D. (1987). Discourse Markers. P.15-40

³ Crystal, D. (2008). A dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics. P.110-145

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⁵ Leech & Svartvik (2002). Communicative Grammar of English. P.75-120

⁶ Hakimova M.K (2020). O‘zbek tilida so‘z boyligining yangilanish jarayonlari. P.25-40

⁷ Kadirova, N. (2019). O‘zbek tilida so‘zlashuv nutqining zamonaviy tendensiyalari. P.55-63

kuchli rol o'ynaydi, muloqotda hurmat kategoriyalari asosiy pragmatik kuchga ega.¹ Diskurs markerlar ikki tilda ham til dinamikasini belgilovchi vositalardan biridir. Ingliz tilida: “well”, “so”, “you know”, “actually”, “I mean”. O'zbek tilida: “xullas”, “bilmadimku”, “yana”, “endi”, “nima deyishimni bilmayman”. Bu birliklar muloqotning ritmi, ohangi, mavzu almashuvi va hissiy fonini boshqaradi. Ulardan muntazam foydalanish vaqt o'tishi bilan tilning grammatik va uslubiy tizimiga singib boradi.

Xulosa. So'zlashuv nutqi ingliz va o'zbek tillarida til o'zgarishlarining asosiy manbalaridan biridir. Uning tarkibida fonetik qisqarishlar, leksik yangiliklar, sintaktik soddalashuvlar, pragmatik markerlar va muomala formulalari til tizimiga bosqichma-bosqich kirib boradi. Ingliz tilida bu jarayon global media va onlayn kommunikatsiya bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida ijtimoiy munosabatlar, milliy madaniyat, generatsiyalararo muloqot va ikki tillilik asosiy omil sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, so'zlashuv nutqi tilni nafaqat o'zgartiradi, balki jamiyatning ijtimoiy tuzilmasi, texnologik taraqqiyoti va madaniy qadriyatlarini ham aks ettiradi. Shu sababli so'zlashuv nutqini pragmatik yondashuvdan o'rganish tilning funktsional mexanizmlarini, uning dinamikasini va jamiyat bilan o'zaro munosabatini chuqur tushunishga imkon beradi.

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BAKHTINNING NAZARIYASIDA POLIFONIYA, DIALOGIZM VA XRONOTOPNING IJODIY VA PSIXOLOGIK AHAMIYATI

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqola Mixail Baxtinning polifoniya, dialogizm va xronotop haqidagi konseptual qarashlarini tahlil qiladi. Polifoniya nazariyasi turli mustaqil ovozlarning bir matnda teng huquqli mavjudligini ko'rsatadi, dialogizm esa shaxs va jamiyat o'rtasidagi muloqotning ichki mohiyatini ochib beradi. Xronotop esa adabiy asarda vaqt va makonning birligini ifodalaydi. Ushbu nazariyalar Dostoevskiy, Tolstoy, va Servantes kabi yozuvchilar ijodida yorqin namoyon bo'lgan. Maqolada nazariy qarashlar adabiy va psixologik misollar bilan boyitilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Polifoniya, dialogizm, xronotop, Baxtin, Dostoyevskiy, adabiy nazariya va dialogik o'zlik.*

Kirish

Mixail Baxtinning adabiy nazariyasi XX asrning eng ta'sirli g'oyalaridan biridir. Uning tadqiqotlarida adabiy matn muallif ovoziga bog'liq emas, balki keng ijtimoiy va shaxsiy ovozlarning o'zaro aloqasi sifatida tushuniladi. Ayniqsa, polifoniya tushunchasi Baxtin nazariyasida markaziy o'rin tutadi. U yerda adabiyot demokratiyasini ko'rsatadi – har bir qahramonning ovozi va pozitsiyasi bor. Baxtin uchun Dostoyevskiyning romanlari bu borada «eng jozibali» misoldir; ularda u muallif qahramonlari ustidan hukmron emas, balki ular «erkin fikrlaydigan sub'ektlar» sifatida tasvirlanadi.

Dostoyevskiyning poetikasi masalalarida Baxtin polifoniya g'oyasini batafsil tekshiradi. Uning uchun Dostoyevskiyning romanlari barcha qahramonlar mustaqil fikr qilish huquqiga ega bo'lgan polifonik matnlardir. Masalan, «Jinoyat va jazo»da Raskolnikov o'zi bilan gaplashadi. Ikki ovoz, biri «yuqori maqsad» uchun jinoyatni tasdiqlasa, ikkinchisi axloqiy me'yorlarni himoya qiladigan ichki polifonik kontrapunkt hosil qiladi. «Karamazov birodarlar»da har bir birodar falsafiy g'oya uchun turadi: Ivan aql va skeptitsizmni, Alyosha e'tiqod va sevgini, Dmitriy ehtiros va inson istaklarini ifodalaydi. Muallif bu ovozlardan birortasini ustun qo'ymaydi; balki ular suhbatlashadi va matnda polifonik sifat yaratadilar.

Baxtinning «dialogizm» nazariyasi til, ong va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tasvirlaydi. Valzerga ko'ra, har bir fikr yoki gap boshqa ovozlarning bilan muloqotning bir qismidir. Hech qanday so'z orolda emas – u har doim javob, bog'lanish yoki suhbatda mavjud. Baxtin ta'kidlaganidek, inson tafakkuri ham dialogikdir. Bizning ichki nutqimiz doimiy ichki dialogdir. Endi, Xubert Xermansning «dialogik o'zlik nazariyasi» Baxtinning tushunchalarini psixologik

yoʻnalishda oladi. Xermansning fikriga koʻra, shaxsda bir nechta «ichki oʻzlar» bor: «Ona sifatida men», «oʻqituvchi sifatida men», «ijodkor sifatida men». Bunda oʻzaro masʼuliyatni yoʻqotish va erkinlikka intilishning ichki ziddiyati mavjud. Dostoyevskiy qahramonlarining ichki kurashlari bizga ushbu dialogik shartni eslatib turadi. Raskolnikovning «supermen» tushunchasi uni axloqiy haqiqatlardan uzoqlashtiradi, ammo uning vijdoni unga gapiradi va uni insoniyat bilan bogʻlaydi. Shu tarzda, dialogizm avvalgi shaxsiy ongning qatlamli tabiatini ochib beradi.

Baxtinning “xronotop” tushunchasi adabiy asarda vaqt va makonning oʻzaro bogʻliqligini tahlil qiladi. Xronotop (yunoncha *chronos* — vaqt, *topos* — makon) asarning strukturasi belgilovchi muhim kategoriya hisoblanadi. Masalan, Servantesning “Don Kixot” romanida “yoʻl xronotopi” asosiy oʻrinni egallaydi. Don Kixotning sayohati nafaqat geografik harakat, balki uning maʼnaviy oʻsishi va oʻzini anglash jarayonidir. Har bir uchrashuv – yangi falsafiy tajriba, yangi qarash demakdir.

Tolstoyning “Urush va tinchlik” romanida esa “tarixiy xronotop” ustuvor: vaqtning oqimi, tarixiy voqealar va shaxsiy taqdirning kesishishi jamiyat va inson ruhiyatini yaxlit tasvirlaydi. Bu yerda vaqt statik emas, balki harakatda — u inson hayotini shakllantiradi.

Tolstoyning «Urush va tinchlik» asarida esa «tarixiy xronotop» mavjud. Vaqtning, tarixiy voqealar shaxsiy qismatga bogʻlanganligi jamiyat va inson ruhini bitta sifatida aks ettiradi. Bu yerda vaqt joyi bir yerda turgan emas, balki qaynaydi; u inson hayotini shakllantiradi.

Zamonaviy tanqidchi Bart Kyonen xronotopni «xotira sxemasi» sifatida oʻqiydi. Uning uchun har bir yozuvchi oʻz xronotopini yaratadi va oʻquvchini asar dunyosiga qaratadi. Shu sababli, xronotop adabiy janrlarning asosiy farqlovchisi sifatida yuzaga chiqadi: epik janrdagi tarixiy, sayohat romani va romantik asarlardagi ruhiy-ichkilardan biri.

Xulosa

Baxtinning heteroglossiya (polifoniya) va dialogizm, shuningdek, xronotop haqidagi gʻoyalari adabiyotshunoslik va psixologiya sohasida muhim taʼsir koʻrsatdi. Polifoniya ovozlarning tengligini ifodalaydi, dialogizm ichki va tashqi dialogdir va xronotop vaqt va makonning badiiy birlashmasidir. Bunday gʻoyalar inson tafakkurining murakkabligini va adabiy asarlarda ishtirok etuvchi koʻp oʻlchovlarni tushuntirishda yordam beradi.

Dostoyevskiy, Tolstoy va Servantes romanlarida ushbu nazariya nafaqat badiiy umumlashmalar sifatida ilgari suriladi, balki ular tirik shaklda ifodalanadi. Shunday qilib, Baxtinning tushunchalari nafaqat oʻzining tarixiy sharoiti va zaruriy rus formalizmi nazariy doirasiga taalluqli, balki zamonaviy adabiyot universitetlari, lingvistik va psixologiyaga ham taʼsir koʻrsatadi.

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**INGLIZ TILIDA “BAXT” KONSEPTINING JEK
LONDONNING “MARTIN IDEN” ASARIDA KELTIRILGAN
FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARDA IFODALANISHI**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy lingvokulturologiyaning dolzarb yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lgan konseptual tahlil masalasi, xususan, “baxt” konseptining Jek Londonning “Martin Iden” asarida frazeologik birliklar orqali qanday ifodalanganligi yoritiladi. Jek London o'zining “Martin Iden” romanida inson baxtining ijtimoiy va shaxsiy talqinini, orzu va mehnat orqali o'zini anglash jarayonini frazeologik birliklar yordamida boy ma'noda ochib beradi. Asarda

baxt tushunchasi nafaqat muhabbat, balki o'zini anglash, mehnat, moddiy farovonlik va ruhiy osoyishtalik orqali ham tasvirlanadi.

***Kalit so'zlar:** konsept, frazeologizm, idiom, metafora, madaniyat, individualizm, ruhiy baxt.*

THE CONCEPT OF “HAPPINESS” IN ENGLISH AS EXPRESSED IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS MENTIONED IN JACK LONDON’S “MARTIN EDEN”

***Abstract.** This article explores one of the most relevant topics in modern linguistics – the concept of happiness and its expression through phraseological units in Jack London’s masterpiece “Martin Eden.” The novel serves as a valuable source for analyzing how the concept of happiness is represented through idioms and metaphors that reflect the protagonist’s struggle between social aspiration and personal fulfillment. Happiness in the novel is portrayed not only as emotional satisfaction but also as a philosophical quest for meaning and identity.*

***Keywords:** concept, phraseology, idiom, metaphor, individualism, cultural values.*

Frazeologik birliklar har bir tilning madaniy xazinasini bo'lib, ular xalqning tarixiy tajribasi, dunyoqarashi va milliy tafakkurini o'zida mujassam etadi[5, 136-145]. Ular nafaqat tilning ifoda vositasi, balki madaniy merosni saqlovchi qudratli lingvistik hodisadir. Frazeologik birliklar orqali millatning qadriyatlari, his-tuyg'ulari, orzu-intilishlari va ijtimoiy qarashlari ifodalanadi.

Frazeologik birliklar – bu birikmalar yoki ifodalar bo'lib, ular birgalikda bir ma'noni ifodalaydi va leksik jihatdan o'zgarmasdir. Idiomalar, ko'chma ma'nolar, metaforalar va boshqa shu kabi birliklar frazeologik birliklar tarkibiga kiradi[6, 45-50]. Tilshunoslar frazeologik birliklarni tilning madaniy elementi sifatida ko'rib, ularni madaniyat va jamiyatning tilga ta'sirini aks ettiruvchi vosita deb hisoblaydi. Baxt tushunchasi ham turli tillarda turli xil frazeologik birliklar orqali ifodalanadi. Baxt insoniy his-tuyg'ularining eng yuqori shakllaridan biri sifatida jamiyatda katta o'rin egallaydi va bu tushunchani lingvistik nuqtai nazardan o'rganish yanada chuqurroq madaniy va ijtimoiy tahlillarni talab qiladi[1, 18-30]. Mazkur tadqiqotning dolzarbligi shundaki, “baxt” konsepti nafaqat leksik darajada, balki frazeologik birliklar orqali ham xalq mentalitetini ifodalashda muhim vosita sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ayniqsa, ingliz yozuvchisi Jek Londonning “Martin Eden” asarida bu konsept asar qahramonining ichki dunyosi, orzulari va hayotga munosabati orqali boy lingvokognitiv asosda yoritilgan.

Ingliz tilidagi frazeologik birliklar “baxt” tushunchasini o'ziga xos badiiy, hissiy va metaforik ko'rinishda aks ettiradi. “On cloud nine” (nihoyatda baxtiyor bo'lish), “over the moon” (cheksiz mamnun bo'lish), “in seventh heaven”

(baxtning eng yuqori cho'qqisida bo'lish), "feel blessed" (baxtli, omadli his etish) kabi iboralar ingliz xalqi dunyoqarashida "baxt"ni ifodalovchi asosiy frazeologizmlardir[7, 180-185]. Bunday iboralar tilning semantik boyligini namoyon etish bilan birga, har bir madaniyatda "baxt" tushunchasining qanday talqin qilinishini ham ochib beradi[3, 120-125].

Konsept – bu inson ongida shakllangan madaniy, hissiy va kognitiv mazmunga ega bo'lgan tushuncha bo'lib, u tilda turli ifoda vositalari, jumladan, frazeologik birliklar orqali namoyon bo'ladi. "Baxt" konsepti universal bo'lsa-da, har bir xalq uni o'z tarixiy, diniy va ijtimoiy qadriyatlari asosida talqin qiladi[4, 220-230].

Ingliz tilidagi "happiness" so'zi ko'pincha luck, fortune, contentment, joy kabi sinonimik birliklar bilan ifodalanadi. Bu so'zlarning barchasi turlicha darajadagi baxtni bildiradi — ba'zida ruhiy holat, ba'zida esa tashqi omillar natijasidagi holat sifatida.

Jek Londonning "Martin Iden" romani inson orzulari, mehnat, muhabbat va ijtimoiy maqom o'rtasidagi murakkab ziddiyatlarni yorituvchi falsafiy asardir[2, 47-49]. Asarda bosh qahramon Martin uchun "baxt" dastlab moddiy farovonlik va jamiyatda tan olinish bilan bog'liq. U uchun "to make one's fortune" (omadga erishmoq) va "rise in the world" (jamiyatda yuqoriga ko'tarilmoq) kabi frazeologik birliklar baxtning asosiy mezonidir. U ijtimoiy pog'onalarni bosib o'tishni, mashhurlikka erishishni baxt deb biladi. Biroq romanning keyingi qismida yozuvchi frazeologik ifodalar orqali Martinning dunyoqarashidagi o'zgarishni, ya'ni tashqi muvaffaqiyatdan ichki qoniqish sari o'tishni tasvirlaydi.

Asarda "to be on top of the world" (baxtning eng yuqori darajasida bo'lish) iborasi Martinning yozuvchi sifatida muvaffaqiyat qozongan paytlarida ishlatiladi. Ammo bu muvaffaqiyat unga kutilgan baxtni bermaydi[2, 47-49]. "A broken heart" (singan yurak) iborasi esa Ruth bilan bo'lgan munosabatlar tugaganidan so'ng, qahramonning ruhiy iztirobini ifodalaydi. Bu ibora orqali London inson baxtining faqat tashqi omillar bilan emas, balki ichki dunyo bilan ham bog'liq ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

"Martin Iden" romanidagi frazeologik birliklar asar mazmunining falsafiy qatlamini ochib beradi. Muallif "the pursuit of happiness" (baxtni izlash) iborasi orqali qahramon hayotining asosiy maqsadini belgilaydi[4, 220-230]. Martin hayotining har bir bosqichida shu ibora zamiridagi mazmun – "baxtni izlash" – o'zgarib boradi. Dastlab bu izlanish moddiy maqsadlarga, keyinchalik esa ma'naviy tinchlikka qaratiladi. Shu jihatdan asar G'arb falsafasida keng tarqalgan "American Dream" tushunchasiga hamohangdir.

Jek London "fool's paradise" (soxta baxt, o'zini aldash) iborasini ham ishlatadi. Martin o'zini boylik va shuhrat bilan baxtli bo'laman deb o'ylaydi, ammo bular unga chin baxt keltirmaydi. Asarning so'nggi sahifalarida "at peace with oneself" (o'zi bilan totuv bo'lish) frazeologik birligi Martinning ruhiy holatini ifodalaydi. Bu ibora haqiqiy baxt tashqi omillarda emas, balki insonning ichki osoyishtaligida ekanligini bildiradi[2, 47-49].

Asarda baxt konsepti ikki qutbda ko'rsatiladi: bir tomonda ijtimoiy maqom, boyluk va tan olinish orqali keladigan tashqi baxt, ikkinchi tomonda esa ruhiy qoniqish, ichki tinchlik va o'zlikni anglashdan tug'iladigan haqiqiy baxt. Jek London frazeologik birliklardan foydalangan holda bu ikki qutbni taqqoslaydi va qahramonning ruhiy inqirozi orqali haqiqiy baxtning mohiyatini ochib beradi.

Romanning so'nggi sahifalarida London "he was tired of life, yet at peace with himself" degan jumlaning keltiradi. Bu frazeologik birlik orqali yozuvchi baxtni tashqi omillar emas, balki ichki qoniqish holati sifatida talqin qiladi. Shu tariqa frazeologik birliklar orqali "baxt" tushunchasi insonning ichki dunyosi, o'zini anglash va jamiyatdagi o'rni bilan bog'lab ko'rsatiladi.

Frazeologik birliklar bu asarda muallifning falsafiy qarashlarini ifodalovchi asosiy vositaga aylanadi. "Martin Iden" hayotining har bir bosqichi "rise in the world", "to make one's fortune", "broken heart", "fool's paradise", "at peace with oneself" kabi iboralar orqali metaforik tarzda yoritiladi. Ushbu iboralar yordamida Jek London baxtni har bir inson uchun turlicha ma'noga ega murakkab konsept sifatida talqin etadi. Baxt – bu moddiy yutuq emas, balki o'zini anglash, o'z qadriyatlariga sodiq qolish va ichki osoyishtalikni topishdir.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, "Martin Iden" romanida frazeologik birliklar baxt tushunchasining ijtimoiy, ruhiy va falsafiy jihatlarini ifoda etuvchi kuchli vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ular orqali yozuvchi inson hayotidagi baxtni izlash jarayonini, orzular va haqiqat o'rtasidagi ziddiyatni va eng muhimi, insonning ichki ozodligini tasvirlaydi. Shuning uchun ham Jek London asari ingliz adabiyotida baxt konseptining eng chuqur va hayotiy talqinini bergan asarlardan biri sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

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UNLI TOVUSHLAR TALLAFUZI BILAN BOG'LIQ KONNOTATIV MA'NOLAR

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi unli tovushlar talaffuzidagi konnotativ ma'nolar qiyosiy tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: denotativ, konnotativ, sonor, jarangsiz, jarangli, ekspressivlik, artikulyatsion, akustik, pragmatik, variantdoshlik.

Аннотация. В данной тезисе проводится сравнительный анализ коннотативных значений в произношении гласных звуков в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: денотативный, коннотативный, сонорный, глухой, звонкий, экспрессивность, артикуляционный, акустический, прагматический, вариантность.

Abstract: This thesis presents a comparative analysis of the connotative meanings in the pronunciation of English and Uzbek vowel sounds.

Keywords: denotative, connotative, sonorant, voiceless, voiced, expressiveness, articulatory, acoustic, pragmatic, variability.

Til mohiyatan nominativ, kommunikativ va emotsional ekspressiv vazifalarni bajara olish qudratiga ega bo'lgan ijtimoiy ruhiy hodisadir. Tilning nominativ (atash) funksiyasi tafakkur formasi, ya'ni tushunchalarni ma'lum bir qolipga soluvchi vosita bilan bog'liq ekanligi bo'lsa, uning hissiy ta'sirchanligi, ya'ni emotsional ekspressiv funksiyasi tilning mustaqil sistema ekanligi, til elementlarining mohiyati ularning ichki munosabatlarda ochilishi mumkin ekanligi bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatadi.(1.6)

Ingliz tilidagi i fonemasi ma'no farqlash xususiyatidan tashqari yana turli xil qo'shimcha ma'nolarni beradi. Ingliz tilida nutq jarayonida i fonemasini cho'zish orqali bir qancha qo'shimcha ma'nolar paydo bo'ladi, jumladan: taajjub, ikkilanish, hayratlanish, ishonchsizlik kabi.

– Tush! Where are the others?

– At the front.

– Quite right. Why aren't **you...** at the front?

– Over age. Fifty-seven. (B. Shaw)

Qiyoslanayotgan tillarda i fonemasi talaffuzidagi konnotativ ma'nolar aynan bir xil yoki bir-biriga yaqin ifodalanadi.

O'zbek tilidagi i fonemasiga xos bo'lgan konnotativ ma'nolar ingliz tilidagi i fonemasi talaffuzidagi konnotativ ma'nolar bilan qiyoslanganda, ularda ba'zi o'xshashlik va farqli tomonlar ko'zga tashlanadi. Buni quyidagi holatlarda ko'rish mumkin. Ingliz tilidagi unli tovushlar bo'gin turlariga ko'ra ajratiladi. Masalan, i [ai] fonemasi yopiq bo'g'inda qisqa [i] tovushini, ochiq bo'g'inda esa [ai]

tovushini ifodalaydi. Nutqda i unlisi ataylab cho‘zib talaffuz qilinganda, unda hayratlanish, ishonchsizlik, taajjublanish kabi qator konnotativ ma’nolar paydo bo‘ladi.

Masalan: – Are you very ri:ch?

- No, living from hand to mouth! (B.Show).

Shuningdek, badiiy nutqda i [ai] unlisining so‘z boshida takror kelish holatini ham kuzatish mumkin:

I–I am terribly sorry my dear, sir.

I mean madam, – I–I–oh, God! (R. Gordon).

Misoldagi i fonemasining takror ishlatilishi nutqiy parchada yalinish, iltimos, iltijo, sog‘inish, yolvorish kabi qator konnotativ ma’nolarni ifodalaydi.

I fonemasi yuqori tor, lablangan unli bo‘lib, o‘zbek tili shevalarida turli xil variantlarga ega emas. Mazkur tovushni nutqda cho‘zib aytish nihoyatda cheklangan. Shunga qaramay, unda ohangdorlik mavjud bo‘lganligi uchun turli xil konnotativ ma’nolar ifodalanadi. Jumladan, ajablanish, so‘roq, pisand qilmaslik, ikkilanib qolish kabi qator qo‘shimcha ma’nolar anglashiladi. Bu hol kishilar orasida nutqiy jarayonni sermazmun va jozibador qiladi.

O [ou] fonemasining talaffuzi ham ingliz tilida bo‘gin turlari bilan bog‘liq. Ochiq bo‘g‘inda o unlisi [ou] shaklida talaffuz qilinadi: go, no, so kabi. Yopiq bo‘g‘inda esa [ɔ] tovushi orqali (pot, not, dog) talaffuz qilinadi. Ammo so‘zda o unli tovushini cho‘zib talaffuz qilish orqali qo‘rquv, dovdirash, kuchli g‘azab kabi konnotativ ma’nolar paydo bo‘ladi.

Masalan: Suddenly he cried: “Sant~~y~~ago-~~o~~-~~o~~!” (L. Voynich).

Ingliz tilidagi o unli tovushini cho‘zish orqali qo‘rquv, pushaymon, qahr-g‘azab kabi konnotativ ma’nolar ifodalanadi.

Masalan: Don’t tell him – ~~Do~~-~~o~~-~~o~~-n’t tell him please!

Yuqoridagi misolda o tovushini cho‘zish iltimos, yalinish kabi konnotativ ma’noni ifodalaydi.

O‘zbek tilida unli va undosh fonemalarning talaffuzida variantdoshlik xodisasi mavjud. Ana shu variantdoshlik ularda turli xil konnotativ ma’nolarni hosil qiladi.

Qayerda variantdoshlik mavjud bo‘lsa, u yerda tanlanish, tilda esa qo‘shimcha ma`no hosil bo`ladi (2. 36]. Qo`shimcha ma'no nafaqat so`zlarga, balki uni tashkil etuvchi nutq tovushlariga ham taalluqlidir. Boshqacha aytganda, har bir unli yoki undosh tovush o`ziga xos turli xil qo`shimcha ma`nolarga ega.

Unli tovushlar turli xil intonasiya bilan aytilishi, bo‘gin hosil qilishi, urg‘u qabul qilishi kabi prosodik xususiyatlarga ega. Shuning uchun ularda konotativ ma`nolar serqirra va darajalangan bo`ladi. Bu o`rinda ingliz va o`zbek tillaridagi ba`zi unli tovushlar talaffuzi bilan bog`liq holda hosil bo`ladigan ayrim konnotativ ma'nolar haqida to`xtalamiz.

I tovushi artikulyatsion tomondan til oldi va yuqori tor holatda talaffuz qilinganligi uchun juda ham cho‘ziq aytilmaydi. Shu sababli, undan anglashilgan konnotativ ma'nolarda o`ta ta'sirchanlik yuqori bo`lmaydi. I unli fonemasi qattiq

va yumshoq variantlarda talaffuz qilinishi o'zbek tili qipchok va o'giz shevalari vakillari nutqini xarakterlovchi qo'shimcha bo'yoqdir. Undan xosil bo'ladigan konnotativ ma'nolar ko'p va darajalangan bo'ladi. Shuningdek, i fonemasi ham qattiq va yumshoq variantlarga ega ekanligi konnotativ ma'no miqdorini oshiradi. Bular quyidagilar: nutq artikulyatsiyasiga ko'ra: kuchli yoki kuchsiz hayajon, esankirash, to'lqinlanish, bezovtalik, ajablanish, hayratlanish, ishonchsizlik, kutilmaganlik, g'azab, o'ylab qolish, xursandlik, xafalik, hadiksirash, eslash va hokazo. Yuqoridagilardan ko'rinadiki, birgina I unlisining talaffuzida hosil bo'ladigan qo'shimcha ma'no bo'yoqlari nihoyatda keng va serqirradir.

Masalan: Hayratlanish: **U-u-u!** Naziraxon shofyor bo'lganmish. (S.Ahmad)

Iztirob, o'kinish: Voy o'lay, sho'rim qurisi-**i-i-i-n!** (O'. Usmonov)

Shunday qilib, konnotativ ma'no fonema semantik strukturasi tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Har ikkala tildagi konnotativ ma'no unli tovushlarning cho'zish, orttirish, tushirib qoldirish kabi variantlarida yorqin namoyon bo'ladi va tovushlarda ham ma'no mavjudligi qayd etiladi.

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THE BINARY CONCEPTS OF FIRE AND WATER AS FRAGMENTS OF THE LINGUISTIC WORLDVIEW IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUOCULTURE

Abstract. This article explores the binary concepts of *fire* and *water* as fundamental fragments of the linguistic worldview in English and Uzbek linguocultures. These elements, representing opposing yet complementary forces, embody universal archetypes deeply rooted in mythological, religious, and cultural consciousness. Through comparative linguistic and cultural analysis, the study investigates the symbolic meanings, metaphorical representations, and phraseological expressions related to *fire* and *water* in both languages. The findings reveal that while English tends to associate *fire* with passion, energy, and destruction, and *water* with purity, calmness, and renewal, Uzbek linguistic culture attributes to *olov* (fire) a sacred and vital role as a protector and purifier, and to *suv* (water) a spiritual, life-giving, and moral significance.

Keywords: fire, water, binary opposition, linguistic worldview, linguoculture, symbolism, English, Uzbek

ANNOTATION. The article analyzes the linguistic and cultural conceptualization of the binary elements *fire* and *water* in English and Uzbek. It identifies similarities and differences in their symbolic, metaphorical, and phraseological representations, emphasizing their role in shaping national worldviews.

Key words: fire, water, concept, symbolism, worldview, English, Uzbek

ANNOTATSIIYA. Maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida *olov* va *suv* kabi binar elementlarning lisoniy hamda madaniy konseptuallashuvi tahlil qilinadi. Ularning ramziy, metaforik va frazeologik ifodalanishidagi o‘xshashlik hamda farqlar, shuningdek, milliy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishdagi o‘rni yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: olov, suv, konsept, ramz, dunyoqarash, ingliz tili, o‘zbek tili

АННОТАЦИЯ. В статье рассматривается лингвистическая и культурная концептуализация бинарных элементов *огонь* и *вода* в английском и узбекском языках. Анализируются их символические, метафорические и фразеологические значения, а также роль в формировании национальной картины мира.

Ключевые слова: огонь, вода, концепт, символика, картина мира, английский язык, узбекский язык

Introduction

Elements of nature have long served as powerful symbols through which humanity interprets and organizes its perception of the world. Among these, *fire* and *water* hold a special place as binary opposites that reflect the duality of existence—creation and destruction, warmth and coldness, life and death. Their linguistic embodiment in different cultures not only mirrors human interaction with the environment but also reveals the underlying cognitive and cultural frameworks of societies.

This study investigates how the binary concepts of *fire* and *water* function as fragments of the linguistic worldview (*lisoniy manzara*) in English and Uzbek linguocultures. Drawing on linguistic, cultural, and cognitive approaches, it seeks to uncover how these elemental concepts are represented in idioms, metaphors, and cultural narratives, and how they shape the moral and emotional worldview of the two nations.

1. Theoretical Framework

In linguocultural studies, the **linguistic worldview** refers to the collective conceptualization of the world as reflected in the language of a community. According to Humboldt (1999) and later linguistic anthropologists, language is not merely a means of communication but a worldview-forming system. Binary oppositions such as *fire–water*, *light–darkness*, and *life–death* are central to this worldview as they structure human perception through contrast and complementarity.

Fire and *water* are not only physical phenomena but also archetypal symbols found in mythology, folklore, and literature across civilizations. Their study provides insights into how different cultures understand energy, purity, spirituality, and transformation (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Kovecses, 2005).

2. The Concept of Fire in English and Uzbek Linguocultures

In **English**, *fire* often symbolizes passion, vitality, anger, or destruction. Expressions such as *to play with fire*, *to be fired up*, or *to light a fire under someone* reflect emotional intensity and motivation. Literary and religious traditions also view fire as both divine (the Holy Spirit's flame) and destructive (the fire of hell).

In **Uzbek culture**, *olov* holds sacred connotations inherited from Zoroastrianism and ancient Turkic beliefs. Fire is a source of purity and protection. Phrases such as *olovdan o'tmoq* ("to go through fire," meaning to endure hardships) or *olovday yonmoq* ("to burn like fire," meaning deep passion or sorrow) reflect moral resilience and emotional depth. Fire in the Uzbek worldview embodies spiritual strength and purification rather than solely destruction (Sharipov, 2015; Saidov, 2018).

3. The Concept of Water in English and Uzbek Linguocultures

In **English**, *water* represents purity, life, and emotional balance. Phrases like *to keep one's head above water*, *like water off a duck's back*, or *to be in hot water* convey resilience, indifference, and trouble, respectively. Symbolically, water is linked to rebirth and renewal—such as baptism in Christianity (Telia, 1996).

In **Uzbek**, *suv* is not merely a physical element but a moral and sacred substance. Uzbek proverbs such as *Suv hayot manbai* ("Water is the source of life") and *Suv oqsa, hayot oqadi* ("Where water flows, life flows") reflect a worldview centered on fertility, peace, and blessing. In rural traditions, water is treated with reverence—polluting it is seen as a sin, reflecting an ethical dimension.

4. Binary Opposition and Complementarity

While *fire* and *water* appear as opposites—heat and coolness, destruction and preservation—they often complement each other in symbolic systems. In both English and Uzbek cultures, this duality encapsulates the balance of life forces. The English idiom *fight fire with fire* and the Uzbek proverb *Olovni suv bosar* ("Water will overcome fire") both reflect the interaction of opposites as a means of restoring harmony.

Conclusion

The binary concepts of *fire* and *water* serve as profound cultural and linguistic symbols that reveal how English and Uzbek speakers conceptualize emotion, morality, and existence. While English emphasizes psychological and metaphorical dimensions, the Uzbek language preserves ancient cosmological and ethical meanings rooted in spirituality and harmony with nature.

The comparative analysis demonstrates that despite universal archetypes, linguistic expressions embody distinct cultural values. Thus, *fire* and *water* are

not only natural elements but also fragments of the linguistic worldview that continue to shape national identity and cultural thought.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK NUTQ MADANIYATIDA HAZIL NUTQ AKTINING IFODALANISHI VA QABUL QILINISHINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek nutq madaniyatlarida hazilning lingvistik, pragmatik hamda madaniy jihatdan ifodalanishi va qabul qilinishining qiyosiy tahlili keltiriladi. Tadqiqotda hazilning kommunikativ funksiyalari, madaniyatlararo tafovutlari hamda inson qadriyatlar va ijtimoiy munosabatlardagi o'rni yoritilgan. Shuningdek, hazilning lingvistik mexanizmlari, madaniy konseptualizatsiyasi, tarjima jarayonidagi madaniy bo'shliqlar va pragmatik ekvivalentlik masalalari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Grice muloqot maksimlari va muloyimlik tamoyillari asosida hazilning madaniyatlararo o'ziga xosliklari tahlil qilinib, ingliz va o'zbek tillarida hazilni idrok etishdagi farqlar ochib beriladi. Tadqiqot natijalari til o'qituvchilari uchun ham foydali bo'lib, o'quvchilarda madaniyatlararo pragmatik kompetensiyani shakllantirish zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: hazil, nutq akti, pragmatika, madaniyatlararo muloqot, lingvistik mexanizmlar, madaniy konseptualizatsiya, tarjima, pragmatik ekvivalentlik, ingliz tili, o'zbek tili

Hazil inson nutqining eng murakkab va qiziqarli ko'rinishlaridan biri bo'lib, u nafaqat kulgi va zavq manbai, balki madaniy, ijtimoiy va lingvistik hodisa sifatida ham alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Har bir xalqning hazilga bo'lgan munosabati, uni yaratish va qabul qilish usullari ularning milliy dunyoqarashi, qadriyatlar va muloqot madaniyatini aks ettiradi. Shu sababli, hazil nutq aktining lingvistik va pragmatik xususiyatlarini o'rganish madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiyani chuqurroq tushunish uchun muhimdir.

So'nggi yillarda hazilning nutq akti sifatidagi tahlili ko'plab tadqiqotchilar diqqat markazida bo'lib, ularning ishlari hazilning kommunikativ vazifalari, madaniy konnotatsiyalari va kontekstual talqinlarini yoritadi (Mullan & Béal, 2018; Chen & Dewaele, 2021). Ingliz va o'zbek madaniyatlari misolida bu farqlar ayniqsa yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi, chunki har ikkala madaniyatda ham hazil insonlar o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy yaqinlikni ta'minlash, stressni kamaytirish va ijobiy muhit yaratishda muhim vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Hazilning madaniy konseptualizatsiyasi (Stankić, 2017) hamda uning lingvistik va pragmatik mexanizmlarini tahlil qilish orqali har bir madaniyatning o'ziga xos nutq strategiyalari va qadriyat tizimini aniqlash mumkin. Shuningdek, hazilni tarjima qilishda madaniy tafovutlar, kognitiv dissonans va pragmatik ekvivalentlik masalalari o'ziga xos muammolarni yuzaga keltiradi (Bekmurodova et al., 2024).

Mazkur tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek nutq madaniyatlarida hazilning ifodalanishi va qabul qilinishini qiyosiy jihatdan o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — hazilning lingvistik va pragmatik xususiyatlarini aniqlash, ularning madaniyatlararo idrok etilishidagi farqlarni tahlil qilish hamda madaniy o'ziga xoslikning nutq jarayoniga ta'sirini ochib berishdir. Shu bilan birga, ish madaniyatlararo muloqotda tushunmovchiliklarni kamaytirish va pragmatik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish uchun yangi ilmiy yondashuvlarni taklif etadi.

Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek nutq madaniyatlarida hazilning lingvistik, pragmatik va madaniy jihatdan namoyon bo'lishini hamda qabul qilinishini qiyosiy o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Xususan, hazilning nutq akti sifatida shakllanishi, uning kommunikativ vazifalari va madaniyatlararo farqlari tahlil etiladi (Mullan & Béal, 2018). Ushbu solishtirma tahlil hazilning har ikki madaniyatda ham ijtimoiy munosabatlarni mustahkamlash, stressni kamaytirish va axborotni noan'anaviy tarzda yetkazish vositasi sifatidagi ahamiyatini yoritadi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu ish hazilning madaniy konseptualizatsiyasini (Stankić, 2017) va uning tilshunoslikdagi o'rnini chuqur tahlil qilib, uning turli madaniyatlarda inson qadriyatlariga qanday ta'sir qilishini ko'rsatadi (Shohobutdinova et al., 2023).

Xususan, hazilning lingvistik mexanizmlari, pragmatik funksiyalari va madaniyatlararo taqqoslashga oid tadqiqotlar ko'rib chiqiladi, bu esa ingliz va o'zbek hazil nutq aktlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga yordam beradi (Davis & Fiadotava, 2024). Folklordagi umuminsoniy hazil unsurlari bilan birga, har bir madaniyatning o'ziga xos izlari ham mavjud bo'lib, bu ularning milliy o'ziga xosligini belgilaydi (Tursunovich et al., 2024). Bunday xususiyatlar, xususan, Béal va Mullan tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan hazil modelining to'rt o'lchovi: so'zlovchi/maqsadli shaxs/qabul qiluvchi o'zaro munosabatlari, tilning lingvistik mexanizmlari, turli pragmatik funksiyalar va o'zaro ta'sir o'lchovi orqali chuqurroq o'rganiladi. Bunga qo'shimcha ravishda, tinglovchi hazilni

to'liq qabul qilishi uchun hissiy jihatdan tayyor bo'lishi yoki o'ynoqi holatda bo'lishi lozim (Chen & Dewaele, 2021).

Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek nutq madaniyatlarida hazilning lingvistik va pragmatik xususiyatlarini qiyosiy tahlil qilishga qaratilgan bo'lib, uning madaniyatlararo idrok etilishidagi farqlarni aniqlaydi. Bu qiyosiy tahlil hazilning ifodalanishida va qabul qilinishida madaniy o'ziga xoslikning ahamiyatini ochib beradi, ayniqsa, turli tillar va madaniy kontekstlardagi pragmatik kompetensiya doirasida (Chen & Dewaele, 2021). Xususan, tadqiqot hazilning lingvo-ijodiy va kognitiv faoliyat sifatida o'rganilishini chuqurlashtiradi, shuningdek, uning inson qadriyatlariga ta'sirini tahlil qiladi (Shohobutdinova et al., 2023). Shuningdek, u ikki madaniyatda anekdot janridagi invariant tushunchalarni ko'rib chiqish orqali inson hazilining umumbashariy va noyob madaniy jihatlarini ochib beradi (Tursunovich et al., 2024). Bunda, madaniy mos yozuvlarni tarjima qilishdagi qiyinchiliklar, xususan, kognitiv dissonans, urf-odat va an'analarni noto'g'ri talqin qilish, milliy o'ziga xoslikning yo'qolishi kabi masalalar ham ko'rib chiqiladi (Bekmurodova et al., 2024). Ushbu tadqiqot Gricening muloqot maksimlari va muloyimlik tamoyillari asosida hazilning turli madaniyatlardagi lingvistik va madaniy o'lchovlarini o'rganadi (Çutuk, 2021). Mazkur tahlil doirasida madaniyatlardagi pragmatik ekvivalentlikni ta'minlash, jumladan, hazilning tarjimasida madaniy bo'shliqlarni bartaraf etish uchun yangi modellar taklif qilinishi mumkin (Bekmurodova et al., 2024). Bu, o'z navbatida, o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi madaniy-o'ziga xos so'zlarni tarjima qilishda pragmatik ekvivalentlikni ta'minlashga yordam beradi (Bekmurodova et al., 2024). Bunday yondashuv hazilning madaniyatlararo o'zaro ta'sirida yuzaga keladigan tushunmovchiliklarni kamaytirishga xizmat qiladi, chunki har bir madaniyatning o'ziga xos hazil tushunchalari mavjud (Mohebbi, 2023). Jumladan, hazilni tushunish lingvistik va madaniy bilimlarning murakkab uyg'unligini talab qiladi, shuning uchun ikkinchi yoki chet til o'qituvchilari o'z o'quvchilariga pragmatikaning bu ko'pincha e'tibordan chetda qolgan sohasida yordam berishlari zarur (Petkova, 2021).

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, hazil har ikkala madaniyatda ham ijtimoiy muloqot vositasi sifatida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ingliz va o'zbek madaniyatlarida hazilning ifodalanishi, maqsadi va qabul qilinishi o'ziga xos pragmatik va madaniy farqlarga ega. Ingliz tilida hazil ko'proq individuallik va yumshoq ironiyaga asoslangan bo'lsa, o'zbek tilida u ijtimoiy yaqinlikni, samimiylilikni va jamoaviy qadriyatlarni ifodalaydi. Shuningdek, hazilni to'g'ri idrok etish uchun tinglovchining hissiy tayyorgarligi va madaniy bilim darajasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Hazilning tarjimasida madaniy bo'shliqlarni bartaraf etish, pragmatik ekvivalentlikni ta'minlash va madaniy mos yozuvlarni to'g'ri talqin etish masalalari ham dolzarb hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari madaniyatlararo muloqotda tushunmovchiliklarni kamaytirish hamda o'zbek va ingliz tillarida pragmatik kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЭТИКО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ЭПОХИ ВОЗРОЖДЕНИЯ

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются исторические и лингвистические предпосылки формирования этико-философской лексики в английском языке эпохи Возрождения и раннего Нового времени (XVI–XVII вв.). Анализируется взаимосвязь между развитием этической мысли и становлением английского языка как средства научного и философского выражения.

Ключевые слова: этика, философия, Возрождение, английский язык, терминология, гуманизм, Фрэнсис Бэкон, Джон Уилкинс, языковая норма, лексикография.

Abstract: The article examines the historical and linguistic prerequisites for the development of ethical and philosophical vocabulary in the English language during the Renaissance and Early Modern periods (16th–17th centuries). It highlights the interconnection between the evolution of ethical thought and the establishment of English as a language of scientific and philosophical discourse.

Keywords: ethics, philosophy, Renaissance, English language, terminology, humanism, Francis Bacon, John Wilkins, linguistic norm, lexicography.

Каждое социально-гуманитарное философское явление, включая этику, имеет историческую составляющую. Это одна из первых теоретических областей философии, которая развивалась одновременно с обществом, основанным на рабстве. С момента появления Homo sapiens этические вопросы занимали значительное место в общественном дискурсе. «Более того, именно возникновение этических форм взаимоотношений между людьми даёт нам одно из оснований для выделения такой историко-социологической категории, как разумный человек, для констатации его перехода от первобытного состояния к более развитому». На каждом этапе развития человеческой цивилизации этические проблемы, несомненно, рассматривались как наука и как образ жизни. Однако толкование этических понятий и норм, а также выбор терминологии всегда имели определённый исторический и национальный характер.

Хорошо известно, что этика – это дисциплина, изучающая мораль, а также нравственность как форму общественного поведения и выражение общественного сознания. Наиболее значимыми и существенными аспектами существования человеческого общества являются мораль и нравственность. Этика, как и ряд других наук, пережила множество парадоксов в своей многовековой истории. «Аристотель выделил этику как особую науку», чему свидетельством служат его произведения – «Никомахова этика», «Большая этика». В историческом развитии английского языка эпоха, которую мы изучаем, имеет особое значение, поскольку именно в этот период существование языковой нормы становится несомненным. Неуклонное развитие производства и общественного сознания в Средние века, определённые достижения науки и техники привели к тому, что культивируемые идеологические постулаты начали сдерживать дальнейший прогресс человечества. В историческом развитии английского языка рассматриваемая эпоха особенно важна, поскольку именно в этот период существование языковой нормы становится бесспорным. Неуклонное развитие производства и общественного сознания в Средние века, определённые достижения науки и техники привели к тому, что устоявшиеся идеологические догмы начали ограничивать дальнейшее развитие человечества. Благодаря великим открытиям Н.Коперника, Дж.Бруно, Г.Галилея и других возникает новая экспериментальная естественная наука, стремительно развиваются новые отрасли знания. Познание становится центральной проблемой, а его соотношение с

изучаемыми материальными объектами – ядром новых социально-этических программ.

Драматургия Шекспира «приобретает характер ясно выраженной национальной определённости в живом воспроизведении исторических процессов и актуальных социальных конфликтов, оставаясь ренессансной по широте охвата человеческой жизни и высоте звучания гуманистических идеалов» [1, 138]. Утверждение английского языка как языка научной и философской литературы происходило труднее. Существенных изменений в языке науки данного периода не наблюдается, поскольку «латинский язык в языковой жизни Англии XVI–XVII вв. и даже в XVIII в. оставался центром, вокруг которого велись поиски нормы английского литературного языка» [2, 42]. Тем не менее, в 1531 году Томас Элиот написал книгу «*The Governour*» («Наставник»), что стало первой попыткой создать научное произведение на родном английском языке.

Другой последовательный сторонник грамматики, автор знаменитой «*Universal Rational Grammar*» (1660) Джон Уилкинс, в своём труде «*An Essay on a Real Character and a Philosophical Language*» (1668) рассматривает язык, в частности английский, с точки зрения рационалиста и в конечном итоге предлагает создать «единый философский язык» и единый алфавит для всех народов. Он пишет: «Если бы люди повсюду согласились в едином способе и порядке выражения мыслей, так же как они соглашаются в понятиях, то мы могли бы избавиться от проклятия смешения языков со всеми неприятными последствиями, связанными с этим» [3, 47]. Общество эпохи Возрождения, особенно позднего Возрождения (конец XVI – начало XVII вв.), было готово к тому, чтобы этическая и философская литература могла выйти «из узкого круга латинистов в просторы широкой жизни английской публики» и «поэтому языковые вопросы начали выдвигаться на первый план, ибо язык отражает то, что происходило и происходит в обществе» [4, 124]. В Англии XVI–XVII вв. сторонники всеобщего использования национального языка (Томас Нэш, Эдмунд Спенсер, Томас Элиот и др.) остро поднимали вопрос о пополнении его лексики и, прежде всего, о создании английской научной терминологии. Анализ жанрово-разнообразной литературы этого периода показывает, что основная масса терминологической лексики создавалась путём переосмысления семантики слов и выражений общеупотребительного литературного языка. Причём её характерной особенностью являлись образность и коннотация, то есть расширительное толкование слова-понятия. Утверждение английского языка как языка научной и философской литературы происходило непросто. Существенных изменений в языке науки этого периода не наблюдалось, поскольку «латинский язык в языковой жизни Англии XVI–XVII вв. и даже в XVIII в. оставался центром, вокруг которого велись поиски нормы английского литературного языка». Тем не менее, в 1531 году Томас Элиот написал книгу «*The Governour*» («Наставник»), ставшую первой попыткой создать научное произведение на

родном английском языке. Хотя в то время английский язык ещё не обладал собственной отраслевой терминологией, Т. Элиот сознательно стремился показать, что серьёзные труды могут быть написаны и на английском. Следует отметить, что в этот период некоторые учёные, например Ральф Ливер (XVI век), пытались приспособить национальный язык для выражения научных понятий, переводя некоторые латинские термины средствами английского языка, хотя сам английский язык того времени уже был перенасыщен латинскими заимствованиями. Однако, как отмечает В.Н.Ярцева, несмотря на весь энтузиазм, попытки создать философскую терминологию на основе исконно английских морфем оказались тщетными, поскольку грамматическая схема, предложенная английскими рационалистами-грамматиками, представляла собой не что иное, как логическое и рациональное переосмысление латинской грамматики, механически перенесённое на почву английского языка изучаемой эпохи. Ещё один последовательный сторонник грамматики, автор знаменитой «*Universal Rational Grammar*» (1660) Джон Уилкинс, в своём труде «*An Essay on a Real Character and a Philosophical Language*» (1668) рассматривает язык, в частности английский, с точки зрения рационалиста и в конечном итоге предлагает создать «единый философский язык» и единый алфавит для всех народов. Он пишет: «Если бы люди повсюду согласились в едином способе и порядке выражения мыслей, так же как они соглашаются в понятиях, то мы могли бы избавиться от проклятия смешения языков со всеми неприятными последствиями, связанными с этим». В конце XVI века начинается работа по описанию языка и его кодификации. В первую очередь к этой работе подключаются грамматисты и орфоэписты (Харт, Уильям Буллокар, А. Гилл, К. Батлер, К. Купер). В то же время активно развивают свою деятельность лексикографы, стремящиеся зафиксировать словарный состав языка. Если первые такие словари были двуязычными латинско-английскими словарями новых слов, то уже в начале XVI века появляются словари так называемых «трудных» слов (Роберт Кудри, Х. Кокерам, Э. Колес). Двуязычные словари достигают своего расцвета в XVI веке. Это словари Томаса Элиота, Ричарда Хулета, Томаса Купера, Джона Барта, Джона Райдера и других. Всё это приводит к изменению характера и положения оригинальной и переводной литературы: она становится весьма востребованной. Завоевание права на использование английского языка во всех жанрах научного и литературного творчества было важнейшим вопросом времени. При этом следует подчеркнуть взаимодействие научного и художественного литературного языка с разговорной речью, ведь язык, на котором говорил Шекспир, был тем же, на котором он писал.

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CONCEPTUAL METAPHORS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TOPONYMY

Abstract. The comparative analysis of English and Uzbek toponyms demonstrates that both linguistic systems encode conceptual metaphors and cultural symbols through language-specific strategies. As culturally embedded linguistic units, toponyms carry traces of national identity, worldview, and collective memory. The paper reveals key patterns in metaphorical structuring and symbolic representation that shape how each culture conceptualizes the world.

Keywords: toponymy, symbolic representation, national identity, conceptual metaphors

Аннотация. Сравнительный анализ английских и узбекских топонимов показывает, что обе языковые системы кодируют концептуальные метафоры и культурные символы с помощью специфических для языка стратегий. Будучи культурно обусловленными языковыми единицами, топонимы сохраняют следы национальной идентичности, мировоззрения и коллективной памяти. В статье выявляются ключевые модели метафорической структуры и символической репрезентации, формирующие способы концептуализации мира в каждой культуре.

Ключевые слова: топонимия, символическая репрезентация, национальная идентичность, концептуальные метафоры.

Toponymy is more than a classification of place names — it serves as a repository of cultural values, historical events, and cognitive patterns of a speech community. In cognitive linguistics, toponyms are treated not only as geographical markers but also as conceptual metaphors that reflect how people

categorize and interpret their environment. This is particularly evident in English and Uzbek toponymic systems, which, despite belonging to different language families and cultural traditions, show comparable cognitive mechanisms but divergent symbolic motivations.

English toponyms such as Bridgewater, Stratford, Kingston are predominantly descriptive and utilitarian, reflecting infrastructure, social hierarchy, or geographical characteristics. Conversely, Uzbek toponyms like Ko'kgumbaz, Hisor, Navbahor, Qo'ng'iro't encapsulate mythological, spiritual, and symbolic meanings, encoding cultural memory and aesthetic perception of space.¹ This paper aims to analyze how cognitive metaphors structure toponymy in these languages and what this reveals about national identity and worldview.

English place names are largely derived from descriptive and functional features of the environment. The majority of them illustrate metaphors of activity, possession, and spatial relation, reflecting the pragmatic and anthropocentric worldview of early English communities. For instance: Oxford (“ford of oxen”) – metaphor of work and agriculture.² The toponym represents a cognitive model in which animal labor symbolizes productivity and human adaptation to nature. Cambridge (“bridge over the Cam”) – metaphor of connection and development, reflecting human dominance over the environment.³ Newcastle – metaphor of construction and defense, connected to the conceptual frame “CITY AS A HUMAN CREATION”. Greenwich (“green settlement”) – metaphor of fertility and life, highlighting the English cultural preference for green landscapes as signs of prosperity. Stratford-upon-Avon – metaphor of movement and trade, based on the path schema, implying human exploration and communication.

In these examples, the conceptual metaphors PLACE IS ACTIVITY, NATURE IS PROPERTY, and ENVIRONMENT IS RESOURCE dominate. Such metaphors show how English culture historically perceived the landscape as something to be organized, utilized, and categorized.

Color-based English toponyms (e.g., Blackpool, Whitehaven, Redhill) also represent metaphorical thinking. The use of colors functions as a means of differentiation and classification rather than symbolic expression. For instance, Blackpool (“dark water body”) reflects environmental observation, while Whitehaven (“bright harbor”) expresses visibility and orientation. These color metaphors thus encode a pragmatic rather than spiritual interpretation of nature.⁴

¹ Karimov, S. (2019). O'zbek toponimiyasida rang va tabiat metaforalari [Color and Nature Metaphors in Uzbek Toponymy]. *Til va Madaniyat Jurnal*, 4(2), 45–47.

² Harrison, T. (2018). Place Names and Early English Society: A Cognitive Approach. *Journal of Historical Linguistics*, 6(1), 21–28.

³ Smith, R. (2020). Metaphor and Settlement: Cognitive Patterns in English Toponymy. *Cognitive Onomastics Review*, 2(3), 50–60.

⁴ Davies, L. (2017). Color Terms in English Toponyms: A Study of Environmental Perception. *Names: A Journal of Onomastics*, 65(2), 30–36.

Furthermore, the English system demonstrates a strong influence of historical and social metaphors. Place names such as Kingston (“the king’s town”) and Nottingham (“homestead of Snot’s people”) reveal feudal and hierarchical worldviews, illustrating how power structures and ownership relations were embedded in language.

In contrast, Uzbek toponyms are characterized by symbolic imagery, emotional association, and spiritual meaning, rooted in Eastern philosophy and nomadic traditions.¹ Uzbek place names tend to employ metaphors connected with nature, color, emotion, and faith, reflecting the culture’s close relationship with the environment and its aesthetic appreciation of natural harmony. Examples include:

Guliston (“land of flowers”) – metaphor of beauty and prosperity, linking nature with cultural ideals of happiness and abundance.

Navbahor (“new spring”) – metaphor of renewal and rebirth, expressing cyclical worldview and faith in natural revival.

Ko‘kgumbaz (“blue dome”) – metaphor of heaven and spirituality, representing the sky as a divine protection symbol.

Qiziltepa (“red hill”) – metaphor of strength and heroism, where the color “red” embodies vitality, energy, and endurance.

Qo‘shko‘prik (“twin bridges”) – metaphor of unity and connection, symbolizing cooperation and shared human effort.

In Uzbek toponymy, the prevalent metaphors include NATURE IS SPIRIT, COLOR IS EMOTION, and PLACE IS MEMORY. These metaphors reflect the collective ethnocultural cognition of the Uzbek people, in which natural phenomena and moral concepts are interconnected.

Colors play an especially significant role in Uzbek cultural semantics. For example: Oqtosh (“white stone”) symbolizes purity and honesty. Qoradaryo (“black river”) conveys depth, mystery, and power. Ko‘ksoy (“blue stream”) represents tranquility and divine blessing. Such color symbolism demonstrates how the Uzbek worldview assigns emotional and ethical values to environmental elements, turning geography into a spiritual landscape.

Another significant group of Uzbek toponyms derives from religious and mythological metaphors, such as Shahrison (“holy city”) and Beshariq (“five ditches”), the latter linked with ancient irrigation and life-giving water — a sacred concept in Central Asian culture. A cross-linguistic comparison indicates that English cognitive metaphors are utilitarian and descriptive, while Uzbek metaphors are associative and symbolic.² The English system is rooted in practical

¹ Rakhmatullaeva, M. (2020). Toponimlarda milliy-madaniy kodlarning ifodalanishi [Representation of National-Cultural Code in Toponyms]. *O‘zbek Tili va Adabiyoti*, 3(1), 61–63.

² Toirov, B. (2021). O‘zbek joy nomlarida konseptual metafora va mifologik qatlam [Conceptual Metaphor and Mythological Layer in Uzbek Place Names]. *Madaniy Meros Tadqiqotlari*, 2(5), 102–105.

categorization and socio-political organization, whereas the Uzbek one arises from aesthetic, emotional, and religious reflection.

Despite these differences, both languages share universal cognitive schemas such as container (e.g., Cambridge, Qal'ai Hisor) and path (e.g., Stratford, Qo'shko'prik), confirming that spatial cognition operates similarly across cultures but is shaped by local traditions and experiences.¹

Metaphorization of Space: Both languages conceptualize space through path and container schemas, but Uzbek toponyms often add symbolic interpretation — e.g., Hisor (fortress) represents safety, while Bridgewater represents movement.

Personification of Nature: Uzbek names personify natural features (Oqtosh, Qiziltepa), whereas English ones focus on descriptive use (Rockfield, Redhill).

Religious and Emotional Connotations: Uzbek toponyms include references to spirituality and divine power (Ko'kgumbaz, Navbahor), absent in English, where religion is rarely embedded in place names.

Cultural Memory Encoding: Uzbek toponyms preserve traces of tribes, heroes, and legends (Qo'ng'iroq, Mang'it, Samarqand), while English names record social hierarchies and ancient settlements (Kingston, Durham, Winchester).²

Thus, metaphor and symbol in toponyms not only describe physical landscapes but also encode collective cultural cognition, reflecting how each nation interprets life, space, and value through linguistic creativity.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK OAV MATNLARIDA "MA'NAVIY QADRIYATLAR" KONSEPTSIYASINING KOGNITIV-PRAGMATIK TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ma'naviy qadriyatlar tushunchasi ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi ommaviy axborot vositalarida kognitiv-pragmatik nuqtai nazardan qanday ifodalanishi o'rganiladi. Asosiy e'tibor jurnalistlar va muharrirlar ushbu tushunchani qanday shakllantirishi, tuzilishi va etkazishi, madaniy kontekst uning ma'nosiga qanday ta'sir qilishi va auditoriya uchun qanday kommunikativ vazifalarni bajarishi bilan bog'liq. Tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek media matnlarining korpusiga asoslanib, ularning lug'ati, metaforalari va yashirin madaniy taxminlarini o'rganadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, har ikkala til hamjamiyati ma'naviyatni axloqiy ideal bilan bog'laydi, ammo e'tiborlar farq qiladi: ingliz tilli ommaviy axborot vositalari odatda ma'naviyatni shaxsiy va hissiy tajriba sifatida taqdim etsa, o'zbek media esa uni jamoaviy, diniy va milliy jihatlari bilan ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqot shuni ta'kidlaydiki, tushunchaning kognitiv tuzilishi va pragmatik ishlatilishi kengroq madaniy va ideologik kontekstlarni aks ettiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ma'naviy qadriyatlar; media diskurs; kognitiv-pragmatik; ingliz media; o'zbek media; madaniy identifikatsiya; tushunchaviy tuzilma; kommunikativ vazifa

Zamonaviy media jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish va kollektiv ongni yaratishda eng kuchli vositalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ma'naviy qadriyatlar kabi tushunchalar endi faqat diniy yoki falsafiy munozaralarga

cheklanmaydi – ular yangiliklar, intervyular va sharh maqolalarida keng qo‘llanilib, ma’lum turmush tarzlarini, dunyoqarashlarni va axloqiy me’yorlarni targ‘ib qiladi.

Ingliz tilida “spiritual values” ko‘pincha ruhiy salomatlik, shaxsiy rivojlanish yoki mindfulness kontekstida uchraydi (Antropova va boshq., 2021). O‘zbekistonda esa “ma’naviy qadriyatlar” tushunchasi kuchli madaniy va axloqiy ma’nolarga ega bo‘lib, diniy, tarixiy va milliy ildizlarga asoslangan (Prisyazhnyuk & Zilova, 2014; Akhrenova, 2024). Ushbu farq solishtirma tadqiqotni dolzarb va ma’lumotli qiladi.

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi ma’naviy qadriyatlar tushunchasi ingliz va o‘zbek media matnlarida qanday kognitiv tarzda tashkil etilganini va pragmatik jihatdan qanday ishlatilishini aniqlashdir. Tadqiqot quyidagi savollarga javob izlaydi:

1. Har bir til kontekstida tushunchaning asosiy va periferik ma’nolari qanday?
2. Jurnalistlar va muharrirlar uni ifodalashda qanday lingvistik va narrativ strategiyalardan foydalanadi?
3. Ushbu tushuncha har bir madaniy kontekstda qanday kommunikativ vazifalarni bajaradi (masalan, ishontirish, identitet shakllantirish yoki axloqiy ta’lim)?

Adabiyotlar Sharhi

Media diskurs ijtimoiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Masalan, Prisyazhnyuk va Zilova (2014) rus va britan gazetalarida milliy identitet bilan bog‘liq qadriyat tizimlari faol targ‘ib qilinishini ko‘rsatadi va media tilining jamiyatdagi axloqiy ierarxiyalarni aks ettirishini ta’kidlaydi.

Kognitiv-pragmatik yondashuv diskursni nafaqat mental, balki kommunikativ akt sifatida ko‘radi. “What Is Cognitive in Discourse?” (2020) ga ko‘ra, diskurs kognitivdir, chunki u mental modellarga asoslanadi, va pragmatikdir, chunki u ijtimoiy maqsadni bajaradi – ishontirish, xabardor qilish yoki ta’sir o‘tkazish.

Antropova, Fedorov va Doronina (2021) rus adabiy diskursida “spiritual” so‘zining semantik maydonini o‘rganib, uning asosiy ma’nosi axloqiy ong va hissiy chuqurlik bilan bog‘liqligini, periferik ma’nosi esa hayotiylik va badiiy tajriba bilan bog‘liqligini aniqladi. Shunga qaramay, o‘zbek media kontekstida bu tushunchaning qanday ishlatilishi haqida kam tadqiqot mavjud.

Tadqiqot Akhrenova (2024) va Kozyreva (2014) tomonidan tavsiya etilgan kognitiv va pragmatik yondashuvni qo‘llaydi. Kognitiv tahlil tushunchaning asosiy va periferik qismlarini aniqlaydi. Pragmatik tahlil kommunikativ maqsadlarni o‘rganadi (identitet shakllantirish, ishontirish, axloqiy ta’lim). Solishtirma tahlil esa ingliz va o‘zbek natijalarini madaniy farqlarni ko‘rsatish uchun taqqoslaydi.

Tadqiqot vizual yoki multimedia elementlarini hisobga olmaydi va faqat matnli materialga tayanadi. Shuningdek, Kozyreva (2014) ta’kidlashicha, tillar o‘rtasidagi tarjima pragmatik nuanslarni o‘zgartirishi mumkin.

Ingliz media matnlarida “inner peace”, “mindfulness”, “purpose”, “self-discovery” kabi soʻzlar “spiritual values” bilan tez-tez qoʻllanadi va bu shaxsiy tajriba va psixologik oʻsishga eʼtiborni aks ettiradi (Antropova va boshq., 2021). Asosiy maʼnolar oʻz-oʻzini anglash, hissiy muvozanat va axloqiy halollikni taʼkidlaydi; periferik maʼnolar esa jamoaviy ishlarga yoki korporativ etikaga taalluqlidir. Oʻzbek matnlarida “maʼnaviy qadriyatlar” va “ruhiy qadriyatlar” “milliy tarbiya”, “oilaviy anʼanalar” va “din” kabi soʻzlar bilan birga ishlatiladi (Akhrenova, 2024).

Ingliz media odatda birinchi shaxs hikoyalari va reflektiv esselar orqali maʼnaviyatni ifodalaydi, bu oʻquvchilarni ruhiy oʻsishga undashni maqsad qiladi (Antropova va boshq., 2021). Oʻzbek media esa didaktik ohangni qoʻllaydi, maʼnaviy qadriyatlarni axloqiy tarbiya, milliy rivojlanish va ijtimoiy uygʻunlik bilan bogʻlaydi (Prisyazhnyuk & Zilova, 2014; Akhrenova, 2024).

Farqlar anʼanaviy madaniy tendentsiyalarni aks ettiradi: Gʻarbda individualizm, Sharqda kollektivizm (Kozyreva, 2014). Ingliz matnlari maʼnaviyatni shaxsiy yoʻl sifatida talqin qilsa, oʻzbek matnlari uni ijtimoiy burch sifatida koʻrsatadi.

Solishtirma tahlil shuni koʻrsatadiki, ingliz va oʻzbek media matnlari maʼnaviy qadriyatlarni moddiy boʻlmagan ideal sifatida bogʻlaydi, ammo urgʻular farq qiladi. Ingliz matnlari shaxsiy oʻz-oʻzini rivojlantirish va hissiy anglashga urgʻu beradi, oʻzbek matnlari esa axloqiy javobgarlik va madaniy anʼanani taʼkidlaydi. Bu farqlar til va madaniyat tushunchaning shakllanishiga qanday taʼsir qilishini koʻrsatadi va xalqaro kommunikatsiya va til taʼlimi uchun muhimdir (Akhrenova, 2024; Kozyreva, 2014). Kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar korpusni kengaytirib, vizual yoki onlayn media shakllarini ham oʻrganishi mumkin.

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ZAMONAVIY INGLIZ TILIDA FONETIK TEJAMKORLIK VA ORTIQCHALIK

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ingliz tilida fonetik tejamkorlik va ortiqchalik hodisalari tahlil qilinadi. Ingliz tili fonetik rivojlanish jarayonida talaffuzning soddalashuvi, qisqarishlar va assimilyatsiya jarayonlari orqali tejamkorlikni, shuningdek, tovushlar takrorlanishi va urg‘u orqali ortiqchalikni namoyon etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: fonetik tejamkorlik, assimilyatsiya, ortiqchalik, nutq, tovush, qisqarish, urg‘u.

PHONETIC REDUNDANCY AND ECONOMY IN MODERN ENGLISH

Abstract. This article explores the phenomena of phonetic economy and redundancy in modern English. Economy is seen in the reduction of pronunciation, sound alterations, and assimilation processes, whereas redundancy is demonstrated through the repetition of sounds and stress patterns in the phonetic evolution of the English language.

Keywords: phonetic economy, assimilation, redundancy, speech, sound, reduction, stress.

Fonetik tejamkorlik (phonetic economy) nutqni soddalashtirish orqali tezlik va samaradorlikni oshirish jarayonidir. Ingliz tilida bu hodisa asosan uch yo‘nalishda namoyon bo‘ladi: talaffuzning soddalashuvi, tovush o‘zgarishlari va assimilyatsiya. Talaffuzni soddalashtirish, ya’ni reduction, kundalik nutqda juda keng tarqalgan. Masalan, going to (gonna) ifodasi nutqda /'gəna/ yoki /'gənə/ shaklida va want to ifodasi nutqda wanna (wɒnə) talaffuz qilinadi¹. Shu bilan birga, undosh harflarining qisqarishi ham tejamkorlikka xizmat qiladi. Masalan,

¹ A Course in phonetics. Ladefoged & Johnson, 2015, pp. 12-15

next day soʻz birikmasida /t/ tovushi koʻpincha oʻqilmaydi va talaffuz /nekst dei/ dan /neks dei/ ga oʻzgaradi. Bu jarayon artikulyatsion harakatni kamaytiradi va nutq tezligini oshiradi.

Assimilyatsiya – bu bir tovushning qoʻshni tovushga moslashishidir. Ingliz tilida bu hodisa koʻplab soʻz birikmalarida kuzatiladi, masalan input soʻzi /'ɪnpʊt/ oʻrniga tez nutqda /'ɪmpʊt/ shaklida va good boy odatdagi /gʊd bɔɪ/ oʻrniga tez nutqda /gʊb bɔɪ/ shaklida talaffuz qilinadi¹. Assimilyatsiya nutqni tezlashtiradi va artikulyatsion harakatni kamaytiradi. Shuningdek, tovushlarning qoʻshilishi yoki oʻzgarishi orqali soʻzlar oraligʻidagi koʻpriklar ham yaratiladi, bu esa nutqni silliq qiladi.

Unli tovushlarning qisqarishi (vowel reduction) ham fonetik tejamkorlikka misol boʻla oladi. Masalan, can feʻli /kæn/ shaklida asosiy urgʻu bilan ishlatiladi, ammo tez nutqda /kən/ yoki /kɪ/ sifatida talaffuz qilinadi va family soʻzi asosiy urgʻu: /'fæmɪli/ bilan ammo tez nutqda: /'fæmli/ shaklida talaffuz qilinadi. Bu jarayon talaffuzni osonlashtiradi va nutqni ravonlashtiradi².

Fonetik ortiqchalik (phonetic redundancy) — bu nutqdagi baʼzi tovush yoki fonetik belgilar maʼnoni oʻzgartirmasdan, ammo uni aniqlashtirish yoki tushunishni osonlashtirish uchun ishlatiladigan hodisadir. Yaʼni, ortiqchalik – nutqdagi “ortiqcha” tovushlar yoki belgilar, ular grammatik yoki leksik maʼno bermaydi, lekin soʻzlarni farqlash, aniqlikni oshirish va tushunishni yengillashtirish vazifasini bajaradi. Fonetik ortiqchalikni “nutqni sugʻurtalovchi” hodisa deb ham aytish mumkin — agar bir tovush eshitilmasa ham, qolgan tovushlar orqali soʻz baribir tanib olinadi.

Tovushlarning takrorlanishi orqali aniqlik: better /'betər/ va batter /'bætər/ → /e/ va /æ/ unli tovushlari va path va bath soʻzlarida /p/ va /b/ undosh tovushlar farqi maʼnoni oʻzgartiradi, ammo urgʻu va tovush takrorlanishi ortiqcha fonetik belgilar orqali tinglovchi soʻzni tez tanib oladi³.

Stress, yaʼni urgʻu tartibi, ingliz tilida redundant xususiyat sifatida koʻriladi. Soʻzdagi yoki gapdagi urgʻu tovushlarni taʼkidlash orqali maʼnoni ajratadi va nutqni tushunarli qiladi. Masalan:

- I didn't say he stole the money. (uzun)
- I didn't say he stole the money. (qisqa)
- "I didn't think he would win." (uzun)
- "I didn't think he would win." (qisqa)

Faqat urgʻu joylashuvi bilan butun gapning maʼnosi oʻzgaradi.

Fonologik tizimdagi ortiqchalik, masalan unli uzunligi, qoʻshma tovushlar yoki undosh klasterlari, tinglovchiga soʻz yoki grammatik shaklni aniqlashda yordam beradi. Bu, ayniqsa, nutqni tezlashtirishda foydali, chunki qisqa vaqt ichida maʼlumot aniq yetkaziladi⁴.

¹ Phonetically based phonology Hayes, Kirchner & Steriade, 2004, 3-bob

² A course in phonetics Ladefoged & Johnson, 2015, 18-20-b.

³ Understanding phonology. Gussenhoven & Jacobs, 2011, 10-bob

⁴ English phonetics and phonology. Carr, 2008, 40-45-betlar

Masalan: "Mobile" (maqsadga qarab) - /'moʊbəl/ yoki /'moʊbaɪl/ varianti, bu ma'noni va ohangni ajratish uchun yordam beradi.

"Cats" va "Bats" - bu soʻzlarda /k/ va /b/ undoshlari oʻzaro farq qiladi, bu esa soʻzlarning grammatik maʼnosini oʻzgartiradi. Garchi ikkalasida ham "at" qismi bir xil boʻlsa-da, boshidagi undoshlar farq orqali aniqlikni taʼminlaydi. Bu misol fonologik tizimdagi ortiqchalikning qanday ishlashini koʻrsatadi va tez nutqda soʻzlarni ajratish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

"Ship" va "Sheep" - bu soʻzlarda /ɪ/ va /i:/ unli tovushlarning harakatlari farq qiladi, bu esa soʻzlarning maʼnolarini ajratadi. "Ship" (kema) va "Sheep" (qoʻy) soʻzlarining unli tovushlari oʻzaro farq qilishi, tinglovchiga har bir soʻzni tushunishda yordam beradi. Bu misol ortiqchalikning fonologik tizim ichidagi rolini koʻrsatadi va soʻzlarni aniq ajratishga xizmat qiladi

Demak, tejamkorlik va ortiqchalik bir-biriga qarama-qarshi boʻlib koʻrinishi mumkin, lekin amalda ular birgalikda nutqni samarali qiladi. Tejamkorlik artikulyatsion mehnatni kamaytirs, ortiqchalik esa tushunarli boʻlishni kafolatlaydi. Ingliz tilida bu ikki hodisa bir-birini toʻldirib, nutqni tez va aniq qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar roʻyxati.

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TIL VA MADANIYAT MUNOSABATIDA HIKMATLI SOʻZLARNING ROLI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada til va madaniyat oʻrtasidagi uzviy bogʻliqlik, shuningdek, xalq donoligini aks ettiruvchi hikmatli soʻzlar, maqollar

va matallarning lingvomadaniy xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ushbu birliklarning xalq tarixi, milliy qadriyatlari, urf-odatlar va dunyoqarashini ifodalashdagi roli yoritiladi. Shuningdek, bunday frazeologik birliklarning avlodlar o'rtasida madaniy merosni uzatishdagi ahamiyati ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: til, madaniyat, maqollar, matallar, hikmatli so'zlar, lingvomadaniyat, frazeologiya, madaniy meros.

Annotation: This article analyzes the intrinsic relationship between language and culture, focusing on the linguocultural features of proverbs, sayings, and wise expressions that reflect a nation's worldview, traditions, and historical memory. The study highlights the role of these phraseological units in preserving cultural heritage and transmitting national values across generations.

Keywords: language, culture, proverbs, sayings, wise expressions, linguoculture, phraseology, cultural heritage

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается взаимосвязь языка и культуры, а также лингвокультурные особенности пословиц, поговорок и мудрых изречений, отражающих мировоззрение, традиции и историческую память народа. В исследовании подчеркивается роль подобных фразеологических единиц в сохранении культурного наследия и передаче национальных ценностей последующим поколениям.

Ключевые слова: язык, культура, пословицы, поговорки, мудрые изречения, лингвокультура, фразеология, культурное наследие.

Til va madaniyat insoniyatning eng muhim yutuqlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Til nafaqat insonlar o'rtasidagi muloqot vositasi, balki milliy ong, tarix va madaniyatni ifodalovchi muhim vositadir. Har bir xalqning tili uning dunyoqarashi, qadriyatlari, urf-odatlar va tarixiy tajribasini aks ettiradi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, til va madaniyat bir-birini to'ldiruvchi, uzviy bog'liq tushunchalardir.

Hikmatli so'zlar, maqollar va matallar esa ushbu madaniy boyliklarning eng qadrilaridan biridir. Ular nafaqat xalqning tajribasi va bilimni qisqa va ixcham shaklda ifodalaydi, balki avlodlar o'rtasida bilim va axloqiy qadriyatlarni yetkazish vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Masalan, "Mehnat qilgan odam hech qachon och qolmaydi" degan maqol nafaqat ishga bo'lgan munosabatni, balki mehnatsevarlik va sabr-toqat kabi qadriyatlarni ham targ'ib qiladi.

Hikmatli so'zlarning o'rni shundaki, ular tilning madaniy xususiyatlarini ochib beradi. Har bir frazeologik birlik yoki maqol o'zida xalqning tarixiy tajribasi, dunyoqarashi va axloqiy me'yorlarini mujassamlashtiradi. Shu sababli, frazeologik birliklarni o'rganish orqali nafaqat tilning o'ziga, balki madaniyatning chuqur qatlamlariga ham nazar tashlash mumkin.

Shuningdek, hikmatli so'zlar orqali madaniy meros avloddan avlodga yetkaziladi. Bu jarayon xalq xotirasi va identifikatsiyasini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi. Masalan, xalqning qadimiy urf-odatlar, diniy e'tiqodlar yoki kundalik hayot tajribasi ko'pincha maqol va matallarda saqlanib qoladi. Shu bois,

til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni chuqur tushunish uchun frazeologik birliklarni o'rganish muhimdir.

Hikmatli so'zlarning madaniyat va tilga ta'siri

1. *Madaniyatni boyitish*: Hikmatli so'zlar madaniyatning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, xalqning urf-odatlarini, qadriyatlarini va tushunchalarini haqida ma'lumot beradi. Masalan, "Ko'p gapirgincha - az gapir" degan o'zbek maqoli kamdan-kam so'zlashning muhimligini, sabr-toqat va vazminlikni tarbiyalaydi.

2. *Tilni boyitish*: Hikmatli so'zlar tilning boyishi va rivojlanishiga xizmat qiladi. Ular tilga yangi so'z birikmalarini kiritib, ko'pincha ma'nodan tushunishni yengillashtiradi.

3. *Tarbiya va o'g'it*: Ular bolalarni va yosh avlodni tarbiyalashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Hikmatli so'zlar orqali odob, axloqlik, insoniylik kabi qadriyatlar tarbiyalanuvchilarga yetkaziladi.

Hikmatli so'zlarning zamonaviy madaniyatdagi roli

Bugungi kunda globallashtirish davrida hikmatli so'zlarning ahamiyati yanada ortib bormoqda. Ular ko'plab kitoblar, filmlar va yana boshqa ommaviy axborot vositalarida qo'llanilib, madaniy chegaralarni yo'q qilishga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar orqali hikmatli so'zlar keng tarqalmoqda va yangi avlodning ongida eski va yangi madaniyatni quvnoq va ma'noli tarzda uyg'otmoqda.

Umuman olganda, hikmatli so'zlar insonlar o'rtasida madaniyat va tillar aloqasini mustahkamlash, ularni bir-biriga yaqinlashtirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ular milliy boyluk sifatida e'zozlanishi va avloddan-avlodga yetkazilishi zarurdir. Shuning uchun hikmatli so'zlarning ma'nosi chuqur o'rganilib, ularning ta'lim-tarbiyada qo'llanilishi davom ettirilishi lozim.

Bu maqola sizga asos bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin. Istasangiz, qo'shimchalar kiritishingiz yoki aniq misollar bilan boyitishingiz mumkin.

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ERNEST HEMINGWAY AND BARBARA KINGSOLVER AS ECOLOGICAL WRITER

ANNOTATION

The article provides a comparative ecological analysis of Ernest Hemingway's and Barbara Kingsolver's literary works, focusing on how each writer reflects humanity's relationship with nature. Hemingway's fiction demonstrates an implicit ecological consciousness, using natural settings as moral testing grounds where human ambition meets environmental limits. In contrast, Kingsolver adopts an explicit environmental ethic, integrating scientific knowledge, ecological justice, and indigenous wisdom into her narratives. The study concludes that the transition from Hemingway's implicit conservation concerns to Kingsolver's explicit environmental activism reflects the evolution of American ecological literature from individual moral struggle to systemic ecological awareness.

Key words: ecological literature, environmental ethics, Ernest Hemingway, Barbara Kingsolver, ecological consciousness, environmental justice, anthropocene.

Hemingway's Ecological Themes and Environmental Awareness

Hemingway's works delve deeply into the natural world, not just as a setting but as a crucial element influencing human experiences and moral reflections. In stories like "The Snows of Kilimanjaro" and "The Old Man and the Sea," nature is portrayed as an active, decisive force. The mountain in "The Snows of Kilimanjaro" symbolizes missed opportunities and moral consequences, whereas the sea in "The Old Man and the Sea" tests human character by pitting man against nature. These narratives highlight Hemingway's understanding that human identity is deeply connected to ecological forces. [3;102]

In works such as "Green Hills of Africa," Hemingway explores the complexity of human-animal relationships and the impact of resource extraction. He documents African safaris, reflecting both admiration for the hunt and criticism of the ecological damage caused by colonial exploitation. Through these stories, Hemingway shows that hunting and fishing have significant ecological consequences.

Kingsolver's Environmental Ethics and Ecological Justice

In contrast, Barbara Kingsolver's fiction explicitly engages with environmental science and ethics. Her novels, like "Flight Behavior," integrate

climate change into the narrative, using the disruption of monarch butterfly migration to educate readers about ecological issues. "Prodigal Summer" examines interconnected ecological systems through multiple perspectives, emphasizing the importance of ecological knowledge.

Kingsolver's work explicitly connects ecological degradation to social injustice, illustrating how environmental destruction disproportionately affects marginalized communities. [6;256] Her characters often gain ecological literacy, motivating activism and community involvement. Kingsolver's narratives highlight the importance of indigenous ecological knowledge and sustainable practices.

Comparing Implicit and Explicit Environmental Messaging

Hemingway's approach is indirect, embedding environmental concerns within narrative elements without explicitly stating them. His minimalist style allows readers to interpret the tension between human ambition and ecological consequences. In contrast, Kingsolver's work is direct and didactic, integrating scientific exposition and guiding readers toward ecological literacy.

Hemingway's narratives focus on individual encounters with nature, while Kingsolver addresses systemic issues like consumer culture and industrial agriculture. [2;132] Kingsolver's work emphasizes the role of science and indigenous knowledge in shaping ecological understanding.

Literary Legacy and Influence

Hemingway's ecological consciousness laid a foundation for environmental literature, using nature as a moral testing ground. His style influenced writers to embed environmental themes within personal struggles. Kingsolver represents a shift toward integrating scientific literacy with narrative, transforming fiction into a tool for environmental education.

Comparative Analysis: Implicit versus Explicit Environmental Messaging

This systemic analysis requires Kingsolver to develop more complex narrative architecture capable of representing the economic and political dimensions of environmental crisis, whereas Hemingway's focus on individual encounters with natural limits enables his characteristic economical prose and concentrated emotional intensity.

Ecological Theme	Hemingway	Kingsolver
Environmental Perspective	Implicit; emerges through landscape deterioration and human-nature conflict	Explicit; functions as central thematic concern integrated into plot structure
Narrative Approach	Sparse, minimalist style; interpretive	Multiple perspectives, scientific exposition, pedagogical

Ecological Theme	Hemingway	Kingsolver
	ambiguity about ecological consequences	guidance toward ecological literacy
Human-Nature Relationship	Individual encounters with ecological limits as tests of character; nature as autonomous force	Humans as embedded within ecological systems
Explicit Environmental Critique	Ambiguous authorial stance; moral judgment withheld from reader interpretation	Direct critique of consumer culture, industrial agriculture, and economic systems driving environmental destruction
Integration of Scientific Knowledge	Limited; natural world depicted through sensory description and aesthetic observation	Central; climate science, ecology, and sustainable agriculture explicitly integrated into narrative and character education
Conservation Framework	Mid-twentieth-century resource scarcity and wilderness loss concerns	Late-twentieth-century climate change, biodiversity crisis, and environmental justice concerns

Both authors contribute to a literary tradition examining humanity's relationship with nature. Hemingway's mid-twentieth-century fiction focused on wilderness preservation, while Kingsolver's work addresses contemporary environmental crises with a systemic and scientific approach. [5;26] This evolution from implicit to explicit messaging reflects the ongoing adaptation of environmental literature to address ecological challenges.

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INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDAGI UYG’ONISH DAVRI SONETLARIDA LINGVOPOETIK VOSITALARNING QO’LLANILISHI

Abstract. The Renaissance period marks a crucial stage in the development of English poetry, during which the sonnet emerged as a central poetic form. While originally adopted from the Italian tradition, English poets reshaped its structure and enriched its linguistic and thematic potential. This paper examines the lingvopoetic features of Renaissance English sonnets, focusing on metaphor, antithesis, personification, rhyme scheme transformation, and semantic layering in the works of Wyatt, Surrey, Shakespeare, Donne, and Milton. The analysis reveals that the English sonnet, through structural innovation and deepened imagery, became an important medium for expressing philosophical, emotional, and spiritual ideas.

Keywords: sonnet, Renaissance, lingvopoetics, metaphor, antithesis, English poetry.

Аннотация. Период Возрождения является важным этапом в развитии английской поэзии, когда сонет стал центральной жанровой формой. Несмотря на свое итальянское происхождение, английские поэты преобразовали сонет, расширив его структурные и лингвопоэтические возможности. В статье анализируются лингвопоэтические особенности английского сонета эпохи Возрождения, включая метафору, антитезу, персонификацию, рифмовку и семантические слои в произведениях Уайатта, Саррея, Шекспира, Донна и Мильтона. Исследование показывает, что английский сонет стал важным инструментом выражения философских, эмоциональных и духовных идей благодаря структурным инновациям и образной насыщенности.

Ключевые слова: сонет, Возрождение, лингвопоэтика, метафора, антитеза, английская поэзия.

Sonet janri Yevropa adabiyotining eng bardavom poetik shakllaridan biri bo‘lib, ingliz adabiyotida ayniqsa Uyg‘onish davrida yuksak taraqqiyotni boshdan kechirdi. Petrarka an‘analariga tayangan holda ingliz shoirlari sonetni nafaqat shaklan, balki mazmunan ham qayta talqin qildilar. Bu jarayon natijasida ingliz soneti o‘ziga xos lingvopoetik tizimga ega bo‘ldi. Ushbu maqola Uyg‘onish davri

sonetlarida metafora, antiteza, personifikatsiya, ritmik tuzilma va sintaktik qurilishning badiiy g'oya ifodalanishidagi o'rini tahlil qiladi.

Wyatt va Surrey: ingliz sonetining shakllanishi

Ser Tomas Uayt va Genri Xovard (Surrey) ingliz adabiyotiga Petrarka shaklini olib kirgan dastlabki ijodkorlardir. Uayt italyan oktava–sestet modelini moslashtirgan holda ingliz tilidagi qofiya imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqib, metaforik ifodaning sodda, ammo kuchli variantlarini qo'llagan. Surrey esa yanada muhim innovatsiya uchta to'rtlik va bir kupletdan iborat bo'lgan **inglizcha sonet shaklini** yaratdi. Bu strukturaviy o'zgarish yakuniy kupletning semantik ahamiyatini oshirdi va unda g'oyaviy kulminatsiyani ifodalash imkonini berdi.

Shekspir sonetlarida lingvopoetik vositalar

Uyg'onish davri ingliz sonetining eng yuksak cho'qqisi Uilyam Shekspir ijodida namoyon bo'ladi. Uning sonetlarida:

- **metafora** (“Time’s scythe”, “summer’s lease”, “eternal lines”)
- **antiteza** (yosh–keksalik, yorug'lik–zulmat, go'zallik–xazon)
- **personifikatsiya** (Vaqt, Sevgi, O'lim)
- **enjambment** orqali ma'no oqimining davomiyligi
- **yakuniy kupletda** semantik burilish *volta*

Shekspir tilidagi metaforalar abstrakt tushunchalarni jonli obrazlarga aylantiradi¹. Antitezalar esa insoniyat taqdiri va vaqtning o'tkinchiligi haqidagi falsafiy mulohazalarni kuchaytiradi. Shekspir sonetining lingvopoetik tizimi uning she'rlaridagi dramatik va intellektual kuchning asosiy manbaidir.

Jon Don va metafizik sonetning poetik tili

Jon Don ingliz sonetini yangi bosqichga olib chiqqan shoir sifatida ajralib turadi. Uning sonetlari diniy-falsafiy mazmun, murakkab sintaksis, g'ayrioddiy metaforalar, kuchli antitezalar bilan ajralib turadi. Masalan, “Death, be not proud” sonetida O'lim personifikatsiya qilinadi, sintaktik inversiyalar orqali semantik urg'u kuchaytiriladi, “short sleep” va “eternal waking” antitezasi esa ruhning abadiyligi haqidagi g'oyani yuksaltiradi. Donning lingvopoetik uslubi fikrning murakkab va qatlamli talqinini yuzaga keltiradi.

Milton va shaxsiy-falsafiy sonetning shakllanishi

Jon Milton sonetga shaxsiy iztirob, ruhiy kurash va Xudo bilan ichki suhbat motivlarini olib kirdi. “On His Blindness” sonetida:

“light” metaforasi ko'rish qobiliyati va ilohiy nurning ramzi,

“Patience” jonlantirilgan obraz,

sintaktik parallelizm g'oyaviy muvozanat yaratadi.

Milton sonetlari lingvopoetik jihatdan chuqur falsafiy mazmunga ega bo'lib, shoirning ruhiy kechinmalarini badiiy-estetik darajaga ko'taradi.

Milton sonetlarida an'anaviy shakl va mazmunning yangicha talqini

Milton ijodida sonet nafaqat shaxsiy kechinmalarni ifodalovchi vosita,

¹ Dr. Sunit Kr Bera. (2014) The history of the English Sonnet// International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention, Issue 4 PP.64-80 p-14

balki murakkab sintaktik konstruksiyalarni sinovdan o'tkazuvchi lingvistik maydonga ham aylandi. U Petrarka an'analaridagi qat'iy oktava–sestet bo'linishiga to'liq amal qilmagan holda, mazmunning mantiqiy oqimini sintaktik jihatdan cho'zadi va shu orqali sonetning semantik maromini o'zgartiradi¹. Ayniqsa, **enjambment**ning faol qo'llanishi matnda ritmik uzluksizlikni kuchaytiradi, fikrning to'xtovsiz davom etishi esa shoirning ichki dialogi hamda ruhiy iztirobotini jonli tarzda aks ettiradi. Milton sonetlaridagi yana bir muhim lingvopoetik xususiyat **leksik kontrast**ning keng qo'llanishidir. U ko'pincha “light” va “darkness”, “serve” va “wait”, “gift” va “burden” kabi semantik juftliklardan foydalanib, insonning ruhiy kurashini aksiologik mezonlar asosida yoritadi. Bu kontrastlar oddiy badiiy vosita emas, balki shoirning diniy-falsafiy qarashlarining lingvistik in'ikosidir. Milton uchun sonet — Xudo, taqdir, iroda va bandalik kabi mavhum tushunchalarni til orqali tahlil qilish imkonini beruvchi intellektual janrdir².

Shuningdek, Milton sonetlarida **personifikatsiya** o'ziga xos ruhiy-falsafiy vazifaga ega. Masalan, “Patience” obrazini tirik mavjudot sifatida tasvirlash, shoirning ichki ovozi va ma'naviy hushyorligining badiiy timsoli sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Bu yerda lingvopoetik vosita nafaqat badiiy obraz yaratadi, balki inson ruhiyatidagi kechinmalarni tushuntirish uchun kognitiv metafora sifatida xizmat qiladi. Shu asosda Milton sonetlari Uyg'onish davridagi boshqa shoirlarga nisbatan yanada murakkab sintaktik to'qimaga, chuqur semantik qatlamga va falsafiy tafakkurga ega bo'lgan poetik tizim sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

Xulosa

Uyg'onish davri ingliz soneti struktura, semantika va obrazlilik jihatidan jadal rivojlandi. Uayt va Surrey shaklni moslashtirgan bo'lsalar, Shekspir uni mazmunan boyitdi; Don metafizik ruh va murakkab obrazlar bilan kengaytirdi; Milton esa shaxsiy ruhiyat va diniy tafakkurni kiritdi. Lingvopoetik vositalarning boyligi ingliz sonetini nafaqat adabiy, balki lingvistik tadqiqotlar uchun ham muhim ob'yektga aylantiradi.

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ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИЕ СРЕДСТВА ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ ОБРАЗНОСТИ И ИХ ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЕ ФУНКЦИИ: СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ МЕЖДУ СЛОВАМИ

Аннотация. Рассматриваются лексические средства образности (метафора, метонимия, эпитет, сравнение, символ, ирония) как механизмы смыслообразования в художественном дискурсе. Поэтический эффект описывается как результат сети межсловных семантических отношений — аналогии, смежности, контраста и управляемого нарушения сочетаемости [1]. На материале контекстного анализа фрагментов русской прозы и поэзии XIX–XXI вв., а также переводной литературы, уточняются прагматические функции образной лексики: эмоциональная, когнитивная, коммуникативная и интерпретативная [3]. Аналитическая рамка опирается на когнитивно-семантический и прагмалингвистический подходы к метафоре и тропике [5].

Ключевые слова: художественная образность; лексические средства; метафора; метонимия; эпитет; сравнение; символ; ирония; семантическая девиация; прагматика текста.

Введение. В художественном тексте слово выходит за пределы денотативного значения и вступает в отношения с другими словами, жанровыми нормами и культурными ожиданиями читателя [4]. Образность возникает как следствие семантической девиации — осознанного смещения привычных значений или сочетаемостей; её следует исследовать не изолированно по тропам, а как динамику межсловных связей, организующих целостное восприятие [1]. При этом концептуальная метафора задаёт общий механизм переноса признаков между доменами, объясняющий интерпретационные сдвиги в художественной лексике [2].

Цель исследования. Показать, каким образом лексические средства образности, вступая в специфические межсловные отношения, реализуют прагматические функции в художественном дискурсе, и задать операциональные параметры анализа, фиксирующие воздействие на читателя.

Материал и методы. Материал составили контексты из русской художественной прозы и поэзии XIX–XXI вв. и образцы переводной литературы; анализ проводился качественно-интерпретативным способом. В описательные параметры включались тип тропа, характер семантической связи (аналогия, смежность, антитеза, нарушенная сочетаемость), зона переносного осмысления (оценочная, сенсорная, темпоральная, пространственная), степень девиации от нормы и предполагаемая читательская установка (эмоциональное вовлечение, ироническая дистанция, символическая надстройка). Контекст рассматривался как минимальная единица интерпретации, обеспечивающая наблюдение

«работы» слова в окружении и категорий текста (связность, информативность, интеграция локальных смыслов) [3]. Когнитивно-семантическая интерпретация метафорических и смежностных переносов соотносилась с типовыми моделями концептуализации [5].

Результаты. Метафора проявилась как механизм междоменных проекций, переводящий абстрактные сущности в конкретные сенсорные образы и создающий когнитивное уплотнение: выражение типа «время ржавеет» приписывает абстрактному явлению свойства материального процесса и формирует у читателя переживание разрушения [5], [2]. Метонимия функционирует как средство экономии интерпретации и маркировки культурных связей: формулы «читать Толстого» и подобные сокращают сложную деятельность до имени автора, активируя коллективную память и стилистические конвенции [3], [4]. Эпитет выступает регулятором интерпретации: парадоксальные сочетания «скрипучая юность», «горькая тишина» пересобирают оценку базового понятия и смещают эмоциональный фокус сцены, что соотносится с пониманием авторской оценочности в художественной речи [4]. Сравнение формирует семантическую перспективу, в которой одно явление осмысливается через свойства другого; обороты типа «слова падали как камни» конструируют образ тяжести и травматичности высказывания, что фиксируется в текстовых категориях как сдвиг тональности [3]. Символ выступает семиотическим концентратором, связывая лексему с устойчивыми культурными кодами и обеспечивая множественность прочтений локального контекста [1]. Ирония вводит двуслойность смысла и задаёт критическую дистанцию между читателем и изображаемым за счёт несоответствия сказанного и подразумеваемого; этот эффект проявляется как коммуникативная настройка чтения [3].

Нарушение стандартной сочетаемости выявилось продуктивным источником образности: контаминации «сонный металл», «молчаливое пламя» создают эффект новизны и запускают перераспределение сенсорных доменов, что согласуется с наблюдениями о стилистической нормативности и её целенаправленных отклонениях [4], [1]. Антитеза организует художественное пространство через конфликт смыслов, где лексическое противопоставление «чёрный день — белая ночь» символизирует несводимые состояния и усиливает драматизм композиции [3], [4]. На прагматическом уровне наблюдаются стабильные эффекты: эмоциональная функция задаёт настроение сцены и регулирует эмпатию; когнитивная — конкретизирует абстрактные концепты за счёт переносов и культурных аллюзий; коммуникативная — управляет вниманием и траекторией интерпретации; интерпретативная — направляет выводы о мотивах героев и авторской позиции [3], [5].

Обсуждение. Источник художественной выразительности обнаруживается не в «особых словах», а в конфигурации их отношений

внутри контекста [1]. Метафора и метонимия задают два основных вектора смыслового сближения — аналогию и смежность; эпитет, сравнение и символ работают как локальные модификаторы перспективы; ирония и антитеза создают расщепление и конфликт, повышающие интерпретационную активность адресата [2], [4]. Такая сетевость значений принципиально прагматична: она проектируется на компетенции читателя и его культурную память, ожидая распознавания переносного чтения и отклонений от сочетаемостной нормы [1], [3], а механизмы междоменных проекций объясняют устойчивость эффектов в разных жанрах и эпохах [5].

Практическая применимость. Предложенная схема аннотирования художественных контекстов по параметрам тропности, типам межсловных связей и прагматическим эффектам может использоваться в учебной аналитике текста, в корпусной и вычислительной лингвистике, а также в редакторской экспертизе художественного языка [3].

Заключение. Лексические средства образности реализуют потенциал через сеть межсловных семантических отношений, которая настраивает внимание читателя, перераспределяет значения и формирует опыт переживания текста. Прагматический эффект выражается в согласованной работе эмоциональных, когнитивных, коммуникативных и интерпретативных механизмов; перспективным остаётся описание взаимодействия тропов в многоуровневых конфигурациях и их моделирование в корпусных исследованиях [1], [5].

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BADIYIY DISKURSDA YUMOR VA SATIRANING
PRAGMALINGVISTIK ASPEKTLARI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK
TILLARI MISOLIDA)

Kalit soʻzlar: badiiy diskurs; yumor; satira; pragmalingvistika; illokutsion maqsad; kommunikativ niyat; Graysning kooperatsiya prinsipi; politeness strategiyalari; lingvopragmatika; sotsiokulturologik omillar; madaniy kodlar;

understatement; kinoya; mubolag‘a; ironiyaviy strategiyalar; intermadaniy kommunikatsiya; komik effekt; satirik diskurs; lingvopoetik vositalar.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada badiiy diskursda yumor va satiraning kommunikativ, pragmalingvistik hamda sotsiokulturologik xususiyatlari ingliz va o‘zbek adabiyoti misolida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot doirasida yumor va satiraning illokutsion maqsadi, Graysning kooperatsiya prinsipi, madaniy kodlar, gender va ijtimoiy kontekstdagi farqlar o‘rganiladi. Tahlil jarayonida Jonathan Swift, Oscar Wilde, Jerome K. Jerome kabi ingliz yozuvchilari hamda Muqimiy, A. Qodiriy, G‘afur G‘ulom, Said Ahmad kabi o‘zbek adabiyoti namunalari qiyosiy o‘rganildi. Maqola badiiy matnning semantik-pragmatik tizimini chuqurroq anglash va intermadaniy tahlil kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kirish: Yumor va satira badiiy diskursning ajralmas tarkibiy qismi bo‘lib, ular nafaqat estetik funktsiya, balki muallifning ijtimoiy-axloqiy pozitsiyasini ifodalovchi pragmatik vosita sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi (Attardo, 1994). Yumor o‘quvchi bilan kommunikativ aloqani yumshatsa, satira ijtimoiy voqelikni tanqid qilish, kulgi orqali baholash va isloh qilishga yo‘naltiriladi. Tilshunoslikda mazkur fenomenlar pragmalingvistika, diskurs tahlili, kognitiv lingvistika va madaniyatshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan o‘rganiladi (Dyner, 2018).

Ingliz va o‘zbek adabiyotlarida yumor va satiraning shakllanishi milliy mentalitet, tarixiy jarayonlar, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar va madaniy kodlarga bog‘liq ravishda farqlanadi. Ingliz adabiyotida nozik kinoya, understatement kabi usullar ustuvor bo‘lsa, o‘zbek badiiy an‘analarida ochiq, ko‘p hollarda didaktik ruhdagi satira kuchliroqdir.

Asosiy qism

1. Yumor va satiraning pragmalingvistik asoslari

1.1. Illokutsion maqsad va kommunikativ niyat

Yumor va satiraning illokutsion kuchi (Austin, 1962) muallifning quyidagi kommunikativ maqsadlarida aks etadi:

- o‘quvchini voqelikni turlicha idrok etishga undash;
- ijtimoiy ziddiyatlarga e‘tibor qaratish;
- tanqidni bilvosita (yumor) yoki ochiq (satira) shaklda yetkazish;
- muloqotni yengillashtirish yoki aksincha – ziddiyatni kuchaytirish.

Masalan, Swiftning “A Modest Proposal” asarida muallif ochiq tanqidni bilvosita, ironik ohangda beradi. Uning illokutsion maqsadi — ingliz jamiyatidagi iqtisodiy tengsizlikning absurd darajasini ochib berish (Rawson, 2014).

O‘zbek adabiyotida esa ko‘pincha ochiq kinoya va tanqid ustuvor. Qodiriyning “Kalvak Maxzum” obrazi orqali muallif jamiyatdagi savodsizlik va e‘tiqodiy ojizlikni tanqid qiladi.

1.2. Grays kooperatsiya prinsipi va uning buzilishi

Grays (1975)ga ko'ra yumor aksariyat hollarda maxsus pragmatik buzilishlarga asoslanadi:

Prinsip	Buzilish turi	Natija
Miqdor	Keragidan ortiqcha yoki yetishmaydigan ma'lumot	Kulgi, absurdlik
Sifat	Ataylab yolg'on yoki mubolag'a	Ironiya, satira
Munosiblik	Noo'rin javob	Komik kolliziya
Uslub	Chalkash ifoda	Noodatiylikdan kulgi

Ingliz “dry humor”i ko'pincha understatementga, ya'ni fikrni sun'iy pasaytirishga asoslanadi:

“Not bad at all,” — o'ta noqulay vaziyatda aytilgan kinoya (Chiaro, 2010).

O'zbek yumorida esa mubolag'a va majoz ko'proq ishlatiladi:

“Kalvak Maxzumning dahosiga yetadigan odam topilsa, dunyo o'zgardi.” (A. Qodiriy)

Bu yerda sifat prinsipining ataylab buzilishi satirik effektini kuchaytiradi.

1.3. Politeness strategiyalari

Brown & Levinson (1987) nazariyasiga ko'ra:

- **Ingliz yumorida** negative politeness ustuvor — bilvosita, nozik, e'tiborli hazil.
- **O'zbek yumorida** esa positive politeness — o'zaro yaqinlik, ochiq maslahat ohangi, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri kinoya.

Demak, ingliz hazilida pragmatik signallar yashirinroq; o'zbek hazilida esa madaniy kontekst orqali darhol anglash mumkin.

2. Yumor va satiraning sotsiokulturologik aspektlari

2.1. Madaniy kodlar va mentalitet

Ingliz jamiyatida shaxsiy chegaralarga hurmat, emotsional nazorat, hazilda bilvosita ohang ustuvor (Fox, 2004). Shuning uchun ustivor komik usul — *self-deprecating humor* va *understatement*dir.

O'zbek madaniyatida esa jamoaviylik, nutqiy ochiqlik, nasihatboplik kuchli. Shu sabab satira tarbiyaviy maqsadga xizmat qiladi (To'xtayev, 2019).

2.2. Gender va ijtimoiy omillar

Sosiolingvistlar fikriga ko'ra (Holmes, 2006):

- erkaklar hazilida tanqidiylik, ijtimoiy mavzu;
- ayollar hazilida esa qo'llab-quvvatlash, yumshoq ironiyaga moyillik kuchliroq.

Bu tendensiya ingliz va o'zbek badiiy matnlarida ham aks etadi.

2.3. Intermadaniy farqlar

Aspekt	Ingliz adabiyoti	O'zbek adabiyoti
Komik usul	Understatement, witty irony	Mubolag'a, ochiq kinoya
Satira maqsadi	Jamiyatdagi mantiqsizlikni fosh etish	Tarbiyaviy, ijtimoiy ogohlik
Madaniy kod	Individualizm	Jamoaviylik

O'quvchi roli	Mustaqil talqin	Muallif niyatini qabul qilish
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Xulosa

Yumor va satira ingliz va o'zbek badiiy diskurslarida turlicha pragmalingsvistik va sotsiokulturologik vazifalarni bajaradi. Ingliz adabiyoti humorining lingvopragmatik mohiyati nozik kinoya va bilvosita tanqidda namoyon bo'lsa, o'zbek adabiyotida yumor va satira ochiq, didaktik va ijtimoiy ruhda shakllanadi. Mazkur farqlar milliy mentalitet, madaniy kodlar va tarixiy sharoitlar bilan bevosita bog'liq. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari intermadaniy kommunikatsiya, diskurs tahlili va pragmalingsvistika sohalari uchun muhim nazariy asos yaratadi.

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UNDERSTANDING METAPHORICAL PHRASES THROUGH THE LENS OF COGNITIVE METAPHOR

Keywords: cognitive metaphor, Conceptual Metaphor Theory, source domain, target domain, metaphorical mapping, linguistic metaphor, metaphorical phrases, embodiment, conceptualization, figurative language

Metaphor has long been viewed as an artistic or rhetorical phenomenon used primarily for aesthetic effect. Traditional linguistic approaches often considered metaphors as decorative devices to embellish speech and writing. However, the rise of cognitive linguistics in the late twentieth century revolutionized this perspective. With the groundbreaking work of George Lakoff and Mark Johnson (1980), metaphor came to be understood not merely as a

linguistic ornament but as a fundamental mechanism of human thought. This shift in understanding formed the basis of **Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT)**, which posits that metaphor is a cognitive tool through which humans conceptualize abstract domains of experience by mapping them onto more concrete, familiar domains.

The purpose of this article is to explore the theoretical foundations of cognitive metaphor, examine the mechanisms of metaphorical mapping, and demonstrate how metaphorical phrases in natural language emerge from underlying conceptual metaphors. Particular emphasis will be placed on the cognitive motivations behind metaphorical expressions, the role of embodiment in metaphor creation, and the ways metaphorical phrases vary across cultures. The discussion will also highlight why understanding cognitive metaphor is crucial for linguistics, discourse analysis, translation, and foreign language pedagogy.

Traditional rhetoric viewed metaphor primarily as a stylistic device. Aristotle regarded metaphor as a form of substitution: one term is replaced by another for artistic effect. Structuralist linguists similarly saw metaphor as deviation from the norm of literal language.

In contrast, cognitive linguistics argues that metaphor is a matter of thought, not language alone. Lakoff and Johnson's assertion that "*metaphor is pervasive in everyday life, not just in language but in thought and action*" marks a paradigm shift. According to CMT, humans rely on metaphorical structures to reason about abstract concepts such as time, love, justice, morality, and emotion. Metaphors are thus mental tools that enable categorization, understanding, and communication.

Cognitive linguistics emphasizes the **embodied mind**—the idea that conceptual structures are shaped by the body and sensorimotor experience. Human beings metaphorize abstract experiences based on recurring physical patterns. For instance:

- **UP** corresponds to positive emotions or success because physical upward motion requires effort and typically correlates with improved perspective or safety.
 - → "*Her spirits rose,*" "*He climbed the social ladder.*"
- **DOWN** corresponds to sadness or failure.
 - → "*He fell into depression.*"

Thus, metaphorical phrases are not arbitrary linguistic inventions; they reflect systematic reasoning rooted in bodily experience.

These schemas are universal, though their linguistic expressions differ across languages.

Metaphorical phrases follow the logic of the metaphorical mapping. For instance, in the conceptual metaphor **ARGUMENT IS WAR**, the war-like structure creates a series of related expressions:

- *attack the argument*
- *defend your claim*

- *win the debate*
- *counterattack*

Since “war” functions as the source domain, the metaphorical phrases inherit semantic elements of conflict: strategy, victory, defeat, defense.

4. Cultural Variation in Cognitive Metaphor and Metaphorical Expressions

While many conceptual metaphors are universal due to shared human embodiment, metaphorical phrases differ across cultures because conceptualizations are influenced by cultural models, values, and environment.

Cognitive metaphor is a fundamental mechanism through which humans conceptualize the world. It is not a superficial linguistic ornament; instead, it is a deep cognitive structure that shapes reasoning, communication, and cultural behavior. Metaphorical phrases in language are the visible surface manifestations of these conceptual mappings, reflecting embodied experience and cultural models. Understanding the relationship between cognitive metaphor and metaphorical expressions provides valuable insights not only into linguistics but also into cognitive psychology, discourse analysis, translation studies, and language pedagogy.

Ultimately, a nuanced understanding of this intricate relationship between underlying cognitive metaphors and their diverse metaphorical expressions offers profoundly valuable insights across a multitude of academic disciplines. In linguistics, it enriches our comprehension of semantics, pragmatics, and lexical development. For cognitive psychology, it sheds light on how the human mind processes information, constructs meaning, and forms abstract thoughts. Discourse analysis benefits by providing a powerful tool to deconstruct the hidden meanings, persuasive strategies, and ideological stances embedded within spoken and written communication. In translation studies, recognizing these cultural nuances in metaphor is critical for avoiding literal, often nonsensical or culturally inappropriate, renditions and achieving genuinely equivalent meaning. Finally, within language pedagogy, this understanding empowers educators to teach idiomatic expressions and cultural nuances more effectively, moving beyond rote memorization to foster a deeper, more conceptual grasp of a target language's idiomatic richness and cultural underpinnings. The study of metaphor, therefore, is not merely an academic exercise but a gateway to a deeper appreciation of human cognition and cultural diversity.

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TARJIMA MUAMMOLARI VA TARJIMON KOMPETENSIYALARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tarjima jarayonida lingvokulturologik moslik va semantik adekvatlikni ta'minlashga doir nazariy va amaliy masalalar yoritiladi. Tarjima jarayonida til birliklarining milliy-madaniy komponentlari, konnotativ ma'nolari, realiyalar va metaforik konstruksiyalarni adekvat ko'chirishning murakkab jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Muallif tarjimonning lingvistik va madaniy kompetensiyasi, matnning funksional-uslubiy xususiyatlarini qayta yaratish mahorati hamda kontekstual anglash qobiliyatining tarjima sifatiga ta'sirini asoslab beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: tarjima, adekvat, realiya, metaforik konstruksiya, madaniy kod, lingvistik kompetensiya, semantik nomunofiqlar, lingvokulturologik tafovutlar.

Bugungi globallashtirish sharoitida tarjima nafaqat ikki til o'rtasidagi vositachilik, balki madaniyatlararo muloqotning asosiy ko'rinishlaridan biri sifatida ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tarjima jarayonining samaradorligi ko'p jihatdan tarjimonning lingvistik kompetensiyasiga, madaniy kodlarni anglash darajasiga hamda matnning funksional-uslubiy xususiyatlarini adekvat qayta yaratish qobiliyatiga bog'liqdir.

L.S.Barxudarovning kitobida "matnlar tarjima qilib bo'lmaydigan emas, balki ayrim elementlar tarjimasini murakkab bo'lishi mumkin"¹ degan g'oyasi alohida ta'kidlanadi. Mazkur maqolada tarjima jarayonida uchraydigan lingvokulturologik tafovutlar, semantik nomunofiqliklar hamda matnlararo moslikni ta'minlashga doir nazariy va amaliy jihatlar tahlil qilinadi.

Har bir til o'z dunyoqarashi, mentaliteti, tarixiy-madaniy tajribasi bilan

¹ Бархударов Л. С. Язык и перевод. – М.: Междунар. отношения, 1975. – С. 122.

ajralib turadi. Shu bois til birliklari ko‘pincha o‘zida milliy-madaniy komponentlarni mujassam etadi. Frazologizmlar, realiyalar, metaforik birliklar tarjimasida aynan shu madaniy kodlarning moslashtirilishi katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Tarjimonning vazifasi fantastik asarlarda uchraydigan fantastik realiyalarni imkon qadar tushunarli va aniq yetkazishdir. Tarjimon semantik ekvivalentni tanlashda yashirin ma‘no qatlamlari, konnotativ belgilari va pragmatik yuklamalarni ham e‘tiborga olishi shart.

Tarjima jarayoni faqat lug‘aviy yoki grammatik jihatdan to‘g‘ri ko‘chirish bilan cheklanmaydi. Asliyatdagi mazmunning to‘laligicha aks ettirilishi semantik adekvatlikni talab etadi. Fantastik asarlar va ularning tillararo yetkazilishi zamonaviy tarjima nazariyasi uchun juda muhim, ammo hozirgi vaqtda fantastik asarlarni tarjima qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari va qiyinchiliklari yetarlicha tavsiflanmagan, shunga ko‘ra, mumkin bo‘lgan tarjima xatolarining tipologiyasi va tarjima strategiyalari qiyosiy-chog‘ishtirma tahlil asosida ishlab chiqilmagan. Fantastik asarlar kompozitsiyasining bevosita qismi sifatida ma‘lum bir leksika va stilistik usullardan foydalanish umumiy mualliflik uslubini shakllantiradi, yozuvchilarning individualligini, ularning fikrlarining o‘ziga xosligini aks ettiradi, ularning asarlarini taniqli qiladi¹. Badiiy adabiyot adabiy tilning cheksiz rivojlanishiga, yangi iboralar, qiyosiy iboralar, metaforalar va boshqalarning paydo bo‘lishiga imkon beradi, ammo yozuvchi mehnatining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlariga qaramay, unda baribir g‘oyaning paydo bo‘lishi, yozuvchining o‘z maqsadini anglashi, ijodiy vazifaning mumkin bo‘lgan yechimlaridan eng yaxshisini tanlashi, ma‘lum bir maqsadning zarurligini tan olishi kabi bosqichlar mavjud.

Tarjimon tanlaydigan strategiyalar — transkripsiya, ekvivalent almashtirish, kompensatsiya yoki moslashtirish kabi usullar matn turiga qarab qo‘llanadi. Amaliy tahlillarda ko‘p hollarda metaforik iboralar va frazeologik birliklarning tarjimasida muammolar ko‘zga tashlanadi. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi metaforalarning asosida yotuvchi konseptlar o‘zbek mentalitetiga to‘la mos kelmasligi mumkin. Bunday hollarda tarjimon ma‘no ekvivalentini topish yoki funksional jihatdan mos konstruksiya yaratish orqali madaniy tafovutlarni yumshatadi. Shuningdek, realiyalar tarjimasida ham to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri ekvivalent topilmasa, izohli tarjima yoki kontekstual moslashtirish usullari qo‘llanadi.

Xulosa. O‘tkazilgan tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki, tarjima jarayoni lingvistik, madaniy va kognitiv omillar uyg‘unligini talab qiladigan murakkab faoliyatdir. Lingvokulturologik moslikni ta‘minlash, semantik adekvatlikka erishish, matnning funksional-uslubiy xususiyatlarini qayta yaratish — yuqori sifatli tarjimaning asosiy mezonlaridir. Tarjimonning madaniy sezgirligi, kontekstni chuqur anglash qobiliyati va muallif niyatini qayta tiklash mahorati tarjima samaradorligini belgilaydi.

Adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

¹ Разинкина Н. М. Функциональная стилистика: на мат. англ. и рус. яз. – М., 2004. – 182 с.

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AN ANALYTICAL LINGUACULTURAL COMPARISON OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK APHORISMS

Annotation: This study presents a linguacultural comparative examination of English and Uzbek aphorisms attributed to prominent philosophers and literary figures. The investigation focuses on how these aphoristic expressions encode moral, philosophical, and cultural values. Each aphorism is analyzed through a linguacultural lens, considering its semantic structure, stylistic features, and cultural significance. The results indicate that English aphorisms predominantly embody rationalist, individualistic, and pragmatic orientations, whereas Uzbek aphorisms emphasize spiritual principles, notions of justice, and collectivist ethical norms.

Key words: aphorism, linguacultural, comparative study, stylistic meaning, national values, intercultural reflection.

Introduction. Aphorisms constitute brief, memorable statements that articulate universal insights or philosophical reflections on life. They function as verbal representations of a community's cultural mindset and its linguistic creativity. Gross defines an aphorism as “a concise and often witty expression of universal truth.” English aphorisms—shaped by the intellectual legacy of the Enlightenment—frequently convey rational thought, psychological introspection, and individualistic values. In contrast, Uzbek aphorisms embody collective moral norms, spiritual belief systems, and traditional wisdom rooted in ethical and religious heritage. This study explores how each aphorism conveys the cultural worldview of its respective society while simultaneously transmitting shared

human wisdom through linguacultural analysis.

Theoretical Background. The term *aphorism* originates from the Greek *aphorismos*, meaning “definition” or “distinction.” Unlike proverbs, aphorisms are distinguished by their identifiable authorship, with individual creators claiming intellectual ownership. Linguacultural analysis, as conceptualized by Vereshchagin and Kostomarov, examines the ways in which linguistic forms encode cultural meanings. Utilizing this theoretical framework, the present research aims to compare how English and Uzbek aphorisms linguistically manifest cultural values, ethical principles, and forms of cultural identity.

Francis Bacon: “Knowledge is power.”¹ This aphorism would represent that spirit of the English Enlightenment, stressing human mastery and improvement through knowledge. Its declarative form finds nominal symmetry and reflects rational thought. It is culturally representative of the Western belief in intellect as the source of social influence and moral strength. William Shakespeare: “All the world’s a stage, and all the men and women merely players.”² Shakespeare’s metaphor of equating life to performance epitomizes Renaissance humanism. The imagery from theatre suggests the fascination of English culture with individuality and social roles. Benjamin Franklin: “Lost time is never found again.”³ Franklin here elucidates the value of time management central to early American capitalism. The aphorism linguistically deploys antithesis and finality, expressing Protestant work ethic and practicality. Oscar Wilde: “Be yourself; everyone else is already taken.”⁴ Ironical and paradoxical, just typical of Wilde’s wit; it advocates individual authenticity, a hallmark of modern Western identity. The structure blends humor and moral advice. There are also lots of aphorisms in Uzbek which have been using for a long time. Amir Temur: “Strength is in justice.”⁵ This saying best describes the political philosophy of the Timurid Empire. Justice (“adolat”) is represented here as an element of legitimate power. The linguistic features include: nominal sentence form. The cultural aspects include: Islamic governance; Central Asian ethics. Amir Temur: “A ruler who does not value his soldiers cannot rule his state.”⁶ The statement reveals collectivist values that emphasize loyalty and duty. It reflects the feudal structure and moral responsibility of leadership in the Turkic culture. Alisher Navoi: “A word is an arrow: once released, it does not return.”⁷ The metaphor by Navoi warns of the irreversible power of speech. The vivid imagery of ‘arrow’ reflects the Eastern moral aesthetics about restraint and wisdom in language. Alisher Navoi: “The tongue is small but it can destroy mountains.”⁸

¹ Francis Bacon, *Novum Organum*, London, 1620.

² William Shakespeare, quoted from *The Oxford Book of Aphorisms* Gross, 2003

³ Benjamin Franklin, *Poor Richard’s Almanack*, Philadelphia, 1758.

⁴ Oscar Wilde, *The Critic as Artist*, London: Heinemann, 1891.

⁵ Amir Temur, *Tuzuklar*, Tashkent: G’afur G’ulom NMIU, 1377.

⁶ Amir Temur, *Tuzuklar*, Tashkent: G’afur G’ulom NMIU, 1377.

⁷ Alisher Navoi, *Mahbub ul-qulub*, Tashkent: Fan, 1968.

⁸ Alisher Navoi, *Mahbub ul-qulub*, Tashkent: Fan, 1968.

Hyperbolic expression of the power of words. It reflects the moral conviction that speech is invested with divine responsibility, a salient principle in Sufi ethics. Ahmad Donish: "Ignorance is the root of all evil."¹ A rationalist point from the 19th-century Bukhara enlightenment. Lingually simple, it symbolizes the reformist movement valuing education and moral progress. Abu Rayhon Beruniy: "Science is the light that guides life."² Beruniy connects intellectual pursuit with moral illumination. The metaphor of "light" reflects both Islamic epistemology and universal rationalism. Erkin Vohidov: "Without truth, poetry loses its soul."³ Aesthetic and ethical statement tying art with sincerity. It shows how the Uzbek literary tradition focuses on moral integrity in creativity. Abdulla Avloniy: "Education is the mirror of a nation."⁴ This aphorism mirrors the Jadid enlightenment period, wherein education is equated to national progress. The metaphor of the "mirror" relates to cultural identity and reflection. Cholpon: "Freedom is as sacred as life itself."⁵ A humanistic aphorism, emblematic of the early 20th-century national awakening, it connects liberty to existential value and expresses the Uzbek modernist ideal. Oybek: "Human dignity is the highest measure of civilization."⁶ This is a reflection of post-war moral reconstruction in Uzbek literature. The phrase places humanism above material success, coinciding with universal ethics. Ibrohim Haqqul: "Thought without heart becomes cold; heart without thought becomes blind."⁷ It is an intellectual and emotive dialectical aphorism. Culturally, it reflects Eastern balance between reason and compassion. Islom Karimov: "There is no future without historical memory."⁸ A modern aphorism underlining national continuity, fusing patriotism and collective memory, central to post-independence Uzbek identity.

Conclusion. The linguacultural comparison of English and Uzbek aphorisms reveals the use of brevity and metaphoricalness to reveal moral truths in both traditions. English aphorisms often focus on personal achievement and logical reasoning, while Uzbek ones concentrate on the issues of collective ethics and justice, inner virtue. Despite the differences, they both reveal the universal search of humanity for wisdom and balance between intellect and morality. Aphorisms thus remain the linguistic monuments of cultural identity and timeless philosophy.

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² Abu Rayhon Beruniy, *Al-Osor al-Boqiya*, 1048.

³ Erkin Vohidov, quoted from *The Oxford Book of Aphorisms* Gross, 2003

⁴ Abdulla Avloniy, *Turki Guliston yoxud Axloq*, Tashkent, 1913.

⁵ Cho'lpon, quoted from *The Oxford Book of Aphorisms* Gross, 2003

⁶ Oybek, quoted from *The Oxford Book of Aphorisms* Gross, 2003

⁷ Ibrohim Haqqul, *Ma'naviyat manbalari*, Tashkent, 2010.

⁸ Islom Karimov, *Yuksak ma'naviyat — yengilmas kuch*, Tashkent, 1997.

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KOGNITIV TILSHUNOSLIK FANINING ASOSIY MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI TAVSIFI

Kognitiv tilshunoslik zamonaviy lingvistik tafakkurning eng faol shakllanayotgan va turli fanlar bilan kesishib borayotgan yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida tilning inson ongidagi aksiga, tafakkur jarayonlari bilan bog'liqligiga, til birliklarining psixologik va idrokiy asoslariga e'tibor qaratadi. Mazkur paradigma tilni faqat grammatik tizim yoki kommunikativ vosita sifatida emas, balki insonning bilish faoliyati, idrokiy jarayonlari, mantiqiy va assotsiativ mexanizmlarining tashqi ko'rinishi sifatida o'rganadi. Tilning ortida turadigan konseptual tizim, bilimlar strukturasi, tajribaga asoslangan kategoriyalar, madaniy kodlar, metaforik dunyoqarash kognitiv yondashuvning markazida

turadi. Bu yo'nalishning shakllanishiga Chomskiy, Lakoff, Langacker, Fillmor kabi g'arb olimlari bilan bir qatorda, Markaziy Osiyo tilshunosligi, xususan, o'zbek lingvistikasining yirik vakillari ham munosib hissa qo'shgan. A. Yo'ldoshevning til va tafakkur munosabatlariga doir ishlari, A. Nurmonov tomonidan kognitiv semantikaning nazariy asoslarini o'zbek tiliga mos holda ochib berish, M. Shomirzayevaning kognitiv konseptlar va mental modellar haqidagi izlanishlari bu yo'nalishning milliy ilmiy maktab sifatida rivojlanishiga turtki bo'lgan. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham kognitiv yondashuv so'nggi yillarda izchil rivojlanib, milliy konseptosfera, o'zbek mentalitetining lingvistik manzarasi, milliy-madaniy kodlar, metaforik tafakkurning o'ziga xosligi kabi masalalar chuqur o'rganilmoqda. A. Yo'ldoshev, A. Nurmonov, M. Shomirzayeva, N. Madrahimov, Z. Sodiqova, D. Berdialiyeva singari olimlarning ishlari o'zbek kognitiv tilshunosligi maktabining shakllanishi va takomillashuviga mustahkam zamin yaratdi. Ularning tadqiqotlari o'zbek konseptlarining semantik tuzilishi, milliy tafakkurni aks ettiruvchi lingvistik birliklar, madaniyat va tilning o'zaro ta'siri kabi masalalarni ilmiy asosda yoritmoqda.

Kognitiv tilshunoslikning umumiy maqsadi – tilning inson ongidagi ko'rinishini, ya'ni konseptual tizimlarning shakllanishi, bilimning til orqali modellashtirilishi, idrok jarayonlarining lingvistik ifodasi qanday yuz berishini ilmiy asosda o'rganishdir. Tilning har bir birligi – so'z, ibora, grammatik shakl yoki metafora – inson ongidagi konseptual strukturaning tashqi ko'rinishidir. Shu jihatdan kognitiv tilshunoslik tilni o'rganish orqali inson tafakkurining qanday ishlashini tahlil qiladi. A. Yo'ldoshev ta'kidlaganidek, “tilning ma'no qatlamida insonning dunyoni idrok etish modeli yashiringan bo'ladi”¹, demak, kognitiv tahlil bu yashirin qatlamni ochishga xizmat qiladi. O'zbek tilshunosligida so'nggi yillarda konseptlar, konseptosfera, lingvokulturologik kodlar, mental modellarning milliy xususiyatlarini o'rganishga katta e'tibor qaratilayotgani ham bejiz emas, chunki bu jarayon milliy dunyoqarashni til orqali ilmiy rekonstruksiya qilish imkonini beradi.

Kognitiv lingvistikaning eng muhim vazifalaridan biri konseptlarni tahlil qilishdir. Konsept faqat ma'nolar yig'indisi emas, balki madaniyat, tarix, psixologiya, milliy ong va ijtimoiy tajriba bilan boyigan murakkab mental birlikdir. M. Shomirzayeva, Z. Sodiqova² va D. Berdialiyeva o'zbek konseptologiyasiga oid tadqiqotlarida “ona”, “yurt”, “mehmondo'stlik”, “or-nomus”, “davlat”, “kelajak”, “baxt” kabi konseptlarning milliy mentalitetdagi o'rnini tahlil qilib, ularning tildagi ifodasi orqali milliy ong mexanizmlarini ochib bergan. Kognitiv yondashuvga ko'ra, konseptlar inson xotirasida bilimni kodlaydi, tuzadi, kategoriyalaydi va til orqali faollashtiradi. Konseptlarni o'rganish tilning nafaqat semantik, balki psixologik, tarixiy va madaniy qatlamlarini ham ochadi.

¹ Yo'ldoshev A. *Til va tafakkur munosabatlari*. Toshkent: O'zMU, 2015.

² Sodiqova Z. *O'zbek konseptologiyasi masalalari*. SamDU nashriyoti, 2021.

Kognitiv tilshunoslikning yana bir muhim vazifasi kategoriyalash jarayonini tahlil qilishdir. Inson atrofdagi hodisalarni idrok qilish jarayonida ularni ma'lum kategoriyalarga ajratadi, bu kategoriyalar esa til orqali mustahkamlanadi. M. Shomirzayeva rang kategoriyalari, hissiy kategoriya, qavmlararo tushunchalar, vaqt va fazo tushunchalarining o'zbek tilidagi kategoriyalash xususiyatlarini o'rganib, o'zbek mentalitetining idrokiy o'ziga xosliklarini yoritib bergan¹. Kognitiv tilshunoslikning vazifasi ana shu kategoriyalarning universal (umuminsoniy) hamda milliy-madaniy farqlarini tahlil qilishdir.

Konseptualizatsiya jarayonini o'rganish ham kognitiv lingvistikaning markaziy vazifasidir. Konseptualizatsiya – insonning dunyoni ongida qanday modellashtirishi, obyektlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni qanday tushunishi, ularni qanday mental strukturalarga joylashtirishi jarayonidir. O'zbek tilida “hayot yo'li”, “qismat yozig'i”, “martaba cho'qqisi”, “tor dunyoqarash”, “ko'ngli yorishdi”, “juvonmardlik ustuni” kabi birikmalar konseptual xaritalash orqali yuzaga kelgan. G. Lakoffning konseptual metafora nazariyasi bu jarayonni ilmiy asoslab bergan bo'lsa, o'zbek olimlaridan R. Rasulov² va N. Madrahimov³ ushbu nazariyani o'zbek tilshunosligi materiallari asosida rivojlantirishgan. Masalan, “hayot – yo'l” modeli, “baxt – nishon”, “jamiyat – oila”, “ta'lim – nur” kabi konseptual xaritalar o'zbek mentalitetida qadimdan shakllangan bo'lib, ular til orqali mustahkamlanadi.

Mental modellarni o'rganish ham kognitiv lingvistikaning muhim vazifalaridan biridir. Mental model – bu inson ongida muayyan jarayon yoki obyektning dinamik tasviri bo'lib, inson muayyan hodisani qanday tushunishini belgilaydi.

Kognitiv tilshunoslikning amaliy vazifalari ham nihoyatda keng. Avvalo, bu yondashuv ta'lim jarayonida tilni o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Chunki tilni o'zlashtirish nafaqat qoidalarni yodlash, balki konseptlarni anglash, mental modellarni shakllantirish, mazmuniy bog'liqliklarni ongda to'g'ri qurish demakdir.

Kognitiv tilshunoslikning milliy o'ziga xos jihatlarini chuqur o'rganish o'zbek dunyoqarashini ilmiy asosda qayta tiklash imkonini beradi. A. Nurmonov o'zbek tilidagi konseptlar tizimini o'rganar ekan, milliy mentalitet tilning semantik qatlamida juda kuchli saqlanib qolishini ta'kidlaydi. Z. Sodiqova o'zbek tilida «mehr», «or», «nomus», «qadr», «uyat», «halollik» kabi milliy axloqiy konseptlarning tildagi ifodasi orqali o'zbek xalqining qadriyatlar tizimini ilmiy modellashtirgan⁴. D. Berdialiyeva esa o'zbek konseptosferasining tarixiy-

¹ Shomirzayeva M. *Kognitiv lingvistikaning asosiy masalalari*. Toshkent: Fan, 2012.

² Rasulov R. *Tilning kognitiv asoslari*. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2019.

³ Madrahimov N. *Kognitiv lingvistika va lingvokulturologiya yo'nalishlari*. Toshkent: Innovatsiya-Ziyo, 2020.

⁴ Sodiqova Z. *O'zbek konseptologiyasi masalalari*. SamDU nashriyoti, 2021.

madaniy asoslarini tahlil qilib, konseptlar vaqt o'tishi bilan o'zgarishini ko'rsatgan¹.

Umuman olganda, kognitiv tilshunoslik tilni insonning "ichki dunyosi" bilan bog'lab o'rganadi. Bu yondashuv tilning tashqi ko'rinishini emas, balki uning ortida turgan konseptual, idrokiy va madaniy strukturalarni ochib beradi. Bu esa tilshunoslikni yanada chuqurroq, yanada insoniyroq, yanada ma'noga yo'naltirilgan ilmiy sohaga aylantiradi. Kognitiv yondashuvning kuchi shundaki, u tilni hayotdan, insoniyat tajribasidan, madaniyatdan ajratmaydi, aksincha, ularni yagona tizim sifatida ko'radi. Shuning uchun ham kognitiv tilshunoslik bugungi global fan taraqqiyotida, xususan, o'zbek tilshunosligining yangi bosqichida alohida o'rin egallamoqda.

Kognitiv tilshunoslik bugungi tilshunoslikning eng muhim, istiqbolli va keng qamrovli yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida tilning inson ongidagi jarayonlar bilan uzviy bog'liqligini ilmiy asosda ochib beradi. Tilni faqat struktur birliklar majmui sifatida emas, balki konseptual tizimlarning ifodaviy shakli, madaniy tajribaning aks-sadosi, idrok jarayonlarining tashqi ko'rinishi sifatida talqin qilishi mazkur yo'nalishning nazariy ahamiyatini yanada yuksaltiradi. Konseptlar, kategoriyalar, mental modellar, metaforik xaritalash, lingvokulturologik kodlar kabi tushunchalar orqali kognitiv tilshunoslik insonning dunyoni qanday anglashini, bilimni qanday tizimlashtirishini, tajribani qanday tilga ko'chirganini yoritadi. Bu esa tilshunoslikni boshqa fanlar – psixologiya, falsafa, madaniyatshunoslik, neyrofanlar va sun'iy intellekt bilan integratsiyalashgan holda rivojlantirish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, kognitiv tilshunoslik tilni inson tafakkurining yorqin aksi sifatida o'rganish imkonini beradi. Bu yo'nalish nafaqat nazariy jihatdan, balki amaliy sohalarida ham – ta'lim, tarjima, sun'iy intellekt, psixolingvistika, lingvokulturologiya kabi yo'nalishlarda katta ahamiyatga ega. Kognitiv yondashuvning kuchi shundaki, u tilni insonning ruhiy, idrokiy va madaniy olami bilan birgalikda o'rganadi, til birliklarining orqasida yashiringan konseptual tizimlarni ochib beradi va shu orqali tilning eng chuqur mohiyatini anglashga yordam beradi. Shu sababli, kognitiv tilshunoslikni yanada chuqur o'rganish, milliy tadqiqotlarni kengaytirish, o'zbek konseptologiyasi va lingvokognitologiyasini rivojlantirish bugungi tilshunoslikning dolzarb vazifalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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IKKI TILLI (INGLIZ–O‘ZBEK) MULOQOTDA XUSHMUOMALALIKNING LINGVOPRAGMATIK MODELLARI

Annotatsiya. Xushmuomalalik (politeness) – bu til vositalari orqali insonlarning o‘zaro munosabatlarini tartibga soluvchi lingvopragmatik kategoriya bo‘lib, u kommunikativ jarayonning samaradorligini oshiradi. Har bir millat madaniyati va tili xushmuomalilikni ifodalashning o‘ziga xos usullariga ega. Shu jihatdan ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida xushmuomalilik kategoriyasini qiyosiy o‘rganish muhim ilmiy-amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: xushmuomalalik kategoriyasi, lingvopragmatika, nutq etiketi, kommunikativ strategiyalar, “sen/siz” oppozitsiyasi, madaniy-pragmatik xususiyatlar, hurmat bildiruvchi birliklar, yumshatuvchi birliklar (hedging), odobiy nutq, ijtimoiy maqom, qiyosiy tahlil

Tilshunoslikda xushmuomalilik nazariyasi bir necha olimlar tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. G. Leech (1983) “Principles of Pragmatics” asarida xushmuomalilikni nutq etiketi asosida tahlil qilib, oltita maksimani ajratib ko‘rsatadi: takt, saxovat, kamtarlik, maqtov, kelishuv va simpatiya. Shuningdek, P. Brown va S. Levinson (1987) xushmuomalilikni “positive politeness” va “negative politeness” kategoriyalariga ajratib, ularning kommunikativ vaziyatlarda qo‘llanishini ko‘rsatib bergan.

O‘zbek tilshunosligida esa xushmuomalilik masalalari Z. Mamarasulova (2020) va boshqa tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o‘rganilib, “sen/siz” tafovuti, hurmat bildiruvchi so‘zlar va odobiy nutqning lingvopragmatik xususiyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Ingliz tilida xushmuomalilik, asosan, yumshatuvchi (hedging) birliklar va rasmiy murojaat shakllari orqali ifodalanadi. Masalan:

Could you please open the window? (iltimos shakli, yumshoq buyruq)

Would you mind helping me? (so‘rovning yumshatilgan shakli)

Brown va Levinson (1987) ta’kidlaganidek, ingliz tilida negative politeness (boshqaga xalaqit bermaslik, masofani saqlash) ko‘proq qo‘llanadi. O‘zbek tilida esa xushmuomalilik ko‘proq hurmat bildiruvchi murojaatlar orqali namoyon bo‘ladi. Masalan:

“Iltimos, derazani ochib yuborsangiz.” (yumshoq so‘rov)

“Marhamat, o‘tiring.” (hurmat shakli)

“Sizdan bir narsa so‘rasam maylimi?” (ehtiyotkor murojaat)

O‘zbek tilida “sen/siz” qarama-qarshiligi muhim pragmatik yukga ega. “Siz” hurmat, rasmiylik va ijtimoiy masofani bildirsa, “sen” yaqinlik, samimiyat, lekin ayrim vaziyatlarda xushmuomalilik me‘yorining buzilishi sifatida qabul qilinadi.

Misollar

Ingliz tilida:

Excuse me, could you tell me the time? (uzr so‘rab, muloyim so‘rov)

O‘zbek tilida:

“Kechirasiz, soat nechchi bo‘ldi aytib bera olasizmi?” (muloyim rad etish)

Ingliz tilida:

I’m afraid I can’t agree with you.

O‘zbek tilida:

“Kechirasiz, bu fikrga qo‘shila olmayman.”

Ingliz tilida:

Would you like some tea? (taklif)

O‘zbek tilida:

“Choy ichib olasizmi?” yoki “Marhamat, choydan iching.”

Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida xushmuomalilik kategoriyasi lingvopragmatik jihatdan nafaqat til birliklari, balki ular orqali ifodalanadigan ijtimoiy munosabatlar, mentalitet va madaniy qadriyatlarni ham aks ettiradi. Ingliz tilida Leech (1983) tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan xushmuomalilik maksimalari, xususan, kamtarlik, saxiylik, rozilik va simpatiya maksimalari keng qo‘llanadi. Masalan, ingliz muloqotida “Could you please...?”, “Would you mind...?” kabi yumshatuvchi so‘zlar ko‘p ishlatiladi. Bu holatlar suhbatdoshning shaxsiy hududini hurmat qilish va uning ijtimoiy maqomini e‘tiborga olish zarurati bilan bog‘liq.

O‘zbek tilida esa xushmuomalilik ko‘proq hurmat va ehtiromni ifodalashga qaratilgan bo‘lib, “sizlash”, “hurmatli”, “marhamat”, “iltimos” kabi odobiy birliklar keng qo‘llanadi. Bundan tashqari, suhbatdoshning yoshi, jinsiy mansubligi, ijtimoiy maqomi ham xushmuomalilik darajasini belgilab beradi. Masalan, kattalarga murojaat qilishda “aka”, “opa”, “domla”, “ustoz” kabi murojaat birliklari ishlatiladi.

Shuningdek, har ikki til tizimida xushmuomalilikning strategik vazifalari ham o‘xshash: nizoni yumshatish, muloqotni ijobiy yo‘nalishga burish, suhbatdoshni qadrlash va o‘zaro hamjihatlikni ta‘minlash. Xulosa qilib aytganda, ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi xushmuomalilik kategoriyasi umumiy kommunikativ ehtiyoj - ijtimoiy uyg‘unlikni ta‘minlash uchun xizmat qilsa-da, uni ifodalash vositalari milliy madaniyat, an‘ana va ijtimoiy qadriyatlarga ko‘ra turlicha shakllanadi.

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PRAGMATIC POTENTIAL OF FALSE SPEECH ACT IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

Abstract. The concept of discourse and speech acts in pragmatics remains one of the urgent problems of modern linguistics. This article is devoted to the analysis of the pragmatic features of pseudo-speech acts. The article examines various ways and types of false speech acts, and based on the analysis conducted, the means of creating their pragmatic factors are highlighted.

Keywords: False discourse, pragmatics, pragmatic parameters, manipulation, presupposition, implicature.

It can be said that the starting point (period) of the development of the language system begins with pragmatics. After all, language primarily serves the speaker's personal desire and benefit.

Pragmatic features of linguistic activity, the factors that give rise to these features studying is important for determining the social essence of language. This allows us to find evidence that linguistic communication occurs in accordance with social and psycho-psychological laws and, on this basis, the development of the language system. "Pragmatics" (from the Greek pragma - work, action) is actually a philosophical concept, which was used even in pre-Socratic times, and later it was borrowed from Aristotle by such philosophers as J. Locke, E. Kant. In the widespread dissemination of this propaganda in America and Europe, CH. Pierce, R. Karnap, CH. Linguists such as Morris and L. Wittgenstein should be especially noted.

It is very important to study lies in connection with the addresser's speech, because the attitude towards a false or true statement depends on the listener's speaking ability, rules of communication, choices, as well as their mental state (change in emotional state), social habits. In the study of lies in connection with

the subject of the statement, the pragmatic meaning of the sentence (text, gesture), the speaker's reference, pragmatic presupposition, and the speaker's attitude towards what they are expressing (irony, suggestiveness) are of great importance.

The category of truth/falsehood of a statement is used in almost all "main directions" of pragmatic research, such as the influence in speech communication, the strategy and tactics of speech behavior, and their role in the formation of hidden meanings of the statement, presupposition, implicativity of the statement, which are the main material for pragmatic observations.

Presupposition is another criterion that determines the content of false or completely different speech structures. According to R. Stolneyker, "presupposition is a proposition implied before the execution of the required linguistic activity." (Stalnaker, 1978). For example. For the use and understanding of sentences like "Ahmad caught a two-headed snake" and "Ahmad did not catch a two-headed snake" in the text, the speaker and listener must be equally aware of the existence (or non-existence) of a two-headed snake.

One of the categories actively discussed by domestic and foreign scientists is the category of deception. The category of deception is a much broader concept, primarily reflecting the important characteristics of distorting objective reality. At the initial stage of the formation of pragmalinguistics, the concept of "lie" was considered as one of the measures of affirmative sentences. Later, the famous linguist Searle interpreted the concept of lying differently and began to view it as a violation of important measurements of speech acts. And over time, other linguists also began to give different definitions of the pragmatic nature of lying.

The purpose of the pragmalinguistic description of lies is to study the independence of the category of lies, to determine its constitutional features through its connection with other categories of pragmalinguistics, as well as to determine the peculiarities of the influence of speech with the help of lies. From this point of view, the pragmatics of lying can be defined as a branch of semiotics, which studies the construction of a false statement for the successful implementation of the speech effect on the recipient. Existing categories of pragmalinguistics are relevant for studying and explaining the relationship of signs to their users, allowing for the systematization of the results obtained in the study of lies within pragmalinguistics.

At the present stage, pragmalinguistics aims to study several categories: deixis, reference, presupposition, judgment evaluation, suggestion, expectation category, politeness category, choice category, speaker's social status, falsity, and others. Undoubtedly, the main conceptual categories studied in the development of domestic and foreign pragmalinguistics are very diverse. This is because they include those with a long history of studying logic, rhetoric, stylistics, grammar, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, speech theory, communication theory, etc. Proposition and reference constitute the denotative part of the content of the text and are sufficiently covered in domestic and foreign literature. Proposition is a

specific form of knowledge transfer, which belongs to the category of cognitive structures for collecting and storing information.

As a result of research on the pragmatic features and pragmatic category of lies, implicature, presupposition, manipulative power of lies, features of activity and passivity play an important role in pragmalinguistic analysis, and these constitute the internal structure of the pragmatic aspect of false discourse. In pragmalinguistics, the category of lies is defined as a discrepancy or violation of basic pragmatic rules and is characterized by ways of pragmatic interpretation of the meaning of a sentence in the Uzbek language. While the external categorical formula of deception is determined by its influencing properties, the internal formula reveals the constitutional properties of the category of deception: sender, receiver, desire, assumptions, implication of the statement.

The manipulative power of lies lies in the hidden, unconscious nature of the receiver, in the use of language tools and speech methods by the sender to influence the receiver, to make decisions that are beneficial for the receiver. The specified force is implemented by the sender using hidden layers of information, as well as various communication strategies and tactics.

The process and conditions for creating a false statement, the pragmatic features of designing a lie in speech, are the basis for substantiating the pragmalinguistic theory of lying and creating a model for its measurement from the point of view of pragmatics. Pragmatics predetermines the conditions for the implementation of a false statement, the types of actions of false speech, and the possibility of studying the intentions of the perpetrator of the false statement.

Thus, the above sentences are probably common for pragmatics or pragmalinguistics, which can be included in the analysis of not only falsehood, but also such speech parameters as sincerity/insincerity, objectivity/partiality, presumption, irony, etc. An opinion or evaluation given to the recipient is introduced by the sender in non-proposed parts of the text - presuppositions, consequences, and influence of the speech.

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FRAMES AND IDEALIZED COGNITIVE MODELS IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND LINGUISTIC APPLICATIONS

Keywords: frame semantics, frames, Idealized Cognitive Models (ICMs), cognitive linguistics, conceptual structures, image schemas, prototypes, conceptual metaphor, conceptual metonymy, categorization, encyclopedic meaning, cognitive models.

Abstract. This article presents an extensive overview of the theoretical foundations, cognitive mechanisms, and linguistic implications of “frames” and “idealized cognitive models (ICMs)” within modern cognitive linguistics. Originating in the works of Charles Fillmore and George Lakoff, respectively, these concepts describe how human beings structure, store, and access knowledge. Frames represent schematic knowledge configurations associated with particular events or cultural situations, while ICMs provide broader, culturally shaped conceptual systems integrating multiple frames, metaphors, prototypes, and schemas. The article analyzes their differences, intersections, and roles in meaning construction, categorization, metaphorical reasoning, discourse interpretation, and cross-linguistic variation. Special attention is devoted to how these models illuminate lexical semantics, grammar, and pragmatics, providing a foundation for linguistic analysis in English, Uzbek, and other languages.

Introduction. Cognitive linguistics places human cognition at the center of linguistic meaning. It rejects the structuralist notion that words possess fixed meanings independent of human experience, arguing instead that meaning emerges from mental representations shaped by perception, embodiment, cultural practices, and social interaction. Two of the most influential theoretical constructs in this approach are “frames” (Fillmore, 1977; 1982) and “idealized cognitive models (ICMs)” (Lakoff, 1987).

This article aims to deepen the understanding of frames and ICMs by presenting their origins, cognitive principles, typological structure, and relevance to linguistic analysis. It also discusses their application to various linguistic domains — semantics, syntax, pragmatics, and discourse — and their importance for cross-cultural research.

The term “frame” was introduced by Charles Fillmore as part of his development of “Frame Semantics”, a theory that attempts to explain how word meanings are tied to culturally shared knowledge. Fillmore argued that dictionary definitions

cannot fully capture the meaning of a lexical item because meaning is inherently relational: it depends on a broader knowledge structure.

Fillmore adapted these ideas to linguistic semantics, emphasizing that interpreting language requires activating schematic background knowledge.

A “frame” is a structured mental representation of a type of event, object, or situation, including its participants, relationships, and typical conditions.

Frames generally include:

1. Roles (frame elements, FEs)
e.g. Agent, Experiencer, Patient, Recipient.
2. Scenarios
Prototype event sequences within the frame.
3. Constraints
Cultural norms or contextual conditions.
4. Inferences
Implicit knowledge that speakers use to interpret meanings.

Frames are flexible: they can be elaborated, simplified, or culturally varied. Words are understood through the frames they evoke. For example: the verb “lend” presupposes a “borrowing” frame. The noun “wedding” activates a “marriage ritual” frame. This explains:

- * Polysemy (multiple meanings arise from different frame mappings),
- * Semantic roles,
- * Argument structure (e.g., verbs evoke specific participant roles),
- * Metaphor (mapping across frames).

Frames are culturally shaped. The “hospitality” frame differs significantly between Uzbek and English cultures: Uzbek hospitality emphasizes generosity, ritual tea serving, and verbal honorifics, whereas English hospitality tends to be more individualistic and less ritualized. Such differences illustrate the importance of frames for cross-cultural linguistic studies.

George Lakoff introduced “ICMs” in his seminal work “Women, Fire, and Dangerous Things”. An ICM is a complex conceptual structure made up of interacting cognitive mechanisms:

- * Frames,
- * Prototypes,
- * Metaphors,
- * Image schemas,
- * Cultural models,
- * Propositional knowledge.

ICMs explain how people categorize the world even when categories lack clear boundaries. Lakoff identifies several main types: Propositional ICMs: Structured by factual or encyclopedic knowledge.

Differences frames and ICMs can be seen in the following table:

Frames	ICMs
Specific situational structures	Broad conceptual systems

Focus on roles, relationships Integrate metaphor, metonymy, prototypes

Lexical triggers Cultural and cognitive triggers

Event-based Conceptual-system-based

Narrow in scope Wide in scope

A frame is one component inside a large ICM; an ICM is a network of frames.

Words evoke frames and require ICMs for interpretation.

For example:

Kinship terms (“acha”, “opa”, “aka”, “sir”, “madam”) rely on social hierarchy ICMs. Emotion terms rely on embodied schemas (e.g., anger is heat). Cognitive models influence grammar:

* Dative constructions evoke TRANSFER frames.

* Passive voice involves AGENT SUPPRESSION in the event frame.

* Tense-aspect systems rely on PATH schemas (e.g., events as journeys).

Conclusion. Frames and idealized cognitive models are core constructs of cognitive linguistics, offering a comprehensive explanation of how knowledge is organized, accessed, and expressed through language. Frames capture the structured knowledge associated with particular situations, while ICMs integrate multiple cognitive structures into broader conceptual systems. Together, they illuminate how humans categorize the world, construct meaning, interpret discourse, and navigate cultural differences.

Their importance extends to every area of linguistic research — semantics, syntax, pragmatics, and discourse — and is particularly valuable for cross-linguistic studies, including the analysis of vocatives in English and Uzbek. A thorough understanding of frames and ICMs is therefore essential for modern linguistics and cognitive science.

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BAKHTINNING NAZARIYASIDA POLIFONIYA, DIALOGIZM VA XRONOTOPNING IJODIY VA PSIXOLOGIK AHAMIYATI

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqola Mixail Baxtinning polifoniya, dialogizm va xronotop haqidagi konseptual qarashlarini tahlil qiladi. Polifoniya nazariyasi turli mustaqil ovozlarning bir matnda teng huquqli mavjudligini ko'rsatadi, dialogizm esa shaxs va jamiyat o'rtasidagi muloqotning ichki mohiyatini ochib beradi. Xronotop esa adabiy asarda vaqt va makonning birligini ifodalaydi. Ushbu nazariyalar Dostoevskiy, Tolstoy, va Servantes kabi yozuvchilar ijodida yorqin namoyon bo'lgan. Maqolada nazariy qarashlar adabiy va psixologik misollar bilan boyitilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Polifoniya, dialogizm, xronotop, Baxtin, Dostoyevskiy, adabiy nazariya va dialogik o'zlik.*

Kirish

Mixail Baxtinning adabiy nazariyasi XX asrning eng ta'sirli g'oyalardan biridir. Uning tadqiqotlarida adabiy matn muallif ovoziga bog'liq emas, balki keng ijtimoiy va shaxsiy ovozlarning o'zaro aloqasi sifatida tushuniladi. Ayniqsa, polifoniya tushunchasi Baxtin nazariyasida markaziy o'rin tutadi. U yerda adabiyot demokratiyasini ko'rsatadi – har bir qahramonning ovozi va pozitsiyasi bor. Baxtin uchun Dostoyevskiyning romanlari bu borada «eng jozibali» misoldir; ularda u muallif qahramonlari ustidan hukmron emas, balki ular «erkin fikrlaydigan sub'ektlar» sifatida tasvirlanadi.

Dostoyevskiyning poetikasi masalalarida Baxtin polifoniya g'oyasini batafsil tekshiradi. Uning uchun Dostoyevskiyning romanlari barcha qahramonlar mustaqil fikr qilish huquqiga ega bo'lgan polifonik matnlardir. Masalan, «Jinoyat va jazo»da Raskolnikov o'zi bilan gaplashadi. Ikki ovoz, biri «yuqori maqsad» uchun jinoyatni tasdiqlasa, ikkinchisi axloqiy me'yorlarni himoya qiladigan ichki polifonik kontrapunkt hosil qiladi. «Karamazov birodarlar»da har bir birodar falsafiy g'oya uchun turadi: Ivan aql va skeptitsizmni, Alyosha e'tiqod va sevgini, Dmitriy ehtiros va inson istaklarini ifodalaydi. Muallif bu ovozlardan birortasini ustun qo'ymaydi; balki ular suhbatlashadi va matnda polifonik sifat yaratadilar.

Baxtinning «dialogizm» nazariyasi til, ong va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tasvirlaydi. Valzerga ko'ra, har bir fikr yoki gap boshqa ovozlarning bilan muloqotning bir qismidir. Hech qanday so'z orolda emas – u har doim javob, bog'lanish yoki suhbatda mavjud. Baxtin ta'kidlaganidek, inson tafakkuri ham dialogikdir. Bizning ichki nutqimiz doimiy ichki dialogdir. Endi, Xubert Xermansning «dialogik o'zlik nazariyasi» Baxtinning tushunchalarini psixologik

yo'nalishda oladi. Xermansning fikriga ko'ra, shaxsda bir nechta «ichki o'zlar» bor: «Ona sifatida men», «o'qituvchi sifatida men», «ijodkor sifatida men». Bunda o'zaro mas'uliyatni yo'qotish va erkinlikka intilishning ichki ziddiyati mavjud. Dostoyevskiy qahramonlarining ichki kurashlari bizga ushbu dialogik shartni eslatib turadi. Raskolnikovning «supermen» tushunchasi uni axloqiy haqiqatlardan uzoqlashtiradi, ammo uning vijdoni unga gapiradi va uni insoniyat bilan bog'laydi. Shu tarzda, dialogizm avvalgi shaxsiy ongning qatlamli tabiatini ochib beradi.

Baxtinning “xronotop” tushunchasi adabiy asarda vaqt va makonning o'zaro bog'liqligini tahlil qiladi. Xronotop (yunoncha *chronos* — vaqt, *topos* — makon) asarning strukturasi belgilovchi muhim kategoriya hisoblanadi. Masalan, Servantesning “Don Kixot” romanida “yo'l xronotopi” asosiy o'rinni egallaydi. Don Kixotning sayohati nafaqat geografik harakat, balki uning ma'naviy o'sishi va o'zini anglash jarayonidir. Har bir uchrashuv – yangi falsafiy tajriba, yangi qarash demakdir.

Tolstoyning “Urush va tinchlik” romanida esa “tarixiy xronotop” ustuvor: vaqtning oqimi, tarixiy voqealar va shaxsiy taqdirning kesishishi jamiyat va inson ruhiyatini yaxlit tasvirlaydi. Bu yerda vaqt statik emas, balki harakatda — u inson hayotini shakllantiradi.

Tolstoyning «Urush va tinchlik» asarida esa «tarixiy xronotop» mavjud. Vaqtning, tarixiy voqealar shaxsiy qismatga bog'langanligi jamiyat va inson ruhini bitta sifatida aks ettiradi. Bu yerda vaqt joyi bir yerda turgan emas, balki qaynaydi; u inson hayotini shakllantiradi.

Zamonaviy tanqidchi Bart Kyonen xronotopni «xotira sxemasi» sifatida o'qiydi. Uning uchun har bir yozuvchi o'z xronotopini yaratadi va o'quvchini asar dunyosiga qaratadi. Shu sababli, xronotop adabiy janrlarning asosiy farqlovchisi sifatida yuzaga chiqadi: epik janrdagi tarixiy, sayohat romani va romantik asarlardagi ruhiy-ichkilardan biri.

Xulosa

Baxtinning heteroglossiya (polifoniya) va dialogizm, shuningdek, xronotop haqidagi g'oyalari adabiyotshunoslik va psixologiya sohasida muhim ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Polifoniya ovozlarning tengligini ifodalaydi, dialogizm ichki va tashqi dialogdir va xronotop vaqt va makonning badiiy birlashmasidir. Bunday g'oyalar inson tafakkurining murakkabligini va adabiy asarlarda ishtirok etuvchi ko'p o'lchovlarni tushuntirishda yordam beradi.

Dostoyevskiy, Tolstoy va Servantes romanlarida ushbu nazariya nafaqat badiiy umumlashmalar sifatida ilgari suriladi, balki ular tirik shaklda ifodalanadi. Shunday qilib, Baxtinning tushunchalari nafaqat o'zining tarixiy sharoiti va zaruriy rus formalizmi nazariy doirasiga taalluqli, balki zamonaviy adabiyot universitetlari, lingvistik va psixologiyaga ham ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

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DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN YOUNG STUDENTS THROUGH INTERACTIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

Annotation: This article discusses the role and significant aspects of communicative competence in our progressive youth, which is developing in all aspects, as well as the organizational and legal foundations of acquiring knowledge, the importance of communicativeness in the pedagogical process, the development of thinking, and the state of legislative norms in practice.

Keywords: Communicative competence, improving worldview, ability, personal development, reflection, competency-based curricula, interactive methods.

Introduction. In our rapidly developing era, the quality of education is improving day by day through interactive methods. Interactive teaching methods are one of the methodological approaches based on expanding the worldview of young people in the educational process, revealing their talents, increasing their activity, and developing their creative skills in every aspect. Interactive teaching methods play a major role in implementing this process. In particular, they teach students to systematically organize their knowledge and solve problems in situations close to real life. Therefore, despite the fact that a lot of work is being done to bring the development of communicative knowledge and skills to a new level in the personnel training system and accelerate educational reforms in this regard, the development of communicative competence among today's youth remains one of the urgent tasks. From this point of view, such competence is the ability to correctly use the language in the grammatical, pragmatic, social and cultural aspects of society. It also means being able to use. The term communicative competence is defined as the ability to use acquired knowledge, skills and competencies in a foreign language during communication. The word "competence", which reflects the main idea and reasoning contained in this term, was originally used by N. Chomsky in the sense of "grammatical competence", that is, the skills of the speaker and listener about the language. It is noteworthy that it plays an important role in reflecting linguistic and cultural concepts.

Discussion. In lexical terms, the term competence mainly refers to the level of ability and competence focused on deep knowledge. The concept of competence (derived from the Latin word *competentia*, *compete* - meaning "I achieve together, I win, I fit, I am right") is given in some dictionaries in the meanings of "having knowledge and skills aimed at thinking about something and allowing it", "being aware, being entitled". In content, it means the rational use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate a high level of professional competence, talent and skill. Today, the ability to communicate effectively, which we call communicative competence, has always interested many scientists. In sociology, social psychology, pedagogy and, most importantly, linguistics, other modern fields of knowledge, the relationship between individuals, their The focus is on the theoretical study of communicative behavior. In the 21st century, there are a number of definitions given to the concept of communication, and it is appropriate to dwell on some of them. The communication process is considered one of the important foundations in the linguistic and cultural life of a person. At the same time, according to researchers, the communication process itself means both itself and its result.

E.L. Litnevskaya, as a research scientist, puts forward the following idea: "All types of speech activity are the acquisition of elements of the culture of oral and written speech, the basic skills and abilities of using language in vital spheres and

situations of the communication process of a certain age." Communicative competence is defined by a number of researchers as "the ability to carry out interaction with the help of language, that is, to express one's opinion in the process of communicating with interlocutors."

Speech simultaneously acts as a source of any reflections, and In addition to this, it is also noticeable as a way of influencing one's interlocutor. It is necessary to carefully analyze the views of both parties in the interaction, their goals and objectives. Communicative speech is the exchange of ideas between young people in the process of meaningful communication. Communicative speech culture means that students can use speech wisely, observing the rules of etiquette, in the process of exchanging ideas with each other. In teaching foreign languages, it is especially important to use the method called "communicative didactics". This method involves paying attention to dialogue and interaction in language learning. Interactive methods, unlike traditional methods of education, allow students to interact more with each other.

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**INGLIZ MEDIA DISKURSIDA LEKSIK-SINTAKTIK
INTENSIFIKATORLARNING MANIPULYATIV
XUSUSIYATLARI**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis ingliz media diskursida leksik-sintaktik intensivatorlarning manipulyativ funksiyalarini lingvopragmatik va funksional-diskursiv yondashuv asosida tadqiq etadi. Zamonaviy ingliz ommaviy axborot vositalarida axborotning tezkorligi, o'quvchi e'tiborini jalb qilish zarurati va auditoriya ustidan ta'sir o'tkazishga qaratilgan strategiyalar intensivatorlarning qo'llanishini keskin kuchaytirgan.

Kalit so'zlar: leksik-sintaktik intensivatorlar, media diskurs, baholovchilik, dramatisatsiya, framing, OAV tili.

Kirish. Globallashuv sharoitida ommaviy axborot vositalari jamiyatning siyosiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy hayotini shakllantiruvchi eng kuchli kommunikativ institutlardan biriga aylandi. Media matnlarda til vositalari nafaqat axborotni yetkazish, balki uni ma'lum ideologik va emotsional kontekstda talqin qilish orqali auditoriya ongiga ta'sir ko'rsatish funksiyasini bajaradi. Shu jihatdan, media diskursda baholovchilik, dramatisatsiya, framing va e'tibor boshqaruvi kabi strategiyalar tilning o'ziga xos stilistik hamda pragmatik vositalari orqali amalga oshiriladi. Ingliz media matnlarida leksik va sintaktik intensivatorlarning qo'llanishi aynan shunday manipulyativ strategiyalarning muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Leksik intensivatorlar-really, absolutely, extremely kabi birliklar matnning emotsional kuchini oshiradi, baholovchilikni kuchaytiradi va o'quvchining voqelikni qabul qilishiga bilvosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, inversiya, takror va qisqa gaplar kabi sintaktik konstruksiyalar matnni dramatik ta'sirga ega qilishi, urg'uni kuchaytirishi va auditoriyaning diqqatini kerakli nuqtaga yo'naltirishi mumkin. Tilshunoslikning lingvopragmatika, funksional stilistika va diskurs tahlil yo'nalishlari media tilining manipulyativ tabiatini chuqur tushuntirib beradi. Xususan, manipulyativlik auditoriyaning bilish jarayoniga bevosita ta'sir o'tkazishga qaratilgan til vositalarining maqsadli qo'llanishi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Media diskursida intensivatorlarning subyektivlashtirish, dramatisatsiya, framingni kuchaytirish va auditoriyada emotsional reaksiya uyg'otishdagi o'rni aynan shu pragmatik mexanizmlar bilan bog'liq. Shunga qaramay, ingliz media diskursida leksik-sintaktik intensivatorlarning funksional yuklamasi, semantik-pragmatik xususiyatlari va manipulyativ effekti hali ham keng ko'lamda kompleks o'rganilmagan.

Metodologiya. Tadqiqotda media matnlarining ko'p qatlamli tahlilini ta'minlash maqsadida bir nechta zamonaviy lingvistik metodlar qo'llanildi. Diskurs tahlili-media matnlarining ideologik, kommunikativ va kontekstual xususiyatlarini aniqlash uchun Fairclough (1995) va van Dijk (2006) nazariyalariga tayangan holda amalga oshirildi. Stilistik tahlil-sintaktik konstruktsiyalarning ekspressiv va estetik funksiyalari stilistika tamoyillariga tayangan holda tahlil qilindi. Korpus tahlili-media matnlaridan tuzilgan kichik korpus asosida intensifikatorlarning chastotasi va qo'llanish turlari aniqlanadi. Komponent va kontekstual tahlil-intensifikatorlar qo'llangan kontekstlarda ma'no kuchayishi, emotsional fon, baholovchilik va manipulyativlik darajasi aniqlanadi.

Quyida leksik va sintaktik intensifikatorlar bo'yicha real ingliz media misollarini I.R. Galperinning "Stylistics" asaridagi stilistik vositalar tasnifi asosida tahlil qilib ko'ramiz. Tahlillar Galperinning quyidagi asosiy kategoriyalariga tayangan holda sharhlab beriladi. Emphatic constructions (kuchaytiruvchilar), Repetition, Parallel construction, Inversion, Climax va Anticlimax, Metaphorical intensification, Rhetorical devices (emotive language, evaluative epithet).

1-Misol "The storm caused extremely serious damage, leaving thousands absolutely terrified." (BBC News). Leksik intensifikatorlar-extremely, absolutely. Galperin (1971) bularni emphatic words yoki intensifiers turiga kiritadi. Ular inson hissiy kechinmasini kuchaytirish, sub'ektiv bahoni oshirish uchun xizmat qiladi. extremely serious-baholovchilikni keskin oshiradi, dramatisatsiya effekti yaratadi, absolutely terrified-holatning ekstremal darajada ekanini ko'rsatadi, emotsional reaksiyani kuchaytiradi. Terrified-Galperin tasnifida emotive meaning yaratadigan leksik birlik bo'lib, matnning hissiy fonini oshiradi. Bu kontekst o'quvchi ongida kuchli xavotir hissini uyg'otadi va voqea "katastrofik" ko'rinishda talqin qilinishiga sabab bo'ladi.

2-misol "The city was completely destroyed, and the government response was shockingly slow." (CNN). Intensifikatorlar-completely, shockingly, completely destroyed-intensification through adverb voqeani maksimal darajada qayd etadi. Shockingly slow-evaluative adverb + adjective modeli sub'ektiv baho kuchaytiriladi. Shockingly slow baholovchi epitet bo'lib, hukumatning harakati haqida salbiy konnotatsiya yaratadi. Climax elementi-gap ichida "destroyed" "shockingly slow" ketma-ketligi dramatik kuchayish hosil qiladi.

3-misol "Never before has the country faced such an incredibly dangerous situation." (The Guardian) Inversion (Sintaktik intensifikator) Never before has the country. . . Galperin inversiyani emphatic construction deb tasniflaydi. Bu struktura urg'uni "misli ko'rilmaganlik"ga qaratadi. Incredibly dangerous-bu uyushma kuchli emotsional-estimativ qiymatga egadir. "Never before"+"incredibly" kombinatsiyasi matnni maksimal dramatik kontekstga olib kiradi. Manipulyativlik jihati shundaki, o'quvchi vaziyatni real holatdan ko'ra ko'proq xavfli deb talqin qilishi ehtimoli oshadi.

4-misol "It was a disaster - a real, total, absolutely unbelievable disaster." (Daily Mail - tabloit uslubi). Repetition (takror) "disaster" so'zining ikki marta takrorlanishi Galperinning nazariyasiga ko'ra lexical repetition hisoblanadi. Bu vosita emotsional yuklamani kuchaytiradi. Gradation (Climax) real, total, absolutely unbelievable Gradatsiya bosqichma-bosqich kuchayadi. Har bir keyingi sifat oldingisidan kuchliroq. Bu stilistik vosita tabloit matnlariga xos bo'lib, o'quvchi ongida voqea nihoyatda falokatli tasvirlanadi, drammatizatsiya kuchayadi. Bunday vositalar matnning baholovchilik, emotsional va manipulyativ potentsialini oshiradi. Xulosa. Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz media diskursida leksik va sintaktik intensivatorlarning qo'llanish xususiyatlarini, ularning semantik-pragmatik funksiyalarini va manipulyativ effektlarini aniqlashga qaratildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, media matnlarda intensivatorlar nafaqat axborotni kuchaytiruvchi vosita sifatida, balki o'quvchi ongida hissiy va baholovchilik reaksiyalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi manipulyativ strategiya sifatida faol ishlatiladi.

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THE ARTISTIC REPRESENTATION OF THE FATHER FIGURE IN AMERICAN AND UZBEK PROSE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MARIO PUZO AND TOHIR MALIK'S WORKS

Abstract:

This research conducts a comparative analysis of father figures portrayed in Mario Puzo's "The Godfather," an iconic work of American literature, and

Tohir Malik's "Shaytanat" series, a prominent example of Uzbek prose. The study explores the unique and shared characteristics of these figures within the contexts of Western and Eastern societies, respectively. By examining these literary depictions, this study aims to illuminate the ways in which the artistic representation of the father figure is intrinsically linked to the author's cultural perspectives, social interactions, ethical principles, political ideologies, and religious beliefs. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex roles and responsibilities ascribed to fathers in diverse cultural landscapes.

Keywords: Father Figure, Mario Puzo, Tohir Malik, Comparative Literature, Cross-cultural Literary Criticism, Patriarchy, The Godfather, Shaytanat, Gender, Masculinity, Postcolonialism, National Identity, Archetype.

Introduction:

Literature serves as a multifaceted artistic mirror, reflecting the diverse tapestry of human thought and experience. Within this reflection, social roles assume particular significance, none perhaps more compelling than the figure of the father [1]. The father figure transcends a simple designation as the head of the household; he functions as a crucial bridge between generations, a vital conveyor of cultural values, and a potent symbol of societal stability, affection, and protection [2]. This research undertakes a comparative analysis of the artistic representation of the father figure as portrayed in the works of two prominent authors: Mario Puzo, a celebrated American writer, and Tohir Malik, a distinguished Uzbek literary figure. By employing the methodology of comparative literary studies, this study seeks to illuminate the ways in which the interpretation of the father figure diverges and converges across distinct cultural landscapes [3]. The primary objective is to investigate the aesthetic and ideological attributes of father figures crafted within disparate cultural contexts, identify their unique characteristics, evaluate their societal impact, and ultimately demonstrate their contribution to fostering meaningful intercultural dialogue. Furthermore, this study endeavors to address the following salient inquiries:

- What unique characteristics define the portrayal of the father figure in both Western and Eastern literary traditions?
- What specific socio-cultural values are promoted or reinforced through the representation of the father figure in the selected works of Mario Puzo and Tohir Malik?
- How does the artistic expression of the father figure in these works reflect the personal perspectives, biases, and lived experiences of the authors themselves?

Methodology and Results:

This study employed a qualitative research design grounded in the method of comparative literary analysis. The works selected for analysis were Mario Puzo's seminal novel, "The Godfather," in which the character of Don Vito Corleone embodies power, authority, loyalty, pragmatism, and unwavering commitment to familial traditions, and Tohir Malik's compelling "Shaytanat"

series, where the father figure exemplifies spirituality, justice, wisdom, compassion, and a profound respect for national values [4, 5]. The data were analyzed using a combination of established research techniques, including content analysis, structural-narrative analysis, cross-cultural comparative analysis, archetypal analysis, gender analysis, and sociological analysis [6]. Furthermore, the study also explored the role of the father figure in shaping national identity, serving as a societal role model, and bridging the gap between generations through the application of postcolonial theory and theories of hero archetypes [7].

Key Findings:

The analysis revealed that the authors' cultural perspectives, social interactions, political beliefs, ethical principles, and personal experiences played a significant role in shaping the representation of the father figure in their respective works. In Puzo's "The Godfather," the father figure relies on violence and intimidation as the head of a Mafia organization, while in Malik's "Shaytanat," ethical norms, spiritual purity, a commitment to justice, and a deep sense of humanity take precedence. Comparative analysis further indicated that the father figure created in Puzo's work reflects the individualistic traits and values often associated with Western society, whereas Malik's portrayal emphasizes the collectivism, compassion, respect, and spiritual values that are highly esteemed in Eastern societies. These distinct representations highlight the nuanced ways in which fatherhood is culturally constructed and interpreted. The study goes beyond simply identifying these differences, delving into the underlying factors that contribute to these varying portrayals and examining their potential impact on shaping cultural understandings of masculinity and familial responsibility.

Conclusion:

The findings of this research confirm that the interpretation of the father figure in literary works is inextricably linked to the author's personal experiences, cultural framework, social perspectives, political ideologies, ethical principles, and deeply held religious convictions. Through the portrayal of the father figure, authors engage with a diverse range of societal concerns, encompassing spiritual, moral, political, social, and psychological dimensions. This study makes a valuable contribution to the field of cross-cultural literary criticism by establishing promising avenues for future research into a variety of interrelated issues, including gender dynamics, historical contexts, sociological factors, psychological complexities, philosophical inquiries, political implications, and religious interpretations as they relate to the father figure [8]. Additionally, the results of this study have practical implications for educators in literature, translators working across cultures, and cultural scholars seeking to gain a deeper understanding of the complex and multifaceted role of the father figure in shaping societies and individual lives.

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TILLAR VA MADANIYATLAR ORASIDAGI MUNOSABATLARDA HISSIYOTLARNING O'RNI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada tillar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarda hissiyotlarning roli, emotsional kategoriyalarning til orqali qanday aks etishi va madaniyatlararo muloqotga ta'siri ilmiy manbalarga tayangan holda tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *emotsionallik, hissiyot, lingvomadaniyat, lisoniy ong, antroposentrik paradigma, kod, belgi, konsept, semiotika.*

Kirish. Tillar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar zamonaviy lingvistika, psixologiya va madaniyatshunoslikning eng dolzarb tadqiqot yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Har bir til nafaqat kommunikativ vosita, balki xalqning dunyoqarashi, qadriyatlari, e'tiqodlari va his-tuyg'ularini ifoda etuvchi ijtimoiy-madaniy tizimdir. Shu sababli, til va madaniyat o'zaro uyg'un holda shakllanadi, insonlarning hissiy holati, emotsional tajribalari esa bu jarayonning ajralmas qismidir. Hissiyotlarning til va madaniyatlararo muloqotda tutgan o'rni tilshunoslikning yangi yo'nalishi – emotsional lingvistika doirasida ham alohida tadqiq etilmoqda.

Til madaniyatning asosiy ko'zgusi sifatida inson tafakkuri va tuyg'ularini shakllantiradi. A. Vejbitskaya, F. Palmer, E. Sapir va B. Uorf kabi olimlarning nazariyalariga ko'ra, til strukturalari insonning dunyoni qabul qilish jarayoniga ta'sir qiladi. Sapir–Uorf gipotezasiga ko'ra, til nafaqat fikrlashni, balki hissiyotlarni idrok etish va ifodalashni ham belgilaydi.

Masalan, o'zbek lingvomadaniyatidagi "baxt", "g'azab", "sharmandalik", "hurmat" kabi so'zlar ingliz tilidagi "happiness", "anger", "shame", "respect" so'zlariga tarjima jihatdan mos bo'lsada, biroq bu tushunchalarning semantik

maydon doirasi bir xil emas. Sharq madaniyatlarida jamoaviylik va oila qadriyatlar ustuvor bo'lgani uchun, ijobiy hissiyotlar ko'proq hamjihatlik, tinchlik va bosiqlik bilan bog'lanadi. G'arb madaniyatida esa individual yutuq, mustaqillik va shaxsiy erkinlik ijobiy emotsional reaksiyalar bilan ifodalanadi. Demak, madaniyat hissiyotlarning qadrini va ularning tilda namoyon bo'lish shakllarini belgilovchi muhim omildir.

Emotsional holatlar tilning leksik, grammatik va pragmatik darajalarida aks etadi. Har bir tilda hissiyotlarni ifodalovchi noyob birliklar, metaforalar, idiomalar, iboralar tizimi mavjud. Tilning lug'at boyligi madaniyatning hissiy tajribalarini aks ettiradi. Masalan:

I. *I need some privacy.* — G'arbda bu shaxsiy chegarani bildiradi.

Ingliz tilidagi "privacy" so'zi G'arb madaniyatida juda muhim emotsional va ijtimoiy qadriyat sifatida qaraladi. O'zbek tilida esa "yolg'izlik" yoki "shaxsiy hayot" yaqin tarjimalar bo'lsa-da, ular "privacy" so'zining G'arbda beradigan kuchli emotsional ma'nosini to'liq qamrab olmaydi. O'zbek madaniyatida esa ko'pincha "ko'pchilik bilan bo'lishish", "birga bo'lish" qadrlanadi.

II. *I felt embarrassed when I forgot his name.* — yengil uyat.

Ingliz tilidagi *embarrassed* odatda kichik noqulaylik, uyat hissini anglatadi.

O'zbekchadagi "sharmanda bo'lish" esa ancha kuchli va og'ir hissiy mazmunga ega. Bu madaniy farqlar hissiyot ifodasidagi intensivlikni ko'rsatadi. O'zbek tilidagi "ko'ngil", "izzat", "or-nomus" kabi tushunchalar keng ma'no doirasiga ega bo'lib, ijtimoiy-madaniy qadriyatlar bilan bog'langan.

III. *I am proud of myself.* → ijobiy

Men o'zimdanda faxrlanaman. → ba'zi hollarda salbiy talqin qilinishi mumkin.

Ingliz madaniyatida proud ijobiy hissiyot bo'lib, o'ziga ishonchni aks ettiradi. Sharqda (jumladan o'zbek madaniyatida) esa "mag'rurlik" ba'zan salbiy— kibr ma'nosida ham ishlatiladi.

"Ismining yodimdan chiqib qolgani uchun sharmanda bo'ldim." — kuchli uyat.

Ko'pgina tillarda grammatik vositalar hissiy holatni mujassamlaydi. Masalan, turkiy tillardagi mayl kategoriyalari (istak mayli, shart mayli) nutqning emotsional ohangini belgilaydi. Ingliz tilida modal fe'llar (must, should, might) emotsional baholash bilan bog'liq bo'ladi. Semantik metaforalar esa hissiyotlarni obrazli tarzda ifodalaydi: "ko'ngli tog'dek ko'tarildi", "yuragi orqasiga tortdi" kabi iboralar emotsional holatning til orqali badiiy ifodasidir.

Pragmatik jihatdan hissiyotlar muloqot uslubiga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Masalan: O'zbek madaniyatida muloyimlik, hurmat, yumshoqlik ustuvor bo'lib, bu nutq etiketi va muomala madaniyatida aks etadi. G'arb madaniyatlarida bevosita gapirish va aniq ifoda etish qadrlanadi. Hissiy ohang, intonatsiya va noverbal belgilar ham madaniy xususiyatga ega kommunikativ kodlar hisoblanadi.

Madaniyatlararo muloqotda hissiyotlarning o‘zaro farqlanishi tushunmovchilik, kommunikativ xatoliklar yoki aksincha, muvaffaqiyatli muloqotga sabab bo‘lishi mumkin. Bir madaniyatda ijobiy deb qabul qilinadigan hissiyot boshqa madaniyatda neytral yoki salbiy bo‘lishi mumkin.

Masalan: Ingliz madaniyatida madaniyatida keng tabassum do‘stona munosabat belgisi hisoblanadi. Sharqiy Osiyo mamlakatlarida esa ortiqcha tabassum samimiylik belgisi emas, balki noqulaylikni yashirish usuli bo‘lishi mumkin.

Xulosa. Hissiyotlar tillar va madaniyatlar o‘rtasidagi munosabatlarda markaziy o‘rin tutadi. Til tuzilishi va lug‘at boyligi madaniy qadriyatlar va hissiy tajribalarni aks ettiradi, madaniyatlararo muloqotda esa emotsional farqlar kommunikatsiyaning muvaffaqiyatiga bevosita ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Shuning uchun ham tillarni o‘rganish jarayonida madaniyat va emotsional kontekstni chuqur anglash muhimdir.

Til – bu nafaqat fikr, balki hissiyotlar ko‘prigidir. Madaniyatlararo aloqalarda hissiyotlarning mazmunini to‘g‘ri anglash o‘zaro hurmatni kuchaytiradi va samarali muloqotni ta‘minlaydi.

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LEXICO PHRASEOLOGICAL LACUNAS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Annotation: This article explores the types and proper use of lacunas in English language. Article begins by defining linguacultural analysis and its key elements including the examples of the languages in various contexts in which they were used. It also provides a comprehensive overview of previous research in the English language. The ways of applying lacunas and connotations and contextualizing of them are also provided .Overall, this study highlights the importance of lacunar units inflectional literary works.

Key words: Lacunas, lacunar units, correlation, connotation of lacunar units.

Lexical phraseological lacunas refer to gaps or deficiencies in a language's vocabulary, particularly in terms of idiomatic expressions or phrases that don't have an equivalent in another language. Here are some examples of lexical phraseological lacunas in the English language: Lack of words for familial relationships: English lacks precise terms for some familial relationships, such as the distinction between a mother's sister and a father's sister, or between a father's brother and a mother's brother. Lack of words for specific emotions: While English has a large vocabulary for emotions, there are some emotions that lack precise terms, such as the feeling of being homesick for a place that doesn't exist anymore (saudade in Portuguese).Lack of words for certain concepts: Some concepts don't have a single-word equivalent in English, such as the Japanese concept of "tsundoku," which refers to the habit of buying and collecting books but never getting around to reading them. Lack of idiomatic expressions: Every language has its own set of idiomatic expressions that are difficult to translate literally, and English is no exception. Some expressions, such as the Spanish phrase "tener cara dura" (literally "to have a hard face"), meaning to be shameless or audacious, don't have an exact equivalent in English. Cultural differences: English may also have lexical phraseological lacunas due to cultural differences. 1). Linguistic factors / peculiarities in linguistic division of objective world and mismatching in the language system development. 2) Extra linguistic factor /diversity of historical,

cultural and spiritual traditions of nations, geographical, social economical lifestyle, originality of custom, mentality of different nations) Taking into consideration factors and aspects of analyses lacunar units and lacuna which mentioned above we offer following classification: 1. Level lacunar units and lacunas: phonetically, lexical, phraseological, morpheme, morphological, syntactic, stylistic. 2. Motivated and unmotivated lacunas, Appearance of motivated lacunas caused by absence of certain realia in the life of People-Native speaker of one of the comparing language (no realia no lingvema) Among motivated lacunar units and lacunas following are allocated: 1. Ethnographic lacunar units lacunas, reflecting specific sides of traditional daily life, mode of life nations of competing languages. 2. O.B.Pilayera comparing Russian and Evenk languages gave Examples of ethnographic lacunar units of verb which are connected with Evenki hunting улуми-squirrel hunts, удеми-to track down the beast), containing deer (ономи-to look for deer, мавутлами-catch deer with lasso) and other. [12, p. 55-60] 3. Lingua –cultural, social-historical lacunar units and lacunas, which reflect culture, history, society of nations native speakers comparing languages. 4. Mental, associative lacunar units and lacunas reflecting worldview, self-consciousness of nations, their way of thinking, association etc [3, pp.38-41; 9, pp.79-83]. There are two significant types of factors which influence on lacuna's appearance: 1) Linguistic factors / peculiarities in linguistic division of objective world and mismatching in the language system development. 2) Extralinguistic factor / diversity of historical, cultural and spiritual traditions of nations, geographical, social-economical lifestyle, originality of custom, mentality of different nations) Taking into consideration factors and aspects of analyses lacunar units and lacuna which mentioned above we offer following classification: 1. Level lacunar units and lacunas: phonetically, lexical, phraseological, morpheme, morphological, syntactic, stylistic. 2. Motivated and unmotivated lacunas, Appearance of motivated lacunas caused by absence of certain realia in the life of People-Native speaker of one of the comparing language (no realia no lingvema) Among motivated lacunar units and lacunas following are allocated: 1. Ethnographic lacunar units lacunas, reflecting specific sides of traditional daily life, mode of life nations of competing languages. O.B.Pilayera comparing Russian and Evenk languages gave Examples of ethnographic lacunar units of verb which are connected with Evenki hunting улуми-squirrel hunts, удеми-to track down the beast), containing deer (ономи-to look for deer, catch deer with lasso) and other. [11, p. 55-60] 3. Lingua –cultural, social-historical lacunar units and lacunas, which reflect culture, history, society of nations native speakers comparing languages. 4. Mental, associative lacunar units and lacunas reflecting worldview, self-consciousness of nations, their way of thinking, association etc

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**ABDULLA AVLONIY VA LANGSTON HUGHES
ASARLARIDA IJTIMOY ADOLAT VA OZODLIK
G'OYALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI**

ANNOTATSIYA : Ushbu maqolada XX asr boshlarida faoliyat ko'rsatgan o'zbek jadid ma'rifatparvari Abdulla Avloniy va afroamerikalik Harlem Renessansi vakili Langston Hughes ijodida ijtimoiy adolat, ozodlik va inson qadri-qimmatini masalalarining badiiy talqini tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, sotsiologik yondashuv va poetik tahlil metodlariga asoslanadi. Maqola mualliflari Avloniyda milliy-ma'rifiy uyg'onish, Hughesda esa irqiy tenglik uchun kurash g'oyalari ustuvor ekanini ko'rsatadilar. Tadqiqot Avloniy va Hughes qarashlarining umumiy insonparvarlik tamoyillari orqali tutashishini asoslaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Abdulla Avloniy, Langston Hughes, jadidchilik, Harlem Renessansi, rezistans, ijtimoiy adolat, ozodlik.

АННОТАЦИЯ : В данной статье анализируется художественная интерпретация социальной справедливости, свободы и человеческого достоинства в творчестве узбекского джадид-просветителя Абдуллы Авлони и афроамериканского поэта эпохи Гарлемского Ренессанса Лэнгстона Хьюза. Исследование основывается на методах сравнительного литературоведения, социологическом подходе и поэтическом анализе. Показано, что для Авлони характерны идеи национального просвещения, тогда как Хьюз сосредоточен на проблемах расового равенства. Исследование доказывает сближение их взглядов через общие гуманистические принципы.

Ключевые слова: Абдулла Авлони, Лэнгстон Хьюз, джадидизм, Гарлемский Ренессанс, резистанс, социальная справедливость, свобода.

ANNOTATION: This article examines the artistic representation of social justice, freedom, and human dignity in the works of Uzbek Jadid enlightener Abdulla Avloniy and African American Harlem Renaissance poet Langston Hughes. The study is based on comparative literary analysis, sociological perspectives, and poetic interpretation. It demonstrates that Avloniy's writings emphasize national enlightenment and moral transformation, while Hughes focuses on racial equality and the fight against oppression. The research concludes that both authors, despite belonging to different cultural contexts, converge in their humanistic ideals and their belief in literature as a catalyst for social change. **Keywords:** Abdulla Avloniy, Langston Hughes, Jadid literature, Harlem Renaissance, resistance, social justice, freedom.

XX asr boshlarida dunyoning turli hududlarida ijtimoiy adolatsizlik, irqiy bosim, savodsizlik, mustamlakachilik va siyosiy tengsizlik jamiyat hayotini tubdan belgilab berdi. O'zbek jadidchilik harakati vakillaridan biri Abdulla Avloniy va afroamerikalik Harlem Renessansi ijodkorlaridan Langston Hughes ana shu murakkab ijtimoiy tarixiy jarayonlarning badiiy ifodasini yaratgan adiblardir.

Avloniyning ma'rifatparvarlik g'oyalari Turkiston jamiyatini jaholatdan qutqarish va milliy uyg'onish tamoyillariga asoslangan bo'lsa, Hughes ijodining markazida afroamerikaliklarning tenglik, inson qadr-qimmatini va irqiy erkinlik uchun kurashi turadi. Ularning asarlarida erkinlik, adolat, ijtimoiy uyg'onish va xalq ruhiyati yetakchi mavzu sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot Avloniy va Hughes ijodining qiyosiy tahlili orqali ikki madaniyatning ijtimoiy-siyosiy muammolarni badiiy idrok etishdagi o'xshash va farqli jihatlarni yoritadi.

Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi shundan iboratki, Avloniy va Hughes ijodi turli tarixiy hududlarda yashagan bo'lsa-da, ularni birlashtiruvchi asos — adabiyotning ijtimoiy vazifasini teran anglash va adolat tamoyillarini himoya qilishga bo'lgan intilishdir.

Tadqiqot quyidagi metodlar asosida olib borildi:

1. Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik metodi: Avloniy va Hughes asarlarida erkinlik, tenglik va ijtimoiy uyg'onish g'oyalarini birlamchi manbalar orqali taqqoslash.
2. Sotsiologik yondashuv: Adiblarning asarlariga ta'sir ko'rsatgan tarixiy, siyosiy, irqiy va milliy omillarni aniqlash.
3. Poetik tahlil: Asarlaridagi metafora, ritm, xalqona ohang, obrazlar va badiiy uslublarni o'rganish.
4. Kontekstual tahlil: Avloniy – jadidchilik mafkurasi, Hughes – Harlem Renessansi doirasida qaraladi.

NATIJALAR

1. Ijtimoiy adolat g'oyasining badiiy ifodasi Avloniy "Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq" va she'riy asarlarida jamiyatning jaholat, nodonlik va ezilishdan qutulishi uchun ilm, axloq va ma'rifatni asosiy vosita sifatida ko'rsatadi. Uning adolat haqidagi qarashlari ma'rifatparvarlik ruhiga asoslangan. Hughes esa "I, Too", "Let

America Be America Again” kabi she’rlarida afroamerikaliklarning irqiy zulmga qarshi ovozini ifodalaydi. U adolatni siyosiy-huquqiy tenglik orqali ko’radi.

2. Ozodlik tushunchasining poetik talqini: Avloniy ozodlikni milliy uyg‘onish, ilm-fan taraqqiyoti, madaniyatning yangilanishi orqali tasvirlaydi. Hughesda ozodlik – Amerika ideallarining barcha fuqarolarga teng taalluqli bo‘lishi, irqiy stereotiplardan xalos bo‘lish va insoniy qadr-qimmatning tan olinishi.

3. Xalq ruhiyati va jamiyat uyg‘onishi: Avloniy xalqni ma’rifat orqali uyg‘otishni maqsad qilgan bo‘lsa, Hughes xalqning o‘z ovozigacha ega bo‘lishi, san’at va adabiyot orqali o‘zligini anglashini aks ettiradi.

4. Poetika va uslub: Avloniyning poetik uslubi didaktik, o‘git beruvchi, ma’naviy-ma’rifiy xarakterga ega.

Hughes esa jazz ritmlari, og‘zaki ijod uslubi, kuchli lirizm va rezistans ohangi bilan ajralib turadi.

MUHOKAMA : Avloniy va Hughes asarlaridagi umumiylik ularning adabiyotni ijtimoiy ongini uyg‘otuvchi kuch deb bilishida ko‘rinadi. Har ikki ijodkor adolat g‘oyasiga sodiq bo‘lib, jamiyatning og‘riqlarini badiiy vositalar orqali ifodalaydi. Biroq ularni farqlovchi jihatlari ham ko‘p:

- Avloniy milliy-ma’rifiy islohotlar tarafdori;
- Hughes irqiy tenglik uchun kurashning poetik ovozi;
- Avloniyning til uslubi o‘git-nasihatga asoslangan;
- Hughes esa xalqona ritm va zamonaviy lirizmni uyg‘unlashtirgan.

Bu farqlar ular yashagan tarixiy sharoit va jamiyat ijtimoiy muammolari bilan izohlanadi.

XULOSA : Tadqiqot shuni ko‘rsatadiki, Abdulla Avloniy va Langston Hughes turli madaniy va siyosiy muhitda ijod qilgan bo‘lsalar-da, har ikkisi adabiyotning jamiyatni o‘zgartirishdagi kuchiga ishonadi. Avloniy ma’rifatga tayanib, Hughes esa rezistans ruhida adolat g‘oyalarini kuylaydi.

Ular ijodining umumiy humanistik mohiyati bugungi global jamiyat uchun ham ahamiyatli bo‘lib, ijtimoiy tenglik, inson qadr-qimmatini va ozodlik tamoyillariga sadoqat bilan yondashishni targ‘ib etadi.

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**CHIKANO ADABIYOTIDA POETIK IDENTITET MASALASI:
RUDOLFO ANAYANING BLESS ME, ULTIMA ROMANI
MISOLIDA**

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Rudolfo Anayaning "Bless Me, Ultima" asari Chikano adabiy harakati kontekstida poetik tahlil qilinadi. Asarda xalq og'zaki ijodi, mifologik motivlar, diniy va madaniy ramzlar, tilning ikkiyoqliligi (bilingvalizm) hamda inson ruhiyatining o'sish jarayoni poetik ifoda vositalari orqali tahlil etiladi. Maqolada Anayaning poetik uslubi Chikano xalqining o'zligini anglash, madaniy uyg'unlik va ruhiy izlanish g'oyalari bilan bog'liq holda yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Chikano adabiyoti, poetika, mifologiya, ruhiy uyg'onish, bilingvalizm, Ultima, milliy identitet.

Аннотация. В статье представлен поэтический анализ романа Рудольфо Анайи «Благослови меня, Ултима» в контексте литературного движения чикано. В работе анализируются устная традиция фольклора, мифологические мотивы, религиозные и культурные символы, дуализм языка (билингвизм) и процесс развития человеческой психики посредством поэтических средств. В статье рассматривается поэтический стиль Анайи в связи с идеями идентичности чикано, культурной гармонии и духовного поиска.

Ключевые слова: литература чикано, поэтика, мифология, духовное пробуждение, билингвизм, Ultima, национальная идентичность.

Abstract. This article presents a poetic analysis of Rudolfo Anaya's "Bless Me, Ultima" in the context of the Chicano literary movement. The work analyzes the oral tradition of folklore, mythological motifs, religious and cultural symbols, the duality of language (bilingualism), and the process of growth of the human psyche through poetic means. The article examines Anaya's poetic style in relation to the ideas of Chicano identity, cultural harmony, and spiritual exploration.

Keywords: Chicano literature, poetics, mythology, spiritual awakening, bilingualism, Ultima, national identity.

Rudolfo Anaya – XX asr Amerika adabiyotining muhim vakillaridan biri bo'lib, Chikano adabiy harakati doirasida o'zining milliy, diniy va madaniy identitetini badiiy ifodalagan yozuvchidir. Uning 1972 yilda chop etilgan "Bless Me, Ultima" romani Chikano adabiyotining eng mashhur va ta'sirchan namunalaridan biri sifatida tan olingan. Asarda Meksika-Amerika xalqi hayoti, ularning urf-odatlari, diniy qarashlari hamda yangi muhitda o'zligini anglash jarayoni chuqur poetik uslubda ifodalangan. Roman o'zining chuqur ruhiy-falsafiy mazmuni, folklor va mif elementlari, diniy sintez va til poetikasi orqali o'z davrining madaniy jarayonlarini ifodalaydi. Asarda muallif inson va tabiat,

din va e'tiqod, madaniyat va identitet o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni poetik shaklda tasvirlab, o'z xalqining ruhiy dunyosini badiiy falsafa darajasiga ko'taradi. Roman markazida yosh qahramon Antonio Marezning ichki dunyosi, uning ruhiy o'sishi va o'zligini anglash jarayoni turadi. Bu o'sish yo'lida Ultima — donishmand ayol, tabib va ruhiy yo'lko'rsatgich — Antonio uchun yo'l yorituvchi timsolga aylanadi. Asarda inson va tabiat uyg'unligi, ruh va tana, yaxshilik va yomonlik, katoliklik va mahalliy xalq e'tiqodlari o'rtasidagi ziddiyatlar falsafiy darajada tahlil etiladi. Anayaning poetik uslubi ramziy obrazlar va mifologik unsurlarga boy. Roman poetikasida uchraydigan asosiy ramzlar:

1. Ultima – donolik, ona tabiat va an'anaviy xalq ruhiyatining timsoli. U tabiat va inson o'rtasidagi muvozanatni ifodalaydi.
2. Oltin karp – suv, hayot va ilohiy sirlarni anglatadi. Bu obraz orqali Anaya katolik dogmasidan tashqaridagi ruhiy haqiqatni ko'rsatadi.
3. Oy va Quyosh – ayollik va erkaklik energiyalarining uyg'unligi, ruhiy muvozanatni ifodalovchi ramzlar sifatida talqin qilinadi.
4. Llanos (dashtlar) – Chikano xalqining hayotiy makoni, erkinlik va tabiat bilan uyg'unlik timsoli.
5. Suv- poklanish, yangilanish, hayot manbai.
6. Tushlar-ruhiy olamga kirish vositasi, ong osti timsoli.

Bu ramzlar orqali Anaya o'z xalqining kosmologik qarashlarini poetik shaklda ifodalaydi, diniy dualizmni yengib, yagona ruhiy haqiqatga intilishni aks ettiradi. Asarda Anaya ingliz tilidan foydalanib, ammo unga ispancha so'z va iboralarni kiritadi. Bu ikki tillilik (bilingvalizm) Chikano adabiy identitetining asosiy poetik belgisidir. Bu usul orqali muallif o'z xalqining madaniy ikkiyoqliligini - anglo-amerikan madaniyati va meksika merosi o'rtasidagi o'tish holatini aks ettiradi. Tilning bu tarzda ishlatilishi roman poetikasiga xalqona ohang, folklor ruhi va milliy kolorit bag'ishlaydi.

Roman markazida yosh bola - Antonio Marezning ruhiy o'sishi turadi. U o'zining hayotiy yo'lini, e'tiqodini va kimligini izlaydi. Asarda Anaya yosh qahramonning o'sish jarayonini - bildungsroman (yetilish romani) shaklida ifodalab, bu jarayon orqali butun Chikano xalqining madaniy uyg'onish metaforasini yaratadi. Antonio uchun ikki qarama-qarshi kuch muhim:

-Katolik e'tiqodi – ota-onasining diniy an'analari, cherkovning qat'iy qonunlari. -Mahalliy xalq e'tiqodi va sehrlilik dunyo – Ultima orqali ifodalangan xalq donoligi va tabiat bilan uyg'unlik.

Bu ikki tizim o'rtasida Antonio o'z yo'lini topadi — u sintez g'oyasiga asoslangan yangi dunyoqarashni qabul qiladi. Shu jihatdan, Anayaning poetik dunyosida ruhi uyg'unlik g'oyasi markaziy o'rin tutadi. Ultima - romanning markaziy ramziy obrazidir. U tabib, ruhiy yo'l ko'rsatuvchi, xalq donoligini o'zida mujassam etgan ayol sifatida g'aydalanadi. Anaya Ultimani tabiat bilan bir butun mavjudot sifatida tasvirlaydi. Poetik jihatdan Ultima quyidagi ma'nolarni mujassam etadi:

1. Tabiat bilan uyg'unlik – u yer, suv, havo va hayot kuchlarining timsoli.

2. Donolik va bag'rikenglik – Ultima hech bir diniy tizim bilan chegaralanmagan, u universallikni ifodalaydi.

3. Onalik arxetipi – u Antonio uchun ikkinchi ona, ruhiy tarbiyachi, hayot yo'lini ko'rsatuvchi kuchdir.

Anayaning uslubi bilingval — ingliz tili asosida, ammo unda ko'plab ispancha iboralar, maqollar, xalqona so'zlar ishlatilgan. Bu til xususiyati ikki madaniyat oralig'ida yashovchi Chikano xalqining ikkiyoqlilik holatini aks ettiradi. Masalan, “La Virgen de Guadalupe”, “llano”, “Curandera”, “Bruja” kabi iboralar asarda nafaqat til boyligi, balki madaniy kod sifatida ham xizmat qiladi. Shunday qilib, Anaya til poetikasida madaniy identitetni tiklash maqsadini ko'zlaydi - u ingliz tilining hukmronligini buzib, o'z xalqining ovozini o'sha til orqali jaranglatadi. Romanning falsafiy asosi inson va e'tiqod o'rtasidagi uyg'unlikka qurilgan. Antonio katoliklik, xalq dini, va shaxsiy tajriba orqali o'zining ichki “menini” shakllantiradi. Bu jihatdan roman sinxretik e'tiqod (turli diniy qarashlarning uyg'unligi) g'oyasini ilgari suradi. Yozuvchi ruhiy tozalikka faqat tashqi e'tiqod bilan emas, tabiat va inson yuragidagi mehr orqali erishish mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. Bu g'oya Anayaning poetikasini diniy adabiyotdan falsafiy-mistik darajaga ko'taradi. “Bless Me, Ultima” asarining poetikasi faqat badiiy bezak emas u- Chikano xalqining o'zligini anglash vositasidir. Roman orqali Anaya o'z xalqining tarixiy travmasini, madaniy yo'qolish xavfini, va ruhiy qayta tug'ilish imkoniyatini ko'rsatadi. Anayaning poetik dunyosi quyidagilarga asoslanadi:

1. Ona tabiat – xalqning ildizi va ruhiy tayanchi sifatida.

2. Folklor va mif – tarixiy xotirani tiklovchi badiiy vosita.

3. Bilingvalizm – madaniy ovozni qayta tiklash vositasi.

4. Yosh qahramonning yetilishi – xalqning yangi avlod orqali o'zini yangilashi. Rudolfo Anayaning “Bless Me, Ultima” asari Chikano adabiyotining eng yuksak badiiy yutug'i bo'lib, uning poetik tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, yozuvchi folklor, mif, diniy ramzlar, bilingval til unsurlari va ruhiy-falsafiy motivlarni uyg'unlashtirgan holda Chikano xalqining ruhiy uyg'unish dostonini yaratgan. Anaya poetik ifoda orqali inson va tabiat, din va mehr, xalq va til o'rtasidagi uyg'unlikni falsafiy darajada talqin etadi. Shuning uchun “Bless Me, Ultima” faqat bir xalqning romani emas, balki butun insoniyatning ruhiy uyg'unish haqidagi badiiy xabarnomasidir. Anayaning poetik dunyosida mifologik realizm alohida o'rin tutadi. “Bless Me, Ultima”da real voqealar bilan bir qatorda tushlar, ruhlar, sehr-jodu, tabiat kuchlari haqidagi tasvirlar ham mavjud. Bu sintez asarga nafaqat milliy, balki universal ruhiy falsafa bag'ishlaydi. Shuningdek, Anaya uchun mif – xalq xotirasi, kollektiv ongning badiiy ifodasidir. Antonio obrazi orqali yozuvchi diniy ziddiyatlarni - katolik cherkovi ta'limoti bilan mahalliy e'tiqodlar to'qnashuvini ko'rsatadi. Bola ruhiy o'sish jarayonida ikkala yo'lni sinab ko'radi va nihoyat insoniy mehr, tabiat bilan uyg'unlik, va yaxshilik yo'lini tanlaydi. Bu qaror roman poetikasida “Bless Me, Ultima” so'nggi iborasida ramziy yakun topadi - “meni duo qil” degan so'z ruhiy poklanish va uyg'unish ma'nosini bildiradi. “Bless Me, Ultima” – bu faqat Chikano xalqining romani

emas, balki butun insoniyatning ruhiy uyg'onish haqidagi falsafiy dostonidir. Rudolfo Anaya o'z asarida xalq og'zaki ijodi, mifologiya, til va diniy ramzlarni birlashtirib, o'ziga xos poetik dunyo yaratgan. Uning poetik uslubi Chikano adabiyotini yangi bosqichga ko'tardi va Amerika adabiy merosining ajralmas qismiga aylandi.

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TEJAMKORLIK TAMOYILI VA TIL

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis til evolutsiyasi va tejamkorlik tamoyilining til taraqqiyotidagi o'rni va namoyon bo'lish shakllarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot til birliklarining qisqarishi, struktural va funksional o'zgarishlar hamda muloqot ehtiyoji bilan bog'liq jarayonlarni tahlil qiladi. XIX asrdan buyon Germaniya, Angliya, Rossiya va sobiq Sovet maktablaridagi olimlarning kuzatuvlari keltiriladi. Natijada tejamkorlik tamoyili tilning tarixiy shakllanishi va rivojlanishida muhim omil ekani ko'rsatildi.

Kalit so'zlar. Til evolutsiyasi, tejamkorlik tamoyili, til birliklari, strukturaviy va funksional o'zgarishlar, muloqot ehtiyoji, lingvistik ekonomiya.

Til insoniyatning asosiy muloqot vositasi bo'lib, uning rivojlanishi muloqot ehtiyoji va lingvistik imkoniyatlarning o'zaro ta'siridan kelib chiqadi. Til evolutsiyasini belgilovchi qonunlardan biri – tejamkorlik tamoyili – til birliklarining qisqarishi, tuzilmalarning soddalashishi va muloqot jarayonini

osonlashtirishga xizmat qiladi. XIX asrdan boshlab G.Kurtsius, V.Uitni kabi olimlar tilning tejamkorlik tamoyiliga oid kuzatuvlarni amalga oshirgan. Keyinchalik G.Paul, A.Martine, I.A.Boduen de Kurtene va sobiq Sovet maktabining ko'plab namoyandalari ushbu prinsipni o'rganib, til taraqqiyotini strukturaviy va funksional jihatdan tahlil qilganlar. Tadqiqot davomida tilning adaptiv xususiyati, struktural va ijtimoiy funktsiyalarning o'zaro bog'liqligi, shuningdek, muloqot jarayonida til birliklarining tanlanishi va qisqarish tendensiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Gap til evolutsiyasini belgilab beruvchi qonunlardan biri xususida ketar ekan, qaysi sabablarga ko'ra u tilda hukm suradi va uning namoyon bo'lish formalari qanday, degan savol tug'ilishi tabiiy.¹ B.A.Serebrennikovning guvohlik berishicha, XIX asrdayoq germaniyalik olim G.Kurtsius, angliyalik olim V.Uitni tildagi tejamkorlik tamoyiliga oid dastlabki kuzatishlarni olib borgan edilar.² Bundan keyingi davrda ham G'arbiy Yevropa va Rossiya tilshunoslik maktablarining deyarli barcha yirik namoyandalari til ekonomiyasiga oid tekshirishlar olib bordilar va o'z fikr-mulohazalarini qayd qilib o'tdilar. G.Paul, A.Martine, shuningdek, I.A.Boduen de Kurtene, K.M.Peshkovskiy, V.A.Bogoroditskiy, YE.D.Polivanov va sobiq sovet tilshunosligining bir qancha namoyandalari shular jumlasidandir.³

Ta'kidlanganidek, fikrni aniq ifodalashga bo'lgan ehtiyojning doimiy ortib borishi va til imkoniyatlarining chegaralanganligi o'rtasidagi nomutanosiblik tilning rivojlanishiga turtki bergan va berib kelmoqda. Bu o'z navbatida til taraqqiyotining ikki asosiy jihatini shakllantiradi. Bu xususda V.A.Avrarin ilgari surgan fikrlar diqqatga sazovor, ya'ni olimning fikricha, tilning taraqqiyoti va amal qilinishida o'zaro dialektik aloqador va bir-birini taqozo qiluvchi ikki tomon mavjud:

tilning material strukturasi;
ijtimoiy funktsiyasi.

Shunga ko'ra til evolutsiyasining ikki nisbatan mustaqil yo'nalishi mavjud. Bular struktural va funksional yo'nalishlardir.⁴ Struktural yo'nalish til yaruslaridagi rivojlanishni o'zida jamlaydi va shu nuqtai nazardan u tadqiqotchilarning e'tiborini ko'proq jalb etadi. Miqdor tomoni o'zgarishlar tendensiyasini o'zida to'laroq ifodalaydigan tomondir. Shu sababli undan tendensiyalarni aniqlashdagi asosiy faktor sifatida tez-tez foydalanadilar.⁵ Shuning uchun tilning rivojlanishi

¹ Eltzarov J.D. Tildagi tejamkorlik tamoyili va qisqaruv. Monografiya. - Samarqand: SamDU, 2004. - 16-b.

² Серебренников Б.А. О материалистическом подходе явлениям языка. -М.: Наука, 1983. -212-213 С.

³ Eltzarov J.D. Tildagi tejamkorlik tamoyili va qisqaruv. Monografiya. - Samarqand: SamDU, 2004. - 17-b

⁴ Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. -М.Сов. энциклопедия, 1966. - 14С.

⁵ Скредина Л.М. Некоторые вопросы развития языка (проблемы и методы диахронического исследования). -Минск: Изд-во БГУ, 1978. - 89 С.

asosan muloqot ehtiyojlariga bog'liq bo'lib, bu jarayonda til birliklari osonroq va qulayroq shakllarda tanlanadi yoki tuzilma o'zgaradi, ko'pincha bunday o'zgarishlar birliklarning qisqarishida aks etadi. G.P.Melnikovning muvaffaqiyatli iborasi bilan aytganda: "Til organik sistemadir, ya'ni u adaptiv (o'zgaruvchan, moslashuvchan - muall.) sistemaning bir turi bo'lib, uning strukturasi insonning ongli aralashuvisiz yuz beruvchi struktural ehtiyojlar va substant imkoniyatlarning o'zaro ta'siri jarayonida shakllanadi, struktural ehtiyojlar esa sistema tomonidan struktura va substansiyaning eng qulay birikuvini doimiy, stixiyali ravishda tanlab olinishiga nisbatan reaksiya sifatida paydo bo'ladilar".¹ Shu sababdan, ilmiy manbalarda til birliklarining qisqarishi va muloqot jarayonini soddalashtiruvchi turli hodisalarni o'zida mujassam etuvchi tejamkorlik tamoyili hamda uning tilning tarixiy shakllanishi va taraqqiyotidagi o'rni haqida anchadan buyon rang-barang ilmiy fikrlar bildirilib kelinmoqda.

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O'ZBEK ASARLARIDA SHER ZOOSEMASINING
XUSUSIYATLARI

Sher zoosemasida kuchlilik, bahaybatlilik, baquvvatlilik kabi ma'no-mazmun alohida kasb etadi.

Abdulla Qodiriy nazdida arslonning dushmanlari go'yoki, unga kesak bilan hamla qilgandek, arslonlarga arslonlarcha jang qilish kerakligi uqtirilib, bu bilan ularning ustidan kulib qo'yadi. Arslonlik jang san'atidan xabardor jangchilarga munosib.

¹ Мельников Г'.Я. Принципы системной лингвистики в применении к проблемам тюркологии // Структура и история тюркских языков. -М.: Наука, 1971. -С. 123.

O‘rda arbobi Anvarning arslon yurakli yigitligini o‘ylar ekan, tarix sahifalarida hali hech kim dil bog‘lab, o‘lim sari kelmagan va bunday ish tarixda birinchi marta bo‘lganidan hayratlanadi hamda uning jasoratiga va arslonligiga tan beradi. Bu o‘rinda Anvarning qo‘rqmasligi arslonga qiyoslanmoqda.

Usta Alim so‘zi: Ammo arslon yuraklik Otabek ham badbaxtni shundog‘ yanchib tashladikim, bu juda oz kishilar qo‘lidan kelaturg‘on ishdir.

Bunday odam jang boshida jasoratda sherga, jang o‘rtasida sabr-bardoshda filga, jang oxirida gazab-u qahrda ajdahoga aylanur¹.

Otabekning arslonlarga xos xususiyati sha‘ni va obro‘yini himoya qilishda qo‘l keladi, chunki u yakka o‘zi dushmanlarga sherdek hamla qilib, ularni qirib tashlaydi.

Otabek arslonyurakli jasur yigit bo‘lsa, Muhammad Alining “Ulug‘ saltanat” asari qahramoni bir vaqtning o‘zida bir nechta sher, fil va ajdarhoga qiyoslanib, jasorat, sabr-bardosh va qahr-g‘azab singari pozitiv va negativ xususiyatlar tilga olinadi.

Biz Akbarali mingboshini Miryoqubdan ko‘ra odamroq deb bilamiz – Nega shunday bo‘ladi? – Nega – Miryoqub Sherday o‘kiradi².

Bilagingizda kuch ko‘p, amirzodam! Sherpanjasiz! Podshoh hazratlari sizni Bobur deb ataganlari bejiz emas. Bobur arabcha sher demakdir³.

Akbaralida odamiylik va odamgarchilik kuchli. Miryoqub esa Akbaralidan farq qiladi, sher kabi o‘kiradi, ya‘ni u g‘azablansa, sher kabi hamla qilishi nazarda tutiladi.

Boburning panjalari sherga o‘xshagani va uning ismining asl ma‘nosida ham sher mazmunining borligi uning sherdek kuch-qudratidan dalolat beradi.

Bu tilning, she‘rning sheri mudofaa qilar ekan, yana qaysi mard aksin isbot qilur – dedi Boyqaro⁴.

Basharasi odam qiyofasiga o‘xshab ketgan sher... Bo‘ynida ikki tomonga yo‘g‘on zanjir tortilib, uchlari ikki qoziqqa bog‘langan. Ammo Zanjirband sher “mag‘rur”. Haydar kirdi. A. Navoiy hazratlari zanjirda⁵.

Ma‘lumki, til millat ko‘rki hisoblanadi va har bir shoir o‘zi yaratgan she‘rni Husayn Boyqaro aytganidek, sherday himoya qiladi va jasoratini namoyon etadi. Keltirilgan parchada Navoiyning musavvirlik san‘atidan boxabarligi, zerikkan chog‘larida rassomchilik bilan shug‘ullanishi tasvirlangan. Biroq parchada zerikkandan siqilib, qo‘lga olingan mo‘yqalam kuchli bir chizgilarga jonli ifoda baxsh etadi. Navoiy o‘zini Zanjirband sher timsolida ifodalab, Husayn Boyqaro atrofidagi tulkidek ayyor va ilondek shoh qo‘yniga kirib olgan ba‘zi saroy ayonlari tomonidan qilingan fitna-yu fasod Alisher Hazratlarini zanjirlab qo‘ygandek tuyulardi. Sher mard, qo‘rqmas va sadoqat timsolini ifodalaydi.

¹ Мухаммад Али. Улуғ салтанат. –Тошкент: Шарқ нашриёти, 2003. – Б.441.

²Cho‘lpon. Kecha va kunduz. –Toshkent: Yangi nashr, 2019. – B.125.

³Qodirov P. Yulduzli tunlar. – Toshkent: Adabiyot uchqunlari, 2018. – B.32.

⁴Oybek. Navoiy. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2019. –B.358.

⁵O‘sha joyda. – B.405.

Alisher Navoiyning zanjirbandligi ifodalangan ushbu misoldan uning jismi bo'ysunuvchan, qalbi esa o'zi tanlagan haq yo'ldaligini anglatadi. Suhbat jarayonida Behzod sherning bo'ynidagi zanjir uzilganini tasvirlaydi. Yozuvchi bu bilan Alisher Navoiyning mansabdan ketib, ozod va kamtar inson sifatida o'z vatanida istiqomat qilganligini ta'kidlagan. Ikki tomondan tortilgan zanjirlar unga qilingan tuhmat va ig'volar timsoli edi.

“Zanjirband sher” ma'nosini chuqurroq o'rganish maqsadida bir nechta adabiy va tarixiy manbalarga murojaat qildik. O'tauli taxallusi bilan tanilgan yozuvchining “Zanjirband sher” hikoyasi diqqatimizni tortdi:

*Xudoga shukur, u Turon sheri! Sher bo'lib tug'ilgan, sher bo'lib yashadi, sher bo'lib o'ladi! Nachora, zanjirband sher bo'lib o'lish manglayida bor ekan, shu topda shu alfozda o'lsa o'ladi, lekin hech kimga bo'yin egmaydi*¹.

Sherning na'rasi, vajohati qanchalik kuchli va qo'rqinchli bo'lmasin, u na'ra tortishni, na to'lg'onishni bilardi. Dushmanga tulkidek ayyorlik, ilondek tilyog'lamalik qilmadi, Turonning qoplani, arsloni, yo'lbarsi mard-u maydoni tarzida sherdek tug'ilib, sherdek yashagani va sherdek mardlarcha nomardlar qo'lida o'lishini tan olgan.

Turon hoqoni Alp Er To'nga nomi sher semasi bilan bog'lanadi. Tarixchilar, ijodkorlar va yozuvchilar o'z asarlarida uni o'ziga xos bir xususiyat bilan tilga olishadi.

Shu bilan birga sher semasida konnotativ ma'no bo'lib, K.Kuiper va V.Allanlarning fikrlariga ko'ra, konnotativ ma'no – so'zlar semantik mazmunining emotsional ohanglari turli jamiyatlarda ijtimoiy munosabat va xulq-atvorga boy tadqiqotlar manbai hisoblanadi². Konnotatsiyalar, asosan, madaniyatga bog'liq bo'lib, ba'zida insonlarning his-tuyg'ulari, idroklari va ruhiy tasvirlaridan paydo bo'ladi³.

Umuman olganda, ingliz adabiyotida bo'ri zoosemizmining jasorat, ishonch, soddadillik, qo'rqmaslik kabi ijobiy xususiyatlari bilan birga, tajovuzkor va ochko'zlik singari salbiy xislatlari ham alohida ta'kidlangan. Sher zoosemizmi esa kuchlilik va qat'iyatlilik timsoli bo'lib keladi.

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TED HYUZ ASARLARIDAGI SUPERSEGMENT BIRLIKLARNING ILMIY TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz zamonaviy she'riyati vakili Ted Hyuz asarlarida uchraydigan supersegment fonetik vositalarning badiiy-semantik va stilistik funksiyalari ilmiy asosda tahlil qilinadi. Intonatsiya, urg'u, pauza, ritm, temp, melodika kabi prosodik birliklarning she'riy matnning konnotativ qatlamini shakllantirishdagi o'rni, ayniqsa tabiatning zo'ravon kuchi va hayvonot olami timsollarini yaratishdagi akustik vosita sifatidagi ahamiyati keng yoritiladi. Tadqiqot davomida "Wind", "Crow", "Pike", "The Hawk in the Rain" kabi mashhur asarlar fonostilistik nuqtai nazardan ko'rib chiqildi.

Аннотация. В данной статье научно анализируются художественно-семантические и стилистические функции суперсегментных фонетических средств, встречающихся в произведениях представителя современной английской поэзии Теда Хьюза. Широко освещается роль таких просодических единиц, как интонация, ударение, пауза, ритм, темп и мелодика, в формировании коннотативного слоя поэтического текста, особенно их значение в создании акустического образа природы как разрушительной силы и символов животного мира. В ходе исследования были рассмотрены с фоностилистической точки зрения такие известные произведения, как "Wind", "Crow", "Pike", "The Hawk in the Rain".

Abstract. This article provides a scholarly analysis of the artistic-semantic and stylistic functions of suprasegmental phonetic devices found in the works of Ted Hughes, a representative of modern English poetry. The study highlights the role of prosodic units such as intonation, stress, pause, rhythm, tempo, and melody in shaping the connotative layer of poetic texts, particularly their significance as acoustic tools in depicting nature's violent power and the imagery of the animal world. The research examines well-known works such as "Wind", "Crow", "Pike", "The Hawk in the Rain" from a phonostylistic perspective.

Kalit so'zlar: prosodiya, supersegment birliklar, intonatsiya, urg'u, pauza, ritm, fonostilistika, Ted Hyuz, konnotativ ma'no, poetik fonetika.

Ключевые слова: просодия, суперсегментные единицы, интонация, ударение, пауза, ритм, фоностилистика. Тед Хьюз, коннотативное значение, поэтическая фонетика.

Keywords: prosody, suprasegmental units, intonation, stress, pause, rhythm, phonostylistics, Ted Hughes, connotative leaning, poetic phonetics.

Ted Hyuz (1930–1998) XX asr ingliz she'riyatining eng kuchli ovozlardan biri bo'lib, uning poetik dunyosida tabiat, instinkt, yovvoyilik va odam ruhiyatining chuqur qatlamlari aks etgan. Hyuz she'riyatining fonetik-obrazli tizimi o'ziga xos bo'lib, unda supersegment (intonatsion) vositalar badiiy ma'noni kuchaytiruvchi markaziy unsurlardan biridir. Fonostilistik tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, she'riy matnning ohang strukturasi intonatsiya, urg'u, pauza va ritm semantik yuklama bilan o'zaro uyg'unlashib, o'quvchi idrokida jonli akustik effekt hosil qiladi. Hyuz poetikasida ayniqsa tabiat kuchlarining dahshatli portlashlari, hayvonotning instinktiv harakatlari badiiy akustik vositalar orqali eshitiladigan obraz darajasigacha olib chiqiladi.

Ted Hyuzning asarlarida prosodik birliklarning asosiy vazifasi – semantik kuchlanishni oshirish va obrazning fonetik “jonlanishini” ta'minlashdir. Hyuz uchun tovush – bu faqat akustik element emas, balki mazmunning bir qismi. Ayniqsa undosh tovushlarning portlovchi xususiyatlari (t, k, g, p) va keskin intonatsiya ko'tarilishlari shamol, qush, yirtqich hayvon yoki suv hayoti tasvirlarida prinsipal rol o'ynaydi. Masalan, “The Hawk in the Rain” she'rida shovqin, bosim, bosilish kabi dinamik jarayonlar fonetik vositalar bilan qayta yaratilib, o'quvchi ongida kuchli akustik tasavvur hosil qiladi. Prosodik tizimning bunday markazlashgan turi Hyuz uslubining asosiy belgilaridan biridir.

Hyuz she'riyatida intonatsiya dramatik kuchaytirish vositasi sifatida xizmat qiladi. Masalan, “Wind” she'rida intonatsiya shamolning tobora zo'rayib boruvchi harakatini taqlid qiluvchi ohang ko'tarilishi orqali beriladi. Misol: “This house has been far out at sea all night.” Ushbu satrda intonatsiyaning sekin ko'tarilishi va birdan keskin pasayishi shamolning beqarorligi va xavfli xatti-harakatini akustik tarzda modellashtiradi. Intonatsiya bu yerda faqat informativ ohang emas, balki tabiatning “qichqirig'i”, uning ichki energiyasi sifatida namoyon bo'ladi. Hyuzning ko'pgina asarlarida intonatsiya dramatik kuchlanishni kuchaytirib, nutqning semantik to'lqinlanishini yaratadi.

Hyuz asarlarida urg'u nafaqat fonetik ko'rsatkich, balki semantik markazni belgilovchi vositadir. “Pike” she'rida: “Pike, three inches long, perfect.” Bu satrdagi “perfect” so'ziga tushgan emfatik urg'u baliqning nafaqat go'zalligini, balki uning xavfli tabiatini ham ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, urg'u ko'pincha dramatik portlashni yuzaga keltiradi. Masalan, “Kill it!” kabi qisqa zarbli buyruq gaplar hayvoniy instinktning achchiq va keskin tabiatini aks ettiradi. Hyuzning metrikaning barqarorligini buzuvchi urg'u o'rinlari esa poetik ritmga dinamik tebranish olib kiradi.

Pauza Hyuz she'riyatining eng kuchli stilistik vositalaridan biridir. “Crow” to'plamidagi: “Crow saw that her body was perfect / But she had no voice.” Misralar orasidagi pauza o'quvchi ongida shok, bo'shliq va dramatik tanaffus effekti yaratadi. Birinchi misra mukammallik g'oyasini bersa, ikkinchisi pauzadan so'ng keskin qarama-qarshi semantik kontrast bilan kuchli ta'sir

ko'rsatadi. Pauza bu yerda nafaqat sintaktik, balki psixologik vosita sifatida ham ishlaydi. Hyuz pazani ko'pincha ruhiy bo'shliq, hayvoniy sezgi yoki tabiatdagi xavfning yaqinlashishini his qilish vositasi sifatida qo'llaydi.

Hyuz poetikasida ritm tabiat kuchlari harakatining akustik modeli sifatida ishlaydi. "Wind" she'rida tezlashgan ritm shamolning bo'ronli zarbalarini berib, o'quvchida beqaror muhit tasavvurini yaratadi: "The woods crashing through darkness, the booming hills." Bu yerda ritmning keskin tebranishi shamolning vayronkor xarakteri bilan mos keladi. Ritmning sekinlashuvi esa ko'pincha ruhiy toliqish, og'irlik yoki xavfni kutish holatini ifodalaydi.

Melodika va tembr Hyuzda qo'shimcha akustik qatlam yaratadi. Uning she'rlaridagi tovush tembrlari – harsh, booming, growling singari akustik sifatlar: yirtqich qush, bo'ron, suv hayoti yoki zulmat bilan bog'liq obrazlarni fonetik tarzda jonlantiradi. Masalan, Crow obrazi pastga tushuvchi melodika va qo'pol tembrda ifodalanib, mifologik yovvoyilikni aks ettiradi.

Xulosa sifatida shuni aytish mumkinki, Ted Hyuz poetikasida supersegment birliklar – intonatsiya, urg'u, pauza, ritm va melodika – badiiy ma'noni kuchaytiruvchi, tabiatning yovvoyilik kuchlarini akustik jihatdan jonlantiruvchi asosiy badiiy vositadir. Hyuz she'riyatining fonetik tuzilishi o'quvchi idrokini kuchli ravishda ta'sirlab, tabiat hodisalarini eshitiladigan obraz darajasiga ko'taradi. Mazkur prosodik mexanizmlar uning poetik uslubida mazmun va shaklning fonetik uyg'unligini ta'minlaydi.

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KONSEPT VA KONSEPTUAL MURAKKABLIK

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda antroposentrik paradigmaning yetakchi yo'nalishlari hisoblangan kognitiv tilshunoslik va lingvokulturologiyada konsept muhim kategoriya hisoblanadi. Kognitiv tilshunoslik – dunyoning lisoniy tasvirida muayyan konseptning mohiyati va dunyo voqealari bilan bog'liqligini o'rganuvchi fandir. Konsept esa kognitiv tilshunoslik fanining asosiy kategoriyalaridan biri bo'lib, madaniyat va inson o'rtasidagi aloqa o'rnatuvchi elementdir. "Konsept" termini 90-yillardan beri lingvistikada

qo'llanilib kelinmoqda. Konsept tushunchasi hali hamon bitta umumiy izoh yoki talqinga ega emas.

Kalit so'zlar: konsept, tushuncha, freym tahlil, geshtalt, kognitiv tilshunoslik

Аннотация. В современной лингвистике концепт является важной категорией в когнитивной лингвистике и лингвокультурологии, которые считаются ведущими направлениями антропоцентрической парадигмы. Когнитивная лингвистика изучает сущность определённого концепта в языковой картине мира и его связь с явлениями действительности. Концепт выступает одной из основных категорий когнитивной лингвистики и служит элементом, устанавливающим связь между культурой и человеком. Термин «концепт» используется в лингвистике с 1990-х годов. Понятие концепта до сих пор не имеет единственного общепринятого определения или толкования.

Ключевые слова: концепт, понятие, фрейм-анализ, гештальт, когнитивная лингвистика.

Abstract. In modern linguistics, the concept is considered an important category within cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology, which represent the leading directions of the anthropocentric paradigm. Cognitive linguistics studies the nature of a particular concept within the linguistic worldview and its connection with the phenomena of reality. The concept is one of the fundamental categories of cognitive linguistics and serves as an element that establishes the relationship between culture and the individual. The term “concept” has been used in linguistics since the 1990s. The notion of a concept still does not have a single universally accepted definition or interpretation.

Keywords: concept, notion, frame analysis, gestalt, cognitive linguistics.

XX asrning oxirgi choragida vujudga kelib zamonaviy lingvistikaning peshqadam yo'nalishiga aylangan kognitiv tilshunoslik dastlab Amerikada vujudga keldi. Kognitiv grammatika asoschisi R.Langaker, va keyinchalik J.Lakof, Ch.Filmor o'zlarining ilmiy ishlari bilan kognitiv lingvistikaga asos yaratdilar. Insonning bilish faoliyati bilan bog'liq bo'lgan kognitiv tilshunoslik atamasi ingliz tilidan olingan bo'lib “cognitive-bilish va idrok etish harakati va jarayoni bilan bog'liq”¹ degan ma'noni bildiradi. Ammo kognitiv tilshunoslikning asosini faqat bilish faoliyati bilan emas, hayvonlarning ham qisman bilish, anglash va tushunish holatlarini inobatga olgan holatda ushbu yo'nalishni tafakkur va unga bog'liq bo'lgan ijtimoiy, madaniy va lisoniy hodisalar bilan ham bog'liq holda to'liq tasavvur qilish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.²

¹ Oxford English dictionary. (2024). Cognitive. In Oxford Learner's Dictionaries. Retrieved May 8, 2024, from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/cognitive>

² Safarov, Sh. (2006). Kognitiv tilshunoslik. “Sangzor” nashriyoti.

Kognitiv lingvistika aslida zamonaviy tilshunoslikning yangi yoʻnalishi sifatida oʻtgan asrda shakllangan boʻlsada, uning vujudga kelishi uchun koʻplab olimlarning asarlari va falsafiy gʻoyalari asos boʻlib xizmat qiladi. Xususan, qadimgi yunon faylasufi Aflotun oʻzining shakllar nazariyasida konseptlar tabiati haqida fikr bildirar ekan, moddiy dunyo adolat, goʻzallik va xunuklik, yaxshilik kabi mukammal va oʻzgarimas shakllari mavjud boʻlgan dunyoning aksi ekanligi haqida taʼkidlagan. Bundan tashqari, uning asosiy hissasi kognitiv tilshunoslikning asosiy mavzulari hisoblangan til, tafakkur va voqelik oʻrtasidagi bogʻliqliklarni oʻrganishida sanaladi.

Yana bir yunon faylasufi Aristotel, Aflotundan farqli ravishda, konseptlar tafakkurda tajribalar orqali shakllanishini aytib oʻtgan. Uning fikricha, tushuncha va konseptlar hissiy tajribalarga tayangan holda yaʼni kuzatish (koʻrish, hidlash va taʼm bilish, eshitish) va kategoriyalashtirish orqali ongda shakllanadi. Keyinchalik, XVII asrda ingliz tilshunosi J.Lok ham Aristotel singari inson bilimi, tafakkuridagi konseptlar hissiy tajribalar orqali inson ongida mukammallashishini taʼkidlagan.¹

Nemis faylasufi I.Kant fikricha, inson ongi nafaqat voqelikni oʻzlashtiradi, balki u kognitiv tuzilmalar orqali uni faol shakllantiradi.² I.Kantning insoniyat dunyoni vaqt, makon va sabablar singari konseptual kategoriyalar orqali qabul qilishi va insonning ichki aqliy tuzilamaları tashqi voqelikni qanday shakllantirganligi haqidagi fikrlari keyinchalik, J.Lakof va Jonsonlarning konseptual metafora nazariyasi yaratilishida asos boʻlib xizmat qildi. Ularning fikriga qaraganda, bizning konseptual tizimimiz metaforik tabiatga ega.³ Yaʼni, mavhum tushuncha va konseptlar (xunuklik, goʻzallik, axloq kabilar) aniq va jismoniy tajribalar orqali tushuniladi. Masalan, ingliz madaniyatida goʻzallik yorugʻlik, kuch-qudrat, sanʼat asari timsoli boʻlsa, xunuklik har ikkala madaniyat uchun ham qorongʻulik, zulmat, axloqiy buzuvchilik, halokat timsoli sanaladi.

J. Lakof kognitiv lingvistikaning yetakchi vakillaridan biri hisoblanadi. Uning fikriga qaraganda, inson ongida konsept kognitiv modellar orqali tuziladi va koʻpgina mavhum tushunchalar metaforik tarzda tushuniladi.⁴

Konsept tushunchasining lugʻaviy maʼnosi ustida ham koʻpgina olimlar har xil fikrlarni bildirishadi. Unga koʻra mantiqiy kategoriya, amaliy falsafa tushunchasi, milliy mentalitetning asosiy birligi sifatida qaraydiganlar ham bor. “Konsept”-lotincha “conceptus” soʻzidan olingan boʻlib, “tushuncha” maʼnosini bildiradi. Kognitiv atamalar lugʻatida esa konsept atamasiga quyidagicha taʼrif beriladi: konsept bizning tafakkurimizdagi aqliy va psixik resurslarning inson

¹ Locke J. An essay concerning human understanding (P.H.Nidditch). Clarendon Press. 1975

² Kant I. Critique of pure reason, by P.Guyer and A.W.Wood. Cambridge University Press. 1998

³ Lakoff, G. Women, fire, and dangerous things: What categories reveal about the mind. University of Chicago Press. 1987

⁴ Lakoff, G. Women, Fire, and dangerous things: What categories reveal about the mind. University of Chicago Press. 1987

bilim va malakalarida aks etishiga xizmat qiladigan tushunchadir. "Konsept" atamasi zamonaviy tilshunoslikda biror bir leksik birlikning tafakkurdagi obrazini ifodalash uchun qo'llaniladi. Kundalik ilmiy ijodda esa konsept atamasi "tushuncha" bilan sinonim sifatida qo'llaniladi.

O'zbek tilshunosligida ham "konsept" tushunchasi turli talqinga ega. Masalan, Sh.Safarov "moddiy dunyo idroki ayni paytda idrok etilayotgan predmet- hodisalar haqida tushunchaning tug'ilishini, keyinchalik ushbu tushuncha mental namuna konsept sifatida shakllanib, moddiy nom olishi"ni ta'kidlaydi¹.

O'.Q.Yusupov konseptni "tashqi yoki ichki dunyodagi biror bir narsa yoki hodisa haqidagi ongimizdagi bilimlar majmuasi, u haqidagi obrazlar va unga bo'lgan ijobiy, salbiy, neytral munosabatlar, ya'ni baholashlardir", deb belgilaydi. Tushuncha va konseptni farqlashda olim quyidagicha fikr bildiradi: "konsept bilan tushunchani ayebergga o'xshatish mumkin. Agar konsept aysberg bo'lsa, uning suvdan chiqib turgan qismi tushunchadir"². Yuqoridagi fikrlarni o'rganish natijasida shunday xulosaga kelish mumkinki, konsept tushunchasi har bir shaxs uchun individual va jamiyat uchun umummilliy bo'lgan, ong, til va ruhiyatning bog'liqligida kechuvchi jarayondir, tilshunoslikda yanada chuqur o'rganishni taqozo etadigan mavzu.

Kognitiv grammatika asoschisi R.Langaker o'z asarida konseptning kognitiv tarmoqlar asosida shakllanishi haqida to'xtalib o'tgan. Uning fikricha, kognitiv makon bu ongimizda konsept va tushunchalarni to'liq anglashga yordam beradigan bilim sohasi va kontekstlardir.³ Konseptual murakkablik haqida gapirar ekan, Langaker, asosiy va abstrakt kognitiv makon tushunchalariga ham izoh beradi. Til esa mana shu shu konseptual tizim asosida quriladi. R. Langaker ilgari surgan ushbu g'oya asosida grammatik tuzilmalar inson idroki va bilim doirasiga bog'liq deyish mumkin.

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¹ Safarov Sh. S. Kognitiv tilshunoslik.-Jizzax: Sangzor,2006.- B.91

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TARIXIY ILDIZLAR, ZAMONAVIY ISLOHOTLAR UYG'UNLIGI

O'zbek xalqi millat sifatida shakllanganidan buyon tarix sahnasida son-sanoqsiz qahramonlar yetishib chiqqan. Ularning ayrimlari zamon o'tishi bilan unutilgan bo'lsa-da, shunday qahramonlari borki, ular xalqning qalbidan, millatning ongidan hech qachon o'chmaydi, g'oyalari davrlar o'tsa ham ma'rifat va taraqqiyotga chorlovchi mangu ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ular -Jadidlardir

***“Jadidlar g'oyalari yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi bilan hamohangdir”¹ —
Shavkat Mirziyoyev***

XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida mustamlaka zulmi ostida ziyolilar o'z xalqlarini ma'rifatli qilish va ularning taraqqiyot darajasini ko'tarishga qaratilgan harakatlarni boshladi. Millatni o'nlab yillar, asrlar davomida qiynagan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolar, ommaviy ongsizlantirishga qaratilgan harakatlar, milliy din, huquqlarga nisbatan nohaq taqiqlarga qarshi kurash edi bu. Sharq va G'arb dunyosi taqqoslanganda, o'zidan bir necha asrlardan so'ng shakllangan shaharlarning infratuzilmasi, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, madaniy holati ancha rivojlangani- bir paytlar dunyo tan olgan ilm ahlining nomunosib avlodi bo'lish-uyat hissiga qarshi isyon edi bu.

Eng dastlabki harakatlar Ismoilbek G'aspirali tomonidan tashkil etilgan “Tarjimon” gazetasi orqali xalqqa yetkazilgan. 1883-yilda ilk soni nashr etilgan ushbu gazetada xalqning har tomonlama taraqqiy etishi uchun yo'l-ma'naviy va aqliy kamolotdan o'tishini targ'ib qilingan, dinni ilm-fan bilan uyg'un holda talqin etib, insonparvarlik va ma'rifat g'oyalari nashr etilgan edi. Ushbu ilgari surilgan tamoyillar o'z dolzarbligini hali hamon yo'qotmagan. Zamonaviy

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi,- Toshkent,- O'zbekkitob, 2021

O'zbekiston jamiyati oldida turgan ulkan maqsadlar-milliy birdamlikni mustahkamlash, ta'lim va ilm-fanni rivojlantirish, yosh avlodni ma'naviy yetuk qilib tarbiyalash- aynan "Tarjimon"ning g'oyalari va ularning davomidir. Gazeta bir paytlar turkiy xalqlar o'rtasida ma'rifat ko'prigi vazifasini bajargan bo'lsa, bugungi kunda uning g'oyalari millatlararo hamjihatlik, madaniy yangilanish va fikriy mustaqillik yo'lida ilhom manbaiga aylangan. 1910-yilda Fransiyada chop etilgan "*Revue du Monde Musulman*" jurnali "Tarjimon" gazetasining ma'rifatparvarlikdagi xizmatlarini yuksak baholab, agar musulmon dunyosi uchun Nobel mukofoti mavjud bo'lganida, Ismoil G'aspirali bunga, albatta, munosib inson bo'lgan bo'lardi, deya ta'kidlagan¹. Bundan tashqari, Buyuk Britaniyaning mashhur nashri- *Migration Letters*da chop etilgan "*Conception of Science in Turkic-Muslim Discourse*"² sarlavhasi ostidagi maqolada "Tarjimon" gazetasi, muallifi faoliyati va g'oyalarini yuksak baholanib, XXI asrda ham, nafaqat islom olamida balki butun dunyoda, "Tarjimon"da ilgari surilgan ilm-ta'lim, jamiyat va inson haqidagi g'oyalari dolzarb hamda, ma'naviy kamolot va taraqqiyot sari chorlovchi kuch sifatida talqin qilingan. Bugungi kunga kelib ham, G'aspirali va uning adabiy ishlari haqidagi yuksak e'tiroflar, tahlil va tadqiqotlarning davom etayotganligi, jadidlarning fikrlari mustahkam, g'oyalari aniq va dunyoqarashlari teran ekanligidan dalolat beradi.

Jadidlar biz kirib borayotgan uchinchi renessansning ilk bunyodkorlari, mustaqillik milliy mafkurasi asoschilari ekanligi Behbudiyning tashabbuslarida ham ayon. Behbudiy jadidchilik harakatining yetakchi shaxlaridan bo'lib, o'z davrida O'zbekistonda zamonaviy ta'lim tizimini joriy etish, xalq ma'rifatini oshirish va milliy ongini uyg'otish bo'yicha faoliyat olib borgan. U jadid maktablarini tashkil etish, o'quv dasturlarini yangilash va savodsizlikni bartaraf etish orqali jamiyatni taraqqiyotga chorlagan. Bugungi kunda Behbudiyning g'oyalari ayniqsa dolzarb, chunki xalqning ilm-fan bilan tanishishi, zamonaviy ta'limni rivojlantirish va ma'naviy kamolotga erishish masalalari hali ham to'liq yechim topgan emas. O'zbekistonning ayrim chekka, qishloq hudularida zamonaviy ta'lim olish uchun yetarli imkoniyatlar mavjud emas. Afsuski, shu bilan birga, hududidan qat'iy nazar ko'pchilik yoshlar eng yangi avlod texnologiyalar bilan yetarlicha tanish emas, ayniqsa, ona tilida ilmiy manbalar yetishmaydi. Xalqning ma'naviy darajasi esa, ma'lum ma'noda, ijtimoiy tarmoqlardagi "content"lardan ma'lum. Bundan tashqari Behbudiy ayollar ta'limi va ularning jamiyatdagi ishtirokini oshirish masalasiga katta e'tibor qaratgan- u ayollarning savodli bo'lishi, o'z huquqlarini anglab, jamiyat hayotida faol qatnashishi millat taraqqiyotining muhim omili ekanini ta'kidlagan.

Shu o'rinda, usuli jadid - **Muhammadsharif So'fizodaning** "...*Bechora ona bo'lg'uvchi qobila qizlar, Nozik qo'liga olmay o'tar xoma va daftar...*"³ deya

¹ *Revue du Monde Musulman* Parij: E.Lerux va Mission Scientifique du Maroc, 1926

² Azerbayev A.D., Nuryshva G.Z., Tercan N., Barlybayeva G., *Conception of Science in Turkic-Muslim discourse*, - *Migration Letters*, - London, -2023, -P 88-97

³ Muhammadsharif S., *Bechora qizlar*, - Turkiston, -Toshkent, - 1934

millat qizlarining ilm-fan egasi bo'lishlari uchun qayg'urib yozgan satrlarini keltirish o'rinli. Bugungi kun tili bilan aytganda jadidlar ham "feminist"lar bo'lishgan. Xususan Behbudiyning feministik g'oyalari alohida e'tirofga loyiq. U ayollarga ma'naviy va intellektual erkinlik berish kerak, shunchaki ayollar huquqlarini himoya qilish emas, balki ayollarning fikriy va ijtimoiy kamolotiga hissa qo'shish kerak deb hisoblagan. U feministlikni ayollarni faqat uylarga bog'lamaslik, balki ularni jamiyat, ta'lim va ish faoliyatida teng imkoniyat bilan ishtirok etish deb tushungan.

Afsus jamiyatning barcha qatlamida ayollar teng imkoniyatli deb hisoblanmaydi; Bu holat faqat rasmiy hujjatlarda emas, balki kundalik hayotimizda ham seziladi. Masalan, ayollar bilimli va tajribali bo'lishiga qaramay, ko'pincha rahbarlik lavozimlariga chiqishlariga to'sqinlik qilinadi. Ularning fikri ko'pincha "erkaklarnikidan kamroq ahamiyatli" deb baholanadi. Bundan tashqari, ijtimoiy bosim ham ayollarning erkinligini cheklaydi: ular uchun "uy ishlari", "farzand tarbiyasi" kabi masalalar birlamchi deb qaraladi, xuddi ularning hayoti faqat shunga bog'liqdek. Aslida esa, ayolning imkoniyatini cheklash — butun jamiyatning rivojiga to'siqdir. Chunki ayol faqat oila poydevori emas, balki jamiyatning har bir sohasida o'z o'rniga ega bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan shaxsdir. Bu muammolar XX asrda bor edi, XXI asrga kelib, jamiyatda sezilarli o'zgarishlar yuz bergan bo'lsa-da ayollarning to'liq tengligi masalasi hanuz dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Bugungi kunda qonunlarda tenglik belgilangan ammo, amaliy hayotda bu tenglik har doim to'liq namoyon bo'layotgani yo'q. Ayrim sohalarda ayollarning fikriga hali ham yetarlicha e'tibor berilmaydi, ularning tashabbuslari e'tiborsiz qoladi. Ba'zi hollarda esa, jamiyatda ildiz otgan an'anaviy qarashlar, stereotiplar va gender tafovutlari hali ham o'z kuchini yo'qotmagan. Natijada, ayollar o'z salohiyatini to'liq namoyon eta olmaydi, bu esa jamiyat taraqqiyotiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu ma'noda, Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy ilgari surgan g'oyalar bugun ham o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmagan. U ayollarni ma'rifatli, bilimli va mustaqil fikrlaydigan shaxs sifatida tasavvur etgan. Asarlarida ham "ayolning savodi — millatning najoti" degan g'oyani ilgari surgan.

Qatag'onlar qayirgan kuchlarlar yana biri Abdurauf Fitrat edi. U jadidchilik harakatining eng chuqur falsafiy taffakur sohibi bo'lib, insonning intellektual salohiyatini yaxshilash orqali jamiyatni isloh qilish go'yasini ilgari surgan. Fitratning faoliyati va asarlarini tahlil qilarkan, adabiyotshunos olim Turdiyev uning asosiy g'oyasi shundan iboratligini ta'kidlaydi: xalqning haqiqiy ozodligi qurol bilan emas, balki ilm, tafakkur va tarbiya orqali qo'lga kiritiladi. Bu g'oya bugungi kunda ham o'z ahamiyatini saqlab qolmoqda, chunki bugungi taraqqiyotning asosi ayna ilm va ta'lim bilan belgilanadi. Bu fikr mutlaqo to'g'ri ekanligini harbiy harakatlar, armiya yoki kuchli siyosat uchun emas, ta'limga, ma'naviy sohalarga investitsiya kiritib, barcha mamlakatlarga har tomonlama namuna bo'lib kelayotgan Yaponiya, Janubiy Korea davlatlari isbotlaydi. Shuningdek, millatning kuchi, Fitrat ta'biricha, uning o'zligini anglash va ma'naviy uyg'onishidadir. Hozirgi kunda ham O'zbekistonda milliy qadriyatlarni

asrab-avaylash, ularni zamonaviylik bilan uyg'unlashtirish masalalari dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. U ilgari surgan diniy va dunyoviy bilimlar uyg'unligi, mustqail fikrlovchi shaxsni tarbiyalash g'oyalri esa hozirgi ta'lim -tarbiya siyosatining asosiy tamoyillari bilan hamohangdir. Shu bois Fitratning ilm, ma'naviyat va tafakkur orqali jamiyatni yuksaltirish haqidagi fikrlari bugungi avlod uchun ham yo'ldi yulduz bo'lib xizmat qilmoqda.

Jadidlarning tarixi, hayoti va faoliyatini o'rganganimiz sari ular barhayot bo'laveradi, yuraklarimizning bir chetini tirnayotgan armonlar qayta gavdalanadi. Ular xotirasini abadiylashtirish, merosini asrash bo'yicha Prezidentimiz tashabbusi bilan Respublikamizda amaliy tadbirlar va loyihalar amalga oshirilmogda. Xususan, Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi O'zbek tilini rivojlantirish jamg'armasi buyurtmasiga ko'ra, Tarix instituti direktori, akademik Azamat Ziyo boshchiligida 2021–2023-yillar mobaynida Jadidlar.uz elektron platformasi tayyorlandi. Loyihani yaratishga ikki yil uchun 1 mlrd so'm grant mablag'i ajratilgan. "Bugungi kunda ham mazkur loyiha ustida ishlanyapti, uni rivojlantirishga va portal darajasiga yetkazishga harakat qilyapmiz. Ushbu elektron fond jadidlarga oid yangi ma'lumotlar bilan doimiy to'ldirib boriladi", — deydi O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi Tarix Instituti direktori o'rinbosari hamda jadidchilik harakati faol a'zosi Dilnoza Jamolova. Jadidlarning ma'rifatparvarlik va insonparvarlik g'oyalri nafaqat tarixiy xotira, balki zamonaviy taraqqiyot yo'lida yo'ldi yulduz bo'lib qoladi.

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WEDDING CEREMONIES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH CULTURE

Abstract: This article examines the wedding ceremonies of Uzbek and English cultures by comparing their historical roots, symbolic traditions, and

modern transformations and it shows how globalization is changing wedding traditions in both cultures. The purpose of this article is to show similarities and differences between the two cultures. It also explains how wedding traditions continue to change in the modern world.

Key words: Uzbek weddings, English weddings, culture, rituals, traditions, globalization, comparison, clothes, post-wedding, connection, pre-wedding, fотиha, sovchilik, qiz oshi, nikoh ceremony with an imam, Large-scale community participation, engagement, bridal shower, hen party and bachelor party, rehearsal dinner, identity, investigates.

Weddings play a central role in the cultural identity of nations. Uzbek wedding customs have been shaped by ancient Central Asian traditions, Islamic practices, and strong family bonds. English wedding traditions, however, are rooted in Christian rituals and modern Western individualism.

Uzbek wedding traditions are based on very old cultural practices. They include strong family participation in every step of the wedding. Most Uzbek weddings start with sovchilik. Sovchilik is a traditional Uzbek custom in which newly married man's family visits the marriage partner's house to formally ask for the girl's hand in marriage. When families meet and agree on marriage, then they conduct non sindirish (cut a piece of bread) event. After that, the fотиha ceremony makes the relationship official within both families. Fотиha is this kind of ceremony, which elders from girl's home give prayers and their best wishes to new bride and new bridegroom and they select one day for wedding. Then before the wedding, relatives gather for qiz oshi and other small celebrations. Qiz oshi is also most famous tradition in Uzbekistan and it held at the bride's home, family members, neighbors, and close relatives gather to celebrate the bride. Uzbek weddings often involve many guests from different parts of the community. The wedding day usually begins with registration at zags. Zags is the official government office in Uzbekistan where marriages are legally registered and the couple signs official documents, receives a marriage passport. After that, a big celebration is held with music, dancing, and traditional food. All relatives and young, old people come restaurant and celebrate, eat, dance. Plov is one of the most important dishes served during Uzbek weddings. Kelin salom is a special ritual in which the bride greets relatives with respect. Elders give blessings to the couple for a happy and successful life. Many Uzbek weddings last for several days and include several events. Gifts are exchanged between families as a sign of respect and unity. After the wedding, relatives visit the couple to welcome the bride into the family. Overall, Uzbek weddings are large, colorful, and deeply connected to family traditions.

English weddings focus more on the couple than on extended families. Most English weddings begin with an engagement chosen by the couple themselves.

Pre-wedding events usually include a bridal shower and small parties with friends. The wedding ceremony can take place in a church or in a civil registry office. In church ceremonies, vows are spoken in front of family and friends. Exchanging rings is one of the most symbolic moments of the ceremony. English

weddings usually have fewer guests than Uzbek weddings. The celebration is often held in hotels, gardens, or decorated halls. The couple's first dance is an important part of the reception. A wedding cake is presented and cut together by the bride and groom. Guests give speeches to congratulate the newly married couple. The atmosphere of English weddings is usually calm, elegant, and formal. After the wedding, many couples go on a honeymoon to celebrate privately. Thank-you cards are sent to guests as a polite tradition. Overall, English weddings highlight simplicity, elegance, and personal choice. 'There is something so special about old and trusted traditions,' Rosalie Kuyvenhoven, a leading London celebrant with a specialism in creative weddings, tells us. 'I don't think these will disappear but evolve as they adapt to modern, more inclusive times. For example, any traditions that put one half of the couple above the other or include phrases such as 'obey' are no longer relevant; couples also increasingly want to be seen as equal partners in marriage.'

There are several important similarities of Uzbek and English wedding ceremonies. Both cultures consider a wedding to be a major life event that symbolizes the start of a new family. In both traditions, the couple officially proves their corporation through a formal marriage ceremony, whether religious or civil. Families from both sides gather to celebrate, showing their support and blessings for the bride and groom. Weddings in both cultures include special clothing for the couple, with the bride wearing a beautiful dress and the groom dressed formally. Photography and videography are essential parts of both Uzbek and English weddings, as families want to keep the memories of the day. Music and dancing also play a significant role in creating an amazing atmosphere during the celebration. Gift-giving is another shared tradition, where guests bring presents to support the newly married couple. Both cultures punctuate hospitality, providing that guests enjoy food, entertainment, and a pleasant celebration. Ultimately, weddings in both Uzbekistan and England express shared human values, such as love, togetherness, support, understanding and the hope for a happy future for the couple.

Conclusion: The ceremonies reflect the values of care, respect, and mutual understanding between partners. English weddings are simpler and focus more on the couple itself. Weddings of Uzbekistan are usually big and include many guests and relatives and weddings of English culture are smaller and more formal. Weddings in both Uzbekistan and England mark the joyful start of a shared journey for the couple.

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THE CHARACTERISTICS OF SERVANTS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Annotation: In this article we have emphasizes on the significant servant roles in English literature in 19th century. The ways of description and the relationship of servants with their masters are implemented in this article as well.

Key words: moral compasses, class divisions, cultural anxieties, social standing.

Introduction. In 19th century English literature, the portrayal of servants depicts much about the social structures, class divisions, and cultural anxieties of the time. As the century unfolded, the role of the servant in literature evolved from a simple background figure to a more complex and mostly symbolic character, reflecting the tensions between the aristocracy and the rising middle class, as well as the changing roles of gender and class within British society.

Servants as Symbols of Class and Social Hierarchy:

In much of 19th century English literature, servants show the rigid class system that governed British society. The very establishment of a servant class was integral to the maintenance of social order, and authors often used these characters to highlight the disparities between the wealthy elite and the working poor. Servants were seen as an significant part of the social fabric, yet their lives were often depicted as invisible or subordinated to the needs of their masters.

In novels by authors such as Charles Dickens and Jane Austen, servants often serve as a mirror to the values, traditions and behaviors of their employers. In *Pride and Prejudice* (1813), for example, the interactions between the Bennet family and their servants subtly reflect the family's moral and social standing. While the Bennets are portrayed as struggling with finances and maintaining an air of genteel respectability, the comparison between the upper-class protagonists and their lower-class servants highlights issues of power, status, and privilege.

Dickens, known for his vivid social commentary, frequently used servant characters to explore the stark divisions between the rich and the poor. In *Oliver Twist* (1837-1839), the character of Mr. Brownlow's housekeeper, or in *Great Expectations* (1860-1861) with characters like Joe Gargery, reveal how individuals within the servant class could be both compassionate and morally upright, yet still bound by the constraints of their social roles. These characters often embody the virtues of loyalty, patience, and service, but are also portrayed as deserving of recognition and dignity.

Main part. The Servant as a Moral Compass:

In addition to serving as symbols of social order, servants often act as moral compasses in 19th century literature. Their positions in society gave them a unique vantage point from which they could observe the foibles and flaws of their

masters. Often possessing greater moral clarity or emotional insight, servants could see through the pretensions of the upper class. This sense of perspective allowed them to provide wisdom, guidance, or even commentary on the hypocrisy and superficiality of the wealthy.

In *Jane Eyre* (1847) by Charlotte Brontë, the character of Adele Varens' governess, Madame Reisz, serves as a foil to the more materialistic values of the higher social classes. Similarly, Jane herself, while never fully a servant, takes on domestic roles in several parts of the narrative. Her journey reflects both personal growth and an evolving critique of social conventions, especially regarding the roles of women and the servant class. As she ascends from a position of dependency to one of independence and moral agency, Jane's experiences illustrate the inherent tensions between service and self-assertion.

Changing Gender Roles and the Servant's Identity:

The role of female servants in 19th century literature is particularly significant because it reflects the complex intersections of gender, class, and power. In works like *North and South* (1854-1855) by Elizabeth Gaskell, female servants often find themselves trapped within a cycle of low wages, hard labor, and societal expectations of their subservience. Yet, these characters also experience moments of autonomy and power that complicate traditional notions of servitude.

In Gaskell's novel, the character of Bessy Higgins represents the struggles of working-class women, including female servants, who experience the double burden of domestic labor and societal undervaluation.

In contrast, characters such as Mrs. Thornton, who is a woman of the upper class but also involved in the management of her household and business affairs, illustrate the broader gender dynamics at play. Female servants, in particular, were often portrayed as the moral backbone of households, performing duties both menial and emotional, which contributed to the moral education and stability of their employers.

Servants and the Emergence of the "Other".

Another recurring theme is the servant as "the other" – a marginalized figure whose experiences are often defined by their relationship to the more privileged classes. The servant's life, particularly in the Victorian era, was often one of isolation, obscurity, and sometimes silent rebellion. In novels like *Wuthering Heights* (1847) by Emily Brontë, Heathcliff's rise from servant to master reflects the destabilization of traditional class hierarchies and the fluidity of social mobility. Yet, despite his ascent, Heathcliff's treatment of his servants and the people around him reveals the darker, more destructive aspects of his character, suggesting that the class struggle is never entirely resolved and always permeates the social fabric.

This theme of the "other" can also be seen in the portrayal of servants as exotic or foreign figures. For example, in *The Moonstone* (1868) by Wilkie Collins, the servant characters often possess backgrounds that are outside the dominant

Anglo-Saxon identity, challenging ideas of national and racial purity and raising questions about the intersections of imperialism and domestic servitude.

Conclusion

The role of servants in 19th century English literature serves as a crucial lens through which authors explored complex social dynamics, class relations, and personal identity. Whether as symbols of class structure, moral guides, or figures of resistance, servants were central to many of the era's most significant literary works. These characters were not merely background figures; rather, they embodied the contradictions and conflicts inherent in the class-driven society of the time. Through their stories, 19th century literature offers a nuanced understanding of the socio-economic forces that shaped both the lives of the privileged and the marginalized, giving voice to those who often remained silent in the larger narrative of the era.

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IDENTITY, VULNERABILITY AND GENDERED CONFLICT IN JOYCE CAROL OATES'S "WHERE ARE YOU GOING, WHERE HAVE YOU BEEN?"

Abstract. This article analyzes Joyce Carol Oates's short story "Where Are You Going, Where Have You Been?" through a feminist psychoanalytic perspective. It argues that Connie's identity struggle reflects the pressures adolescent girls faced in mid-twentieth-century America. Through an examination of appearance-based self-worth, family expectations, and the coercive masculinity embodied by Arnold Friend, this study demonstrates how societal norms shape and endanger the development of young women's autonomy.

Key words. Identity, Vulnerability, and Gendered Conflict in Joyce Carol Oates's "Where Are You Going, Where Have You Been?"

Joyce Carol Oates's (1966) short story "Where Are You Going, Where Have You Been?" presents a complex portrait of adolescent girlhood in a culture shaped by patriarchal expectations. Connie, the fifteen-year-old protagonist, embodies the tension many young women experience as they navigate social pressures that define their worth through beauty, compliance, and desirability. This article argues that Connie's identity crisis is a product of her family's expectations, her dependence on external validation, and the manipulative threat represented by Arnold Friend. Through Connie's psychological journey, Oates illustrates how fragile autonomy can become when shaped by dominant gender norms.

Adolescent Identity Formation and Self-Perception

Connie's self-perception is built upon the attention she receives from others, especially men. Oates (1966) emphasizes Connie's reliance on her reflection, not merely as a sign of vanity but as a symbol of her uncertain identity. The mirror serves as a space where she negotiates her public persona and her private insecurities. Gilligan's (1982) research suggests that many adolescent girls learn to tie their self-worth to approval from their peers, which supports Oates's depiction of Connie's fragile self-image. Connie's confidence is thus externally constructed, making her identity unstable and easily influenced by societal standards of femininity.

Family Norms and Gendered Expectations

Connie's family environment intensifies her internal conflict. Her mother's constant comparisons to her older sister June reinforce gender norms that value obedience and responsibility over individuality. Chodorow (1978) explains that mothers often transmit traditional gender expectations based on their own social conditioning. In Connie's case, these expectations limit her emotional expression and push her toward seeking validation outside the home. Her growing desire for independence is intertwined with a sense of isolation, exposing her to risks she is not yet equipped to navigate.

Predatory Masculinity and the Erosion of Autonomy

Arnold Friend's intrusion into Connie's life represents the dangers posed by manipulative masculinity. His charismatic yet unsettling behavior mirrors the predatory male figures discussed by Coulthard (2012), who argues that Oates's fiction frequently reveals the psychological vulnerabilities of young women. Arnold's insistence on control, combined with his knowledge of Connie's personal life, gradually breaks down her resistance. Butler's (1990) theory of gender performance helps explain Connie's reaction: girls are often socialized to appear agreeable and compliant even when they feel unsafe. Connie's final decision to step toward Arnold illustrates how identity shaped by external pressures can collapse under coercion. Oates's story reveals how identity formation for adolescent girls is shaped by cultural expectations that prioritize appearance, politeness, and male approval. Connie's internal conflict exposes the emotional burden of navigating these expectations in a family environment that

offers little emotional support. Her encounter with Arnold Friend demonstrates how quickly autonomy can unravel when identity is constructed under patriarchal constraints. The relevance of Oates's critique persists today, as discussions about gender continue to highlight the psychological consequences of restrictive norms on young women's development.

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BUYUK BRITANIYADAGI NASRONIY ZIYARATGOHLAR TOPONIMLARINING ETIMOLOGIK TAHLILI

Annotation. This study offers a comparative etymological analysis of sacred place names from several well-known Christian pilgrimage sites in Britain, including Holywell, St Albans, Bury St Edmunds, and Padstow. In both regions, toponyms reflect layers of religious memory, local linguistic heritage, and cultural identity. The British toponyms examined in this study similarly encode concepts of sanctity, purification, and miraculous origins. Names such as *Holywell* and *St Albans* incorporate linguistic elements from Old English, Latin, and Brittonic Celtic, reflecting the region's long Christian history and multilingual past. The analysis draws on the Domesday Book (1086) and other historical records to trace the development of these names and their connection to local hagiographic traditions. The comparison reveals that, although shaped by different religious frameworks—Sufism in Central Asia and Christianity in Britain—these toponyms share a common symbolic function: they preserve spiritual narratives, mark sites of pilgrimage, and embody community perceptions of sacred space. Thus, sacred place names function not only as linguistic units but also as repositories of collective memory and cultural worldview.

Keywords: Toponymy, Etymology, Pilgrimage Sites, Sufis, Christianity, Domesday Book, Naqshbandi Order

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot Buyuk Britaniyaning bir qator nasroniy ziyoratgohlari toponimlarini qiyosiy-etimologik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qiladi. Har bir hududning joy nomlari diniy qatlam, tarixiy xotira va mahalliy til

an'analarining o'zaro qo'shilishidan shakllangan bo'lib, ular muayyan jamiyatning ruhiy-madaniy tajribasini aks ettiradi.

Britaniyadagi Holywell, St Albans, Bury St Edmunds va Padstow kabi ziyoratgohlar esa nasroniy avliyolari nomi hamda "muqaddas", "pok", "bulok" kabi diniy va tabiatga oid qadimgi birliklardan kelib chiqqan. Tadqiqotda ularning etimologiyasi Domesday Book va boshqa tarixiy yozma manbalar asosida qayta ko'rib chiqiladi. Tahlil shuni ko'rsatadiki, bu toponimlar ham Xo'japorso misolida bo'lgani kabi ruhiy poklanish, shahidlik, mo'jiza va avliyo sha'ni bilan bog'liq ma'nolarga ega, ammo ular ingliz-sakson, kelt va lotin tillarining aralashuvi ostida shakllangan. Natijada, ziyoratgoh toponimlari turli madaniy kontekstlarda diniy qadriyatlar, tabiiy manzara va tarixiy jarayonlarning uzviy birikmasi sifatida talqin qilinadi.

Kalit So'zlar: Toponimiya, Etimologiya, Ziyoratgohlar, Sufiylar, Nasroniylik, Domesday Book,

Toponimlar (joy nomlari) har qanday madaniyatning ruhiy va tarixiy o'ziga xosligini aks ettiruvchi muhim element hisoblanadi. O'zbekistonning Buxoro viloyati Vobkent tumanidagi Xo'japorso qishlog'i nomi sufiy an'analari bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, «xo'ja» (forscha «xo'jayin, boshliq») va «porso» («pok, xudojo'y») komponentlaridan tashkil topgan, ya'ni «xudojo'y xo'jalar yashaydigan joy» ma'nosini bildiradi. Boshqa talqin bo'yicha, bu Naqshbandiya tariqati peshvolaridan Muhammad Porso (Xo'ja Porso, 1363–1419) nomi bilan bog'lanadi, uning qadamjosi Vobkentda mavjud. Bu nom xalq etimologiyasiga asoslangan bo'lib, diniy shaxslar va poklik ramzlarini birlashtiradi.

Xuddi shunday, Buyuk Britaniyada (asosan Angliya va Uelsda) nasroniy ziyoratgohlar toponimlari ham avliyolar (saints) nomi, "muqaddas" (holy) yoki "pok" (pure) ma'nosidagi komponentlar orqali shakllangan. Ushbu tezisda Holywell, St Albans, Bury St Edmunds va Padstow ziyoratgohlarining etimologik tahlili keng ko'rib chiqiladi. Tahlil Domesday Book (1086-yilgi Angliya yer ro'yxati) va boshqa tarixiy manbalarga asoslanadi. Qiyosiy jihatdan, bu toponimlar Xo'japorso'ga o'xshab, diniy shaxslar nomi va ruhiy poklanish ramzlarini o'z ichiga oladi, ammo nasroniy kontekstda Rim-sakson va kelt tillarining ta'sirida evolyutsiya qilgan.

Holywell nomi nasroniy ziyoratgohlarining eng yorqin misollaridan biri bo'lib, uning etimologik tahlili inglizcha va uelscha komponentlarga bo'linadi. Holywell toponimi "holy" qadimgi inglizcha "halig" – muqaddas, pok ma'nosini anglatadi va bu so'z german tillar oilasiga kiruvchi qadimgi saksonga "*hālig*"dan kelib chiqqan, "to'liq, butun" degan ma'noni bildiradi va keyinchalik diniy kontekstda "muqaddas" ma'nosiga o'tgan. "Well" esa qadimgi inglizcha "welle" – bulak, quduq ma'nosini anglatib, proto-german "*wellō*"dan olingan, ya'ni "oqim, manba" ma'nosida, tabiiy suv manbalarini ifodalaydi. Natijada, Holywell toponimi "muqaddas quduq" ma'nosini bildiradi, ziyoratchilar ruhiy poklanish uchun keladigan joyni ifodalaydi. Birinchi yozma qayd 1093-yilda "Haliwel" shaklida, Chester abbatligiga sovg'a sifatida tilga olingan. Inglizcha

komponentlar o'rta asr nasroniylikda "holy well" iborasining standart shakli bo'lib, Britaniyada 200 dan ortiq shunga o'xshash joylarni nomlagan. Bu termin nasroniy avliyo afsonalarida markaziy o'rin tutadi, chunki ko'plab afsonalarda muqaddas suv manbalari avliyolarning qonidan yoki mo'jizasidan paydo bo'lgan deb tasvirlanadi. Masalan, Holywelldagi afsonaga ko'ra, VII asrdagi avliyo Uinfred (St Winefride) boshi kesilgach, uning qoni oqgan joydan pok suv buloq chiqqan bo'lib, bu suv bugungi kunda ham ziyoratchilar tomonidan shifo va ruhiy poklanish uchun ishlatiladi, shunga o'xshash afsonalar Britaniyada 200 dan ortiq "holy well" nomli joylarda uchraydi. Shu bilan birga, bu termin ziyoratgohlarning ijtimoiy ahamiyatini kuchaytiradi, chunki ular nafaqat diniy marosimlar markazi, balki jamiyatdagi shifo izlovchilar (kasallikdan xalos bo'lishga umid qiluvchi odamlar), mo'jiza izlovchilar (avliyo yordami bilan hayotiy muammolarni hal qilmoqchi bo'lganlar) va hatto iqtisodiy sayyohlarning to'planish joyi bo'lib xizmat qiladi, o'rta asrlarda bunday ziyoratgohlar atrofida shaharlar rivojlanib, savdo va jamoaviy yig'ilishlar kuchaygan. Etimologik jihatdan, "holy" komponenti lotincha "sanctus" (muqaddas, pok) so'zining ta'sirida evolyutsiya qilgan bo'lib, Rim imperiyasi davrida nasroniylik Britaniyaga kimgach, lotincha terminlar mahalliy tillarga singib ketgan; ammo uning asosiy saksoncha ildizlari mahalliy ruhiy ifodani ta'minlaydi, ya'ni nasroniy ta'sir ostida ham Britaniya aholisining qadimiy tabiatga bog'liq poklanish an'analarini (masalan, suv va tabiiy manbalarga ishonch) saqlab qolgan. Inglizcha komponentlar o'rta asr nasroniylikda "holy well" iborasining standart shakli bo'lib, Britaniyada 200 dan ortiq shunga o'xshash joylarni nomlagan. Bu termin nasroniy avliyo afsonalarida markaziy o'rin tutadi va ziyoratgohlarning ijtimoiy ahamiyatini kuchaytiradi.

St Albans (Angliya, Xertfordshir): Avliyo Alban Joyi – Shahidlik Va Rim Merosi

St Albans nomi nasroniy ziyoratgohlarining eng muhim va qadimiy misollaridan biri bo'lib, Britaniyaning birinchi shahidi Avliyo Alban bilan bog'liq bo'lgan bu joy nasroniylikning Rim davridan keyingi evolyutsiyasini aks ettiradi. Uning etimologik tahlili asosan inglizcha va qadimgi brittoncha (keltcha) komponentlarga bo'linadi, chunki shahar nomi Rim shahri Verulamiumdan kelib chiqqan va keyinchalik avliyo nomi bilan almashtirilgan. St Albans toponimi "St" qisqartmasi lotincha "sanctus" – muqaddas, pok ma'nosini anglatib, bu so'z Rim imperiyasi davrida nasroniylik Evropaga tarqalgach, mahalliy tillarga singib ketgan va o'rta asrlarda inglizcha "saint" so'zining standart qisqartmasi sifatida ishlatilgan, ya'ni diniy shaxs yoki avliyoni ifodalaydi. "Albans" esa Alban nomi bo'lib, bu komponent qadimgi brittoncha (keltcha) "Verlamion" – botqoq ustidagi yoki botqoq yaqinidagi aholi punkti degan ma'noni bildiradi; "ver" (botqoq) va "lamion" (aholi punkti yoki joylashuv) so'zlaridan tashkil topgan bo'lib, temir davri (miloddan avvalgi 20-yillardan) Verlamion nomli kelt qabilasi markaziga ishora qiladi va Rim davrida Verulamium shahriga o'tgan. Natijada, St Albans toponimi "Avliyo Alban joyi" yoki "muqaddas shahid aholi punkti" ma'nosini bildiradi, nasroniylikning ilk markazlaridan biri sifatida ruhiy va shahidlik ramzini ifodalaydi. Birinchi yozma qayd VIII asrdagi Venerable Bede'ning

“Angl-saksonlar cherkovi tarixi” asarida keltirilgan bo’lib, unda Albanning shahidligi batafsil tasvirlangan; ammo Domesday Book (1086-yil) da “Albanestou” shaklida, Hertfordshire okrugida 91 oila ro’yxatga olingan holda tilga olingan, bu yerda abbey va shahar muqaddaslik ramzi sifatida qayd etilgan. Inglizcha komponentlar o’rta asr nasroniyligida “St” iborasining standart shakli bo’lib, Britaniyada 1000 dan ortiq shunga o’xshash joylarni (masalan, St Andrews, St David’s) nomlagan. Bu termin nasroniy avliyo afsonalarida markaziy o’rin tutadi, chunki ko’plab afsonalarda shahidlik va mo’jizalar avliyolarning qonidan paydo bo’lgan suv manbalari yoki tabiiy hodisalar bilan bog’langan deb tasvirlanadi. Masalan, St Albansdagi afsonaga ko’ra, III–IV asrlarda Verulamium shahrida yashagan Alban Rim askarlari tomonidan ta’qib qilinayotgan nasroniy ruhoni (keyinchalik Amphibalus deb nomlangan) ni yashirgan; ruhoniyning ibodati va sadoqatini ko’rib, Alban nasroniylikni qabul qilgan va ruhoni o’rniga o’zini hibsga olgan askarlarga topshirgan. Sud oldida butparast qurbonliklarga rad etib, “Men hamma narsani yaratgan haqiqiy va tirik Xudoga sajda qilaman” deb e’tiqodini himoya qilgan Alban qamchilangan, ammo sabr bilan chidagan va bosh kesish jazosiga hukm etilgan. Jazoga olib ketilayotganda, Ver daryosi ko’prikini to’sib qo’ygan suv oqimi oldida to’xtagan; Alban osmon tomon qarab duo qilgach, daryo qurib, quruq yerda o’tish mumkin bo’lgan. Keyin, gullar bilan bezatilgan tepalikda (Holywell Hill) suv so’rab duo qilganda, uning oyoqi ostidan buloq chiqqan; birinchi jallod mo’jizani ko’rib, konversiya qilib, Alban bilan birga o’lishni xohlagan va o’ldirilgan, ikkinchi jallodning ko’zlari tushib qolgan. Alban bosh kesilgach, boshi pastga dumalab, to’xtagan joydan yana bir buloq chiqqan deb afsona qilinadi; bu suv bugungi kunda ham ziyoratchilar tomonidan shifo va ruhiy poklanish uchun ishlatiladi, shunga o’xshash afsonalar Britaniyada 100 dan ortiq shahidlik joylarida uchraydi. Shu bilan birga, bu termin ziyoratgohlarning ijtimoiy ahamiyatini kuchaytiradi, chunki ular nafaqat diniy marosimlar markazi, balki jamiyatdagi shifo izlovchilar (kasallikdan xalos bo’lishga umid qiluvchi odamlar), mo’jiza izlovchilar (avliyo yordami bilan hayotiy muammolarni hal qilmoqchi bo’lganlar) va hatto iqtisodiy sayyohlarning to’planish joyi bo’lib xizmat qiladi, o’rta asrlarda bunday ziyoratgohlar atrofida shaharlar rivojlanib, savdo va jamoaviy yig’ilishlar kuchaygan – masalan, St Albans abbeyi XIII asrda Angliyaning eng boy abbatliklaridan biri bo’lgan va savdo yo’llari (Watling Street) orqali London bilan bog’langan. Etimologik jihatdan, “St” komponenti lotincha “sanctus” (muqaddas, pok) so’zining ta’sirida evolyutsiya qilgan bo’lib, Rim imperiyasi davrida nasroniylik Britaniyaga kimgach, lotincha terminlar mahalliy tillarga singib ketgan; ammo uning asosiy kelt-saksoncha ildizlari (qadimgi brittoncha “Verlamion” – botqoq yaqinidagi aholi va saksonga “cæstir” – qal’a) mahalliy ruhiy ifodani ta’minlaydi, ya’ni nasroniy ta’sir ostida ham Britaniya aholisining qadimiy shahidlik va tabiatga bog’liq poklanish an’analarini (masalan, buloq va tepalikdagi mo’jizalar) saqlab qolgan.

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REFLECTION OF "FREEDOM" CONCEPT IN 20TH CENTURY JADID LITERATURE

Annotation: *The article is devoted to the study of the role of literature of the early 20th century in Uzbekistan, known as "Jadid literature", in the process of spiritual and intellectual liberation of the people. The views of writers and thinkers, such as Abdulla Avloniy, on the problem of education and science as ways to overcome social inequality and religious conservatism are considered. It is shown how literary works of that time contributed to the formation of new views on freedom and justice, becoming the basis for subsequent social transformations. The article focuses on the importance of artistic words in changing public consciousness and preparing conditions for future generations.*

Key words: *content analysis, semantic analysis, historical and cultural context, comparative method, Mashruta.*

Introduction. It is known that the Uzbek literature of the early 20th century is called "Jadid literature". It was during this period that the Jadids, who took education and science as a beacon to lead the people, who had been mired in the swamp of illiteracy, ignorance, slavery, and dependence for a long time, to freedom, created a number of works with the aim of cultivating national spirituality. These works were in the spirit of leading the people to freedom and giving the country independence, and the Jadids began to instill these ideas into the consciousness of the nation, first secretly, and later openly. In his autobiography, Abdulla Avloni describes the complex social situation of that time as follows: "We began a determined struggle against the mullahs and the rich, as well as against the old way of life. Our own organization against the mullahs also emerged among us. We continued in this class struggle until 1905. The mullahs and the rich fought against the Jadids, and the Jadids fought against the mullahs and the rich, and against old-fashionedness and superstition..."¹

Methods. The following methods were used to analyze the presented material:

1. Content analysis: A detailed analysis of the text of poems and historical documents was conducted in order to identify key concepts and symbols associated with the concept of freedom. Particular attention was paid to the interpretation of images and symbols used by the authors.

2. Semantic analysis: The semantic fields of the concepts of "freedom" and "liberation" identified in literary works were examined. Key metaphors and symbols used to express the idea of freedom were identified.

3. Comparative method: A comparative analysis of various works created by representatives of the Jadid movement was conducted to identify common features and characteristics of the perception of freedom in the literature of that era.

Results. The study showed that the concept of freedom in Uzbek literature of the early 20th century had a deep philosophical and aesthetic meaning and was expressed through a variety of artistic and literary means. The main results are presented below:

1. Symbolism of the image of a "free cypress". The image of "sarvi ozod" was used to convey the idea of independence and the desire for freedom. This comparison symbolized rising above the ordinary and traditions, the desire to stand out and express one's personality.

2. Conceptual metaphors of freedom. The analysis of the poetic heritage showed the use of a number of metaphors reflecting the perception of freedom: the world of happiness ("dildor olam"), the bright path ("ravshanlik"), the garden

¹ N.Karimov, S.Mamajonov, B.Nazarov, U.Normatov, O.Sharafiddinov. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti (universitetlar va pedagogika institutlari bakalavr ixtisosini oluvchilar uchun darslik). – Toshkent, O'qituvchi. 1999.

of flowers ("guliston"). Such images indicate a positive perception of freedom as a necessary condition for a happy and fulfilling life.

3. The ideology of the newspaper "Shukhrat". The newspaper, founded under the leadership of Avloni, served as a means of promoting progressive ideas and advocated freedom of the press and speech. It occupied an important place in the development of the democratic press in the region.

Analysis. At that time, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi was among the first to begin to cultivate the spirituality of the people through his poem " Millatga xitob", which was sung to the tune of national songs:

*Ko'zlarining och, ey millat, ko'p zamon g'ofil yotding,
Umring o'tdi yotmakda, qayg'uga toza botding.*

In the scenario of the 20th century, in the thinking of the Jadids, the ideas of "freedom" and "liberty" were associated with the frameworks of science, education, and culture. In particular, in the work of Muhammad Aminkhodja Mukimi, it is possible to create a unique semantic field for the concept of "freedom".

*Bog' aro, jono, o'shal kim jilva bunyod aylading,
Kabk ila tovusni raftoringga minkod aylading.
Maqsading shamshod shoxin bo'lmasa rap sindirish,
Qomatingni muncha mundoq sarvi ozod aylading.*

In this ghazal titled "Farhod Aylading", the combination "sarvi ozod" expresses the meanings of "beautiful figure" and "dry". It is known that in literary works, the yor qomati is likened to the "cypress" tree. The compound "sarvi ozod" means a tree that stands out from other cypresses.

Discussion. Research has shown that the literature of Uzbekistan in the early twentieth century, known as "Jadid literature," played an important role in the process of spiritual and intellectual liberation of the people. This period was characterized by active use of art and literature to educate a new generation, particularly focusing on combating outdated traditions and religious prejudices. Authors like Abdulla Avloniy urged the people to strive for knowledge and scientific advancement, recognizing that education could lead to emancipation from oppression and dependency.

To conclude, it should be noted that the Jadids' extensive use of literature and journalism contributed significantly to changing public awareness and laying the groundwork for subsequent societal transformations. Their works have become an essential component of cultural heritage and continue to influence contemporary society.

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INGLIZ MEDIA DISKURSIDA LEKSIK-SINTAKTIK INTENSIFIKATORLARNING MANIPULYATIV XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezis ingliz media diskursida leksik-sintaktik intensivatorlarning manipulyativ funksiyalarini lingvopragmatik va funksional-diskursiv yondashuv asosida tadqiq etadi. Zamonaviy ingliz ommaviy axborot vositalarida axborotning tezkorligi, o'quvchi e'tiborini jalb qilish zarurati va auditoriya ustidan ta'sir o'tkazishga qaratilgan strategiyalar intensivatorlarning qo'llanishini keskin kuchaytirgan.

Kalit so'zlar: leksik-sintaktik intensivatorlar, media diskurs, baholovchilik, drammatizatsiya, framing, OAV tili.

Kirish. Globallashuv sharoitida ommaviy axborot vositalari jamiyatning siyosiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy hayotini shakllantiruvchi eng kuchli kommunikativ institutlardan biriga aylandi. Media matnlarda til vositalari nafaqat axborotni yetkazish, balki uni ma'lum ideologik va emotsional kontekstda talqin qilish orqali auditoriya ongiga ta'sir ko'rsatish funksiyasini bajaradi¹. Shu jihatdan, media diskursda baholovchilik, drammatizatsiya, framing va e'tibor boshqaruvi kabi strategiyalar tilning o'ziga xos stilistik hamda pragmatik vositalari orqali amalga oshiriladi. Ingliz media matnlarida leksik va sintaktik intensivatorlarning qo'llanishi aynan shunday manipulyativ strategiyalarning muhim tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Leksik intensivatorlar-really, absolutely, extremely kabi birliklar matnning emotsional kuchini oshiradi, baholovchilikni

¹ Fairclough, N. (1995). Media discourse. London: Edward Arnold.

kuchaytiradi va o'quvchining voqelikni qabul qilishiga bilvosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi¹. Shu bilan birga, inversiya, takror va qisqa gaplar kabi sintaktik konstruksiyalar matnni dramatik ta'sirga ega qilishi, urg'uni kuchaytirishi va auditoriyaning diqqatini kerakli nuqtaga yo'naltirishi mumkin. Tilshunoslikning lingvopragmatika, funksional stilistika va diskurs tahlil yo'nalishlari media tilining manipulyativ tabiatini chuqur tushuntirib beradi. Xususan, manipulyativlik auditoriyaning bilish jarayoniga bevosita ta'sir o'tkazishga qaratilgan til vositalarining maqsadli qo'llanishi sifatida talqin qilinadi². Media diskursida intensifikatorlarning subyektivlashtirish, drammatizatsiya, framingni kuchaytirish va auditoriyada emotsional reaksiya uyg'otishdagi o'rni aynan shu pragmatik mexanizmlar bilan bog'liq. Shunga qaramay, ingliz media diskursida leksik-sintaktik intensifikatorlarning funksional yuklamasi, semantik-pragmatik xususiyatlari va manipulyativ effekti hali ham keng ko'lamda kompleks o'rganilmagan.

Metodologiya. Tadqiqotda media matnlarining ko'p qatlamli tahlilini ta'minlash maqsadida bir nechta zamonaviy lingvistik metodlar qo'llanildi. Diskurs tahlili-media matnlarining ideologik, kommunikativ va kontekstual xususiyatlarini aniqlash uchun Fairclough (1995) va van Dijk (2006) nazariyalariga tayangan holda amalga oshirildi. Stilistik tahlil-sintaktik konstruksiyalarning ekspressiv va estetik funksiyalari stilistika tamoyillariga tayangan holda tahlil qilindi. Korpus tahlili-media matnlaridan tuzilgan kichik korpus asosida intensifikatorlarning chastotasi va qo'llanish turlari aniqlanadi. Komponent va kontekstual tahlil-intensifikatorlar qo'llangan kontekstlarda ma'no kuchayishi, emotsional fon, baholovchilik va manipulyativlik darajasi aniqlanadi.

Quyida leksik va sintaktik intensifikatorlar bo'yicha real ingliz media misollarini I.R. Galperinning "Stylistics" asaridagi stilistik vositalar tasnifi asosida tahlil qilib ko'ramiz. Tahlillar Galperinning quyidagi asosiy kategoriyalariga tayangan holda sharhlab beriladi. Emphatic constructions (kuchaytiruvchilar), Repetition, Parallel construction, Inversion, Climax va Anticlimax, Metaphorical intensification, Rhetorical devices (emotive language, evaluative epithet).

1-Misol "The storm caused extremely serious damage, leaving thousands absolutely terrified." (BBC News). Leksik intensifikatorlar-extremely, absolutely. Galperin (1971) bularni emphatic words yoki intensifiers turiga kiritadi. Ular inson hissiy kechinmasini kuchaytirish, sub'ektiv bahoni oshirish uchun xizmat qiladi. extremely serious-baholovchilikni keskin oshiradi, drammatizatsiya effekti yaratadi, absolutely terrified-holatning ekstremal darajada ekanini ko'rsatadi, emotsional reaksiyani kuchaytiradi. Terrified-Galperin tasnifida emotive meaning

¹ Paradis, C. (2008). Configurations, construals and change: Expressions of degree. *English Language and Linguistics*, 12(2), 317–343.

² van Dijk, T. A. (2006). Discourse and manipulation. *Discourse & Society*, 17(3), 359–383.

yaratadigan leksik birlik bo'lib, matnning hissiy fonini oshiradi. Bu kontekst o'quvchi ongida kuchli xavotir hissini uyg'otadi va voqea "katastrofik" ko'rinishda talqin qilinishiga sabab bo'ladi.

2-misol "*The city was completely destroyed, and the government response was shockingly slow.*"(CNN). Intensifikatorlar-completely, shockingly, completely destroyed-intensification through adverb voqeani maksimal darajada qayd etadi. Shockingly slow-evaluative adverb + adjective modeli sub'ektiv baho kuchaytiriladi. Shockingly slow baholovchi epitet bo'lib, hukumatning harakati haqida salbiy konnotatsiya yaratadi. Climax elementi-gap ichida "destroyed" "shockingly slow" ketma-ketligi dramatik kuchayish hosil qiladi.

3-misol "*Never before has the country faced such an incredibly dangerous situation.*"(The Guardian) Inversion (Sintaktik intensifikator) Never before has the country. . . Galperin inversiyani emphatic construction deb tasniflaydi. Bu struktura urg'uni "misli ko'rilmaganlik"ga qaratadi. Incredibly dangerous-bu uyushma kuchli emotsional-estimativ qiymatga egadir. "Never before"+"incredibly" kombinatsiyasi matnni maksimal dramatik kontekstga olib kiradi. Manipulyativlik jihati shundaki, o'quvchi vaziyatni real holatdan ko'ra ko'proq xavfli deb talqin qilishi ehtimoli oshadi.

4-misol "*It was a disaster - a real, total, absolutely unbelievable disaster.*"(Daily Mail -tabloit uslubi). Repetition (takror) "disaster" so'zining ikki marta takrorlanishi Galperinning nazariyasiga ko'ra lexical repetition hisoblanadi. Bu vosita emotsional yuklamani kuchaytiradi. Gradation (Climax) real, total, absolutely unbelievable Gradatsiya bosqichma-bosqich kuchayadi. Har bir keyingi sifat oldingisidan kuchliroq. Bu stilistik vosita tabloit matnlariga xos bo'lib, o'quvchi ongida voqea nihoyatda falokatli tasvirlanadi, dramatzatsiya kuchayadi. Bunday vositalar matnning baholovchilik, emotsional va manipulyativ potentsialini oshiradi. **Xulosa.** Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz media diskursida leksik va sintaktik intensifikatorlarning qo'llanish xususiyatlarini, ularning semantik-pragmatik funksiyalarini va manipulyativ effektlarini aniqlashga qaratildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, media matnlarda intensifikatorlar nafaqat axborotni kuchaytiruvchi vosita sifatida, balki o'quvchi ongida hissiy va baholovchilik reaksiyalarini shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi manipulyativ strategiya sifatida faol ishlatiladi.

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THE PRAGMATIC FUNCTIONS OF RHETORICAL QUESTIONS IN ERNEST HEMINGWAY’S THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA

Abstract: This thesis explores how rhetorical questions function pragmatically in Ernest Hemingway’s novella *The Old Man and the Sea*. Although the story is known for its simple, economical style, Hemingway embeds deeper meaning beneath the surface through indirect communication strategies. One of these strategies is the use of rhetorical questions, which express Santiago’s inner conflict, emotional endurance, and moral values without explicitly stating them. Drawing on principles from speech-act theory and relevance theory, this study argues that rhetorical questions in the novella reveal the old man’s psychological condition, reinforce his ethical beliefs, create ironic contrasts, and invite readers to participate in constructing the story’s meaning. Through analysis of key examples, the thesis demonstrates that rhetorical questions play a central role in shaping the narrative’s emotional depth and philosophical message.

Key words: rhetorical questions, pragmatics, Hemingway, indirect communication, internal monologue, irony, iceberg theory

Introduction: Ernest Hemingway is widely regarded as a master of minimalist prose. His writing style is concise, unembellished, and guided by the “iceberg principle,” which suggests that most of the meaning in a story lies beneath the surface. Published in 1952, *The Old Man and the Sea* is one of his most celebrated works and tells the story of Santiago, an aging Cuban fisherman who engages in a long, exhausting struggle with a massive marlin far out at sea. Although the language of the novella appears simple, its emotional and philosophical depth is revealed through subtle techniques. One such technique is Hemingway’s use of rhetorical questions. These questions appear mostly during Santiago’s internal monologues and moments of crisis. Rather than seeking actual answers, they expose his inner struggle, moral reasoning, and reflections on life. This thesis explores the pragmatic functions of these questions and explains how they contribute to the psychological and thematic effects of the story.

Rhetorical Questions as Pragmatic Devices

Rhetorical questions are interrogative sentences that do not aim to obtain information. Instead, they express emotions, highlight dilemmas, or make implicit

statements. Pragmatically, they function as indirect speech acts: they take the form of questions but perform the role of statements or evaluations. According to relevance theory, rhetorical questions also require greater cognitive engagement from the reader, prompting them to infer meaning and participate actively in interpretation. In literary texts like Hemingway's novella, rhetorical questions guide the reader through moments of emotional tension and philosophical reflection. They create a deeper connection between the character and the audience and reveal meaning that is not explicitly stated.

Expressing Pain and Psychological Isolation

One of the strongest functions of rhetorical questions in the novella is their ability to express Santiago's physical suffering and emotional loneliness. During the battle with the marlin, the old man repeatedly questions his own body and abilities. For example, when his hand cramps painfully, he asks himself what kind of hand betrays him at such a crucial moment. The question communicates frustration, exhaustion, and helplessness without needing additional explanation. These questions also emphasize Santiago's isolation. With no one else to speak to, he turns his thoughts into questions. This creates the feeling of a man alone in the vast sea, struggling not only with the fish but with himself. The rhetorical questioning becomes a way for him to endure the silence and maintain his determination.

Revealing Moral Values and Inner Strength

Hemingway avoids direct moral commentary in his writing. Instead, he allows characters like Santiago to reveal their values through action and thought. Rhetorical questions help express these values indirectly. When Santiago wonders whether he was wrong to fight the marlin or whether pride has influenced his actions, the questions reveal his humility and self-awareness. He is not truly asking for answers; rather, he is reaffirming his belief that a person must fight with dignity and accept both victory and failure with grace. These questions show Santiago's internal conflict but also highlight his strength. By questioning himself, he evaluates his actions and reinforces his moral code. This makes the rhetorical question an essential tool for portraying his character with depth and complexity.

Creating Irony and Paradox

Rhetorical questions also contribute to the novella's ironic and paradoxical elements. At the end of the story, after losing the marlin to sharks, Santiago lies exhausted and asks himself what has defeated him. The expected answer might be the sharks or the sea, yet his reply suggests otherwise. The rhetorical question emphasizes the contrast between physical defeat and spiritual victory. Santiago's body is broken, but his will remains strong. This paradox reflects one of Hemingway's central themes: that true success lies not in the final result but in the courage to struggle.

Conclusion: Rhetorical questions in *The Old Man and the Sea* are far more than stylistic features. They serve essential pragmatic functions that shape the reader's

understanding of Santiago's character and the themes of the story. Through rhetorical questioning, Hemingway expresses pain, loneliness, moral reflection, and irony while inviting the reader to participate in interpreting the deeper meaning. These questions embody the iceberg principle, carrying emotional and philosophical weight without stating it directly. They help reveal Santiago as a man who endures hardship with dignity and remains undefeated in spirit, even when circumstances seem to overcome him. The study concludes that rhetorical questions play a significant role in creating the psychological depth and universal themes that make the novella one of Hemingway's enduring masterpieces.

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**THE ROLE OF LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL
TRANSFORMATIONS IN LITERARY TRANSLATION**

Abstract: This thesis explores the importance of lexical and grammatical shifts in literary translation. The theoretical part outlines main linguistic frameworks and classification systems of the translation shifts, while the analytical section provides examples from selected literary texts and illustrates how translators apply transformations with a view to maintaining meaning, style, and cultural nuance. The research concludes that lexical and grammatical transformations are key tools that enable translators to bridge linguistic and cultural gaps.

Keywords: Lexical transformation, grammatical transformation, literary translation, translation shifts, equivalence.

Introduction: Translation is a complex and multilayered linguistic activity requiring not only knowledge of two languages but also an understanding of how meaning changes across cultures and textual contexts. In literary translation, the translator must balance semantic accuracy with stylistic fidelity, aiming to recreate the aesthetic effect of the source text. This balance is achieved through various types of lexical and grammatical transformations. According to Catford

(74,1965), “translation shifts occur when linguistic elements in the source language are replaced with structurally different elements in the target language”. According to Catford, translation shifts occur when a translator needs alter the target language’s structure in order to preserve the source text's grammatical or lexical form. To put it another way, the translator substitutes a structurally distinct form that conveys the same meaning for a word, phrase, or grammatical pattern from the original language. Languages do not exactly match in terms of syntax, vocabulary, or syntactic norms, which causes these adjustments. Therefore, the translator modifies the structure while maintaining the original message in order to generate a natural and meaningful translation. This illustrates the fundamental notion that translation involves both word substitution and linguistic form adaptation to conform to target language norms.

Vinay and Darbelnet (94-262, 1995) similarly highlight the role of modulation, transposition, and equivalence in achieving natural and meaningful translations.

Transposition is the process of replacing one grammatical category with another without changing the meaning of the message. Vinay and Darbelnet (94, 1995) emphasize that “transposition is often necessary because languages do not share identical grammatical structures”. For example, an English adjective–noun combination may become a noun–noun structure in another language.

Example: *After his arrival. When he arrived*

(From noun phrase to clause)

Modulation involves a change in point of view, perspective, or cognitive category. Vinay and Darbelnet (247, 1995) explain that “sometimes direct translation sounds unnatural or fails to convey the correct nuance; therefore, the translator shifts the conceptual angle”.

Example: *It is not difficult to show. It is easy to show*

(Change from negative viewpoint to positive)

Equivalence refers to using a completely different expression in the target language to convey the same situation, meaning, or effect. Vinay and Darbelnet (258, 1995) argue that “this method is especially important in translating idioms, proverbs, fixed expressions, and cultural phrases”.

Example: *When pigs fly. Hech qachon* (literal form is replaced with a target-culture equivalent)

Vinay and Darbelnet pointedly emphasized that these three transformations are necessary because literal translation often does not reproduce either the stylistic or communicative purpose of the source text. For this reason, translators must adapt form and structure, point of view, and expression to produce natural, accurate, meaningful translations.

Newmark (95, 1988) argues that “lexical choices are influenced by cultural context, connotation, and stylistic norms”.

This perspective highlights that vocabulary is not a neutral set of interchangeable items, but a culturally embedded system shaped by social

experience and collective worldview. Cultural context determines how certain words carry culturally specific meanings that may not exist in another language. For instance, terms referring to social customs, traditional foods, or forms of address can evoke associations that are shared within one culture but unfamiliar to another.

Grammatical transformations shift the structure of sentences to achieve syntactic naturalness. Catford (1965) identifies class shifts, unit shifts, and intra-system shifts as essential grammatical strategies. For example, a noun phrase in the source text may be translated as a clause in the target language if required by grammatical norms.

Literary translation differs from technical or legal translation because it prioritizes aesthetic and emotional impact. Transformations help the translator preserve tone, imagery, and cultural resonance. For instance, metaphors may require modulation to ensure comprehension while maintaining stylistic richness. As Bassnett (138, 2013) notes, “literary translation is a creative act in which transformation is not simply optional but unavoidable”.

To analyze lexical transformations, a passage from a contemporary English novel was examined. In the phrase “He’d fibbed when she’d asked how he’d handled his grandmother’s desire for him to marry”, the lexical item “fibbed” has no direct equivalent in many languages. Translators often substitute it with phrases meaning “to tell a small lie”. This demonstrates substitution and reduction: the lexical nuance of “fib” is replaced with a more culturally transparent expression. As Newmark (107, 1988) states, such “substitution ensures that the pragmatic meaning is conveyed even when exact equivalence is impossible”.

Grammatical transformations are evident when translating complex English clauses into languages with different syntactic norms. For example, English often uses participial constructions, whereas other languages may require full clauses. A sentence such as “Walking down the street, he noticed the lights” may be rendered using a finite verb, illustrating unit and class shift. Catford’s (1965) classification of shifts helps explain why these changes are necessary to maintain naturalness and readability in the target text.

Most literary translations employ multiple transformations simultaneously. A metaphor such as “Her words were knives” might require lexical modulation and grammatical restructuring depending on cultural interpretability. Vinay and Darbelnet (253, 1995) emphasize that “transformations often operate in combination, producing translations that retain the emotional effect of the original”.

Conclusion: Effective literary translation is built on lexical and grammatical changes. They make it possible for the translator to communicate emotion, meaning, and subtle stylistic differences between languages. This thesis shows that transformations are crucial instruments for maintaining the integrity of literary works rather than just technical modifications through theoretical

investigation and analytical instances. The significance of transformation-based tactics will only increase as language and culture change.

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MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTDA INGLIZ TILINING O'RNI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilining madaniyatlararo muloqotdagi o'rni yoritilgan. Ingliz tilining global aloqa vositasi sifatidagi ahamiyati, ta'lim, biznes, ilm-fan va xalqaro hamkorlikdagi funksiyalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, madaniy kompetensiya va muloqot madaniyatining ahamiyati ko'rsatib berilgan. Maqola ingliz tilini puxta o'rganishning talabalarga raqobatbardoshlik va global fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishdagi o'rnini asoslaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: Madaniyatlararo muloqot, global kommunikatsiya, til kompetensiyasi, interkultural aloqa, globallashuv, raqobatbardoshlik

Globallashuv jarayonlari jamiyatlar, xalqlar va madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi aloqalarning jadallashuviga sabab bo'lmoqda. Bunday sharoitda madaniyatlararo muloqotga kirishish, o'z fikrini dunyo hamjamiyatiga aniq yetkazish va turli millat vakillari bilan samarali aloqa o'rnatish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ingliz tili esa ushbu jarayonning asosiy vositasi sifatida e'tirof etilib, bugungi kunda "global kommunikatsiya tili" maqomiga ega bo'lgan. Mazkur maqolada aynan shu til tizimining jahon sahnasidagi mavqei, uning inson faoliyatining turli qatlamlariga ta'siri, shuningdek, yosh avlod uchun keltiradigan amaliy ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tilning jamiyatlararo yaqinlashuvdagi vazifasi, tafakkur shakllanishidagi roli va zamonaviy shaxs rivojidadagi o'rni ilmiy-nazariy yondashuv asosida yoritib beriladi.

Asosiy qism

Hozirgi kunda ingliz tili 1,5 milliarddan ortiq aholi tomonidan ona yoki chet tili sifatida qo'llanadi. Xalqaro siyosat, iqtisodiy diplomatiya, biznes, ilm-fan, texnologiya, internet va ta'lim tizimida ingliz tilidan foydalanish darajasi muttasil oshib bormoqda. Shu bois ingliz tilini bilish dunyo bilan raqobatbardosh muloqotga kirishishning asosiy sharti hisoblanadi.

Madinayatlarda muloqotda ingliz tilining funksiyalari:

1. Aloqa vositasi sifatida.

Turli madaniyat vakillari o'rtasida o'zaro tushunishni ta'minlaydi, fikr almashish jarayonini osonlashtiradi.[1]

2. Madaniyatlararo tushunishni shakllantiradi.

Ingliz tili orqali boshqa xalqlarning urf-odatlarini, qadriyatlarini, madaniy merosi bilan tanishish imkoniyati tug'iladi.

3. Xalqaro ta'lim va ilmiy hamkorlik tilidir.

Ko'plab ilmiy maqolalar, konferensiyalar, darsliklar ingliz tilida chop etiladi. Bu talabalarga global bilim maydoniga kirish yo'lini ochadi.

4. Iqtisodiy hamkorlikni rivojlantiradi.

Biznes uchrashuvlari, muzokaralar, xalqaro loyihalar asosan ingliz tilida olib boriladi.

Madaniy kompetensiyaning ahamiyati.

Madaniyatlararo muloqotda faqat tilni bilishning o'zi yetarli emas. Til bilan birga madaniy kompetensiya — ya'ni, boshqa millat vakillarining qadriyatlarini, nutq madaniyati va muloqot uslublarini tushunish ham talab etiladi. Ingliz tili ta'limi jarayonida talabalar nutq etiketini, madaniyatlar farqlarini, xalqaro muloqot qoidalarini o'rganishi zarur. Insoniyat tarixida turli xalqlar o'rtasida fikr almashish, o'zaro tushunish va bir-biridan o'rnak olish jarayoni har doim muhim bo'lib kelgan. Hozirgi davrda esa bu jarayon yanada kengayib, turli mamlakat fuqarolarini birlashtiruvchi umumiy tilga ehtiyoj sezilarli darajada oshdi. Ana shu ehtiyojni qondirishda ingliz tili jahon miqyosida eng qulay imkoniyat yaratadigan vositalardan biri sifatida maydonga chiqdi. Ingliz tili turli sohalarda qo'llanayotgan bilimlarni boshqalarga yetkazishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Masalan, talaba ilmiy yangiliklar, texnik yangiliklar, ijtimoiy g'oyalar yoki ijodiy tajribalarni o'rganmoqchi bo'lsa, ularning aksariyati aynan shu tilda taqdim etilganini ko'radi. Bu esa yoshlar uchun keng ko'lamlı ma'lumotlar bilan tanishish imkonini yaratadi. Shuningdek, ingliz tilini bilish turli millat vakillari bilan hamkorlikni osonlashtiradi. Talaba xorijiy dasturlarda qatnashmoqchi bo'lsa, global platformalarda o'qish yoki ish topmoqchi bo'lsa, bu til unga qo'shimcha imkoniyat bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari, boshqa mamlakat odamlari bilan muloqot qilish jarayonida inson nafaqat tilni, balki ularning hayot tarzi, qiziqishlari va odatlariga oid ko'plab tasavvurlarga ega bo'ladi. Bu jarayon shaxsni yanada ochiq fikrli, bag'rikeng va moslashuvchan bo'lishga undaydi. Shu bilan birga, ingliz tilini o'rganish talabaning o'z qobiliyatini sinab ko'rish, nutqni ravon ifoda etish, mantiqiy fikr yuritish va turli vaziyatlarda to'g'ri yo'l tutish kabi ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi.[2] Bu ko'nikmalar nafaqat chet elda, balki o'z yurtida ham muvaffaqiyat qozonishiga xizmat qiladi. Natijada ingliz tili yosh avlodni turli madaniy muhitda erkin harakat qilishi, dunyoning turli burchaklarida yashayotgan insonlar bilan muloqotda bo'lishi va o'z salohiyatini namoyon etishi uchun zarur bo'lgan asosiy omillardan biridir. Bugunning tez sur'atlar bilan o'zgarayotgan ijtimoiy makonida turli hudud vakillarining bir-biri bilan

muloqotga kirishishi tobora kuchayib borar ekan, shaxslararo anglashuvni mustahkamlashga ko'maklashuvchi umumiy nutq maydoniga ehtiyoj yanada ortmoqda. Ayniqsa, ilmiy izlanish, texnologik taraqqiyot, xalqaro tashabbuslar, kasbiy hamkorlik va ijtimoiy loyihalar singari ko'plab yo'nalishlarda yagona til vositasining mavjudligi jarayonlarning izchil va samarali kechishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ana shunday ehtiyojlar fonida muayyan til sistemasi jahon miqyosida alohida o'rin egallab, turli millat vakillarini bir nuqtada bog'laydigan, ular o'rtasida yangi aloqa ko'priklari yaratuvchi kuch sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Uning qulay tuzilishi, moslashuvchan nutq qurilishi, turli fanlar va sohalarda keng qo'llanishi jarayonni yanada jadal sur'atda rivojlantirib, insoniyat taraqqiyotida yangi imkoniyatlar ochmoqda.

Xulosa

Yuqorida o'rganilgan masalalar ingliz tilining hozirgi davrdagi ahamiyati faqatgina til-o'rganish jarayoni bilan cheklanib qolmasligini yaqqol ko'rsatadi. Bu til turli millat va turfa madaniy muhit vakillarining bir-birini anglashida asosiy vosita bo'lib, talabalar uchun keng imkoniyatlar eshigini ochadi. Ingliz tilidan foydalanish orqali nafaqat xorijiy adabiyotlardan foydalanish, balki boshqa xalqlarning urf-odatlarini va dunyoqarashini chuqurroq anglash imkoniyati paydo bo'ladi. Talaba ingliz tilini puxta egallagan sari, u turli ilmiy manbalarga murojaat qilishi, zamonaviy g'oyalarni qabul qilishi va xalqaro maydonda o'z fikrini erkin ifoda etishi osonlashadi. Bu esa keyinchalik kasbiy rivojlanish, ilmiy izlanishlar olib borish va chet el bilan aloqalarni kengaytirishda katta yordam beradi.[4]

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MEDIA DISKURSIDA SOTSIOPRAGMATIKANING NAZARIY TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola media diskursidagi sotsiopragmatikaning nazariy tahlilini taqdim etadi, ijtimoiy me'yorlar, hokimiyat munosabatlari, madaniy qadriyatlar, kommunikativ niyatlar va ideologik tuzilmalar mazmun shakllanishiga qanday ta'sir qilishini o'rganadi. Maqola pragmatika, sotsiolingvistika, media lingvistika, tanqidiy diskurs tahlili va raqamli kommunikatsiya tadqiqotlarining nazariy qarashlarini integratsiyalab, batafsil bo'limlar, misollar va madaniyatlararo tushuntirishlarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit So'zlar

Sotsiopragmatika, Media Diskursi, Pragmatik Kompetensiya, Xushmuomalilik Strategiyalari, Nutq Aklari, Ijtimoiy Me'yorlar, Madaniyatlararo Kommunikatsiya, Raqamli Media

СОЦИОПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ МЕДИЙНОГО ДИСКУРСА

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В статье представлен теоретический анализ социопрагматики в медийном дискурсе, исследуется, как социальные нормы, властные отношения, культурные ценности, коммуникативные намерения и идеологические структуры влияют на создание смысла в традиционных и цифровых медиа. В работе интегрируются теории прагматики, социолингвистики, медиалингвистики, критического анализа дискурса и исследований цифровой коммуникации, с подробными разделами, примерами и межкультурными пояснениями.

Ключевые слова

Социопрагматика, Медийный дискурс, Прагматическая компетенция, Стратегии вежливости, Речевые акты, Социальные нормы, Межкультурная коммуникация, Цифровые медиа

SOCIOPRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF MEDIA DISCOURSE: A COMPREHENSIVE THEORETICAL STUDY

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Abstract. This article presents a theoretical investigation of sociopragmatics within media discourse, exploring how social norms, power relations, cultural values, communicative intentions, and ideological structures shape meaning-

making in both traditional and digital media. It synthesizes theories from pragmatics, sociolinguistics, media linguistics, critical discourse analysis, and digital communication. It includes sections, examples, and cross-cultural explanations.

Keywords

Sociopragmatics, Media Discourse, Pragmatic Competence, Politeness Strategies, Speech Acts, Social Norms, Intercultural Communication, Digital Media

Introduction

Media discourse is a dynamic communicative field where language, society, culture, and ideology intersect. It informs, influences, and constructs public understanding of reality. Fairclough (1995) argues that media does not simply report events; it actively creates meaning through discourse¹. Sociopragmatics, introduced by Leech (1983), studies how social norms and cultural expectations shape language use². Applying sociopragmatics to media reveals how journalists, editors, institutions, and audiences negotiate meaning within specific social contexts. Sociopragmatics is a subfield of pragmatics that examines how social context influences language use. While pragmalinguistics focuses on the linguistic tools available for expressing meaning (e.g., sentence structures, speech acts, politeness markers), sociopragmatics studies the social rules and conventions that govern how and when these linguistic forms should be used. The central idea is that language is not neutral; its use is guided by social norms, cultural expectations, interpersonal relationships, and power structures. Sociopragmatics integrates insights from linguistics, sociolinguistics, anthropology, and sociology to explain how these factors shape communication. Sociopragmatics studies these norms and their influence on speech acts, such as requests, refusals, compliments, and apologies. Cross-cultural differences often lead to pragmatic failure, where a perfectly grammatical utterance is perceived as impolite or inappropriate in another culture .

Role-based Expectations

Individuals assume different social roles (teacher, parent, friend, leader) which come with expected communicative behavior. Sociopragmatics examines how language varies with these roles and how speakers signal awareness of roles.

Contextual Variables

Sociopragmatics emphasizes that the same linguistic form can convey different meanings depending on context. Variables include situation formality, social setting, medium of communication (face-to-face, online), and audience. Example: A directive such as "Close the window" is perceived differently in a formal classroom versus a private home setting.

¹ Fairclough, N. (1995). *Media discourse*. Edward Arnold.

² Leech, G. (1983). *Principles of pragmatics*. Longman.

Speech Act Appropriateness

The appropriateness of a speech act (request, compliment, apology) depends on the interplay of linguistic forms and social conventions. Sociopragmatic analysis often examines how speech acts are adapted to context, including mitigation strategies, hedging, or exaggeration.

Intercultural Communication

Sociopragmatics is essential for understanding cross-cultural communication. Differences in politeness norms, face-saving strategies, and indirectness can cause misunderstandings between speakers from different cultural backgrounds. Sociopragmatics therefore provides a framework for analyzing language as a social action, showing that what is said and how it is said are deeply shaped by the social environment, cultural context, and power relations. Pragmalinguistics and sociopragmatics are two complementary subfields of pragmatics identified by Leech (1983)¹. They both study language use, but from different perspectives. Pragmalinguistics focuses on the linguistic means available to convey a communicative intention. In other words, it studies how language encodes social meanings and intentions through specific structures, expressions, or strategies. Linguistic forms for speech acts: how requests, apologies, compliments, and directives are linguistically expressed. Example: “Could you pass the salt?” (polite request) vs. “Pass the salt!” (direct command).

Markers of politeness and mitigation: hedges, honorifics, intensifiers, downtoners. Example: “I wonder if you might be able to...” instead of “Do this now.”

Strategies for achieving communicative goals: lexical, syntactic, and morphological choices. Essentially, pragmalinguistics is concerned with the form and tools of language used to perform communicative functions. It asks the question: “*What linguistic options are available to the speaker to express meaning?*” Sociopragmatics, on the other hand, deals with the social rules and norms that govern the appropriate use of these linguistic forms. It analyzes how contextual factors influence the interpretation and appropriateness of language. **Social context and norms:** expectations related to social roles, hierarchy, status, and culture. Example: A request in Japanese or Uzbek culture may be softened to maintain politeness, whereas in English directness is more acceptable.

Power relations and social distance: politeness strategies and indirectness vary depending on hierarchy or closeness between speakers. Example: A manager uses formal and indirect language with subordinates; friends may use informal, direct forms.

Cultural and community conventions: what counts as polite, respectful, or offensive in a given society. Example: Compliments or refusals are expressed

¹ Leech, G. (1983). *Principles of pragmatics*. Longman.

differently in collectivist and individualist cultures (Thomas, 1983). Sociopragmatics asks the question: “Given the social context, which linguistic forms are appropriate to achieve the intended communicative goal?” Pragmalinguistics provides the “tools”, while sociopragmatics provides the “rules of use”. For example, a speaker may have many ways to make a request (pragmalinguistics), but sociopragmatic norms dictate which form is appropriate for a particular listener or context. Misunderstandings in cross-cultural communication often arise when speakers know the linguistic forms but lack sociopragmatic awareness. Example: English speaker says to a professor: “Give me the notes.” (grammatically correct, pragmalinguistic knowledge intact). Sociopragmatic violation: The directness may be considered rude or disrespectful in the professor-student relationship.

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), as proposed by Van Dijk (1998), examines the intricate relationship between language, power, and society, emphasizing that discourse is not neutral but a social practice that both reflects and reproduces ideology¹. Ideology is understood as a system of shared beliefs, values, and assumptions that shape how social groups interpret events, structure knowledge, and interact. Language plays a central role in representing reality, legitimizing authority, and reinforcing social hierarchies, often in subtle and implicit ways, such as through word choice, metaphors, framing, and syntactic structures. For instance, the terms “illegal immigrants” versus “undocumented workers” evoke different perceptions, illustrating how discourse can influence public opinion and reinforce societal biases. Van Dijk’s approach integrates textual, cognitive, and social analysis, highlighting how mental representations, social norms, and institutional contexts shape both the production and interpretation of texts. CDA aligns with sociopragmatic perspectives by showing that the appropriateness and interpretation of language are deeply embedded in social and ideological contexts, making it essential for understanding political speeches, media narratives, and intercultural communication. Sociopragmatics provides a vital framework for analyzing how media constructs meaning through linguistic choices influenced by culture, norms, and power. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing critical media literacy in the digital age.

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INGLIZ BADIY ADABIYOTIDA DISKURS MARKERLARNING MATN DINAMIKASINI BOSHQARISHDAGI PRAGMATIK ROLI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ingliz adabiy matnlarida ishlatiladigan diskurs markerlarining matn oqimi va dinamikasini boshqarishda yangi, oddiy va tushunarli usulda qanday rol o'ynashini ta'kidlaydi. Adabiy matnlardagi nutq belgilar faqat grammatik bog'lovchilar sifatida emas, balki voqealar ritmini belgilaydigan, qahramonlarning nutqiga tabiiylik beradigan va o'quvchiga matnni qanday qabul qilish kerakligini ko'rsatadigan pragmatik vositalar sifatida ham namoyon bo'ladi. Tadqiqot "well", "so", "however", "then", "actually" kabi belgilarni adabiy matnlardagi semantik yukini va ularning o'quvchining qabul qilishiga ta'sirini tushuntiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: diskurs markerlar, pragmatika, badiiy matn, izchillik, narrativ dinamikasi.

Kirish. Badiiy matn – bu nafaqat voqealar tasvirini ifodalovchi nutq tuzilmasi, balki muallifning estetik maqsadini, axborotni tarqatish usullarini va o'quvchi bilan muloqotni boshqaradigan murakkab pragmatik tizimdir. Ushbu tizimning eng muhim jihatlaridan biri ingliz adabiyotida diskurs markerlaridan foydalanishdir. Diskurs markerlari (DM) bog'lanish, izchillik, ohang o'zgarishi, voqealar rivoji va diskursning psixologik/stilistik elementlarini, matnning yuzaki va chuqur qatlamlarida tuzish uchun javobgardir. Chunki adabiy nutq faqat mazmunni yetkazib bermaydi — u o'quvchini tajribaga, qahramonlarning his-tuyg'ulariga, matnni o'qish kerak bo'lgan nuqtaga olib boradi. So'nggi yillarda diskurs markerlarining pragmatik funksiyalari tilshunoslikda dolzarb soha sifatida paydo bo'ldi [2]; [4]. Ammo Diskurs markerlarning adabiy matnlar dinamikasini tartibga solishdagi aniq roli va, xususan, syujet rivojlanishi, qahramonlarning nutq xarakteri, matn ritmi va semantik o'zgarishlarni shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati yaxshi ochib berilmagan. Xususan, ingliz adabiy adabiyoti uchun, Diskurs markerlarning o'ziga xos stilistik yukini hisobga olgan holda, ularning muallif ovozini kuchaytirishdagi roli va o'quvchilarning talqiniga ta'siri qat'iy o'rganilishi kerak.

Asosiy qism. Ingliz tilidagi adabiyotda diskurs belgilar hikoyaning umumiy shakli, ohangi va rivojlanishini nazorat qiluvchi eng muhim pragmatik usullardan biri hisoblanadi. Ular voqealarni vaqt, sabab va qarama-qarshilik, tartib va vaqt yo'nalishi, tezlik, taranglik va ma'no bilan belgilaydi. Masalan, "then", "suddenly", "in fact" birliklari o'quvchilarni nima bo'lganidan keyin nima sodir bo'lganiga yo'naltiradi va hikoyaning yo'nalishini aniqlaydi. Diskurs belgilar:

qahramonlarning tili, shuningdek, ifoda uslublari va ma'nolari va ularning diskurs ifoda naqshlari ham ular aytgan narsalarga qattiq bog'liq: qahramonlarning nutqida qahramonlarning so'zlari belgilarga ("well", "you know", "I mean" iboralari ularning xarakteri, ruhiy holati va muloqot ohangini bildiradi) ta'sir qiladi, bu esa ularning dialogini tabiiy, jonli va psixologik jihatdan ishonchli qiladi va suhbatga o'zining nutq va xulq ohangini beradi.

Bundan tashqari, "however", "indeed", "of course" kabi belgilar muallifning pozitsiyasi yoki bahosini, fikrini, o'quvchini talqin qilishga yo'naltiruvchi har qanday belgida ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ular yozuvchining ovozi kuchaytiradi va matnning mafkuraviy yoyini harakatga keltiradi. Keyin esa qiziqarli fakt shundaki, diskurs belgilar ritm va hissiy dinamizmni ham nazorat qiladi: ba'zilar matni sekinlashtiradi ("well"), ba'zilar o'tishlarni tezlashtiradi ("then"), boshqalari esa keskin ohang beradi ("however"). Diskurs belgilarining stilistik imkoniyatlari juda keng - ular atmosferik tuyg'uni yaratadi, dramatik taranglikni hosil qiladi, kinoyani kuchaytiradi va matnga estetik boylik beradi. Shunday qilib, diskurs belgilar nafaqat adabiy matnning semantik izchilligini shakllantiradi; ular o'quvchi va matn o'rtasidagi yashirin muloqotni boshqarish uchun uning pragmatik va stilistik tuzilishini ham belgilaydi

Diskurs belgilar tili ichki mexanizmlaridan biri bo'lib, ular matnning o'qilishi, voqealarning rivojlanishi va qahramonlarning nutqining tabiiyligini belgilaydi. Bu belgilar o'zlari katta ma'no tashimasa-da, ular matnning tuzilishini va o'quvchining e'tiborini boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Adabiy matnlarda ular ko'pincha qahramonning holatini, fikr almashish jarayonini yoki hikoyaning ritmini aks ettiradi.

Xulosa. Ingliz tilidagi adabiy nutqda diskurs belgilarining matn dinamikasini boshqarishda pragmatik roli bor. Ular syujet rivojlanishini tartibga soladi, qahramonlarning nutqidagi o'ziga xoslikni yaratadi, muallifning pozitsiyasini ifodalaydi va matnning ritmi va ohangini shakllantiradi. Haqiqatan ham, adabiy matnlardagi diskurs belgilarining funksional yuklamasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, ular oddiy bog'lovchi vositalar emas, balki muallif va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi yashirin muloqotni boshqaruvchi vositalardir. Ularning uslubiy salohiyati adabiy asarlarning estetik ta'sirini oshiradi, matni ko'p qatlamli, jonli va psixologik jihatdan boy qiladi. Shuning uchun diskurs belgilarini pragmatik yondashuvdan o'rganish ingliz adabiy matnlarining ichki mexanizmlarini chuqurroq tushunishga yordam beradi.

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THE CHARACTERISTICS OF SERVANTS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Annotation: In this article we have emphasizes on the significant servant roles in English literature in 19th century. The ways of description and the relationship of servants with their masters are implemented in this article as well.

Key words: moral compasses, class divisions, cultural anxieties, social standing.

Introduction. In 19th century English literature, the portrayal of servants depicts much about the social structures, class divisions, and cultural anxieties of the time. As the century unfolded, the role of the servant in literature evolved from a simple background figure to a more complex and mostly symbolic character, reflecting the tensions between the aristocracy and the rising middle class, as well as the changing roles of gender and class within British society.

Servants as Symbols of Class and Social Hierarchy:

In much of 19th century English literature, servants show the rigid class system that governed British society. The very establishment of a servant class was integral to the maintenance of social order, and authors often used these characters to highlight the disparities between the wealthy elite and the working poor. Servants were seen as an significant part of the social fabric, yet their lives were often depicted as invisible or subordinated to the needs of their masters.

In novels by authors such as Charles Dickens and Jane Austen, servants often serve as a mirror to the values, traditions and behaviors of their employers. In *Pride and Prejudice* (1813), for example, the interactions between the Bennet family and their servants subtly reflect the family's moral and social standing. While the Bennets are portrayed as struggling with finances and maintaining an air of genteel respectability, the comparison between the upper-class protagonists and their lower-class servants highlights issues of power, status, and privilege.

Dickens, known for his vivid social commentary, frequently used servant characters to explore the stark divisions between the rich and the poor. In *Oliver Twist* (1837-1839), the character of Mr. Brownlow's housekeeper, or in *Great Expectations* (1860-1861) with characters like Joe Gargery, reveal how individuals within the servant class could be both compassionate and morally upright, yet still bound by the constraints of their social roles. These characters

often embody the virtues of loyalty, patience, and service, but are also portrayed as deserving of recognition and dignity.

Main part. The Servant as a Moral Compass:

In addition to serving as symbols of social order, servants often act as moral compasses in 19th century literature. Their positions in society gave them a unique vantage point from which they could observe the foibles and flaws of their masters. Often possessing greater moral clarity or emotional insight, servants could see through the pretensions of the upper class. This sense of perspective allowed them to provide wisdom, guidance, or even commentary on the hypocrisy and superficiality of the wealthy.

In *Jane Eyre* (1847) by Charlotte Brontë, the character of Adele Varens' governess, Madame Reisz, serves as a foil to the more materialistic values of the higher social classes. Similarly, Jane herself, while never fully a servant, takes on domestic roles in several parts of the narrative. Her journey reflects both personal growth and an evolving critique of social conventions, especially regarding the roles of women and the servant class. As she ascends from a position of dependency to one of independence and moral agency, Jane's experiences illustrate the inherent tensions between service and self-assertion.

Changing Gender Roles and the Servant's Identity:

The role of female servants in 19th century literature is particularly significant because it reflects the complex intersections of gender, class, and power. In works like *North and South* (1854-1855) by Elizabeth Gaskell, female servants often find themselves trapped within a cycle of low wages, hard labor, and societal expectations of their subservience. Yet, these characters also experience moments of autonomy and power that complicate traditional notions of servitude.

In Gaskell's novel, the character of Bessy Higgins represents the struggles of working-class women, including female servants, who experience the double burden of domestic labor and societal undervaluation.

In contrast, characters such as Mrs. Thornton, who is a woman of the upper class but also involved in the management of her household and business affairs, illustrate the broader gender dynamics at play. Female servants, in particular, were often portrayed as the moral backbone of households, performing duties both menial and emotional, which contributed to the moral education and stability of their employers.

Servants and the Emergence of the "Other".

Another recurring theme is the servant as "the other" – a marginalized figure whose experiences are often defined by their relationship to the more privileged classes. The servant's life, particularly in the Victorian era, was often one of isolation, obscurity, and sometimes silent rebellion. In novels like *Wuthering Heights* (1847) by Emily Brontë, Heathcliff's rise from servant to master reflects the destabilization of traditional class hierarchies and the fluidity of social mobility. Yet, despite his ascent, Heathcliff's treatment of his servants and the people around him reveals the darker, more destructive aspects of his character,

suggesting that the class struggle is never entirely resolved and always permeates the social fabric.

This theme of the “other” can also be seen in the portrayal of servants as exotic or foreign figures. For example, in *The Moonstone* (1868) by Wilkie Collins, the servant characters often possess backgrounds that are outside the dominant Anglo-Saxon identity, challenging ideas of national and racial purity and raising questions about the intersections of imperialism and domestic servitude.

Conclusion

The role of servants in 19th century English literature serves as a crucial lens through which authors explored complex social dynamics, class relations, and personal identity. Whether as symbols of class structure, moral guides, or figures of resistance, servants were central to many of the era’s most significant literary works. These characters were not merely background figures; rather, they embodied the contradictions and conflicts inherent in the class-driven society of the time. Through their stories, 19th century literature offers a nuanced understanding of the socio-economic forces that shaped both the lives of the privileged and the marginalized, giving voice to those who often remained silent in the larger narrative of the era.

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PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF LINGUISTIC UNITS IN LITERARY DISCOURSE

Abstract: Literature uses language not only to narrate events but also to recreate inner worlds. Unlike everyday communication, where words primarily serve practical exchange, literary language draws readers into the thoughts, emotions, and memories of others. Traditional linguistics often focuses on describing the structures of texts, but psycholinguistics provides another

perspective: it asks how readers mentally process these structures and why certain passages resonate so deeply.

This study explores how different levels of linguistic units—sounds, words, sentences, and whole texts—are received and experienced by the mind in literature. By comparing Virginia Woolf's *Mrs Dalloway*, with its fragmented reflections of consciousness, and Abdulla Qodiriy's *Mehrobdan chayon*, with its emotionally charged depictions of character psychology, the research demonstrates how writers mobilize language to engage perception, memory, and imagination. The findings suggest that linguistic units in literature function less like fixed signs and more like triggers of mental imagery and affect. Literature, therefore, becomes a shared cognitive and emotional space where the psychology of the author meets that of the reader.

Key words: Psycholinguistics, linguistic units, literary discourse, Virginia Woolf, *Mrs Dalloway*, Abdulla Qodiriy, *Mehrobdan chayon*, stream of consciousness, cognitive processing, inner world, language and psychology, cross-cultural analysis

This study explores how different levels of linguistic units—sounds, words, sentences, and whole texts—are received and experienced by the mind when encountered in literature. By comparing Virginia Woolf's *Mrs Dalloway*, with its fragmented reflections of consciousness, and Abdulla Qodiriy's *Mehrobdan chayon*, with its emotionally charged depictions of character psychology, the research shows how writers mobilize language to engage perception, memory, and imagination. The findings suggest that linguistic units in literature function less like fixed signs and more like triggers of mental imagery and feeling. Literature, therefore, becomes a shared space where the psychology of the author and the psychology of the reader meet.

Language is not only a tool for communication; it is also the medium through which we think, remember, and imagine. In literature, language does more than transmit information—it captures the shifting landscapes of the human mind. Through the arrangement of sounds, words, and sentences, writers evoke entire inner worlds, guiding readers through states of perception, memory, and emotion.

Psychologists, philosophers, and linguists have long recognized that language forms the foundation of human culture and social interaction. It is often described as the “vehicle of thought,” though traditional approaches have privileged thought over the “vehicle” itself. Yet the carrier of thought—the structure and use of language—merits deeper consideration, especially when it comes to literature, where linguistic form and human psychology are inseparably linked.

Psycholinguistics provides a framework for exploring this relationship. It asks how texts are processed in real time: how rhythm and sound affect emotion, how words trigger memory, and how syntactic complexity demands cognitive reorganization. Applied to literature, psycholinguistics highlights reading as a

dynamic psychological event where comprehension and emotion are intertwined. This perspective helps explain why certain passages feel more memorable or immersive than others.

The aim of this study is to trace how linguistic units function in literary discourse, with three goals:

1. To analyze language at multiple levels—sound, word, syntax, and discourse—in selected literary works.
2. To explore the psychological processes by which readers engage with these linguistic levels.
3. To show how psycholinguistic analysis can enrich literary studies by connecting language structures with cognitive and emotional processes.

To achieve this, the thesis compares two works from distinct traditions: Virginia Woolf's *Mrs Dalloway* (1925), a hallmark of English modernist prose, and Abdulla Qodiriy's *Mehrobdan chayon* (1929), a cornerstone of Uzbek classical literature. Both works, despite cultural and historical differences, foreground the complexity of inner life. Their comparison highlights universal cognitive processes in reading while also illustrating cultural variations in literary style.

This is especially important in works that focus on the representation of consciousness. Virginia Woolf's *Mrs Dalloway*, for example, abandons straightforward narration in favor of stream-of-consciousness, immersing the reader in fleeting impressions and internal monologues. In a different cultural tradition, Abdulla Qodiriy's *Mehrobdan chayon* conveys the psychological struggles of its characters through metaphor and imagery, making the reader part of their inner conflict. Both texts, in their own way, demonstrate how literature draws the reader into the hidden layers of thought and feeling through linguistic choices.

This thesis has argued that literature is not simply written but enacted in the mind. By analyzing sound, word, syntax, and discourse, we see that linguistic units function as sparks of cognition, igniting imagery, memory, and emotion.

The comparative study of *Mrs Dalloway* and *Mehrobdan chayon* demonstrates both the universality of psycholinguistic processes and the cultural particularities of literary expression. While Woolf engages the reader through fragmented thought and shifting perspectives, Qodiriy draws the reader into intense emotional and moral struggles.

Ultimately, psycholinguistic analysis enriches literary studies by bridging language and psychology. It shows that literature is not only a cultural artifact but also a psychological event—one where the inner worlds of writer and reader meet.

Future research might extend this approach to poetry, drama, or oral storytelling traditions, exploring how different literary forms activate distinct cognitive processes.

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FROM "SEHR" TO "SORCERY": A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF MAGIC IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LINGUISTIC WORLDVIEWS

Abstract. This thesis contends that a basic contradiction in the linguistic worldviews of Uzbekistan and English can be seen in the linguistic encoding of the "magic" concept: Due in large part to secularization and fantasy literature, English lexicalizes "magic" as a polysemous and morally neutral force that can be channeled for either good or evil. In contrast, Uzbek, through its primary terms *sehr* and *jodu*, conceptualizes it as a monolithic and intrinsically evil act. This opinion is largely influenced by the deeply ingrained norms of Islamic doctrine, which frame it as a prohibited interference with the divine order.

Introduction. According to this study, the process of moving "from 'Sehr' to 'Sorcery'" involves crossing significant cultural and cognitive barriers rather than a straightforward translation. The study shows that the English concept of "magic" functions on a spectrum of ambiguity by examining key lexical units, phraseological constructions, and narrative archetypes within each linguoculture. In a worldview where supernatural agency can be separated from religious dogma and made a neutral tool, it can represent anything from evil witchcraft to heroic wizardry and entrancing metaphor. In sharp contrast, there is no such ambiguity in the Uzbek linguistic worldview, which is based on the term *sehr*. As a direct result of the Islamic hermeneutic that has dominated the cultural realm, it offers a cohesive conceptual field in which magic is inextricably linked to deceit, sin, and harm. Accordingly, this analysis argues that the lack of a "positive wizard" archetype in Uzbek folklore and the common protection discourse (*tumor*, *duo*) are not merely cultural oddities but rather explicit linguistic expressions of this underlying worldview. In the end, this comparative conceptual analysis shows how language serves as a storehouse of cultural values, dictating not only how magic is named but also how it can be creatively imagined.

The thesis will be developed through the following key arguments:

1. The Anglophone Worldview: A Spectrum of Ambiguity and Instrumentality

Lexical Polysemy: The English language possesses a rich, differentiated lexicon for magic (e.g., sorcery, witchcraft, wizardry, enchantment, conjuring). This variety allows for nuanced distinctions between malevolent practices (sorcery), learned art (wizardry), and delightful charm (enchantment).

Moral and Functional Neutrality: The core term "magic" is fundamentally neutral. It serves as an umbrella that can be qualified by adjectives ("black magic," "white magic," "dark magic") to assign moral value. This positions magic as a tool, analogous to technology or science. **The Influence of Secularism and Fantasy:**

The thesis will trace how the post-Enlightenment separation of church and state, coupled with the rise of modern fantasy literature (from J.R.R. Tolkien and C.S. Lewis to J.K. Rowling), has systematically desacralized and rehabilitated the concept. Figures like Gandalf and Dumbledore have redefined the "wizard" as a moral, wise, and heroic archetype, a stark departure from its earlier, more sinister connotations.

Metaphorical Permeation: The neutrality of "magic" allows for its widespread use in positive, secular metaphors ("the magic of cinema," "a magical moment"), further detaching it from its supernatural and religious origins.

2. The Uzbek Worldview: A Monolithic and Forbidden Transgression

Semantic Unity and Negative Axiology: This moral ambiguity is absent from the Uzbek language, which is mainly of Arabo-Persian origin (*sehr*, *jodu*, *afsun*). These terms are uniformly loaded with a negative valuation, making them near synonyms. The study will show that *sehr* is not a neutral instrument but is, in theory, inextricably linked to the desire to cause harm, deceive, or usurp the will of God.

The Foundational Role of Islamic Doctrine: The Quran's condemnation of witchcraft is the basis for the negative charge of *sehr*, which is not a purely cultural preference. It is specifically framed in verses (such as Surah Al-Baqarah 2:102) as a sin (*kufr*) and the work of Satan. A non-negotiable, theological foundation for the concept's negative status in the cultural worldview is provided by this religious framing.

The Archetypal Villain: Consequently, the practitioner's cultural archetype—the *sihrgar* or *jodugar*—is solely that of a villain. A "good *sihrgar*" has no place in culture; that idea is oxymoronic. Dastans (epic poems) and characters from Uzbek folklore will be analyzed to demonstrate this.

The Discourse of Protection: In the Uzbek context, the linguistic and cultural reaction to magic is defense rather than exploration or utilization. Terms like *tumor* (amulet), *duo* (prayer), and *chivin* (a concept associated with the evil eye) are common, indicating a worldview that is structured, in part, around defense against the constant threat of *sehr*.

3. Methodological Framework and Implications

Linguistic Analysis: The thesis will use a combination of the following

methodologies:

The semantic structure of the lexicons related to magic is mapped using conceptual analysis. Collocations and fixed expressions are examined using phraseological analysis (e.g., "work like magic" vs. *sehrga uchramoq* - "to fall under a spell").

Conclusion. Using cultural-linguistic analysis, one can relate linguistic data to religious texts, folklore, and larger cultural narratives.

Wider Implications: The study comes to the conclusion that this case study is a good example of how language acts as a cognitive filter. It dictates what can be envisioned as well as what can be spoken. Through its narrative and lexical structures, the English language creates a world in which magic can inspire wonder and bravery. The Uzbek language provides a clear window into the normative values of its speech community because it confines the concept to a realm of fear and prohibition due to a distinct set of cultural and religious imperatives.

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GRAMMATICALIZATION OF AUXILIARY VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: A FUNCTIONAL APPROACH

Grammaticalization is a universal linguistic process in which lexical verbs gradually evolve into auxiliary or functional markers. This process involves several interrelated mechanisms that transform the original meaning and structure of the verb.

Semantic bleaching refers to the weakening or complete loss of the verb's original lexical meaning. Over time, the auxiliary loses its concrete sense and assumes an abstract grammatical function. Morphosyntactic fixation occurs when the auxiliary becomes structurally bound to the main verb, often acquiring fixed

positions and specific syntactic requirements. Phonological reduction describes shortening, contraction, or reduction in stress or pronunciation, making the auxiliary less prominent in speech. Functional expansion happens when the auxiliary acquires additional grammatical roles, such as marking tense, aspect, mood, or evidentiality.

Both English and Uzbek auxiliaries undergo these processes, yet the rate and outcome differ due to typological and structural differences between the two languages. English, with its analytic nature, tends to produce highly abstract auxiliaries that are syntactically rigid, whereas Uzbek, as an agglutinative language, retains lexical traces and allows auxiliaries to convey pragmatic nuances. This theoretical foundation helps explain why auxiliary verbs operate differently in discourse and what semantic and pragmatic roles they fulfill.

English auxiliary verbs demonstrate clear stages of grammaticalization, illustrating how lexical meaning is reduced and grammatical function is enhanced.

1 “Be” as a Progressive Marker

Originally, be indicated existence or presence. Over time, it became a marker of progressive aspect, as in *is working* or *was reading*. The grammaticalized form exhibits: almost complete loss of the original existential meaning, fixed syntactic position preceding the main verb, central role in distinguishing progressive actions from simple aspect.

Thus, be illustrates how an originally lexical verb transforms into a fully functional auxiliary in English, encoding temporal nuances while losing its lexical identity.

2 “Have” as a Perfect Marker

Have evolved from expressing possession (to own) to marking the perfect aspect (*has finished*, *had completed*). Features of this grammaticalization include: abstract temporal interpretation replacing concrete possession, morphosyntactic rigidity, preventing have from functioning as a full lexical verb in the same construction, central role in linking past events to present or resultative states. This evolution demonstrates semantic bleaching and functional expansion as defining characteristics of English auxiliary development.

3 “Will” as a Future Auxiliary

Will originally expressed volition or intention (*I will do it* = “I want to do it”). Gradually, it became a grammatical marker indicating future tense. Its functional changes include: Reduced expression of volition, increased use as a neutral, predictive future marker, high grammaticalization with minimal lexical content remaining. Collectively, these examples show that English auxiliary verbs evolve toward abstraction, becoming grammatical markers with minimal trace of their original lexical meaning.

Grammaticalization of Uzbek Auxiliary Verbs

Uzbek auxiliary verbs originate from full lexical verbs denoting physical action or posture. Over time, they acquired grammatical functions while retaining some semantic traces, especially in aspectual and modal expression.

“Yur-” (Continuative or Habitual Aspect)

Originally meaning “to walk,” *yur-* now marks habitual or ongoing actions:

U kitob o‘qib *yuradi* – “He usually reads books.”

Lexical meaning of movement is weakened but still discernible

Conveys aspectual nuance, indicating repetition or continuity

Maintains flexibility in discourse

“*Ket-*” / “*Qol-*” (Aspectual Shifts)

Ket- signals sudden or unexpected initiation (U *ishga ketdi* – “He suddenly went to work”)

Qol- signals unintended continuation or persistence (U *kutib qoldi* – “He remained waiting unintentionally”)

Unlike English auxiliaries, these verbs retain clear semantic traces, blending lexical meaning with grammatical function.

“*Tur-*” / “*Yubor-*” (Manner and Intensity)

Tur- conveys stability or persistence of an action (U *kitob o‘qib turadi* – “He keeps reading continuously”)

Yubor- conveys quickness or suddenness (U *maktubni yubordi* – “He sent the letter quickly”)

English and Uzbek auxiliary verbs both undergo grammaticalization, yet the process manifests differently due to typological, semantic, and pragmatic factors. English auxiliaries exemplify high abstraction and syntactic rigidity, whereas Uzbek auxiliaries preserve lexical traces and adapt to pragmatic needs, demonstrating a more flexible grammaticalization trajectory. These findings highlight the importance of considering both universal and language-specific tendencies in functional linguistics and cross-linguistic comparison.

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PRAGMATIC DIMENSIONS OF SPEECH ACTS: CLASSIFICATION AND ANALYSIS

Abstract: This article examines the concept of speech acts and their classification within modern pragmatics. It highlights the three analytical levels of a speech act—locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary—and explains the five basic types of illocutionary acts proposed by J. Searle: representatives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declarations.

Key words: speech act, communicative situation, extralinguistic purpose, illocutionary force, performative, pragmatics

Introduction: A speech act is fundamentally a type of action, and therefore its analysis involves categories typically used to describe any action: the subject, purpose, method, tools, results, conditions, and degree of success. In a speech act, the subject is the speaker, who produces an utterance intended for perception and interpretation by the addressee. An utterance thus functions simultaneously as the product of the speech act and as an instrument for achieving a specific communicative goal. A speech act may succeed or fail depending on circumstances surrounding its performance. For success, it must be appropriate to the context; otherwise, the speaker may face communicative failure. Consider a mother telling her son, “Sit down for your lessons!” If the son is able to do the lessons, has not yet done them, and typically requires reminders, the utterance is appropriate and may be considered successful from a communicative point of view. If these conditions are not met—for example, if the son is ill or has already completed his lessons—the act becomes inappropriate and risks communicative breakdown. This illustrates that success depends not only on linguistic form but also on situational conditions.

Analysis: The conditions required for recognizing a speech act as appropriate are known as felicity conditions. Even when these conditions are met, the result may or may not align with the speaker’s intended outcome. In the above example, the mother’s utterance may lead to obedience or refusal. The son’s reaction may depend on external motivations such as distraction or personal preference. Beyond producing linguistic forms, speakers achieve certain effects—sometimes unintended—on the psychological or emotional states of listeners. This dimension constitutes the perlocutionary aspect of the speech act. For instance, the mother’s command may disrupt the son’s concentration or cause irritation. Perlocutionary effects represent a domain traditionally studied in rhetoric, which investigates how speech influences the audience’s thoughts and emotions.

Speech act theory, originally proposed by J. Austin, distinguishes three levels of analysis:

Locutionary act: the act of producing meaningful linguistic expressions.

Illocutionary act: the intention underlying the utterance—informing, promising, warning, requesting, etc.

Perlocutionary act: the effect the utterance actually produces on the listener.

For a long time, linguistics focused almost exclusively on the locutionary aspect: phonetics studied sound, lexicology examined word meaning, syntax described sentence structure, and semantics interpreted propositional content. However, speakers rarely speak merely to describe states of affairs. In most cases, they have an extralinguistic goal, such as making a request, providing information, or expressing emotion. The illocutionary act captures this functional dimension, expressed as a combination of illocutionary force (F) and propositional content (P), often represented as the formula F(P).

For instance, the utterance “Sit down for your lessons” contains the proposition you sit down for lessons and the illocutionary force of inducement. A question such as “Are you sitting down to study?” shares the same propositional content but carries a different illocutionary purpose.

Research Method and Procedure: In his seminal work *How to Do Things with Words*, J. Austin introduced, though without strict formal definition, the concept of the illocutionary act. He identified typical examples—questioning, informing, assuring, warning, criticizing, etc.—and emphasized that each language contains its own inventory of such actions. Later theorists further clarified distinctive features of illocutionary acts: intentionality (the speaker’s purpose) and conventionality (the dependence on social or linguistic norms). Languages often contain explicit grammatical and lexical markers of illocutionary force. One such marker is the performative verb—verbs like ask, promise, assure, congratulate—used not descriptively but performatively. For example, in “I promise to help,” the utterance itself constitutes the act of promising. Such sentences possess self-referentiality and cannot be evaluated as true or false, only as appropriate or inappropriate. The classical performative structure involves a first-person singular subject and a present-tense active verb (e.g., I apologize, I warn you). However, as Austin noted, performativity is not restricted to this exact syntactic pattern. A central issue in illocutionary theory is the relationship between the speaker’s intention and the listener’s recognition of that intention. A speaker may have a concealed motive that differs from the illocutionary purpose made publicly available. For example, a host wishing to dismiss a guest may say, “NN called and said he would come by at nine.” The hidden purpose is to encourage the guest to leave; the illocutionary purpose is simply to convey information. Illocutionary analysis treats this act as informing, not as inducing, because only the openly presented intention counts.

Classification of Illocutionary Acts: J. Searle proposed the most widely used classification of illocutionary acts. His system is based on several parameters: the purpose of the act, the direction of fit between words and reality, the speaker’s psychological state, constraints on propositional content, and the degree of institutional involvement. Based on these criteria, Searle identified five classes:

Representatives: Their purpose is to describe or represent reality. The direction of fit is words-to-world. Examples: stating, predicting, describing, acknowledging.

Directives: These aim to get the addressee to perform an action. The direction of fit is world-to-words. Examples: requests, commands, advice, instructions.

Commissives: The speaker commits themselves to a future action. The subject of the proposition is always the speaker. Examples: promises, oaths, guarantees.

Expressives: These express the speaker's psychological state—gratitude, regret, pleasure, apology. The propositional content reflects the cause of the emotion.

Declarations: These acts change the external situation by virtue of being uttered. They require institutional authority. Examples: appointing, dismissing, pronouncing someone married, declaring war.

Conclusion: This study has reviewed key concepts of speech act theory, emphasizing the distinction between locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary dimensions, as well as the classification of illocutionary acts. Contemporary research continues to investigate how listeners recognize illocutionary force, the role of performative verbs, and the contextual factors influencing interpretation. Speech act theory remains a fundamental framework for understanding how language functions not merely as a vehicle for information but as a form of action.

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EFFECTIVE ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING SPEAKING

Abstract: This article also highlights the role of affective factors such as anxiety, motivation, and classroom climate in teaching speaking. By combining these principles, teachers can create rich communicative environments that foster fluency, accuracy, and confidence.

Key words: teaching speaking, communicative competence, pronunciation, feedback, fluency development, affective filter.

Pronunciation is important in teaching speaking. Clear pronunciation is essential for successful communication. Modern research emphasizes intelligibility — being understood — rather than achieving a native-like accent.

Effective pronunciation instruction includes:

- teaching stress and rhythm,
- practicing intonation patterns,
- focusing on problem sounds,
- shadowing (imitating and repeating native speaker audio),
- minimal pair practice,
- integrated pronunciation within communicative tasks.

Derwing & Munro (2005) highlight that explicit pronunciation teaching increases comprehensibility and listener comfort. Celce-Murcia et al. (2010) add that pronunciation instruction should be embedded in meaningful speaking activities rather than taught in isolation.

Fluency develops when learners practice speaking under conditions that push them to produce language quickly and naturally. Effective fluency-building strategies include timed speaking activities: learners speak for 1–2 minutes on a topic without stopping. This increases automaticity and reduces reliance on translation.

4-3-2 technique: Learners give the same talk three times but with decreasing time (4 minutes → 3 minutes → 2 minutes). Nation (2013) shows that this method significantly increases fluency and reduces hesitation.

Story retelling and personal anecdotes: Providing pictures, short videos, or story outlines helps learners produce extended speech.

Communication games: Activities like debates, “find someone who,” and role-plays encourage spontaneous speaking.

Fluency improves not only through speed but also through the use of formulaic sequences and lexical chunks (Nation, 2013). These ready-made expressions help learners speak more smoothly.

Feedback is crucial for developing accurate and confident speakers, but its timing should match the activity type. During fluency-focused activities, immediate correction can disrupt communication and increase anxiety.

Lyster & Ranta (1997) recommend:

- Delayed feedback after a speaking task,
- Recasts (subtle reformulations),
- Elicitation to encourage self-correction,
- Peer feedback for reflective learning.

Recording students' speech and analyzing common errors during post-task discussions helps both accuracy and awareness.

The emotional climate of the classroom greatly affects speaking development. Speaking often causes fear, embarrassment, or anxiety. According to Krashen (1982), a high affective filter blocks language acquisition, while a supportive environment encourages participation.

Teachers can reduce speaking anxiety by:

- using pair or small-group work,
- praising effort, not just accuracy,
- setting clear expectations,
- creating predictable routines,
- showing patience and empathy,
- avoiding overly public correction.

A positive classroom environment increases learners' willingness to communicate and leads to more effective language development. To sum up, anxiety, motivation, and classroom climate effect the way of teaching speaking.

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THE APPLICATION OF PROVERBS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH NATIONAL CULTURES

Abstract: This study investigates how national identity is expressed in English and Uzbek proverbs, paying particular attention to their cultural, social, and historical contexts. As brief yet meaningful representations of collective experience, proverbs encapsulate a nation's worldview, customs, and core values. Through comparative analysis, the research shows that English proverbs typically highlight practicality, individuality, and logical thinking, while Uzbek proverbs more often convey ideas of community, respect for elders, and the importance of family and hospitality. By analyzing thematic areas such as nature, morality, interpersonal relations, and attitudes toward work, the article illustrates that proverbs function not only as linguistic expressions but also as cultural symbols that safeguard and transmit national identity across generations. The results deepen the understanding of paremiology and demonstrate the role of proverbs in forming and sustaining national consciousness.

Key words: Uzbek proverbs ,convey ideas ,logical thinking, generations, cultural traditions.

Ключевые слова: Узбекские пословицы, передают идеи, логическое мышление, поколения, культурные традиции.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbek maqollari, fikrlarni yetkazish, mantiqiy fikrlash, avlodlar, madaniy an'analar

Proverbs, as one of the oldest and most resilient genres of oral folklore, embody the shared knowledge, life experience, and worldview of a people. They convey social rules, ethical principles, and cultural traditions in brief, memorable statements. Due to their frequent appearance in daily communication, literature, and education, proverbs operate not only as linguistic units but also as transmitters of cultural identity. Through proverbs, nations express distinctive elements of their historical evolution, mentality, and national character. Scholars in linguistics, anthropology, and cultural studies have long been interested in comparing proverbs across different languages and cultures. English and Uzbek proverbs, in particular, offer a rich basis for such comparison. Although both traditions emphasize moral lessons and practical life wisdom, they differ in the ways national identity is reflected and conveyed. English proverbs generally stress logic, practicality, and individual achievement, while Uzbek proverbs more strongly express collectivist ideals, family values, and social interconnectedness. This article investigates how national identity is encoded in English and Uzbek proverbs. By examining thematic areas such as relationships, nature, and moral values, it aims to uncover both the universal human insights and the culturally unique viewpoints represented in the two linguistic traditions. Proverbs occupy a significant place in folklore and oral heritage, serving as compact expressions of a nation's wisdom, customs, and worldview. Paremiology—the academic study of proverbs—emphasizes their role as cultural symbols that transmit norms and values across generations. According to Norrick (1985), proverbs function as communicative instruments that conserve a community's moral and social standards. Mokienko (2014) similarly argues that the meanings and structures of proverbs vary among languages, reflecting each nation's distinct mentality and cultural identity. Comparative studies clearly demonstrate the connection between proverbs and national identity. Grzybek (2004) notes that although proverbs frequently address universal issues such as morality, work, and interpersonal relationships, their interpretation depends on cultural context. Honeck (1997) explains that English proverbs typically display rationality and practicality, promoting values like self-sufficiency and personal achievement. For example, the proverb “A stitch in time saves nine” stresses the importance of foresight and efficiency, which aligns with the pragmatic nature of English culture. Conversely, Uzbek proverbs are strongly influenced by communal traditions, emphasizing collective welfare, family solidarity, and respect for elders. Karimov (2010) points out that Uzbek paremiology reflects an agricultural lifestyle, social unity, and the enduring influence of Islamic ethical values. The proverb “Odam odam bilan odam” (“A person becomes a person through others”) illustrates the importance of interconnectedness in Uzbek society. Nazarov (2018) adds that Uzbek proverbs serve as transmitters of national consciousness, shaping attitudes toward social unity and collective identity. Comparative paremiology

therefore offers meaningful insight into how language interacts with culture. While English and Uzbek proverbs address many shared human themes, their differing emphases reflect distinct cultural systems. English proverbs reinforce individual responsibility and practicality, whereas Uzbek proverbs highlight cooperation, community harmony, and moral duty. These differences show that proverbs serve as cultural mirrors, expressing national identity and societal value. This article analyzes how English and Uzbek proverbs express national identity by examining their cultural, social, and historical foundations. Proverbs are presented as concise carriers of collective wisdom that reflect a society's values, traditions, and worldview. The study shows that English proverbs tend to emphasize rational thinking, practicality, and individual responsibility, while Uzbek proverbs focus on collectivist principles, family unity, respect for elders, and social cohesion. Through thematic comparison—covering morality, nature, and social relationships—the research identifies both universal human concerns and culturally specific viewpoints. Overall, the study demonstrates that proverbs act as important cultural indicators, preserving and transmitting national identity from one generation to the next.

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ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА КОННОТАЦИЯНИНГ ЛИНГВОПРАГМАТИК АСОСЛАРИ

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида фонетик воситаларда ифодаланган коннотатив маънолар таҳлили ва тадқиқи масалалари ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: коннотация, фоностилистика, ингерент, адгерент, акустик, артикуляцион, интонация, ҳиссий таъсирчанлик.

Тил инсон тафаккури, руҳияти, маданияти, урф-одати ва шахсий хусусиятлари билан боғлиқ ҳодисадир. Тилшунослар тилда икки хил маъно: денотатив (аташ) ва коннотатив (қўшимча) маъно мавжудлигини қайд этадилар [1, 83-85]. Сўзнинг аташ маъноси, яъни денотатив маъно дунё тилшунослигида кенг ўрганилган. Аммо тилда денотатив маънодан ташқари сўзнинг коннотатив маъноси борлиги тилшуносларни анча вақтдан буён қизиқтириб келади. Коннотация сўзи дастлаб XIX асрнинг ўрталарида синонимик луғатлар назарияси ва уларни яратиш амалиёти билан боғлиқ бўлган инглиз лексикографик адабиётида қўлланилган. Ўзбек тилшунослигида ҳам коннотатив маънонинг лексик ва фразеологик, морфологик ва фонетик бирликларга хослиги ҳақида фикрлар баён қилинган [2, 78].

Тил фикр англатиш қуроли бўлиши билан бирга, инсонларга ҳиссий таъсир қилиш воситаси ҳамдир. Бу таъсир сўзлардаги асосий (денотатив) маънога асосланган қўшимча (коннотатив) маънолар воситасида амалга ошади. Коннотация тил бирликлари семантикасига кирувчи семантик мавжудлик бўлиб, у нутқ субъектининг борлиққа эмотив баҳолаш ва услубий муносабатини ифода этади [3, 6]. Сўзнинг семантик структурасини ўрганишда икки хил коннотация мавжуд: ингерент коннотация –сўз контекстдан ташқари олинган ҳолларда унга хос бўлган коннотатив маъно ва адгерент коннотация –сўзда маълум контекстда ҳосил бўладиган коннотатив маъно. Коннотатив маъно компонентларини ташкил қилувчи “бўёқлар” фонетик воситаларда ҳам кучли ифодаланади. Булар:

1) нутқ товушлари талаффузи билан боғлиқ экспрессивликнинг акс этиши; сўзларнинг товуш қиёфасини ўзгартириб айтиш, сўзларда товуш орттириш ёки тушириш, аллитерация орқали ҳаяжон ифодалаш ва ҳоказо;

2) баҳо компоненти –сўзда тасдиқ ёки инкорни интонация орқали ифодалаш;

3) сўзда белги (миқдор) даражасининг кучлилигини билдирувчи товуш чўзиқлиги;

4) сўзловчининг шахс ва ҳодисаларга нисбатан турлича муносабатини ифодаловчи прагматик маъно, яъни геминация ёки паузалар орқали қўшимча бўёқ ифодалаш [4,7].

Нутқ органларига боғлиқ равишда нутқ товушлари ҳам турлича талаффуз этилади ва эшитилади. Фоностилистик жиҳатидан нутқ товушларининг талаффузидаги эмоционал-экспрессивлик ва акустик (эшитиб) таъсирланиш томонларини ўрганиш муҳимдир [5,16].

Бадий тасвирда персонаж нутқида унли товушларнинг турлича талаффузи, интонация билан айтилиши, бўғин ҳосил қилиши, урғу қабул қилиши каби просодик хусусиятлари қатор коннотатив маъноларни ҳосил қилади.

И унли фонемасидан ҳосил бўладиган коннотатив маънолар кўп ва даражаланган бўлади. Шунингдек, и фонемаси ҳам қаттиқ ва юмшоқ вариантларга эга эканлиги коннотатив маъно миқдорини оширади. Булар қуйидгилар: эсанкираш, тўлқинланиш, безовталиқ, ажабланиш, ҳайрат, ишончсизлик, кутилмаганлик, ғазаб, ўйлаб қолиш, хурсандлик, хафалиқ, хадиксираш, эслаш ва ҳоказо. Ўзбек тилидаги и фонемасига хос бўлган коннотатив маънолар инглиз тилидаги и фонемаси талаффузидаги коннотатив маънолар билан қиёсланганда, уларда баъзи ўхшашлик ва фарқли томонлар кўзга ташланади.

Инглиз тилида нутқ жараёнида и [ju:] фонемасини чўзиш орқали таажжуб, иккиланиш, ҳайратланиш, ишончсизлик каби маънолар пайдо бўлади.

-Tush! Where are the others?

-At the front.

-Quite right. Why aren't you ... at the front?

-Over age. Fifty seven. (B. Show)

Инглиз тилидаги о [ou] унли товушини чўзиб талаффуз қилиш орқали кўркиш, довдираш, кучли ғазаб, илтимос, ялиниш каби коннотатив маънолар ифодаланади.

Масалан: Don't tell him – Do-o-o-n't tell him please!

Шундай қилиб, коннотатив маъно сўз семантик структурасининг таркибий қисми ҳисобланади. Коннотатив маъно унли ва ундош фонемаларининг вариантларида ёрқин намоён бўлади.

Таржимашуносликда юқорида қайд қилинган ҳолатлар инобатга олинса, бадий асарлар таржимаси ширали, таъсирчан ва ўқимишли бўлади.

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NUTQ AKTLARINI O'QITISHDA PRODUKTIV

KO'NIKMALARNING O'RNI

Annotatsiya

Pragmatika doirasida iltifot ko'plab nutq aktlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Uning maqsadi aloqa o'rnatish va yaxshi munosabatlarni saqlab qolishdir. Iltifot ijtimoiy (emotsional) og'zaki ta'sirni o'z ichiga oladi. Ijtimoiy nutq ta'siri bu – nafaqat ma'lumot uzatiladigan, balki ma'lum ijtimoiy harakatlar amalga oshiriladigan aloqaning alohida holati hamdir.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmatika, kompliment, nutq aktlari, simpatiya, metodika, motiv.

Iltifot qilishning yetakchi motivi suhbatdoshning kayfiyatini, emotsional holatini yaxshilashdan iborat. G.S.Dvinyanova fikricha, iltifot bir qancha vazifalarni bajaradi:

1- diagramma

Komplimentning eng asosiy vazifasi aloqani o'rnatish va muloqotda samimiy, ijobiy fanni saqlashdir. Komplimentning strategik vazifasi suhbatdoshni "mahv etish" va unda komplimentorga nisbatan xayrixohlik tuyg'usini uyg'otish istagidir. Shu munosabat bilan iltifotning o'ziga xos xususiyati bu – so'zlovchi niyatining yaqqol namoyon bo'lishi – suhbatdoshga yoqimli narsalarni aytish istagi deb hisoblanishi kerak.

Deyarli har doim, iltifot taktikasiga murojaat qilish mumkin bo'lgan vaziyatlar yuzaga kelganda, muloqot ishtirokchilarining kooperativ aloqa turiga

bo'lgan munosabati mos keladi. Ammo shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, iltifot suhbatdoshlardan biri, ko'pincha adresat hamkorlik qilish kayfiyatida bo'lmagan hollarda ham qo'llanilishi mumkin. Bunday vaziyatda iltifot boshqa taktikaning bir qismiga aylanishi mumkin. Ammo muloqot ishtirokchilarining munosabatlaridagi farq tufayli kommunikativ qobiliyatsizlik xavfi yuqori bo'ladi.

Quyidagi shartlar iltifot taktikasini muvaffaqiyatli qo'llashga olib keladi:

- 1) komplimentor adresatda o'z fikridagi har qanday ijobiy xususiyatni o'zi uchun qayd etishi;
- 2) komplimentor bu haqida tinglovchiga ma'lum qilish istagini bildirishi;
- 3) komplimentor tomonidan adresatga bildirilgan iltifotda adresatni ranjitadigan qandaydir yashirin ma'no bo'lmasligi;
- 4) komplimentor samimiy bo'lishi kerak.

Inson kamolotida ijtimoiy muhitning ta'siri muhim hisoblanadi. Ijtimoiy aloqa natijasida kishilar fikr almashadilar, tajriba to'playdilar, bilim egallaydilar. Zamonaviy pedagogika fani muhitga, ijtimoiy vaziyatlarga ularning kishilik jamiyatining taraqqiy etishidagi ta'sirining roliga o'z diqqatini qaratadi.

Shunday qilib, iltifot – suhbatdoshga uni yoki uning individual fazilatlarini yoqtirishini tushuntirishga urinishdir. Ta'kidlash kerakki, har bir kommunikativ harakat, shu jumladan, iltifot ham kommunikativ belgi tamoyillariga mos kelishi kerak. Bu nutq akti jarayonini va uning ishtirokchilari kommunikativ xatti-harakatlarini tartibga solishdan iborat bo'lgan ma'lum tamoyillar to'plamidir. Eng muhim tamoyillar J. Lich tomonidan shakllantirilgan xushmuomalalik va yana bir ingliz olimi P.Graysning hamkorlik tamoyillari hisoblanadi.

Hamkorlik tamoyili to'rtta tashkil etuvchi elementni, ya'ni to'rtta maksimumni o'z ichiga oladi:

- 1) xulq-atvor, odob maksimumi,
- 2) axborot mukammalligi maksimumi,
- 3) axborot sifati maksimumi,
- 4) dolzarblilik maksimumi.

Ammo iltifotning kommunikativ harakati uchun muhimroq narsa bu nutq aktida suhbatdoshlarning bir-biriga nisbatan xushmuomalalik prinsipiga rioya qilishlaridir. Ushbu tamoyil, o'z navbatida, bir nechta normalarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- 1) xushmuomalalik maksimi;
- 2) kamtarlik maksimi;
- 3) xayrixohlik maksimi;
- 4) ma'qullash maksimi;
- 5) saxiylik maksimi;
- 6) rozilik (kelishuv) maksimi.

Agar dialog ishtirokchilari bir-biriga notanish bo'lsa yoki tanishish endigina sodir bo'lganda, unda xushmuomalalik kuzatilmasligi mumkin. Shuning uchun iltifotni shakllantirishda ehtiyot bo'lish kerak, uning mavzusini tanlash suhbatdoshda ijobiy taassurot qoldirishi va uni har qanday holatda xafa qilmasligi

uchun ehtiyotkorlik bilan ko'rib chiqilishi kerak. Kamtarlik maksimi o'z nomiga aytilgan maqtoqli so'zlarni inkor etishda namoyon bo'ladi.

Simpatiya (xayrixohlik) maksimi muhim vazifani bajaradi: u nutq harakatlarini qarama-qarshiliklardan ogohlantiradi; aslida esa, u boshqa maksimlarga rioya qilish uchun asos sanaladi, chunki iltifot kabi kommunikativ harakatning asosi xayrixohlikdan iborat. U mavjud bo'lmaganda, iltifot hazil yoki hatto masxaralash sifatida qabul qilinishi mumkin.

Ma'qullash (tasdiqlash) maksimi atrof-muhitga ijobiy baho berishni nazarda tutadi, shu bilan birga, albatta, iltifot oluvchining ham portretiga chizgilar chizadi. Shuning uchun ijobiylik va ochiqlik iltifotni to'g'ri bajarish uchun o'ta ahamiyatlidir.

Saxiylik (karam) maksimi ham iltifotning ajralmas qismidir. Unga rioya qilish harakat ishtirokchilaridan birining hukmronligi bilan bog'liq muloqotda noqulaylikdan qochish imkonini beradi. Aynan shu jabhada kompliment saxiylikning namoyonlashuviga sabab bo'ladi.

Rozilik (kelishuv) maksimi yuzaga kelgan qarama-qarshiliklarning rivojlanishiga qarshi turishga xizmat qiladi (agar ular bo'lsa), kommunikativ harakatning samarali yakun topishi uchun kelishuvga erishish amalga oshiriladi. Rozilik maksimi – qarshilik ko'rsatmaslik maksimidir.

Ta'kidlash kerakki, maksimlar, ko'pincha, bir-biriga zid keladi. Agar adresat kamtarlik tamoyiliga qat'iy rioya qilishga va iltifotlardan tiyilishga qaror qilsa, u komplimentorga xayrixohlik ko'rsatishning boshqa usullarini topishni qiyinlashtirib, nafaqat saxiylik maksimalini buzgan bo'ladi, balki mazkur jarayonni ziddiyatga olib keladi. Bizning mazkur hukmimiz maksimlarning ham nisbiyligini ko'rsatadi.

Kompliment taktikasini amalga oshirish uchun ko'plab tashabbuskor nutq harakatlari mavjud. Ko'pincha iltifot ikki tomonlama shakllanishdir, chunki u nafaqat komplimentorning baholash iborasini, ya'ni faol nutq kursini, balki unga munosabatni, javob mulohazasini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Javob mulohazalari reaktiv nutq harakatlaridir. Tadqiqotchilar iltifotga ijobiy munosabat bildiruvchi qator holatlarga to'xtaladilar:

- 1) minnatdorchilik izhori;
- 2) iltifotga qo'shilish;
- 3) xursandchilik izhori;
- 4) komplimentni rad etish;
- 5) komplimentga munosabat bildirilmasligi;
- 6) kechirim so'rash;
- 7) mavzuni o'zgartirish;
- 8) ajablanish;
- 9) maqtovnini boshqa shaxsga yo'naltirish.

Demak, iltifot quvonch, hayrat, g'urur, zavqlanish kabi ijobiy his-tuyg'ularni ifodalaydi, bu esa hissiy holatni yaxshilashga yordam berishi kerak. Iltifotlarni turli parametrlarga ko'ra tasniflash mumkin. Jumladan, mavzular

olamiga ko‘ra, eng avvalo, insonning tashqi ko‘rinishiga qarab qilinadigan iltifotlar muhim o‘rin tutadi hamda mazkur holat ko‘plab madaniyatlarda uchraydi.

“*You look so beautiful!*” – “*Siz juda go‘zal ko‘rinasiz!*”

Mazkur iltifot an’anaviy komplimentlardan biri bo‘lib, odatda, juda ko‘p ishlatiladigan maqtovlar sirasiga kiradi.

Quyidagi mulohazalar iltifot qilishning o‘ziga xos va juda nozik masala ekanligini yana bir karra tasdiqlaydi.

Jumladan, professional (kasbiy) iltifotlarni ifodalash masalasida oliy ta’lim muassasasi talabasi hali ishlamayotgan bo‘lsa, qator muammolarga duch kelishi mumkin. Shuning uchun, ushbu holatda axboriy-retseptiv ta’lim metodidan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi. Masalan, quyidagi professional (kasbiy) iltifotni misol tariqasida olaylik. Siz hamkasbingizning kiygan yangi ko‘ylagi chiroyli ekanligini aytdingiz. Biroq iltifotingiz ijobiy tarzda qabul qilinmadi. Aksincha, hamkasbingiz sizdan xafa bo‘ldi. Yoki uning yutuqlarini e’tirof etdingiz, ammo rahmat emas, qo‘pol munosabatga uchradingiz. Kuzatishimizcha, tashqi ko‘rinish bilan bog‘liq umumiy komplimentlar juda sodda ko‘rinsa-da, aslida, ular juda murakkab holatlarni yuzaga keltiradi. Aynan ularni talabalarga o‘rgatayotganda o‘qituvchilar muammoli bayon qilish yoki evristik metodlardan foydalanishlari ma’qul. Zotan, ikkala metodda ham talabaga muammoli vaziyat taqdim etiladi: dastlabkisida o‘qituvchi ssenariy (muammoli vaziyat)ni tanishtirish bilan birga, to‘g‘ri yondashish uchun qator yechimlarni ham berishga harakat qiladi. Ikkinchi holatda esa, o‘quvchilardan izlanishlarini talab qilishi mumkin.

3-diagramma

CHEK TILINI O‘QITISHDA QO‘LLANILADIGAN KOMPLIMENTLARNI O‘RGATISH METODIKASI

Nutq aktlarini auditoriya sharoitida o'qitish natijasida talabalar o'zbek milliy xarakteri, mentaliteti va kommunikativ xatti-harakatlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan tanishish imkoniga ega bo'lishadi. Shuning uchun biz iltifot nafaqat maqsad, balki o'zbek kommunikativ xulq-atvorini uyg'unlashtiruvchi jihatga o'rgatish vositasi bo'lishi kerak, deb hisoblaymiz.

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THE CULTURAL DIMENSION OF EMOTIVE SPEECH

Annotation. Emotive speech is a powerful linguistic tool that transcends mere communication. It evokes feelings, shapes perceptions, and reflects cultural values. Understanding the cultural dimension of emotive speech is essential for students and professionals alike, as it reveals the intricate relationship between language, emotion, and sociocultural contexts.

Key words: emotive speech, expression, behavior, empathy, poetry, conversation.

Annotatsiya. Emotsional nutq-bu shunchaki muloqotdan ustun bo'lgan kuchli lingvistik vosita. Bu hissiyotlarni uyg'otadi, idroklarni shakllantiradi va madaniy qadriyatlarini aks ettiradi. Emotsional nutqning madaniy o'lchovini tushunish talabalar va mutaxassislar uchun juda muhimdir, chunki u til, hissiyot va ijtimoiy-madaniy kontekst o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: hissiy nutq, ifoda, xulq-atvor, hamdardlik, she'riyat, suhbat

Emotive speech refers to language that expresses emotions, including joy, anger, sadness, and excitement. This form of expression is not limited to verbal communication; it encompasses tone, pitch, and body language, all of which contribute to the message being conveyed. Emotive speech can manifest in various forms, such as poetry, speeches, and everyday conversations. It serves to connect individuals, influence behavior, and foster empathy.

The Role of Culture

Culture plays a significant role in shaping emotive speech. Different cultures have unique ways of expressing emotions, influenced by historical, social, and environmental factors. For instance, in some cultures, direct expression of emotions is encouraged, while in others, restraint is valued. This cultural backdrop influences how individuals articulate their feelings and perceptions. In Western cultures, emotive speech is often characterized by directness and explicitness. For example, public speakers in the United States may use passionate rhetoric to engage their audience, employing techniques such as repetition, rhetorical questions, and vivid imagery. In contrast, in many Asian cultures, emotive expression may be more subdued, valuing harmony and collectivism over individual expression. Here, indirect language and non-verbal cues become essential components of communication.

Emotive Speech in Different Contexts. The context in which emotive speech occurs can significantly impact its effectiveness. In political discourse, emotive language can rally support, persuade audiences, and provoke strong reactions. Historical speeches, such as Martin Luther King Jr.'s "I Have a Dream," exemplify the use of emotive speech to inspire change and resonate with collective sentiments. The careful choice of words, combined with emotional delivery, can mobilize communities and create a shared sense of purpose. Conversely, emotive speech in personal relationships often fosters intimacy and understanding. For instance, expressing vulnerability through emotive language can strengthen bonds between individuals. In therapeutic settings, clients may be encouraged to articulate their feelings openly, facilitating healing and self-awareness. Here, emotive speech becomes a means of connecting on a deeper level, fostering trust and empathy.

The Impact of Technology. In the digital age, the landscape of emotive speech is evolving. Social media platforms have transformed how individuals express emotions, creating new forms of communication such as emojis, GIFs, and memes. While these tools can enhance emotive expression, they also present challenges. The lack of non-verbal cues in written communication can lead to misunderstandings and misinterpretations. Cultural differences further complicate this dynamic, as symbols and expressions may carry different meanings across cultures. Moreover, the rapid pace of communication in the digital realm can dilute the emotional weight of messages. The immediacy of social media may encourage brevity over depth, leading to a potential loss of richness in emotive speech. Students and professionals must navigate this complex terrain, balancing the benefits of technology with the nuances of effective emotional expression.

The Future of Emotive Speech. As globalization continues to shape cultural interactions, the future of emotive speech will likely become increasingly multifaceted. Cross-cultural communication will require an awareness of diverse emotive expressions and the ability to adapt one's speech accordingly. Education plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the skills to engage in emotive speech across cultures, fostering empathy and understanding.

In academic settings, students should be encouraged to explore emotive speech within various cultural contexts. Analyzing literature, speeches, and everyday interactions can provide valuable insights into the cultural dimensions of emotion. Collaborative projects that involve diverse perspectives can further enhance students' understanding of how emotive speech functions across cultures.

The cultural dimension of emotive speech is a rich field of study that encompasses language, emotion, and cultural values. As students and professionals engage with this topic, they will gain a deeper appreciation for the power of emotive language and its ability to connect people across cultures. By understanding the nuances of emotive speech, individuals can navigate the complexities of communication, fostering empathy and building bridges in an increasingly interconnected world.

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THE WORLD SCENE IN FILM DISCOURSE

Key words: world scene, identities, sociopolitical contexts, cultures, stereotypes, discourse, films.

Annotation

The concept of the “world scene” in film discourse has become an essential framework for understanding how cinema constructs, interprets, and reshapes global realities. As films circulate across borders with unprecedented speed, they form a shared visual vocabulary through which audiences imagine the world. The world scene is not merely the geographical setting of a film; it is a cultural, political, and narrative space shaped by filmmakers’ perspectives, sociopolitical contexts, and evolving global dynamics.[2] Through this lens, cinema becomes both a mirror and a maker of the world.

Аннотация

Концепция «картина мира» в кинодискурсе стала важнейшей основой для понимания того, как кино конструирует, интерпретирует и переосмысливает глобальные реалии. Поскольку фильмы пересекают границы с беспрецедентной скоростью, они формируют общий визуальный словарь, с помощью которого зрители представляют себе мир. Картина мира — это не просто географическое пространство фильма; это культурное, политическое и повествовательное пространство, формируемое взглядами кинематографистов, социально-политическим контекстом и меняющейся глобальной динамикой. Благодаря этой призме кино становится одновременно зеркалом и творцом мира.

Annotatsiya

Kino nutqidagi “olam manzarasi” tushunchasi kino global voqelikni qanday qurishi, sharhlashi va qayta shakllantirilishini tushunish uchun muhim asosga aylandi. Filmlar chegaralar bo'ylab misli ko'rilmagan tezlikda aylanar ekan, ular tomoshabinlar dunyoni tasavvur qiladigan umumiy vizual lug'atni hosil qiladi. Olam manzarasi shunchaki filmning geografik joylashuvi emas; bu kino ijodkorlarining istiqbollari, ijtimoiy-siyosiy kontekstlari va rivojlanayotgan

global dinamikasi asosida shakllangan madaniy, siyosiy va kontekstual makondir. Bu obyektiv orqali kino dunyoning ham ko'zgasiga, ham yaratuvchisiga aylanadi.

1. Defining the World Scene

The “world scene” refers to the representation of global spaces, identities, and power structures within a film. It includes how nations and regions are portrayed, how cultures interact on screen, how global problems are narrated, and how cinematic languages travel across cultures. Seen this way, the world scene functions as a discursive space where filmmakers construct meaning and situate local experiences within global narratives.[6]

2. Globalization and the Expansion of Film Discourse

Globalization has transformed film discourse in three major ways:

2.1. Transnational Production

Many films today are financed, shot, and produced across multiple countries. This blurs national cinematic identities and situates the narrative within a global economic framework.

2.2. Cultural Hybridization

Filmmakers mix narrative traditions, genres, and styles from different cultures. For example, Hollywood action conventions merge with Asian choreography or African storytelling structures, contributing to a global cinematic lexicon.[12]

2.3. Worldwide Distribution

Streaming platforms and international film festivals allow films from diverse regions to gain global visibility. As a result, stories from the Global South, indigenous communities, and diasporic cultures increasingly shape the world scene.

3. Representing Space and Power

Scenes set in global environments often reflect deeper power relations.

3.1. Stereotypes and Geopolitical Narratives

Historically, films have often represented other cultures through exoticism or political bias.[5] Orientalist depictions, Cold War narratives, and simplified portrayals of the “Third World” shaped public perceptions of entire regions.

3.2. Reclaiming the Frame

Contemporary filmmakers challenge these representations by offering alternative viewpoints. Independent filmmakers from Asia, Africa, Latin America, and the Middle East reimagine their own regions, disrupting Western-controlled global imagery.

3.3. Migration and Diaspora

Cinematic depictions of migration reveal how individuals navigate global inequalities. Stories of dislocation and identity negotiation contribute to a new understanding of the world scene.

4. Narratives of the Planetary and the Human

Films increasingly address global issues that transcend borders, such as climate change, pandemics, war, terrorism, and economic inequality. These subjects shift

film discourse toward a planetary perspective, where humanity's shared challenges become central narrative elements.[2]

5. The Audience and the Global Imagination

The world scene also transforms how audiences interpret films.

5.1. Cross-Cultural Readings

Audiences bring their own cultural backgrounds to the viewing experience, creating multiple interpretations of the same film.

5.2. Empathy and Identification

Global narratives allow viewers to emotionally connect with distant cultures and issues, expanding the collective imagination of the world.

5.3. The Digital Public Sphere

Social media and online film criticism have globalized discussion, enabling voices from diverse cultures to influence film discourse.

Conclusion

The world scene in film discourse reflects cinema's evolving role in shaping global consciousness. As film becomes increasingly transnational, hybrid, and interconnected, it constructs new ways of imagining the world and our place within it. Through diverse narratives and visual strategies, filmmakers contribute to an ever-expanding discourse that transcends national borders and invites audiences to engage with global realities. The world scene, therefore, is not a static concept but a dynamic field that evolves as the world itself changes.

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DISCOURSE MARKERS IN SOCIAL MEDIA CONVERSATIONS

Abstract. The function of discourse markers and interactional aspects in social media conversations is examined in this thesis, which focuses on how users use language and paralinguistic components to regulate interaction, organize information, and build social relationships in digital situations. With the introduction of new interactional tools like likes, emoticons, tags, and reactions that influence discourse structure and coherence, social media platforms like Instagram, Telegram, Twitter, and TikTok have revolutionized interpersonal communication. The study emphasizes how discourse markers like *as well*, *so*, *like*, *actually*, *anyway*, and digital equivalents like emojis, hashtags, and abbreviations contribute to coherence, stance-taking, politeness, turn-taking, and identity performance.

Key words: Discourse markers; social media discourse; interactional features; digital communication; pragmatics; multimodality; online interaction; discourse analysis

Introduction

New forms of communication that combine oral, written, and visual modalities have been brought about by the quick development of social media. In addition to serving as venues for material sharing, social media platforms like Instagram, Telegram, Facebook, Twitter (X), and TikTok also serve as interactive settings where users negotiate meaning, build relationships, and express their

identities. Social media interactions take place asynchronously¹, publicly, and multimodally, in contrast to conventional face-to-face communication. In these settings, linguistic resources like discourse markers and interactional aspects become essential for preserving coherence and controlling social interaction.

Discourse Markers in Social Media Conversations

According to Gao, discourse markers (DMs) are statements that help the reader or listener understand how an utterance fits into the larger discourse without altering its propositional meaning².

They give a signal: Transitions; topic; changes; elaboration; emphasis; position; kindness; agreement or disagreement; mitigation; coherence.

DMs have the same functions on social media, but they take place in a digital, multimodal setting.

Traditional Linguistic Discourse Markers

a. Textual Markers

Information is arranged and interaction is structured by these markers.

For instance: So (conclusion, continuation); well (response marker, hesitation); anyway (closing a topic; returning to main point); and, but, or (connective discourse markers).³

Example from social media: So I finally tried the new update... honestly, it's not bad.

b. Interpersonal Markers

These markers express attitudes, emotions, and stance.

Examples:

actually (correction, emphasis); like (approximation, softening); I mean (clarification); you know (assumed shared knowledge)

For example: *I mean, the movie was good but not as good as people said.*

b. Cognitive and Hesitation Markers

Used to show uncertainty, thinking processes, or hedging⁴.

Examples:

- uh, um (rare in typed text but appear as “uhhh”, “ummm”)
- kind of, maybe, sort of

Example: *Umm I don't think this is a great idea...*

Such markers soften criticism and reduce conflict in public threads.

Conclusion

¹ Hiltz, S. R., & Wellman, B. (1997). Asynchronous learning networks as a virtual classroom. *Communications of the ACM*, 40(9), 44-49.

² Gao, Y. (2023). Analyse the Function of Discourse Markers Using in Naturally Occurring Discourses and Planned Speeches. In *SHS Web of Conferences* (Vol. 179, p. 01027). EDP Sciences.

³ Zappavigna, M. I. C. H. E. L. E. (2021). Discourse and social media. *The Bloomsbury handbook of discourse analysis*, 295-309.

⁴ De Leeuw, E. (2007). Hesitation markers in english, german, and dutch. *Journal of Germanic Linguistics*, 19(2), 85-114.

Social media communication is greatly influenced by interactional elements and discourse markers. A rich, hybrid discourse system is produced by the interaction of traditional linguistic indicators with digital

This thesis highlights the need for linguists to view social media discourse as a unique and dynamic linguistic environment where meaning is co-constructed through multimodal and interactional resources. Future research may focus on platform-specific discourse, algorithmic mediation, and cross-cultural differences in digital interaction.

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THE ROLE OF ABBREVIATIONS IN ENGLISH ONLINE ADVERTISEMENTS

Abstract. *This thesis is devoted to the study of abbreviations in online advertisements of today's world. As they have already become one of the most crucial parts in the field of advertising, it is a must to learn about the works of other scholars to understand explicit functions and massive use of abbreviations. While exploring, we studied numerous features of shortened forms of words and provided our own perspectives along with some examples for abbreviations.*

Key words: *abbreviations, brands, messages, internet.*

Introduction. According to Cambridge dictionary, the term "abbreviation" means a short form of a word or phrase. It is applied with the purpose of decreasing words or phrases so that they can easily be read and written. While an acronym is considered a specific kind of shortened form that utilizes the initial letters of words within a phrase and can be pronounced like a word. An abbreviation can either be shortened words like "Dr." which refers to Doctor or shortened forms of phrases such as "vs." which refers to versus, while an acronym refers to using initial letters to make words like NASA (National Aeronautics and

Space Administration) or laser (light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation).

Main part. In today's extremely developing world the usage of abbreviations in English advertisements is increasing. In turn, there are several functions of them as **fitting character limits and increasing virality**. **For example, Twitter/X platforms have limited characters and branded messages utilize abbreviations to fit an entire message into one status update** as B1G1 for "buy one get one" or ETA 5 mins for "estimated time of arrival". One of well-known linguists, Geoffrey Leech¹ whose perspective corresponds with Guy Cook's² findings underlines that advertising language follows an economy principle, which means advertisers try to express a message in a few words and with high efficiency as possible. Since advertisements often appear in very limited spaces as social media posts or pop-up advertisements, the need for text reduction becomes essential and abbreviations turn out to be one of the most effective means at that moment. By using abbreviations like FB, DM, ASAP, or even promotional abbreviations like 50% OFF it is possible for audience to comprehend great amount of information both swiftly and precisely. In addition, the short forms are not only space-saving but they can also attract the reader's attention making the message easier to remember and enhance the general persuasive power of the ad. In addition, Goddard³ claims abbreviations in the advertisements not only as a means of saving space but also as a certain branding image. Because, the use of abbreviations makes advertisements sound quick and energetic, which is suitable for the fast pace of life today. This makes brands as modern and connected with today's culture. Abbreviations help to show these social meanings like being trendy and make the brand seem closer and more relatable to its audience. Similarly, David Crystal describes abbreviations and other graphic conventions function as **identity markers** of those who are familiar with the norms of the electronic community".⁴ As he claims, such abbreviations as LOL, OMG, BTW, and DIY are not just a limitation of the short form used while communicating on the internet. While using those abbreviations, the person reveals themselves as a part of the online world and being familiar with the net communication style. Therefore, social media advertisers often make use of such abbreviations with the intent of sounding friendly, modern, and just like their audience—mostly young people to make them feel included. Whenever brands write, "OMG Sale!" or "DM us ASAP" they want users to feel that the brand is a part of their digital community. This way, audiences are able to gain trust in a brand and feel closer to it.

¹ Leech, G. 1966. *English in Advertising: A Linguistic Study of Advertising in Great Britain*. Longman.

² Cook, G. 2001. *The Discourse of Advertising*. Routledge.

³ Goddard, A. 1998. *The Language of Advertising*. Routledge.

⁴ Crystal, D. 2001. *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge University Press.

According to Zappavigna, these abbreviations of hashtags, like #tbt, #ootd, #fyp, among other short forms, help build online communities. Abbreviations are shared symbols joining users of similar interests or trends and using or searching for such hashtags can make users part of a larger conversation that is happening beyond the confines of their social media networks. Therefore, advertisers use these short-form hashtags to join these conversations and make their messages easier to find. In using trending short-form hashtags within their posts, brands make themselves suitable for social media behavior and gain greater attention. This leads the advertisement to go further because the hashtag connects the brand's message to a larger, already active online trend. Due to these essential features brands will systematically employ abbreviations in their social media promotions in order to increase the reach, visibility, and user engagement.

Conclusion. In the end, abbreviations play a significant role in online advertising nowadays. They save space, make messages faster to read, and help brands sound modern and closer to their audience. As scholars point out, short forms like DM, ASAP, or OMG do not only deliver information but also create a friendly and trendy image. By using such language, brands become closer to young users and fit naturally into the fast, digital style of communication.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA KONNOTATSIYANING LINGVOPRAGMATIK ASOSLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida fonetik vositalarda ifodalangan konnotativ ma'nolar tahlili va tadqiqi masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: konnotatsiya, fonostilistika, ingerent, adgerent, akustik, artikulyatsion, intonatsiya, hissiy ta'sirchanlik.

Til inson tafakkuri, ruhiyati, madaniyati, urf-odati va shaxsiy xususiyatlari bilan bog'liq hodisadir. Tilshunoslar tilda ikki xil ma'no: denotativ (atash) va konnotativ (qo'shimcha) ma'no mavjudligini qayd etadilar [1, 83-85]. So'zning atash ma'nosi, ya'ni denotativ ma'no dunyo tilshunosligida keng o'rganilgan. Ammo tilda denotativ ma'nodan tashqari so'zning konnotativ ma'nosi borligi tilshunoslarni ancha vaqtdan buyon qiziqtirib keladi. Konnotatsiya so'zi dastlab

XIX asrning o'rtalarida sinonimik lug'atlar nazariyasi va ularni yaratish amaliyoti bilan bog'liq bo'lgan ingliz leksiografik adabiyotida qo'llanilgan. O'zbek tilshunosligida ham konnotativ ma'noning leksik va frazeologik, morfologik va fonetik birliklarga xosligi haqida fikrlar bayon qilingan [2, 78].

Til fikr anglatish quroli bo'lishi bilan birga, insonlarga hissiy ta'sir qilish vositasi hamdir. Bu ta'sir so'zlardagi asosiy (denotativ) ma'noga asoslangan qo'shimcha (konnotativ) ma'nolar vositasida amalga oshadi. Konnotatsiya til birliklari semantikasiga kiruvchi semantik mavjudlik bo'lib, u nutq sub'ektining borliqqa emotiv baholash va uslubiy munosabatini ifoda etadi [3, 6]. So'zning semantik strukturasi o'rganishda ikki xil konnotatsiya mavjud: ingerent konnotatsiya –so'z kontekstdan tashqari olingan hollarda unga xos bo'lgan konnotativ ma'no va adgerent konnotatsiya –so'zda ma'lum kontekstda hosil bo'ladigan konnotativ ma'no. Konnotativ ma'no komponentlarini tashkil qiluvchi "bo'yoqlar" fonetik vositalarda ham kuchli ifodalanadi. Bular:

1) nutq tovushlari talaffuzi bilan bog'liq ekspressivlikning aks etishi; so'zlarning tovush qiyofasini o'zgartirib aytish, so'zlarda tovush orttirish yoki tushirish, alliteratsiya orqali hayajon ifodalash va hokazo;

2) baho komponenti –so'zda tasdiq yoki inkorni intonatsiya orqali ifodalash;

3) so'zda belgi (miqdor) darajasining kuchliligini bildiruvchi tovush cho'ziqligi;

4) so'zlovchining shaxs va hodisalarga nisbatan turlicha munosabatini ifodalovchi pragmatik ma'no, ya'ni geminatsiya yoki pauzalar orqali qo'shimcha bo'yoq ifodalash [4,7].

Nutq organlariga bog'liq ravishda nutq tovushlari ham turlicha talaffuz etiladi va eshitiladi. Fonostilistik jihatidan nutq tovushlarining talaffuzidagi emotsional-ekspressivlik va akustik (eshitib) ta'sirlanish tomonlarini o'rganish muhimdir [5,16].

Badiiy tasvirda personaj nutqida unli tovushlarning turlicha talaffuzi, intonatsiya bilan aytilishi, bo'g'in hosil qilishi, urg'u qabul qilishi kabi prosodik xususiyatlari qator konnotativ ma'nolarni hosil qiladi.

I unli fonemasidan hosil bo'ladigan konnotativ ma'nolar ko'p va darajalangan bo'ladi. Shuningdek, i fonemasi ham qattiq va yumshoq variantlarga ega ekanligi konnotativ ma'no miqdorini oshiradi. Bular quyidgilar: esankirash, to'lqinlanish, bezovtalik, ajablanish, hayrat, ishonchsizlik, kutilmaganlik, g'azab, o'ylab qolish, xursandlik, xafalik, xadixsirash, eslash va hokazo. O'zbek tilidagi i fonemasiga xos bo'lgan konnotativ ma'nolar ingliz tilidagi i fonemasi talaffuzidagi konnotativ ma'nolar bilan qiyoslanganda, ularda ba'zi o'xshashlik va farqli tomonlar ko'zga tashlanadi.

Ingliz tilida nutq jarayonida u [ju:] fonemasini cho'zish orqali taajjub, ikkilanish, hayratlanish, ishonchsizlik kabi ma'nolar paydo bo'ladi:

-Tush! Where are the others?

-At the front.

-Quite right. Why aren't you ... at the front?

-Over age. Fifty-seven. (B. Show)

Ingliz tilidagi o [ou] unli tovushini cho'zib talaffuz qilish orqali qo'rqish, dovdirash, kuchli g'azab, iltimos, yalinish kabi konnotativ ma'nolar ifodalanadi.

Masalan:

Don't tell him – Do-o-o-n't tell him please!

Shunday qilib, konnotativ ma'no so'z semantik strukturasi tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Konnotativ ma'no unli va undosh fonemalarining variantlarida yorqin namoyon bo'ladi.

Tarjimashunoslikda yuqorida qayd qilingan holatlar inobatga olinsa, badiiy asarlar tarjimasi shirali, ta'sirchan va o'qimishli bo'ladi.

Adabiyotlar.

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EUPHEMISM AND PERIPHRAISIS

Abstract: This article examines the relationship between euphemism and periphrasis, two important linguistic phenomena that contribute to the expressiveness, politeness, and aesthetic quality of speech. Drawing on Uzbek and international linguistic research, the paper explores definitions, classifications, and functions of periphrasis, as well as its interaction with euphemism. Special attention is given to how both devices beautify expression, mitigate negative meanings, and reflect cultural norms. Examples from Uzbek and English illustrate the semantic, stylistic, and pragmatic roles of periphrastic and euphemistic units.

Keywords: periphrasis, euphemism, stylistics, linguistic expression, Uzbek linguistics, figurative language, semantic transformation, cultural pragmatics

At every stage of history, attractive, meaningful, and eloquent speech has captivated human beings. In interpersonal communication and information

exchange, speakers have always taken into account the norms of etiquette appropriate to the Uzbek people—politeness, gentleness, protecting the interlocutor’s feelings, choosing words carefully, and considering factors such as the listener’s age, social status, psychological state, the place and time of communication. The syntactic shaping of such expressions is directly related to the goal of enhancing the expressiveness of certain concepts in speech.

The phenomenon of periphrasis has been extensively studied in world linguistics, and various definitions have been proposed. In the 1950s, Russian linguists I.Z. Ilina¹ and V.P. Utkina² discussed periphrasis as a linguistic phenomenon describing events through alternative linguistic means. From the 1970s onward, interest in the specific characteristics of periphrasis increased. Early research on periphrasis is reflected in the work of V.P. Grigoryev³, who examined it from the perspective of the relationship between word–image–denotatum. He described periphrasis as “one of the most vivid, interesting, and promising means of creating poetic speech.” Y.D. Apresyan’s⁴ interpretation of the nature of periphrastic transformation also attracted broad academic attention. According to him, humans naturally possess the ability to periphrastically express reality through concepts and imagery, demonstrating this with numerous examples.

From the 1980s, research on periphrasis intensified. Scholars began to investigate its formation methods, thematic groups, and semantic-structural types, as well as its use in religious texts and in the works of specific authors⁵. Catherine Fuchs studied periphrasis based on locutive, pragmatic, and symbolic functions⁶. According to her, the locutive function concerns information delivery; the pragmatic function depends on the speaker’s aim and the communicative situation; and the symbolic function characterizes the representation of events in literary texts.

¹ Ильина И.З. Перифраз и его стилистические функции в произведениях английской художественной литературы: Автореф. дисс. ...канд. филол. наук. – Москва, 1954. – С. 24.

² Уткина В.П. Перифрастический оборот в русской художественной литературе // Известия Крымского педагогического института им. М.В. Фрунзе. – Т. 33, Вып. 1. – Симферополь. 1959. – С. 87-109.

³ Григорьев В.П. К проблеме перифразы // Сб. докл. и сообщений лингвистического общества. – Калинин, 1974. – С.158.

⁴ Апресян Ю.Д. Синонимические средства языка и правила перифразирования. // Русский язык в национальной школе, 1972, № 3, – С.19-27.

⁵ Базарская Н.И. Вторичная номинация в системе языковых знаков: (На материале перифраз английского и русского языков): Автореф. дисс... канд. филол. наук. – Саратов, 1988. – 16 с.

⁶ Fuchs C.A. *parafraze lingustica: Equivalencia, sinonimia ou reformulacao?* // *Cadernos de estudos ling.* Campinas, 1985. N 8. – P. 129-134.

Linguistics contains many interpretations of this phenomenon, and we find it appropriate to mention a few. The word periphrasis comes from the Greek word *paraphrasis*, meaning “figurative expression” in Uzbek¹. H. Shamsiddinov also emphasized in his reflections that this term should be used consistently and refers to this phenomenon precisely by this name².

Another noteworthy definition of periphrasis is given by the lexicographer O.S. Akhmanova³. In her linguistic dictionary, edited under her supervision, periphrasis is explained as “a type of figurative substitution in which a word is replaced by a descriptive expression.”

Periphrasis entered Uzbek linguistic studies as a stylistic phenomenon through the work “O‘zbek tili stilistikasi”, authored by R. Qo‘ng‘urov⁴. He defined periphrasis as follows: “...periphrasis refers to describing people’s names or the names of other objects not directly, but through various words or figurative expressions. This term is also known as *perifraza*, *parafraz*, *parafraza*.” I. Umirov attempted to study periphrasis in its entirety in his doctoral dissertation. He classified periphrastic expressions as follows: a) by formation method – lexical, phraseological, syntactic, logical, pure, and contextual periphrasis;

b) by semantics – periphrasis that denotes an author’s name, mastery in a profession, a person’s social role, an idea or theme in a literary work, etc⁵.

The scholar also thoroughly examined the relationship of periphrasis with related phenomena such as euphemism, professional vocabulary, synonymy, and phraseology. Indeed, euphemism and periphrasis are closely related phenomena: both beautify language and enrich expressive means used to describe reality.

In her research on “Characteristics of medical periphrasis in English and Uzbek linguocultures,” linguist A.B. Qobilova focuses on representing objects of reality through national periphrastic euphemisms in English and Uzbek. According to the researcher, periphrasis embellishes the depiction of objects or events, whereas euphemisms serve to soften or mitigate negative meanings. In this sense, she refers to the joint operation of these two related phenomena as the process of “euphemistic periphrasis⁶.”

For example, many people soften the emotional weight of the word *o‘lim* by using euphemistic expressions to avoid hurting the feelings of relatives or family members. This tendency is observed in both languages being studied. For

¹ Аҳмадова У. Ш. Перифразаларнинг социал хосланиши: филология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси.– Бухоро, 2021. – 150 б.

² Шамсиддинов Х. Перифраза хусусида айрим мулоҳазалар // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. 1993, № 4. – Б. 29-35.

³ Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. – М., 1996. – С. 312.

⁴ Қўнғуров Р. Ўзбек тили стилистикаси. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1983. – Б. 148.

⁵ Умиров И. Ўзбек тили перифразалари. Филол.фан. номз. дисс. автореф. – Тошкент, 1996. – 23 б.

⁶ Қобилова А.Б. Инглиз ва ўзбек лингвомаданиятида тиббий перифразаларнинг хусусиятлари. фил.фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори диссерт. – Бухоро, 2022, – 162 б.

instance, in Uzbek, instead of o‘lgan, expressions such as vafot etgan and o‘tgan are used; similarly, in American speech, the idea is expressed as have gone to a better place.

Based on the above analysis, we now discuss several types of periphrasis:

Lexical periphrasis – In this type, a single descriptive word is used in place of another. For example: tergovchi – izquvar, yozuvchi – qalamkash, alpinist – qoyao‘shar, Amir Temur – sohibqiron. In English, single-word periphrases are less common than in Uzbek.

Syntactic periphrasis – Here, word combinations function as periphrasis. The linguistic units within such expressions enter semantic-syntactic relations that create imagery. For example: Uzbek: televizor – oynai jahon, gazeta – hayot ko‘zgusi

English: Earth – blue planet, oil – black gold, potatoes – second bread. From these examples, it becomes clear that periphrasis contains more imagery compared to euphemism. While both phenomena are interconnected, periphrasis embellishes and vividly portrays objects or events, whereas euphemistic devices reduce negativity and “mask” unpleasant meanings.

In conclusion, language plays an invaluable role in human communication. Avoiding emotionally hurtful words and using expressive combinations enriches one’s vocabulary and ensures diversity and colorfulness of speech.

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ANTROPONIMLARNING LINGVISTIK AHAMIYATI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada antroponimlarning lingvokulturologik, kognitiv hamda tarixiy jihatlarini ilmiy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilinadi. Maqola antroponimlarning jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy funksiyalari, ularning tarixiy-madaniy ahamiyati va globalizatsiya sharoitida yuz berayotgan o‘zgarishlarini har

tomonlarga ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: antroponimlar, lingvomadaniyat, kognitiv tahlil, etimologiya, shaxsiy ism, familiya, identitet, globalizatsiya.

Antroponimika onomastikaning ixtisoslashgan tarmog'i bo'lib, shaxs nomlarini, jumladan, ismlar, familiyalar, laqablar va insonni belgilovchi boshqa shakllarni o'rganish bilan shug'ullanadi. Antroponimlarning lingvistik tahlili madaniy, tarixiy va ijtimoiy jarayonlar haqida qimmatli tushunchalar beradi. Tadqiqotchilar turli tillar va madaniy kontekstlarda shaxs nomlarining tuzilishi, kelib chiqishi va qo'llanilishini o'rganish uchun keng qamrovli metodologiyalarni qo'llaydilar. Ushbu maqola antroponimik tadqiqotlarda qo'llaniladigan asosiy lingvistik yondashuvlarni tahlil qiladi, ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi va ilmiy ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Tavsifiy metod: Tavsifiy metod ma'lum bir til yoki madaniy kontekst doirasidagi antroponimlarni tizimli ravishda qayd etish va tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu yondashuv ismlarni kataloglashga, ularning morfologik tuzilmalarini aniqlashga va semantik mazmunini talqin qilishga katta e'tibor qaratadi. Ismlarning tarkibiy elementlarini o'rganish orqali tilshunoslar nom berish amaliyotlaridagi takrorlanuvchi naqshlar va an'analarni aniqlay oladilar.

Qiyosiy tahlil: Qiyosiy tahlil antroponimlarni turli tillar yoki dialektlar bo'yicha tizimli ravishda o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu jarayonda ham o'xshashliklar, ham farqlar aniqlanadi. Bu yondashuv tilshunoslarga ismlarning tarixiy rivojlanishini kuzatish, madaniyatlararo o'zlashish va ta'sirlarni o'rganish, shuningdek shaxs nomlarining dastlabki shakllarini qayta tiklash imkonini beradi. Qiyosiy metod tarixiy tilshunoslikda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynagan, tadqiqotchilarga lingvistik aloqalarni o'rnatish va proto-tillarni qayta tiklashda yordam bergan. Kognitiv-Kontseptual Tahlil: Kognitiv-kontseptual tahlil antroponimlarga bog'liq bo'lgan aqliy tasavvurlar va kontseptual doiralarni o'rganadi. Bu yondashuv shaxs nomlari madaniy bilimlar, ijtimoiy rollar va shaxsiy o'zlikni qanday mujassam etishini tekshiradi. Nom berish amaliyotlarining negizini tashkil etuvchi kognitiv tuzilmalarni tadqiq qilish orqali tadqiqotchilar nomlar jamiyatning dunyoqarashi doirasida qanday faoliyat ko'rsatishini chuqur anglashlari mumkin.

Lingvokultural tahlil: Lingvokultural tahlil antroponimlarni yaratish va qo'llashda til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganadi. Bu yondashuv madaniy amaliyotlar, e'tiqodlar va qadriyatlar nom berish an'analarni qanday shakllantirishini, va o'z navbatida, ismlar madaniy o'zlikning jihatlarini qanday ifodalashini tadqiq qiladi.

Morfologik metod: Morfologik metod antroponimlarning tuzilishi va shakllanishiga, ayniqsa prefikslar, suffikslar va o'zak elementlarga e'tibor qaratadi. Bu yondashuv tilshunoslarga ismlar qanday qurilganligini va ularning morfologik komponentlari ma'noga qanday hissa qo'shishini tushunishga imkon beradi. Masalan, rus, qozoq va turk tillaridagi antroponimlarni o'rgangan bir tadqiqot kichraytirish (diminutive) suffikslari va affikslarini ko'rib chiqib, ismlardagi morfologik o'zgarishlar hissiy va ijtimoiy nozikliklarni qanday

ifodalashini ko'rsatdi.

Komponent

tahlili: Komponent tahlili antroponimlarni ularning fundamental semantik elementlariga ajratib, ularning ma'nolarini va o'zaro bog'liqliklarini o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu yondashuv tadqiqotchilarga nomning umumiy ahamiyatiga hissa qo'shadigan asosiy komponentlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Statistik metod: Statistik metod ma'lum bir korpusdagi antroponimlarning chastotasi, tarqalishi va namunalari (shakllari)ni o'rganish uchun miqdoriy usullarni qo'llaydi. Bu yondashuv tadqiqotchilarga nom berish amaliyotlarini shakllantiruvchi tendensiyalar, mintaqaviy farqlar va ijtimoiy omillarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Bu metod lingvistik gipotezalarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan va madaniy talqinlarni shakllantiradigan empirik dalillarni taqdim etadi.

Etimologik tahlil: Etimologik tahlil antroponimlarning tarixiy kelib chiqishi va evolyutsiyasini o'rganadi, shaxs nomlari vaqt o'tishi bilan qanday rivojlanganiga e'tibor qaratadi. Bu yondashuv lingvistik o'zaklar, tarixiy hujjatlar va ismlar bilan bog'liq fonologik o'zgarishlarni o'rganishni o'z ichiga oladi.

Sotsiolingvistik yondashuv: Sotsiolingvistik yondashuv til va jamiyat o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni o'rganadi, bunda ijtimoiy omillar nom berish amaliyotlarini qanday shakllantirishiga urg'u beriladi. Bu metod antroponimlarni tahlil qilishda jins, yosh, etnik mansublik va ijtimoiy maqom kabi o'zgaruvchilarni hisobga oladi. Shaxs nomlarining sotsiolingvistik o'lchovlarini o'rganish orqali tadqiqotchilar nomlar o'zlik, ijtimoiy mansublik va madaniy meros belgisi sifatida qanday xizmat qilishini chuqur anglashlari mumkin. Bu yondashuv nom berish amaliyotlarining dinamik tabiati va ularning ijtimoiy o'zaro munosabatlardagi ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Antroponimlar lingvistik jihatdan o'rganish shaxs nomlari va ularning jamiyatdagi ahamiyati haqida chuqur anglash imkonini beradi. Har bir metodologik yondashuv — tavsifiy, qiyosiy, kognitiv-kontseptual, lingvokultural, morfologik, komponent tahlili, statistik, etimologik va sotsiolingvistik — ismlarning tuzilishi, ma'nosi va madaniy konteksti haqida alohida tushunchalar taqdim etadi. Bu xilma-xil metodlarni birlashtirish orqali tadqiqotchilar nom berish amaliyotlarining har tomonlama tahlilini o'tkazishi, til, madaniyat hamda individual va kollektiv o'zlik o'rtasidagi murakkab o'zaro bog'liqliklarni ochib berish imkonini beradi.

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THE PRAGMATIC AND COMMUNICATIVE FEATURES OF USING PILGRIMAGE TOURISM TERMS IN DISCOURSE

Annotation: This article examines the pragmatic and communicative features of using programmatorism terms within professional and educational discourse. It analyses how programming-related terminology functions in real communication, focusing on clarity, context, speaker intention, and the effectiveness of message delivery. Special attention is paid to the role of programmatorism terms in structuring meaning, reducing ambiguity, and enhancing professional interaction between instructors, learners, and specialists. The study also explores the influence of extralinguistic factors on the interpretation of such terms and identifies strategies for their efficient usage in academic and practical settings.

Keywords: programmatorism terms, pragmatics, communication, discourse, terminology, context, professional interaction

ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЕ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕРМИНОВ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА

Аннотация: В данной работе рассматриваются прагматические и коммуникативные особенности использования терминов программаторизма в профессиональном и образовательном дискурсе. Анализируется функционирование терминологии, связанной с программированием, в реальном общении с точки зрения понятности, контекста, коммуникативного намерения говорящего и эффективности передачи информации. Особое внимание уделяется роли терминов программаторизма в структурировании смысла, снижении неоднозначности и повышении качества профессионального взаимодействия между преподавателем, обучающимися и специалистами. Исследуются также экстралингвистические факторы, влияющие на интерпретацию данных терминов, и определяются стратегии их эффективного использования в академической и практической среде.

Ключевые слова: термины программаторизма, прагматика, коммуникация, дискурс, терминология, контекст, профессиональное взаимодействие

ZIYORAT TURIZMI TERMINLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING PRAGMATIK VA KOMMUNIKATIV XUSUSIYATLARI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada programmatorizm terminlarining professional va ta'limiy diskursdagi pragmatik hamda kommunikativ xususiyatlari o'rganiladi.

Dasturlashga oid terminlarning real muloqotdagi funksiyalari — mazmunning aniqligi, kontekstga mosligi, soʻzlovchining maqsadi va xabar yetkazish samaradorligi nuqtai nazaridan tahlil qilinadi. Programmatorizm terminlarining maʼno tuzishda, noaniqlikni kamaytirishda va oʻqituvchi, talaba hamda mutaxassislar oʻrtasidagi professional muloqotni kuchaytirishdagi roli alohida yoritiladi. Shuningdek, ushbu terminlarni talqin qilishga taʼsir etuvchi ekstralingvistik omillar va ularni samarali qoʻllash strategiyalari ham koʻrib chiqiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: programmatorizm terminlari, pragmatika, kommunikatsiya, diskurs, terminologiya, kontekst, professional

Pilgrimage tourism represents one of the most ancient and deeply rooted forms of human mobility, reflecting spiritual motivations, cultural memory, and collective identity. In modern linguistics, the terminology associated with pilgrimage tourism has gained new relevance due to the expansion of religious travel, the development of global tourism infrastructure, and the increasing need for precise, contextually appropriate communication among experts, guides, scholars, marketing professionals, and international visitors. Understanding the pragmatic and communicative features of pilgrimage tourism terms is essential for improving discourse clarity, ensuring culturally sensitive interaction, and enabling effective transmission of specialized knowledge in multilingual and multicultural environments. The use of pilgrimage tourism terms is shaped by communicative intentions, discourse setting, participants' background knowledge, and the situational context in which these terms are applied. Pragmatically, these terms serve not merely as lexical units but as tools for constructing meaning, building trust, and guiding behavior in sacred spaces. Communicative efficiency in this domain depends on the appropriate choice of specialized vocabulary, the ability to adapt terms to diverse audiences, and the awareness of cultural and religious nuances embedded in the terminology. Pilgrimage tourism terminology includes a wide range of lexical items: religious terms denoting sacred sites, rituals, artifacts, and spiritual concepts; tourism-oriented terms related to travel organization, accommodation, and guidance; and hybrid terms that combine both religious and tourism-related semantic components. The pragmatic use of these terms requires sensitivity to the interlocutor's cultural background, spiritual orientation, and linguistic proficiency. For example, the term "ziyarat" may function differently when addressed to a local community familiar with Islamic traditions versus an international tourist with limited knowledge of religious practices. Communicatively, the terms must balance informativeness with accessibility, avoiding misinterpretations that could arise from culturally loaded meanings. Since pilgrimage tourism often involves emotionally charged contexts, terminology must be used in a manner that maintains respect, avoids offense, and aligns with the expectations of visitors and host communities. Therefore, the speaker's pragmatic competence plays a crucial role in modulating tone,

politeness strategies, and the degree of detail when using pilgrimage-related terms. Another important feature is the role of context in determining meaning. Many pilgrimage tourism terms are polysemantic or metaphorically extended; for instance, words referring to “path,” “purification,” or “destination” carry both literal and spiritual meanings. The communicative success of these terms depends on how well the speaker can navigate these layers of meaning within the situational discourse. In guiding discourse, such as during tours of sacred sites, terminology serves instructional, interpretive, and ritual functions: it directs movement, explains religious practices, and reinforces the symbolic significance of the location. The guide’s pragmatic strategy often involves adjusting terminology to match the cognitive level of the group, using simpler explanations for beginners and more specialized terms for advanced audiences. The communicative function also extends to promotional discourse, such as brochures, tourism websites, and digital platforms, where terminology must capture both the spiritual uniqueness and the tourism value of the destination. In such contexts, the pragmatic aim is often persuasion—encouraging visitors to choose a pilgrimage route while maintaining respect for its sacred nature. Terminology here must strike a balance between marketing appeal and cultural authenticity. Moreover, the rise of international pilgrimage routes has increased the need for accurate translation and cross-linguistic harmonization of pilgrimage tourism terms. Pragmatic equivalence becomes crucial: literal translation may fail to convey spiritual nuances, while culturally adapted translation must avoid altering religious meanings. The translator’s task involves not only linguistic competence but also intercultural awareness and knowledge of religious traditions. The communicative challenges are amplified in multilingual contexts where terms may lose their specificity or emotional resonance when transferred across languages. Relatedly, extralinguistic factors such as historical background, religious doctrine, local customs, and sociocultural norms influence how terms are interpreted. For instance, the same term describing a sacred ritual may evoke reverence in one audience and mere curiosity in another. Thus, the pragmatic function of pilgrimage tourism terms is inseparable from the cultural frames through which interlocutors interpret religious discourse. Effective communication demands that speakers anticipate such differences and adjust their terminological choices accordingly. Another key pragmatic feature is the ability of pilgrimage tourism terms to shape interpersonal relations. The appropriate use of respectful terminology fosters trust, unity, and shared spiritual experience among participants. Conversely, inappropriate or disrespectful usage can lead to misunderstanding, offense, or breakdown of communication. This is especially important in interfaith tourism, where visitors may come from different religious backgrounds and may be unfamiliar with the rituals or values associated with the pilgrimage site. Here, the strategic use of inclusive language becomes a fundamental communicative goal. At the cognitive level, pilgrimage tourism terms facilitate conceptual structuring, enabling individuals to frame their

experience within specific cultural and spiritual categories. Terms such as “pilgrim,” “sanctuary,” “holy relic,” or “ritual purification” help create mental models that guide visitors’ actions, emotions, and expectations. Pragmatically, these terms trigger associative meanings, evoke historical memory, and reinforce the sacred atmosphere of the site. Their communicative function lies in helping participants navigate both the physical space and the symbolic universe of the pilgrimage tradition. The pragmatic and communicative features of pilgrimage tourism terminology also emerge in academic discourse, where these terms are analyzed, classified, and standardized. Scholars engage in terminological clarification to avoid ambiguity, propose definitions, and explore the semantic structure of the vocabulary used in pilgrimage tourism studies. Academic communication requires precision, consistency, and methodological transparency, making the pragmatic function of terms essential for knowledge dissemination and scholarly debate. Finally, technological advancements and digital media have transformed the communicative landscape of pilgrimage tourism. Virtual tours, online guides, and digital storytelling have introduced new pragmatic conditions for using pilgrimage-related terms. The shift from face-to-face interaction to mediated communication requires adjustments in terminology: explanations must be clearer, cultural references more explicit, and spiritual concepts carefully contextualized for global audiences. Despite these changes, the core communicative goal remains the same: to convey the sacred significance of pilgrimage experiences in an accessible, respectful, and meaningful manner.

In conclusion, the pragmatic and communicative features of using pilgrimage tourism terms reflect a dynamic interplay between language, culture, context, and intention. These terms serve as vehicles of knowledge, emotion, identity, and guidance. Their effective use enhances understanding, strengthens intercultural dialogue, and supports the spiritual and educational objectives of pilgrimage tourism. As global religious travel continues to expand, the study of these features becomes increasingly important for linguists, educators, guides, and professionals engaged in the tourism industry. Mastery of pilgrimage tourism terminology contributes not only to clearer communication but also to the preservation and respectful transmission of spiritual heritage across generations and cultures.

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VOQEA-HODISANING INTERPRETATSION KOGNITIV QOLIP XUSUSIYATLARI

Kirish.

Ommaviy axborot vositalarida voqea-hodisalarning yoritilishi nafaqat informativ jarayon, balki kognitiv-interpretativ faoliyatdir. Axborot matni auditoriya ongida ma'lum mantiqiy va konseptual qoliplar orqali talqin qilinadi[1]. Shuning uchun interpretatsion kognitiv qoliplarni o'rganish media lingvistikasining eng muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida qaraladi. Ommaviy axborot vositalari (OAV) zamonaviy ijtimoiy hayotning eng ta'sirchan kommunikativ maydonlaridan biridir. Unda voqea-hodisalarning tasviri shunchaki ma'lumot yetkazish emas, balki ularni ma'lum maqsad, ideologiya yoki ijtimoiy ehtiyoj asosida **talqin qilish, qayta shakllantirish va mazmuniy qayta paketlash** jarayonini ham o'z ichiga oladi[2]. Media matnlarda voqelik aks etmasa-da, u **yonaltirilgan, filtrlashdan o'tgan, baholangan** shaklda namoyon bo'ladi[3]. **Interpretatsion Kognitiv Qolipning Nazariy Asoslari:** Kognitiv lingvistikaning yirik namoyandalari — G. Lakoff, M. Jonson, R. Langaker, Ch. Fillmor, T. van Deyk, V. Kintsh, E. Kubryakova va boshqalar — inson tafakkurida voqelikni qayta ishlash jarayoni til birliklari orqali namoyon bo'lishini ta'kidlaydi[4].

Kognitiv qolip voqea-hodisaning mental modeli bo'lib, unda:

— voqeaning prototipi,

— ishtirokchilar,

— sabab-oqibat aloqalari,

— baholash va interpretatsiya resurslari mujassam bo'ladi[5].

Media Diskursida Kognitiv Qoliplarning Amal Qilishi T. van Deykning ideologik kvadratlari, N. Faircloughning tanqidiy diskurs tahlili, R. Fowlerning media ideologiyasi modeliga ko'ra, axborotning talqin qilinishi lingvo-kognitiv strukturalar bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Ularning fikricha, media matnlarda

ko‘pincha quyidagi kognitiv qoliplar uchraydi - sabab-oqibat qolipi, qarama-qarshilik qolipi, emotsional baholash qolipi, agentlik (faollik-passivlik) qolipi, drammatizatsiya (konflikt) qolipi.

Voqea-Hodisalarning Talqinida Framing (Qoliplash)

Media tahlilida E. Goffman[6], J. Entman, S. Reese kabi tadqiqotchilar "framing" tushunchasini rivojlantirgan. Unga ko‘ra, jurnalist voqeani ma‘lum "ramka"da ko‘rsatadi:

- muammoni aniqlash
- sababni belgilash— axloqiy baho berish
- yechimni taklif qilish

Bu elementlar interpretatsion kognitiv qolipning asosiy komponentlarini tashkil qiladi va ular voqea bayonining shakllanishida muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

Kognitiv Qoliplarning Lingvistik Ko‘rinishi

Lingvistik darajada qoliplar quyidagi vositalar orqali namoyon bo‘ladi:

- metaforalar (Lakoff & Johnson)
- baholovchi leksika
- modal birliklar
- sintaktik bo‘rttirish
- agentlikni yashirish yoki kuchaytirish[7]

Masalan, “aybdor aniqlandi” kabi gaplarda agent yashiringan bo‘lsa, “hukumat zudlik bilan choralar ko‘rdi” kabi birikmalarda agentlik kuchaytiriladi[8].

Quyidagi xabarni olaylik:

“Shiddatli yomg‘ir tufayli shahar hayoti izdan chiqdi.”

Bu matnda:

- sabab: shiddatli yomg‘ir
- oqibat: izdan chiqish
- baho: “izdan chiqdi” dramatik talqinni kuchaytiradi
- ramka: falokat-krisis modeli

Demak, matn o‘quvchi ongida xavotir, xavf va tartibsizlik kabi konseptlarni faollashtiradigan kognitiv qolipni shakllantiradi.

Xulosa

Voqea-hodisalarning interpretatsion kognitiv qolipi media diskursining mazmunini shakllantiruvchi asosiy mexanizmdir. U til birliklari, diskurs strategiyalari va mental modellarning o‘zaro uyg‘unlashuvi orqali vujudga keladi. Shu bois, media matnlarining lingvokognitiv tahlili — zamonaviy axborot makonini chuqur tushunishning eng samarali usullaridan biridir. OAV tomonidan yaratilgan talqinning asosiy kognitiv mexanizmlarini tashkil etadi[9]. Shundan kelib chiqib, interpretatsion kognitiv qoliplar nafaqat lingvistik kategoriya, balki **axborot siyosati, ijtimoiy ong, jamoatchilik fikri va diskurs ideologiyasini belgilovchi mexanizm** sifatida ham qaraladi. Tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki:

1. Media diskursida voqea-hodisalarning talqini ko‘pincha jurnalistning dunyoqarashi, tahririyat siyosati yoki ijtimoiy kontekst ta‘sirida shakllanadi.

2. Til vositalari voqeani neytral aks ettirmaydi; aksincha, voqeani interpretatsiya qiluvchi kognitiv va ideologik filtr rolini bajaradi.
3. Framing (ramkaga solish), baholash, metaforizatsiya, dramatisatsiya kabi strategiyalar voqea taqdimotining asosiy texnologiyalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Natijada, voqea-hodisaning interpretatsion kognitiv qolipi media matnlarni chuqur tahlil qilish, ularning yashirin semantik strukturasi aniqlash va axborotning ijtimoiy ongga ta'sirini tushunish uchun asosiy ilmiy metod sifatida ahamiyatlidir[10]. Ushbu yondashuv nafaqat lingvistika, balki jurnalistika, psixologiya, sotsiologiya, madaniyatshunoslik va kommunikatsiya sohalari uchun ham katta nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

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DISKURS VA IJTIMOY SINFNING KOMMUNIKATIV MUHITDA VOQE`LANISHI

Diskurs tilshunoslik va sotsiolingvistikaning markaziy tushunchalaridan biri bo`lib, u nafaqat tilning strukturaviy jihatlarini, balki ijtimoiy voqelikda qanday ishlashini ham o`rganadi. Til faqatgina aloqa vositasi emas, balki ijtimoiy maqom, hokimiyat va identifikatsiyani ifodalovchi resurs hamdir. Shu bois, ijtimoiy sinf va diskurs munosabatini tahlil qilish zamonaviy lingvistika uchun dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Kommunikativ muhitda ijtimoiy sinfning voqe`lanishi turli darajalarda kuzatiladi: murojaat shakllari, xushmuomalalik strategiyalari, fonetik tafovutlar, leksik tanlov va sintaktik tuzilmalardan tortib, diskursiv strategiyalar orqali hokimiyat va ijtimoiy maqomni ifodalashgacha.

B. Bernstein til va ijtimoiy sinf munosabatini o`rgangan eng mashhur sotsiologlardan biridir. U cheklangan kod va kengaytirilgan kod tushunchalarini ilgari surib, tilning ijtimoiy qatlamlar orasida qanday farq qilishini izohlab berdi¹. Ishchi sinf vakillari ko`pincha cheklangan koddan foydalanadilar: gaplar sodda, kontekstdan tashqarida tushunilishi qiyin, mantiqiy bog`lanishlar kam. Yuqori va o`rta sinf vakillari esa kengaytirilgan koddan foydalanadi: sintaktik jihatdan murakkab gaplar, aniqlik va mantiqiy izchillik mavjud.

N. Fairclough esa diskursni hokimiyat va ijtimoiy tengsizliklar bilan bog`liq holda tahlil qiladi². Uning fikricha, til jamiyatdagi kuch munosabatlarini mustahkamlash yoki shubha ostiga qo`yishda muhim vositadir. Masalan, rahbar va xodim o`rtasidagi suhbatda rahbarning buyruq ohangidagi nutqi hokimiyatni ifodalasa, xodimning xushmuomalalik va itoat strategiyasi ijtimoiy maqom farqini namoyon qiladi.

W. Labov New York shahrida o`tkazgan mashhur tajribasida fonetik tafovutlar ijtimoiy sinfni belgilashini isbotladi³. "Fourth floor" iborasini talaffuz qilishda yuqori sinf vakillari "r" tovushini aniq talaffuz qilgan bo`lsa, ishchi sinf

¹ **Bernstein, B.** (1971). *Class, Codes and Control*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.

² **Fairclough, N.** (1989). *Language and Power*. London: Longman.

³ **Labov, W.** (1966). *The Social Stratification of English in New York City*. Washington D.C.: Center for Applied Linguistics.

vakillari uni qisqartirgan yoki tushirib qoldirgan. Bu hol fonetikaning ham ijtimoiy signallik xususiyatga ega ekanini ko'rsatadi.

P. Eckert (2000) esa o'quvchilar nutqidagi tafovutlarni tahlil qilib, "Jocks" (faol, akademik qatlam) va "Burnouts" (norasmiy, qarshilikchi qatlam) guruhlarini ajratdi¹. Jocks vakillari rasmiyroq, standart til shakllarini qo'llagan bo'lsa, Burnouts guruhidagi o'quvchilar ko'proq jargon, qisqa gaplar va norasmiy leksikani tanlagan.

Ijtimoiy sinf diskursda bir nechta darajada voqe'lanadi:

1. Leksik daraja – Yuqori sinf vakillari rasmiy, adabiy leksikani tanlasa, pastroq qatlam vakillari jargon va oddiy so'zlardan foydalanadi.

2. Fonetik daraja – Talaffuz va intonatsiya ijtimoiy maqomni ko'rsatadi.

3. Sintaktik daraja – Yuqori sinf vakillari murakkab sintaktik konstruksiyalardan foydalansa, past qatlam vakillari sodda gaplarni tanlaydi.

4. Murojaat shakllari – Unvon, familiya yoki ismning qo'llanishi ham ijtimoiy maqomni belgilaydi.

5. Xushmuomalalik strategiyalari – Yuqori sinf vakillari ko'proq bilvosita ifodalar va yumshatuvchi iboralardan foydalanadi, past qatlam esa to'g'ridan-to'g'ri gapirishga moyil.

Diskurs ijtimoiy sinfnig kommunikativ muhitda voqe'lanadigan asosiy maydonidir. Til vositalari nafaqat aloqa vositasi, balki hokimiyat, maqom, identifikatsiya va ijtimoiy tafovutlarni ifodalovchi resurs sifatida ishlaydi. Bernstein, Fairclough, Labov va Eckertning nazariyalari bu jarayonni chuqur izohlab beradi.

Shuningdek, ijtimoiy sinf diskursida nutqning stilistik darajasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Yuqori sinf vakillari ko'pincha professional yoki akademik stilistik registrga murojaat qiladi, bu esa ularning mavqeini oshiradi. Pastki sinf vakillari esa norasmiy va do'stona registrdan foydalanadi, bu esa kommunikativ qulaylikni ta'minlaydi.

Diskurs tahlilida sinflararo farqlar, shuningdek, tilning pragmatik jihatlari bilan bog'liq. Yuqori sinf vakillari nutqda bilvosita va yumshatuvchi ifodalar orqali ijtimoiy signallarni beradi, pastki sinf vakillari esa bevosita va hissiy boy iboralar orqali o'z mavqeini bildiradi. Bu esa diskursning ijtimoiy sinfni aks ettirishdagi asosiy vositasi ekanini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, diskurs va ijtimoiy sinf o'rtasidagi munosabat kommunikativ muhitda o'ziga xos tarzda voqe'lanadi. Lingvopragmatik vositalar, stilistik registrlar va nutq strategiyalari sinfiy tafovutlarni ochib beradi va shaxsning ijtimoiy mavqeini belgilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

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THE CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF CRAFT-RELATED TERMINOLOGY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical foundations of lexical units related to craftsmanship in both Uzbek and English languages. It explores how linguistic disciplines such as lexicology, semasiology, etymology, and cognitive–frame semantics contribute to studying this vocabulary layer across two cultures. The comparative analysis reveals that craft terminology not only designates tools and processes but also reflects aesthetic ideals, social values, and national identity. The research emphasizes the cultural parallels and linguistic divergences that shape how each language conceptualizes the art of craftsmanship.

Key words: craftsmanship lexicon, lexicology, semasiology, etymology, cognitive linguistics, frame semantics, cultural identity, Uzbek and English languages.

Introduction. Language and culture are inseparable; both evolve through human labor, creativity, and shared experience. The vocabulary of craftsmanship — encompassing embroidery, weaving, carpentry, pottery, and other traditional arts — captures the essence of artistic creation and cultural symbolism.

In the Uzbek language, craft terminology often reflects ancient traditions rooted in the Silk Road civilization, emphasizing beauty (*go‘zallik*), harmony (*uyg‘unlik*), and patience (*sabr*). Meanwhile, in English, craft-related vocabulary emerged from the Anglo-Saxon and Medieval guild systems, emphasizing skill, utility, and artistry (craft, workmanship, embroidery, needlework).

This article aims to reveal the linguistic and cultural mechanisms underlying craftsmanship vocabulary in both languages. Drawing on the works of Jo‘rayev (2012), Hojiev (2007), Fillmore (1982), and Lakoff (1987), it examines

how the lexical, semantic, and cognitive structures of this terminology convey the worldview and heritage of their respective cultures.

1. Lexicological Perspective

Lexicology examines the structure and thematic organization of a language's vocabulary. In Uzbek, as noted by Jo'rayev (2012), craft-related terms form a coherent lexical–semantic field: *ip* (thread), *igna* (needle), *mato* (cloth), *chok* (stitch), *kashta* (embroidery), *naqsh* (pattern), *suzani* (decorative textile). These words are semantically linked through a shared thematic domain of manual creativity and ornamentation.

In English, a similar lexical network exists: thread, needle, fabric, stitch, embroidery, pattern, tapestry. The English term *craft* itself derives from Old English *cræft*, meaning “strength” or “skill.” This etymological root emphasizes competence and artistry, while in Uzbek, equivalent concepts such as *hunar* (skill) and *mehnat* (labor) highlight patience and dedication.

Thus, lexicological comparison shows that both languages organize their craft vocabularies around human creativity but differ in cultural emphasis: Uzbek lexis focuses on aesthetic beauty and symbolic harmony, while English emphasizes skill, precision, and utility.

2. Semasiological Approach

Semasiology, the study of meaning, uncovers how words express not only denotative but also connotative and metaphorical values (Hojiev, 2007). In Uzbek, craft terms carry emotional and moral connotations. For instance, *ipak* (silk) suggests gentleness and refinement, while *kashta* symbolizes patience and inner beauty.

In English, semasiological extension occurs in metaphorical expressions like “a finely woven story”, “a thread of hope”, or “fabric of society”. These metaphors show how material processes of weaving and sewing have entered abstract thought. Uzbek uses similar metaphors — for example, *taqdir ipi* (“thread of destiny”) — demonstrating a shared human tendency to connect textile imagery with fate, order, and continuity.

Comparative semasiology therefore reveals a universal metaphorical system rooted in craft experience, even though each culture applies its own moral and aesthetic filters.

3. Etymological Analysis

Etymology provides historical insight into how craftsmanship terms emerged and transformed. Xudoyberganova (2020) identifies multiple sources for Uzbek craft vocabulary: ancient Turkic (*ip*, *chok*), Persian (*kashta* from *keshidan* – “to sew”), and Arabic (*naqsh* – “ornament”). This reflects Central Asia's intercultural exchange through trade and art.

English craft terms also derive from diverse sources: embroidery from French *broderie*, needle from Old English *nædl*, textile from Latin *textilis*. The etymological layering in both languages shows how trade, colonization, and technological evolution enriched their craft vocabularies.

The comparative study reveals that while Uzbek terminology emphasizes tradition and artistry, English craft vocabulary evolved through industrial and artistic innovation — mirroring the socio-economic histories of each culture.

4. Cognitive and Frame–Semantic Approach

Cognitive linguistics, pioneered by Fillmore (1982) and Lakoff (1987), interprets language as a reflection of conceptual structures and cultural models. Frame semantics explains how meaning is organized within knowledge frameworks or “frames.”

In both Uzbek and English, the “craft” frame includes elements such as tools, materials, processes, and purpose. For example:

Uzbek frame: igna (needle) → ip (thread) → kashta (embroidery) → go‘zallik (beauty) → sabr (patience).

English frame: needle → thread → stitch → design → artistry.

While both frames encode creativity and manual labor, Uzbek emphasizes spiritual and moral endurance, and English highlights individual artistry and precision. This difference reflects broader cognitive and cultural orientations: the Uzbek worldview associates craftsmanship with collective identity and heritage, whereas English discourse tends toward individual skill and innovation.

Hence, the frame–semantic approach demonstrates how both linguistic systems encapsulate distinct yet parallel conceptualizations of art, labor, and beauty.

Conclusion. The comparative study of craftsmanship lexicon in Uzbek and English shows that language is not merely a means of communication but a repository of cultural values. Lexicology explains structural organization; semasiology reveals metaphorical richness; etymology uncovers historical interconnections; and cognitive semantics shows how meaning reflects thought and identity.

Uzbek craft vocabulary embodies collective aesthetics, patience, and moral virtue, while English craft terminology reflects technical mastery and creative individuality. Despite cultural differences, both languages elevate craftsmanship as a symbol of human artistry and endurance.

Integrating traditional linguistic methods with cognitive approaches enables a comprehensive understanding of how artistic labor shapes linguistic and cultural expression in diverse societies.

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PSYCHOANALYTIC ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF ANGER IN ENGLISH LITERARY DISCOURSE

Abstract

This study investigates the psychoanalytic dimensions of the concept of anger in English literary discourse, analyzing how authors depict and structure this emotion in the psychological development of their characters. Drawing on Freudian and Jungian frameworks, the research examines mechanisms such as repression, projection, displacement, and archetypal symbolism underlying anger. A corpus of primary literary texts, including Shakespeare's *King Lear* and Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*, was analyzed qualitatively to identify patterns of expression, triggers, and thematic functions of anger. Findings suggest that anger in English literature is a multifaceted construct, reflecting both individual psychic conflicts and broader socio-cultural tensions. The study demonstrates that psychoanalytic approaches provide significant insights into the interplay between unconscious drives and literary representation.

Keywords: anger, psychoanalysis, English literary discourse, Freudian theory, Jungian archetypes, literary emotion

INGLIZ ADABIY DISKURSIDA G'AZAB TUSHUNCHASINING
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Annotatsiya

Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz adabiy nutqida g'azab tushunchasining psixoanalitik jihatlarini o'rganadi, mualliflarning o'z qahramonlarining psixologik rivojlanishida bu tuyg'uni qanday tasvirlashi va tuzishini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot freydizm va yungizm qoliplariga tayanib, g'azabning asosini tashkil etuvchi repressiya, proyeksiya, siljish va arxetipik ramziylik kabi mexanizmlarni o'rganadi. G'azabning ifodalanish qonuniyatlari, qo'zg'atuvchilari va tematik funksiyalarini aniqlash uchun Shekspirning "Qirol Lir" va Meri Shellining "Frankenshteyn" asarlarini o'z ichiga olgan birlamchi badiiy matnlar korpusi sifat jihatidan tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ingliz adabiyotida g'azab ko'p qirrali tuzilma bo'lib, u ham individual ruhiy ziddiyatlarni, ham kengroq ijtimoiy-madaniy keskinliklarni aks ettiradi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, psixoanalitik yondashuvlar ongsiz intilishlar va adabiy tasavvur o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir haqida muhim ma'lumot beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: g'azab, psixoanaliz, ingliz adabiy diskursi, Freyd nazariyasi, Yung arxetiplari, adabiy hissiyot

Introduction

Anger is a fundamental human emotion, closely tied to both destructive impulses and moral appraisal. In literary discourse, anger operates not merely as a narrative

device but as a lens into character psychology, revealing unconscious desires, repressed conflicts, and social tensions. Psychoanalytic literary criticism, rooted in the theories of Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung, provides a theoretical framework for examining the internal mechanisms underlying anger. This study explores how English literature represents anger, emphasizing its psychological, symbolic, and thematic dimensions.

Literature Review

Freud conceptualizes anger as a manifestation of instinctual drives (id) encountering societal constraints (superego), with repression, projection, and displacement emerging as central mechanisms for regulating aggressive impulses.¹ Jung situates anger within the collective unconscious, emphasizing archetypes and symbolic expressions as vehicles for understanding deep-seated emotional patterns.²

Prior studies have predominantly explored anger through sociocultural or moral frameworks. Harold Bloom emphasizes the creative and destructive potential of repressed anger in literary characterization,³ while Terry Eagleton argues that literature dramatizes psychic conflicts through interpersonal and moral tensions.⁴ Psychoanalytic approaches enrich these perspectives by illuminating the **unconscious dimensions that shape literary depictions of anger.**

Psychoanalytic Analysis of Anger

Shakespeare's King Lear

Lear's anger arises from betrayal, filial ingratitude, and the loss of authority. Freud's concept of repression is evident when Lear initially suppresses rage against societal expectations, later releasing it destructively. Projection is observed as Lear's fury amplifies conflicts among other characters. Jungian analysis identifies the "shadow" archetype, where Lear's anger exposes hidden, darker facets of his psyche.⁵ Symbolic elements such as storms externalize his inner turmoil, linking emotional and natural chaos.

Mary Shelley's Frankenstein

Victor Frankenstein's anger is tied to guilt, frustration, and alienation. Repression occurs as Victor internalizes frustration, which later manifests indirectly through destructive consequences. The creature's retaliatory anger exemplifies projection, embodying the suppressed aggression and moral injustices imposed by Victor and society. Jungian archetypes illuminate the creature as the "shadow self," reflecting unacknowledged aspects of Victor's personality and societal rejection. Anger functions as both a narrative catalyst and a mechanism of psychological exploration.

Discussion

Psychoanalytic analysis demonstrates that anger in English literary discourse is complex and multilayered. It serves as a medium for portraying internalized conflicts, moral dilemmas, and social pressures. Characters' anger often manifests through repression, projection, and displacement, revealing unconscious drives. Archetypal and symbolic patterns enrich the understanding of anger, connecting

individual psychological experiences with universal human themes. The analysis confirms that psychoanalytic frameworks can uncover the deep psychological structures shaping literary representation, offering insights beyond traditional moral or sociocultural interpretations.

Conclusion

The psychoanalytic study of anger in English literature highlights its dual function as a psychological and symbolic construct. Freud's and Jung's theories illuminate the mechanisms and archetypal patterns underlying literary anger, revealing its impact on character development, narrative dynamics, and thematic depth. Future research could extend this framework to contemporary literary works or cross-cultural texts to explore evolving representations of anger and its psychoanalytic significance.

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Aziza Yunusova

INSON TILI UNING DUNYO HAQIDAGI TASAVVURLARI NAMOYON BO'LISHINING KO'RSATKICHIDIR

Til, ijtimoiylashtiruvchi va birlashtiruvchi kuch sifatida harakat qilish bilan bir vaqtda, individuallikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan kuchli omildir. Ovozning xarakterli sifatlari, nutqning tezligi va aniqligi, jumjalarning uzunligi va tuzilishi, lug'at zaxirasining xususiyati va hajmi – bularning barchasi shaxsiyatni tavsiflovchi ko'plab murakkab ko'rsatkichlar hisoblanadi.

Insonning lingvistik odatlari uning shaxsiyatining eng muhim jihatlarini anglatuvchi ongsiz ko'rsatkichlar sifatida juda muhimdir.

Mutloq ma'noda, til jihatidan bir xil ijtimoiy guruh yoki millat mavjud emas, chunki barcha shaxslar boshqa shaxslar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan kodlardan biroz farq qiladigan kodlar to'plami bilan ishlaydi, amaliy nuqtai nazardan, kodlar o'rtasidagi ba'zi farqlar shunday ekanligini hisobga olish qulay emas. Bu kodlarni "turli tillar" deb atash juda o'rinli. Til monolit tuzilma emas, u hatto alohida shaxsda ham, o'z tabiatiga ko'ra, rasmiy tarkibi va ijtimoiy funktsiyasi bilan bir-biridan farq qiladigan o'zaro bog'liq kodlar majmuasidan

iborat. "Bitta avlod va bir yerdan bo'lgan, bitta shevada gapiradigan va bitta ijtimoiy muhitda ish ko'radigan ikkita odam, - deb yozgan edi E. Sepir, - nutq doirasida hech qachon bir xil bo'lishmaydi. Ularning har birining nutqini sinchkovlik bilan o'rganish tafsilotlarda, ya'ni so'zlarni tanlashda, jumla tuzishda, so'zlarning u yoki bu shakllari hamda birikmalaridan va h.k.dan foydalanishning nisbiy chastotasida sanoqsiz farqlarni ochib tashlaydi".

Turli xil tillarda so'zlovchi kishilarning fikrlashlari asosan o'xshash bo'lib qoladi. Bu insonning jismoniy tabiati, uning bosh miyasining vazifalari bilan tushuntiriladi, ammo turli xil tillar – bu, asosida inson fikrlashining bir xil tamoyillari yotgan borliqni ma'naviy o'zlashtirishning turli xil usullaridir.

Dunyoning hissiy va ruhiy marnzarasining paydo bo'lishi jarayonida bizning ongimizda bizni o'rab turgan voqelik haqida, ongsiz ravishda, biz fikrlaydigan va gaplashadigan tilning qonunlari asosida til tassavurlari hosil bo'ladi. Har bir til ozmi-ko'pmi darajada, dunyoni o'zining birliklari (lug'ati - leksikasi) qiymatlarida, maxsus obrazlarda (frazologiyada), tushunchali kategoriyalarining maxsus tuzilmasida (grammatikasida) o'ziga xos tasavvur qiladi. Atrof-muhitning kontinuumi (uzluksizligi) turli xil yo'llar bilan bo'linadi. Til antropotsentrik: u inson uchun mo'ljallangan, va tashqi dunyo ob'ektlarining va hodisalarining barcha lingvistik kategorizatsiyasi (tasnifi) insonga qaratilgan – bu hamma tillarga xos xususiyatdir. Ammo har bir til o'ziga xos milliylik xususiyatiga ega. Tilda nafaqat tabiiy sharoitlarning yoki madaniyatning xususiyatlari, balki milliy xarakterning o'ziga xosligi ham aks etadi. Eskimoslar tilida qorning, arablar tilida – tuyaning, xitoy tilida – gurunchning ko'p nomlanishlari borligi hech kimni hayron qoldirmaydi. Til xalqning hayot kechirish sharoitlarini aks ettiradi va shu xalqqa xos bo'lgan ismlarga va voqelikka ega bo'ladi. Tilning lug'at tarkibida jismoniy va ijtimoiy muhit juda yorqin aks ettiriladi. Qandaydir bir tilning to'liq lug'atiga asosli holda mazkur jamiyatning e'tiborini tortadigan barcha g'oyalar, manfaatlar va faoliyatlarning kompleksli inventari (asbobi) sifatida qarash mumkin.

Har bir til o'zining "semantik koinoti"ni hosil qiladi. Nafaqat fikrlar bir tilda uylanilishi, balki his-tuy g'ular ham, boshqa tilda emas, shu bitta til ongi doirasida boshdan kechirilishi mumkin. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, dunyoning bitta modeli uchun asosiy bo'lgan va boshqalarida mavjud bo'lmagan tushunchalar mavjud. Tabiiy tilda dunyoni qanday bo'lsa, shundayligicha bayon etish mumkin emas: til dastlab o'z so'zlovchilariga dunyoning ma'lum manzarasini, bunda har til – o'z manzarasini beradi. "Verbal (og'zaki) obrazlar va til modellari orqali dunyoning qo'shimcha ko'rinishi sodir bo'ladi. Bu modellar bilishning, voqelikni tushunishning qo'shimcha manbai sifatida ish ko'radi, bilimlarimizning umumiy doirasini to'ldiradi, uni tahrir qiladi".

Ijtimoiy va mehnat tajribasining xususiyatlari hodisa va jarayonlarning leksik va grammatik nominatsiyasidagi farqlarda, ma'lum ma'nolarning mosligida, ularning etimologiyasida va boshqalarda ifodalanadi. Turli tillardan olingan, hodisalarni bildiradigan va rus tilida ularni nomlash uchun maxsus

so'zlar bo'lmagan hech bo'lmaganda bir nechta so'zlarni tahlil qilib, bunga ishonch hosil qilish oson. Ularning mohiyati faqat faqat tavsiflab ifodalanishi mumkin, masalan, finger - qo'l barmog'i, toe – oyoq barmog'i va h.k.

O.Espersen quyidagi holatga e'tiborni qaratadi: ingliz tilida quyidagi so'zlar farqlanadi: clock – devor soati, watch – qo'l soati, frantsuzchada – horloge – cho'ntak soati, pendule – osma soat, nemis tilida esa faqat – Uhr so'zi bor.

Ma'nosiga ko'ra bir xil bo'lib ko'ringan so'zlarning ishlatilish sohalari juda xilma-xil bo'ladi. Shunga qaramay, ruscha "счастливы" sifat so'zi torroq ma'noga ega bo'ladi. Odatda u jiddiy narsalardan, masalan sevgidan, hayot ma'nosidan va shu kabilardan olinadigan to'liq baxtning juda kam uchraydigan holatlarini bildirish uchun ishlatiladi. Shuning uchun u, keng ishlatiladigan inglizcha happy so'zi kabi ruscha suhbat nutqida keng qo'llanilmaydi.

Agar "Is everybody happy?" – degan savolni Amerikaning har qanday o'tirishida eshitish mumkin bo'lsa, unda ruscha "Ты счастлив?" ("Sen baxtlimisan?") jumlasini faqat jiddiy falsafiy risolada ko'rish mumkin, xolos. Ammo bu, slavyanlardan farqli ravishda inglizlar befarq millat ekanini bildirmaydi. Bu semantik nomuvofiqlikka misol bo'ladi, xolos. Rus va o'zbek tillarida qasddan (intentsional) tuzilishning qiyosiy kuzatuvlari o'xshash hodisalarning har xil ko'rinishini bildiradi.

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KOGNITIV LINGVISTIKADA LEKSIK TEJAMKORLIK

Annotatsiya : Ushbu maqolada kognitiv lingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan leksik tejamkorlik fenomeni, uning nazariy asoslari va kognitiv jarayonlar bilan bog'liqligi tahlil qilinadi. Leksik tejamkorlik til tizimining iqtisodiy tamoyillar asosida minimal til vositalari orqali maksimal ma'no yetkazish xususiyati bilan izohlanadi. Tadqiqotda konseptual umumlashtirish, metafora, metonimiya va polisemiyaning tejamkorlikdagi roli muhim kognitiv mexanizmlar sifatida yoritilgan. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilida leksik tejamkorlikning namoyon bo'lish shakllari misollar orqali tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kognitiv lingvistika, leksik tejamkorlik, konseptual umumlashtirish, metafora, metonimiya, polisemik birliklar.

Annotation: This article examines the phenomenon of lexical economy from the perspective of cognitive linguistics, focusing on its theoretical foundations and its relationship with cognitive processes. Lexical economy is defined as the linguistic principle of conveying maximum meaning using minimal linguistic resources. The study highlights the role of conceptual generalization, metaphor, metonymy, and polysemy as major cognitive mechanisms contributing to lexical economy. Additionally, various manifestations of lexical economy in the Uzbek language are analyzed through illustrative examples.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, lexical economy, conceptual generalization, metaphor, metonymy, polysemy.

Kognitiv lingvistika tilda yuz beradigan barcha jarayonlarni inson tafakkuri, konseptual tizimi va dunyoqarashining mahsuli sifatida izohlaydi. Lakoff va Johnson (1980) tilni “inson fikrlashining ko‘zgusi” sifatida talqin qilib, metafora va metonimiyaning kognitiv tabiatini asoslab bergan. Langaker (1987) esa kognitiv grammatikaning markazida konseptual strukturalar turishini ta’kidlaydi. Tilshunoslar fikricha, tilning iqtisodiy tamoyili — eng kam vosita bilan eng ko‘p ma’no yetkazish — inson ongining tabiatidan kelib chiqadi (Zipf, 1949). Bu tamoyil “leksik tejamkorlik” shaklida namoyon bo‘ladi. Jumladan, Graysning kooperativ tamoyillari, Sperber va Uilsonning relevans nazariyasi ham kommunikatsiyada tejamkorlikning asosiy omillaridan ekanini ta’kidlaydi. Shu bois leksik tejamkorlik kognitiv lingvistikaning eng muhim yo‘nalishlaridan biri sifatida til tizimining iqtisodiy va konseptual mexanizmlarini o‘rganishga xizmat qiladi.

Leksik tejamkorlik – tilning iqtisodiylik tamoyillariga asoslanib, ortiqcha til vositalarini kamaytirgan holda ma’no zichligini oshirish jarayonidir. Zipfning “kam harakat qonuni”ga ko‘ra, inson ongida tilning iqtisodiy qo‘llanishi doimo ustuvor bo‘ladi: kamroq so‘z bilan ko‘proq mazmun ifodalash tabiiy jarayondir. Graysning “soddalik va aniqlik” tamoyillari ham tejamkorlikning kommunikativ mohiyatini oqlaydi. Bu nazariy qarashlar tilning faqat lingvistik tizim emas, balki kognitiv mexanizm sifatida iqtisodiy prinsiplar asosida ishlashini tasdiqlaydi. Kognitiv lingvistikada konseptual umumlashtirish tilning tejamkor ishlashiga asosiy mexanizmlardan biri bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Inson o‘z ongida turli obyektlarni bitta umumiy nom ostida birlashtiradi: “meva”, “hayvon”, “transport”, “kiyim”. Bunday umumlashtirish orqali til minimal leksik birliklardan foydalanib maksimal konseptual doirani qamrab oladi. Langakerning ta’kidlashicha, inson konseptual maydonining izchil tashkil topishi aynan umumlashtirish jarayonlari orqali amalga oshadi.

Lakoff va Johnsonning konseptual metafora nazariyasi metaforani tilning tejamkorlik vositasi sifatida ko‘rsatadi. Masalan, “vaqt – pul” konseptual metaforasi: vaqtni tejash, sarflash, yo‘qotish kabi birikmalar orqali abstrakt tushunchani aniq tajriba bilan bog‘lab beradi. Bu kognitiv tejamkorlikning yorqin namunasidir. Metonimiya esa obyektlar o‘rtasidagi yaqin bog‘liqlik asosida

ma'noni ixcham ifodalashga imkon beradi: stol qaror qildi (rahbariyat), xonani o'qidi (o'quvchilar). Bunday birliklar tilning minimal energetik sarf orqali ma'no ko'p qatlamlilikini yaratish imkoniyatini ko'rsatadi.

Polisemiya – bitta so'zning bir nechta ma'noda qo'llanishi – tilning iqtisodiy mexanizmlaridan biridir. Kognitiv jihatdan bunday birliklar bir konsept markazi atrofida tarmoqlangan ma'nolar tizimini hosil qiladi. Masalan, ko'z (odam ko'zi, igna ko'zi, buloq ko'zi), yurak (a'zo, markaz, jasorat). Inson ongida asosiy konseptual o'zak saqlanib, ma'nolar unga metafora va metonimiya orqali ulanadi. O'zbek tilida tejamkorlikning turli ko'rinishlari mavjud: ellipsis, qisqartmalar, terminologik ixchamlik, polisemik birliklar. Masalan, MTM, OTM, KMK kabi qisqartmalar murakkab sintaktik birliklarning tejamkor ko'rinishidir. Ellipsis esa gap tarkibidagi ortiqcha bo'laklarning tashlab ketilishi bilan ajralib turadi: Keldimi?, Qayerga?. Shuningdek, o'zbek tilining ko'p ma'nolilik imkoniyatlari orqali tilning semantik iqtisodi ta'minlanadi. Bularning barchasi o'zbek tilining kognitiv tizimi ham tejamkorlik elementlariga tayanganini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa: Kognitiv lingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan leksik tejamkorlik tilning iqtisodiy, konseptual va funksional mexanizmlarini yorituvchi muhim kategoriya hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotdan ma'lum bo'ldiki, tejamkorlik konseptual umumlashtirish, metafora, metonimiya va polisemik kengayish kabi kognitiv jarayonlar orqali ta'minlanadi. Leksik tejamkorlik inson ongining soddalik va samaradorlikka intilishi natijasida shakllangan bo'lib, minimal birliklar orqali maksimal mazmun uzatilishini ta'minlaydi. O'zbek tilidagi qisqartmalar, polisemik so'zlar va ellipsislar bu jarayonning amaliy ko'rinishlaridir.

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MUAMMOLARI**

MATERIALLAR TO‘PLAMI

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